

**The state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes between
policy discourse and policy implementation: university teachers'
perceptions**

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Declaration

I hereby certify that this thesis is the result of my own original work, and the use of any quotations and citations has been properly acknowledged. I also confirm that this thesis has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution, neither in the past nor at present.

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Date: 30/01/2024

Dedication

“In the name of Allah, Most Gracious, Most Merciful”

I dedicate this work to the cherished memory of my father, Abd El Aziz

To my mother, Bahia, the greatest and most significant person in my world

To my beloved husband, Nouredine, my lifelong companion

To my brother, Wail; sisters, Soumia and Maram; best friend, Widad

Thank you all for everything

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Abstract

The global demand for incorporating 21st-century competencies into educational systems is escalating rapidly. Educators have emphasized the crucial role of critical thinking in university instruction, particularly in the context of foreign language classes, where it has become an essential attribute expected of graduates. Foreign language teachers are required to create an active learning environment that fosters critical thinking skills. However, in Algeria, critical thinking does not seem to have received the support it deserves, and English language classes appear to lack emphasis on this vital skill. Additionally, there is a scarcity of research on how language teachers conceptualize and implement critical thinking in teaching. This study investigates the representation of critical thinking in English university curriculum documents and explores Algerian EFL university teachers' conceptualisations and pedagogic practices related to critical thinking. Maintaining an interpretivist stance and employing an exploratory case study design, the study utilises methodological triangulation. Data on critical thinking representation were gathered through document analysis, participants' conceptualisations through semi-structured interviews, and their actual pedagogic practices through classroom observations. The findings indicate that critical thinking plays a negligible role in Algerian higher education, with the English language curriculum documents deprioritising its development in students. Inconsistencies between teachers' cognitions and their actual practices were revealed. While Algerian EFL teachers acknowledged the importance of critical thinking, they faced challenges in systematically addressing it during lessons. Additionally, they lacked theoretical knowledge and practical expertise in its implementation. Furthermore, the prevailing exam-centric teaching approach and focus on grades posed obstacles to cultivating higher-order thinking skills, hindering students' critical thinking. The study advocates for customized professional development in integrating critical thinking into English language curricula, materials development, and pedagogical practices. Additionally, it contributes to enhancing critical thinking in Algerian higher education by providing insights for policymakers and educators. The study also offers theoretical and methodological contributions, practical pedagogic implications, and research recommendations for future exploration in this field.

Key words: critical thinking, EFL, curriculum documents, conceptualisations, practices, Algerian higher education.

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List of Abbreviations

LMD: Licence Master Doctorate

CBA: Competency-based Approach

EFL: English as a Foreign Language

MHESR: Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research

ELT: English Language Teaching

MNE: Ministry of National Education

CLT: Communicative Language Teaching

TEFL: Teaching English as a Foreign Language

CBLT: Competency-based Language Teaching

TESOL: Teaching English for Speakers of Other Languages

MENA: Middle East and North Africa

ESL: English as a Second Language

ESP: English for Specific Purpose

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Chapter 1: General Introduction

1.1. Background of the study and statement of the problem

Algeria's history, marked by 130 years of French colonialism, significantly shaped its cultural, governance, and educational system. This prolonged colonial period witnessed the closure of Koranic schools, limiting educational access for Algerians, and the prohibition of teaching Arabic, Islamic history, and Algerian geography (Djabri, 1981; Mami, 2020). The end of this era was characterised by a severe deterioration in the educational levels of Algerians, as evidenced by alarmingly low literacy rates. The year 1962, when Algeria declared its independence, marked the commencement of an extensive reconstruction process that encompassed all sectors, with a primary focus on education.

Aiming to establish a robust educational system, the Algerian government initiated extensive reforms focused on enhancing literacy, reviving Arab and Islamic identity, restructuring the schooling system, and making enhancements to textbooks and curricula (Mami, 2013). These reforms yielded significant quantitative improvements, manifesting in increased access to education, and notable reductions in illiteracy rates. The academic expansion was also reflected in a greater number of schools established across the country. However, the success in expenditure, access to education, and literacy rates coexisted with persistent criticisms of the educational quality in Algeria. Gherzouli (2019) and Messekher and Miliani (2017) share their concerns regarding Algeria's education system's highly centralised nature, attributing the system's low achievement in educational quality to this centralisation - along with other elements discussed in section 2.2. The centralised system has resulted in the marginalisation of teachers, casting them as mere implementors rather than active change agents. The consequences of this marginalisation could include a perceived lack of ownership among teachers, posing a substantial challenge to fostering a dynamic and effective educational environment 'the whole exercise of reforming national education seems to bump into a centralised and vertical system that creates problems more that it actually solves' (Messekher and Miliani, 2017, p.308).

The Algerian higher education also underwent noteworthy changes as part of the significant transformations. Following independence, there was a notable rise in university enrolments, ascending from 2,200 students post-independence to 1.5 million by 2015. This exponential growth led to the gradual expansion of the universities. The 'Algerianization' of the teaching staff emerged as a pivotal development during this period, with the government striving to recruit predominantly Algerian teachers despite a limited number of professors. The implementation of the Arabization

policy affected the curriculum, particularly in the first year of social and political sciences, laws, and economics, which were Arabized to align with the Arabized baccalaureate. However, medical and technical streams continued to be taught in French, creating challenges for Arabic-speaking baccalaureate holders due to language disparities between primary, secondary, and university levels (Benmati, 2008; Rezig, 2011). The Algerian university system underwent various revisions, the major one was in 2004/2005 when the Ministry of Higher Education introduced the Bologna system (LMD: Licence/Bachelor, Master, and Doctorate) to replace the traditional university system (see section 2.2 for more details).

The implementation of the Bologna system was accompanied by a new teaching approach named the Competency-based approach (CBA) represented a paradigm shift which should align Algerian higher education with international norms (Mami, 2013). This system and teaching approach, with their emphasis on a learner-centred approach, redefined the roles of teachers and learners. Learners, actively engaged in the classroom and beyond, embraced diverse tools, predominantly information and communication technologies, for effective interaction, or at least this is how it should be; it was therefore believed to develop the students' autonomy and critical thinking. Critical thinking which has been acknowledged as a cornerstone of global higher education, with the last decade witnessing increased exploration of critical thinking in various contexts. However, in the Algerian context, there remains a notable dearth of studies in this field (Abdoui and Grine, 2020). Critical thinking - the educational ideal of higher education - has become a mandatory objective that academics and educators seek to develop within their students as a crucial skill for their academic success, in the university setting and even beyond in the workplace (Davis, 2011). Norris (1985) could not overemphasise the significance of critical thinking, arguing that it is an intrinsic good, as education itself, and does not require any further justification.

Critical thinking has been always regarded as one of the defining norms of Western universities (Barnett, 1997), but with the demands of the twenty-first century, many countries in the world – in addition to Western countries - have initiated educational reforms trying to ameliorate the students' learning experiences, along similar lines (Bell, Neary, and Stevenson, 2009). However, in Algeria, critical thinking has not received the same attention as other basic skills (Melouah, 2017; Kheladi, 2019). It has not been seriously supported by the educational system, and there is little evidence of it being infused into the curriculum (Benmati, 2008). Djamaa (2016, p.252) claims: ' . . . critical thinking, however the cornerstone of higher education worldwide nowadays, seems lost in the shuffle in Algeria, particularly in the EFL classroom'.

As such, while Algeria's higher education system achieved commendable milestones in terms of quantitative accessibility, persistent quality issues posed significant concerns (Talbi, 2015). The schooling system, despite undergoing numerous reforms, demonstrated shortcomings in prioritising competency over knowledge as it should be in the CBA and neglecting critical thinking, cognition, and metacognition development (El Ouchdi-Miarli, 2021). The prevailing exam-centric teaching approach further compounded the challenge, hindering the cultivation of higher-order thinking skills among students (Benmoussat and Benmoussat, 2018). In this context, The heavy reliance of Algerian students on grades as a primary motivator for learning and the pursuit of high marks often takes precedence over the actual learning process and the content being taught (Mami, 2013). This emphasis on grades echoes the sentiments expressed by Travis and Wade (1997) 'The fact that our school system relies heavily on grades may help explain why the average college graduate reads few books. Like all extrinsic rewards, grades induce temporary compliance but not necessarily a lifelong disposition to learn' (p. 232). The result is generations of students that are not accustomed to practise higher order thinking skills, and that are not challenged to raise the quality of their thinking to the next level. The educational system has been more about a set of prescribed knowledge to be taken-for-granted, then to be memorised and reproduced in exams (Benmoussat and Benmoussat, 2018). Clearly, this exam-centric approach to teaching is not ideal, and does not rise to the expected level and competencies required for the higher education setting. As Rezaei, Derakhshan, and Bagherkazemi (2011) point out, 'old standards of simply being able to score well on a standardised test of basic skills, though still appropriate, cannot be the sole criterion based on which to judge the academic success or failure of students' (p. 769). Placing too much emphasis on grades might discourage learners from engaging in research to gain knowledge, ultimately destroying their creativity and intelligence. To address this issue, it is essential to introduce motivational methods into the Algerian educational system to stimulate curiosity, foster a love for learning, and promote critical thinking, ultimately enhancing the overall educational experience and achievement of teaching goals.

In the Algerian context, where English is learned as a Foreign Language (EFL), the integration of critical thinking poses unique challenges. Similar to other non-native English-speaking countries, there is a perception that critical thinking and English are Western concepts, potentially foreign to both instructors and learners. Ideally, the advancement of English proficiency should align with the cultivation of critical thinking skills. Proficiency in English opens doors to a vast global range of information, allowing students to engage with a broader knowledge scale. Concurrently, fostering

critical thinking equips students with the ability to discern and apply information carefully for personal and collective benefit. Existing literature suggests a symbiotic relationship between students' critical thinking development and their proficiency in the English language. Hence, investigating critical thinking within the realm of EFL education in Algeria proves to be a valuable and enriching area of research.

One notable limitation of existing studies is the scarcity of research exploring the perceptions and practices of university language teachers regarding critical thinking teaching. And even the very few available prior research studies have highlighted that teachers across various disciplines acknowledge the significance of critical thinking, yet there remains a lack of clarity on what critical thinking truly entails and how to effectively integrate it into lessons. While policymakers and researchers advocate for the integration of critical thinking across disciplinary fields, this integration has not become a widespread practice in Algerian higher education. The current study seeks to address this research gap by contributing to the understanding of how university English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers perceive critical thinking and its incorporation into their teaching practices, as well as exploring its representation in the curriculum documents.

This research, therefore, delves into the perceptions and pedagogical practices of university EFL teachers regarding critical thinking and its integration into the curriculum, providing valuable insights for policymakers and educators striving to enhance critical thinking in Algerian higher education.

1.2. Rational and personal motivation

The decision to undertake this research topic was primarily driven by my personal motivation. Additionally, I recognised the theoretical necessity of exploring critical thinking within the Algerian context, an area evidently lacking in research. This motivation was particularly sparked as I embarked on my PhD journey in the UK, where critical thinking seemed a familiar concept. However, in my Algerian educational experience spanning five years, I cannot recall a single instance in which critical thinking was mentioned. As I became accustomed to the UK academic environment during my pre-session course in Canterbury, I found educators placing significant emphasis on the importance of critical thinking in the PhD writing process. Initially confused, I, along with my fellow colleagues, faced with this unfamiliar concept. As such, I found myself struggling to demystify the concept of critical thinking and to be an effective critical thinker. My interest in critical thinking deepened as I delved into research articles, revealing that the lack of understanding of critical thinking wasn't unique to Algerian students but extended to many non-Western countries. Moreover, Atkinson's (1997)

argument against incorporating critical thinking in foreign language classrooms increased my curiosity about its potential application in an EFL setting, although the majority of studies demonstrated favourable outcomes when educational approaches were tailored to incorporate critical thinking. These encouraging results caught my attention, as those who oppose the integration of critical thinking in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) contexts often base their stance on personal assumptions and perspectives, while advocates for critical thinking rely on empirical evidence. In the beginning, the topic idea was not clear, as I considered investigating the impact of direct instruction of critical thinking on EFL students to test Atkinson's theory. However, over time, I realised it might be more significant to initially explore the validity of the perceived lack of criticality and then delve into the roots and reasons behind this phenomenon. I can assert that I had this reflection well before commencing my PhD, at a time when the concept of critical thinking was still unfamiliar to me. Despite consistently being among the top students, I maintained a reserved attitude, often leaning towards silence rather than active participation. Nevertheless, I can remember a notable incident in one of the linguistic sessions, where the teacher explained two theories addressing the same phenomenon. One of these theories did not make sense to me, prompting a desire to express my thoughts. However, the fear of receiving a dismissive reaction from the teacher hindered me, as I was concerned about asserting a strong opinion on a scholar's ideas. Another illustrative example within this context involves frequent instances during my university studies when teachers were firm in awarding favourable grades, particularly during tests and exams, to students who reproduced the exact information provided in lectures or handouts. This approach puzzled me, leading me to question the necessity of copying everything to secure a high mark. These practices appeared rooted in a reluctance to encourage independent thought and a preference for students to replicate precisely what was taught, diverging from an environment conducive to nurturing critical thinking skills. Moreover, I distinctly recall an incident that occurred before forming my research topic, following my pre-sessional experience. During a conversation with a former teacher, I expressed my intention to work on critical thinking as my PhD topic. To my surprise, she commented 'it is difficult to teach them the basic skills; how do you expect us to teach critical thinking' This encounter left me taken aback, sensing a direct attribution of blame to the students' abilities. Consequently, instead of focusing solely on experimenting with variables to enhance students' critical thinking skills, I figured that investigating the state of critical thinking and its core issues was more pertinent and reasonable to ascertain whether students were genuinely the sole contributors to the perceived deficiency.

Conducting this research, I delved not only into the critical thinking cognitions and pedagogical practices of Algerian EFL university teachers, but also engaged in a process of self-reflection, evaluating my growing critical thinking abilities and challenging my own thought processes.

In addressing theoretical gaps, the absence of empirically grounded research on critical thinking within the Algerian context served as a significant motive for undertaking this study. While extensive research on critical thinking has been conducted in Western and, more recently, East Asian contexts, the Algerian perspective remains notably underexplored (see section 2.5). This study aims to fill this void by delving into the phenomenon of critical thinking within an underrepresented context in the existing international knowledge base.

The conception of this research, therefore, emerged from a combination of personal reflections, immersion in a new environment fostering critical thinking, and initial readings of pertinent literature. This led to the formulation of an empirical study focusing on the state of critical thinking and the perspectives and pedagogical practices of teachers. The overarching goal is to introduce critical thinking as a crucial 21st-century skill within the Algerian context, emphasising its integration into higher education curriculum documents and practical implementation in classrooms.

1.3. Significance of the study

The progress of any society is intricately linked to its educational system, and in the context of Algeria, there is a pressing need for a curriculum that fosters critical thinking skills. The current curriculum falls short in providing learners with the necessary skills to effectively navigate life's challenges. To address this, a transformative curriculum is essential, one that not only enriches content but also revolutionises teaching methods, classroom dynamics, and assessment approaches. The integration of critical thinking skills into the curriculum holds the potential to empower EFL learners in Algeria to independently confront and solve challenges. This integration is crucial for several reasons. First, learners actively engaged in their learning journey gain the ability to self-monitor and assess their progress. Second, critical thinking skills contribute to a more meaningful learning experience, steering away from rote memorisation, motivating learners, fostering improvement, and nurturing critical thinking abilities. Third, the Algerian Ministry of Education stands to benefit from the study's findings, gaining insights to enhance the infusion of critical thinking skills into various educational domains, potentially prompting a transformative shift in content, classroom management, teaching methods, and assessment practices. Additionally, EFL teachers can use these guidelines to enhance their teaching approaches. Ultimately, the outcomes of this study - Which, to the best of my

knowledge, is the first one that explored the university curriculum documents - aim to enlighten EFL teachers, policymakers, and curriculum designers in Algeria, promoting a broader understanding of the significance of critical thinking skills. Ultimately, the outcomes of this study—which, to the best of my knowledge, is first to explore university curriculum documents—aim to enlighten EFL teachers, policymakers, and curriculum designers in Algeria. Particularly, the study highlights the need for incorporating critical thinking skills into the curriculum, which could lead to more effective teaching strategies and improved student outcomes. For EFL teachers, this might involve adopting new pedagogical approaches that foster analytical and evaluative skills in students. Policymakers could use the findings to develop educational policies that prioritize critical thinking as a key component of the language learning process. Curriculum designers might revise existing materials or create new ones that integrate critical thinking exercises, ensuring that students are better prepared for the complexities of real-world communication and problem-solving.

Empirical investigation into the implementation of critical thinking has fallen behind, leaving certain questions unanswered (Zhang, Yuan, and He, 2020). As asserted by many studies (Abrami et al., 2008; Alnofaie, 2013; Li, 2016; Wilson, 2016), there is a widely held consensus advocating for the integration of critical thinking into the English language classes. However, a notable challenge persists as teachers often lack the necessary skills and pedagogical knowledge, as identified in studies by Zhang, Yuan, and He (2020) and Li (2016). Furthermore, Huber and Kuncel (2016) highlight a notable scarcity in research, particularly in understanding how EFL teachers grasp the term and how effectively they teach it in university classrooms. This thesis is, therefore, significant as it seeks to offer insights into critical thinking perspectives and instructional practices of Algerian EFL university educators. By examining the teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking, the study aims to reveal pertinent information about the depth of their understanding and awareness of this cognitive skill. Moreover, the research explores teachers' perspectives on the development of critical thinking in their students and scrutinises their own pedagogical approaches. Consequently, the findings may illuminate the progress of critical thinking skills in the Algerian context and pinpoint the influencing factors. This information holds the potential to address the disparity between the theoretical promotion of critical thinking development, as advocated by teachers, and its practical implementation. For future researchers in this field, the study may identify gaps requiring further exploration, contributing unique insights to the literature on critical thinking in the Algerian educational context.

Moreover, This study holds practical significance as it provides a platform for Algerian EFL university teachers to express their views and perspectives on critical thinking. Interpretive research emphasises exploring a phenomenon through participants' insights and conceptualisations, making this approach particularly valuable. The research is grounded in the belief that understanding university EFL teachers' perceptions of critical thinking could be crucial for shaping future directions in Algeria's policy and practice. By uncovering the challenges teachers face and identifying the necessary support, this study's findings offer valuable implications and recommendations for educational reforms by the Ministry of Higher Education (this is discussed further in chapter 7). Sponsored by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research as part of broader government initiatives to enhance the educational system, this thesis will be shared with the MHESR, providing research-based evidence for educational authorities and policymakers. While the research may have limitations in terms of participant number, its findings could be argued as transferable, given the centralised nature of Algeria's educational system and a management structure implying uniformity across universities. Consequently, the results of this study are likely to be applicable and relevant to other university teachers throughout the country.

1.4. Aims and research questions

In light of the issues outlined in sections 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3, and given the scant research on critical thinking in Algeria, this qualitative case study research seeks to examine the state of critical thinking in Algerian university EFL classes. Thus, providing current evidence regarding the existence of this concept within this under-represented context. This study addresses the following research questions and aims:

- **RQ1. To what extent does Algerian higher education encourage the teaching of critical thinking skills?**

This question aims to examine the representation of critical thinking in the EFL curriculum documents disseminated by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR). It seeks to investigate whether there are indications of critical thinking being incorporated into the educational objectives across all subjects. This investigation holds significance as it establishes a foundational understanding of the state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes. It also sheds light on whether policymakers and curriculum designers take critical thinking into account when formulating guidelines and objectives.

- **RQ2. To what extent has critical thinking moved from theory to actual educational practices?**

This question aims to Examine the degree to which teachers attempt to incorporate the ministry guidelines and translate them into practical strategies for fostering critical thinking among students (if there are any educational objectives that promote critical thinking). Additionally, this question seeks to get insights into the realities of critical thinking implementation in university EFL classes. This question is important as it enables cross-checking the data and highlights the prevailing consistencies and discrepancies between how the participant teachers conceptualise critical thinking and its practice and what actually takes place in the classroom.

- **RQ3. What are university EFL teachers' perceptions of critical thinking, and the importance of its integration in their teaching?**

Through this question, the research aims to delve into the perception of Algerian EFL university teachers concerning critical thinking. This question is significant as it allows to explore whether and how EFL university teachers understand the concept of critical thinking and whether they acknowledge its importance in their teaching. Understanding teachers' perceptions is crucial because the teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking often manifest in their practices. This is noteworthy since teachers' practices are heavily influenced and shaped by their perceptions, as highlighted by Borg (2003).

- **RQ4. What practices do EFL teachers enact to, or consider would, foster EFL learners' critical thinking abilities?**

This question aims to identify the practices that teachers employ to foster critical thinking skills, as reported by participant teachers, and to highlight the challenges and barriers they encounter in the process.

As such, To address these questions, I adopted a qualitative case study research design within the interpretive paradigm. Employing document analysis, I analysed the presence of critical thinking in the three EFL university curriculum documents: the License curriculum, the Master's curriculum for Teaching English as a Foreign Language major (Didactics), and the Master's Curriculum for Literature and Civilisation major. Additionally, I conducted 10 semi-structured interviews to explore the perceptions and reported practices of EFL university teachers, as well as the obstacles to implementing critical thinking within the study context. Furthermore, I conducted 10 classroom

observation sessions to observe the actual practices of the participants in the classroom and compare them with their reported practices.

1.5. Structure of the thesis

This thesis is organised into seven chapters. This initial chapter serves as an introduction to the study. It presents the study's background and discusses the rationale and personal motivation behind conducting this research. It highlights also the significance of the research, and outlines the research questions and aims.

Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive background for the study, it offers an overview of the main educational reforms in higher education in Algeria. The subsequent section tackles the prevailing test-oriented approach in the teaching of English language within the Algerian educational system and its negative effects on the fostering of critical thinking skills. The chapter concludes with an exploration of research focused on critical thinking within the Algerian context. This presentation of the research context helps the reader construct a conceptual understanding of the background informing the current study.

Chapter 3, the literature review, delves into relevant studies related to the investigated topic. The organisation of the chapter aligns broadly with the study's research questions. It starts by demystifying the concept of critical thinking, and identifying the necessary skills and dispositions for engaging in critical thinking processes. Following this, the chapter outlines the significance of critical thinking in educational institutions and workplaces, with a specific focus on EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students. This chapter then navigates through the controversial aspects of the field, starting with the debate on whether critical thinking can be effectively taught to EFL students, the various approaches to teaching critical thinking, along with activities and strategies to nurture it in students. Then, it addresses critical thinking assessment and the pitfalls educators should be wary of when evaluating critical thinking. The chapter concludes by examining the challenges that hinder the development of critical thinking skills.

Chapter 4 outlines the research methodology utilised in the present study. It begins by providing a concise overview of the philosophical stance, touching upon the underlying ontological and epistemological principles that support the chosen interpretivist paradigm. The chapter proceeds to examine the selected research approach, research design, and the tools employed for data collection in the current study. Following this, it delves into the sampling process and offers a description of the

sample. Ultimately, the chapter concludes by exploring the approach to data analysis and addressing ethical considerations.

Chapter 5 presents the findings of the study. It addresses the four research questions through data obtained from the three research methods employed. Consequently, it is structured based on both the research questions and the research tools. The initial section delves into the findings derived from document analysis of the three EFL curriculum documents. Subsequently, the results from the semi-structured interviews are presented. The concluding section revolves around the data collected through the classroom observation.

Chapter 6 discusses the most significant findings derived from the three research tools utilised in this study, drawing connections with relevant literature. Employing methodological triangulation, the chapter integrates insights from the three research tools where applicable. The organisation of this chapter follows the sequence of the research questions. The initial section predominantly explores the findings from the analysis of three English university curriculum documents. It also incorporates insights from teachers' interviews regarding their understanding of whether and how critical thinking is represented in the curriculum documents. Moving to the second section, the chapter discussed the findings related to the second research question, focusing on teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking. Subsequently, the third section addresses findings pertinent to research questions three and four. This part involves a comparison between teachers' reported practices during interviews and their actual classroom practices regarding critical thinking as witnessed in the classroom observation. Consistencies or discrepancies between the two are examined. The chapter concludes by delving into the challenges and hindrances highlighted by participant teachers that impede their efforts and aspirations to implement critical thinking in their teaching.

Chapter 7, the concluding chapter, offers a comprehensive summary of the research. It provides also the implications and recommendations of this study across various levels. Furthermore, this chapter outlines the theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions made by this research. Acknowledging the study's limitations, recommendations for future research based on these constraints are suggested. The chapter concludes with a reflection on my PhD journey.

Chapter 2: Context of the Study

2.1. Introduction

This chapter sets a clear background to the context of the study. It starts with an introduction to the chapter, then it presents briefly the most important educational reforms in higher education in Algeria, and the implications these reforms have had on students, teachers, and the quality of teaching. The third section presents the teaching of English language in Algeria and the effects and consequences of the different teaching approaches. The fourth section attempts to shed light on the dominant approach in the Algerian education system - namely the test-oriented approach and its negative impact on the development and cultivation of thinking skills. This chapter concludes with an exploration of research conducted on critical thinking within the Algerian context.

2.2. Educational reforms in higher education

After its independence in 1962, Algeria considered the education sector as one of its major priorities, and consequently, there was a remarkable growth in its infrastructure and also in the number of students at universities all around the country even in the disadvantaged areas. In addition to that, students from primary to secondary schools were taught in Arabic for all school subjects as an act to eradicate all the remnants of the French colonisation. At university, and in order to go hand in hand with the Arabisation policy implemented at the other levels, the first year curriculum of law and economics and social and political sciences had been Arabised. However in other scientific subjects at university such as medical and technical streams, French was still the language of instruction, and that was of a crucial concern for students admitted to university with the Arabised baccalaureate. The gap in the language of instruction between secondary schools and higher education was already a challenge in the educational system (Lakehal-Ayat-Benmati, 2008). The thing which pulled the students into a circle of frustration, pressure and uncertainty about their entire futures, was explained by Entellis (1981):

Indeed, increased arabization of primary and secondary school curriculum without concurrent language uniformity at the higher levels has created enormous tensions and frustrations for those "arabisants"* unprepared to cope effectively with French-language instruction, and therefore destined to "dead-end" jobs, since nearly all openings in the public and private sectors require some level of bilingualism and, in certain fields, trilingualism.

(p.198)

In search of the most effective education system, Algeria's higher education witnessed several changes, with the major reforms being the classical system (1971) and the LMD system (2003).

The classical system (1971) is described as 4 years of Bachelor's, 2 years of Master's, and 4 years of Doctorate. In this system compensation between modules is used, and 5 is considered an eliminatory mark which means that if someone gets a low grade under 10 and above 5 out of 20, he/she can compensate that module with another module in which he/she scored well - that is above 10 -; however, scoring 5 or less in any module necessitates sitting for a resit exam (Lakehal-Ayat-Benmati, 2008). In the case of a student failing to pass the regular exam, there are two resit exams: the first in June and the second in September which offers a great opportunity to pass to the following year. This reform had fallen short of the international education standards which led the Ministry of Higher Education and policymakers to consider an alternative system suited to the fast changes of the globalised world, and this alternative was the LMD system (Abdaoui and Grine, 2020).

The decision to adopt the LMD system (Licence, Master, Doctorate) in Algeria was not random: it was the result of a year of discussion with a panel of experts shaping the National Commission of the Educational System (Ahouari- Idri, 2015). The three-cycle system was finally put into practice in the academic year 2003/2004 after it had been first established in Europe in 1999 (Mami, 2013). This system has shown very positive and satisfying results in many European countries. In the LMD system, the bachelor's degree is granted after 3 years of studies (6 semesters) while it takes 2 years to get the master's degree. Courses, under this system, are comprised of teaching units to be covered in each semester (such as fundamental units, methodological units, and cross-disciplinary units), except for the fourth semester of the master's programme which is devoted to training and conducting a research study before being granted the master degree. The doctorate degree requires 3 years of research to defend a thesis which can be extended (Abdaoui and Grine, 2020). Regarding the LMD evaluation system, students are assessed for each unit by a regular continuous evaluation throughout the whole semester or a final exam, or most likely a mixed assessment of the two where the final exam usually weighs up more than the continuous evaluation (50%-70%) (Decree 712/18 dated 03 November 2011). The LMD system offers new assessment procedures as well as innovative teaching and learning approaches where the role of the teacher changes from spoon-feeding the knowledge to students, to taking a step back and involving the students more in the learning process. Learners hence are expected to be engaged and active in the classroom, and teachers are viewed more as guides and facilitators of the classroom interaction.

The Ministry of National Education has not only adopted these reforms but has also exerted significant efforts to align them with a compatible teaching approach, thereby transitioning from traditional methods to a competency-based approach (Baghoussi and El Ouchdi, 2019), an approach

which is believed to pave the way for a new generation of students that possess skills like critical thinking, autonomy, and creativity.

Although the intentions behind adopting the LMD system were clearly to adapt to the world's fast changes and globalisation, to provide high-quality education, to promote the students' autonomy and skills which are needed for life-long learning, and to make the Algerian diploma recognised at the international level (Saad et al., 2005), this system was criticised on several grounds. First of all, teachers seemed to be unhappy and dissatisfied for not being involved in the overall process of the reform: they were to apply what was dictated on them by policy makers in a top-down process (Ghezouli, 2019). Metatla (2016) highlights the contradiction of what official sources try to show by celebrating the growth of the infrastructure and the number of students, and the frustration and tension experienced and expressed by parents, teachers and faculty staff in reality.

The transformation from the classical system to the LMD system was not as smooth as expected because of the absence of collaboration between all stakeholders (policy makers, inspectors, teachers, parents, students, etc.) and the inadequate evaluation and consultation, resulting in conflict between students of the two systems. LMD students manifested for equivalence with classical system students in future careers and job opportunities whereas classical system students contested against any potential equivalence with LMD students, as they believe that degrees obtained from the classical system are superior and more valuable. Metatla (2016) also believes that the decision to adopt the LMD system was not a result of a thoughtful and deep vision, and that taking out a system which proved to be successful in a particular context, and attempting to imitate it in a different context without a thorough revision of the entire system and its background was not the most brilliant idea. It would have been better to attempt innovation instead of imitation, or at least to adapt the system in a way which works best to our context and background.

2.3. ELT in Algeria

Being the language of globalisation, science and technology and an international language that is used worldwide, English has gained an essential status in the Algerian educational system. It was first introduced in 2001 as one of the results of the educational reform policy. English has been taught in the first year of middle school until university as a second foreign language. It was incorporated to build up more networks with people from different parts of the world, and for Algeria to be more involved in global economic, political and cultural domains. The Ministry of National Education (MNE) (2006) points out:

The aim behind teaching English in Algeria is to help our society to integrate harmoniously into the modern world by getting involved fully and effectively with the world multilingual communities that use this language in all kinds of interactions. Thanks to the sharing and exchanging of ideas, scientific experiments, cultural and economic capital, this involvement will enable a better understanding of oneself and others. In such a perspective, the old and narrow utilitarian conception of English learning will change and thus leading to a more daring approach where citizens will not be consumers, but actors and agents of change. Therefore, everyone will have the opportunity to get access to science, technology, and world culture....

(p.3)

As previously discussed, the Algerian educational system has witnessed several policy changes at the level of teaching approaches. Communicative language teaching (CLT) was one of the most recognised approaches as it was a reaction to the traditional methods which were based on translation and acquiring fixed knowledge of grammatical structures. In the 1970s, there was a significant shift away from traditional language teaching methods, such as Audiolingual and Grammar-Translation methods, which gained momentum globally. These methods, which prioritised grammatical competence through repetitive practice and drilling, fell out of favour. The prevailing belief that language learning meant accumulating a set of grammatically correct sentences was challenged. Instead, attention shifted towards the broader concept of communicative competence. This encompassed not only grammatical proficiency but also the knowledge and skills needed for effective language use in various communicative contexts. Traditional approaches, relying on deductive grammar teaching and prioritising rote memorisation, did not incorporate this holistic understanding. The emergence of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in response to this paradigm shift marked a new era in language education. CLT emphasised authentic communication, inductive learning, and student-centred approaches. It acknowledged that language learning extends beyond grammar, with a focus on practical communication skills. The notion of communicative competence, rooted in linguistics, gained interest as the overarching goal of language teaching, leading to a re-evaluation of syllabuses and methodologies. In planning language courses within a communicative approach, grammar was no longer the starting point, signifying the need for innovative teaching strategies aligned with the principles of CLT (Richards, 2006). However, the communication-based approach was not appropriately adopted in Algeria as schools were not well prepared in terms of the syllabus content and the required conditions for a communicative environment. Benmoussat and Benmoussat (2018a, p.63) argue that 'English classrooms rarely met the criteria of purposefulness and contextualization that defined CLT tasks at the level of the

intended aims and objectives'. They add that this approach has been always debatable as it stands against the traditional concept of "good teaching and learning" where accuracy is prioritised over fluency and communication. Despite the fact that the main objective of the General Inspectorate of English behind applying this teaching approach is to develop communicative skills 'this has rarely been reflected in the classroom where emphasis has been on the development of the reading comprehension skills, vocabulary building and mastery of the structural patterns for the sole purposes of passing the Baccaureate exam' (Benmoussat and Benmoussat, 2018a, p.65).

Having successfully passed the Baccaureate exam, some students decide to enrol at university in a major in EFL, while others are oriented to it only based on the mark they achieve on the Baccaureate exam and it has nothing to do with their personal choice. Usually, those students are aged between 18-22 years old, their first language is Arabic, but they speak a dialect of Arabic or Berber, and they learn French as a first foreign language from the third grade of primary school. Moreover, students who join this course are to study for three years to be granted a Bachelor's degree or "licence" degree. In this three-year period, all the modules present a body of knowledge that conforms to the main characteristics of the English language such as grammar, vocabulary, phonetics, TEFL or didactics, oral expression, written expression, linguistics, sociolinguistics, sociology, translation, civilization, literature, and applied linguistics. These courses vary slightly from one English department to another throughout all the universities across the country. Furthermore, in some universities students are asked to choose their field of expertise in literature and civilisation, applied linguistics or didactics, at the beginning of the third year of the licence degree, yet in other universities, students have the right to specialise only when they decide to proceed with their studies and obtain a Master's degree.

Graduates holding a Bachelor's degree are allowed to teach in schools, but they face difficulties when they are employed in international companies, or when they travel to study abroad as their command of the basic knowledge of the language is not sufficient to interact successfully in such situations. They discover that they need more profound competencies and skills to communicate effectively. Hadjoui and Kheladi (2014) argue that:

The English courses exit-profile facilitates for the "licence" holders to teach straightforwardly in the educational Schools; however... then they realise that successful communication is highly complex and involves much more than the vocabulary items and grammar rules they were taught during their graduate studies.

As a result of the deficiencies demonstrated by the previous teaching approaches, the Algerian educational system decided by 2003 to embrace another approach to teaching which was believed to solve the above-mentioned issues, and to meet the required competencies of the 21st century. This approach is called the Competency-Based approach which was introduced in the US approximately 60 years ago and was first employed in vocational training programmes. This approach was not intended to be adopted in educational settings, but given its effectiveness and the generated positive results, the scope of its implementation was expanded to reach various professional domains (Bowden, 2004). Among these domains, the CBA was applied in the field of foreign and second language teaching, and it was by 1990 that the Competency-Based Language Teaching (CBLT) was well recognised but mainly in teaching programmes designed for refugees and immigrants (Richards and Rodgers, 2001). This approach aims primarily to move from teacher-centeredness to student-centeredness, from content-based to project-based teaching. It also encourages learners' autonomy and the use of higher-order thinking skills by allowing students to take responsibility for their learning, fostering independence and self-motivation. It promotes critical and creative thinking by engaging students in real-world problem-solving projects, where they apply, analyse, and synthesize knowledge. Teachers act as facilitators, providing continuous feedback and creating a supportive environment that encourages exploration and collaboration, thereby enhancing students' ability to think critically and creatively, and the role of students changes from passive recipients to active independent individuals. This seems too good to be true as some studies showed that the execution of this approach in fieldwork was not as expected. After an examination of the implementation of the Competency-based Approach with the Project-based approach between theory and practice in Baccalaureate English class, Baghoussi and El Ouchdi (2019) revealed that teachers found it challenging to apply those approaches in the classroom, mainly due to the teachers' lack of training and lack of knowledge of those approaches and to how to apply them efficiently and effectively.

2.4. The dominance of the exam-centric approach

In searching for the most pertinent approach to teaching English, many propositions were put on the table to move more towards student-centred classrooms rather than teacher-centred classrooms, to get rid of traditional teaching approaches and to embrace more modern communicative approaches such as competency-based approach. However, this was ink on paper as

all that mattered and still matters is “achievement” even at the expense of students’ academic development.

Teaching the English language has witnessed numerous deficiencies in Algeria due to the teach-to-the-test approach where teachers emphasise particular aspects of the language that will be part of tests, ignoring vital skills that students need to develop to cope with the new century demands, to sustain high-quality education, and to provide the best learning experience (Bemoussat and Bouyakoub, 2019). This teaching approach can be clearly exhibited when preparing for the Baccalaureate exam which refers to the last secondary school-leaving exam that allows students to embark on their higher education journey. This high-stakes exam has been always crucial and very stressful for students, parents and the general public where school classes, conventionally, have never been adequate to score well. And here comes one of the most popular aspects of the teach-to-the-test approach which is remedial lessons. Parents pay considerable amounts of money on these out-side schooling remedial classes offered by teachers, and students spend most of their supposed leisure time and holidays preparing and practising exam samples and techniques. This preparation sometimes can take place even before the academic year begins.

The aim behind these additional classes is primarily to go through as many past papers and practice tests as possible, because, according to teachers, this will increase the chances of success for all the students: ‘they believe the best way to prepare students for exams is by doing past papers’ (Lam,1994, p.91), and what helps in that is the small number of students and the inclusive and thorough explanation of teachers to each single aspect in the programme, they even re-practise the exercises they have gone through in the classroom. Moreover, one cannot deny that these remedial classes are considered as a great additional income to teachers (Benmoussat, 2003).

The teach-to-the-test approach or exam-centric education can be therefore defined as the process of spending much of the teachers’ time and effort in and outside class in implementing pedagogical practices and techniques to prepare students for exams. Hence by focusing on what is expected to take place in tests and marginalising what is not, teachers are at risk of losing teaching credibility and assessing reliability. Indeed, teaching and testing are two intertwined concepts worldwide, the existence of one necessitates the other. One also cannot deny the vital role testing plays as a tool of assessment in checking the students’ improvement, evaluating how much and how well learners have learned, and assessing even how efficient was the teaching process. Nonetheless, focusing on the test outcomes at large, and selecting to teach exam-oriented materials would become a serious

challenge for the life-long objectives of education (Benmoussat and Benmoussat, 2018b). Unfortunately, many researchers and educators are nowadays questioning the value of tests for being tools to assess students' reproduction of fixed bodies of knowledge rather than tools to indicate their real skills and abilities development (Schweisfurth, 2011). Even more concerning is the widespread adoption of this pedagogical approach across various educational institutions, extending to universities. To the extent that teachers, students, and parents become accustomed to it, it becomes ingrained that assigning significant importance solely to achievement and final results is the essence of the teaching philosophy. It is argued that 'If schools largely test and award grades for factual recall, teachers will, therefore, stress memorization and recall in their teaching, possibly at the expense of communication skills and critical thinking that are vitally important for students to possess' (The Glossary of Education Reform, 2013). Consequently, Algerian EFL learners join their academic courses in higher education institutions lacking the communicative abilities and analytical skills as a result of the test-oriented English language teaching education they were exposed to in secondary school (Benmoussat and Bouyakoub, 2019). Benmoussat and Benmoussat (2018a) comment:

Regrettably, seldom is testing processed "communicatively"; most Algerian EFL teachers prefer to cling tenaciously to the teach-to-the-test approach "principles". This preference is closely related to the notion of "achievement" which means nothing more than giving the opportunity to the learner to score well on standardized tests and high-stakes exams.

(p.63)

2.5. Critical thinking in the Algerian context

Some of the 21st century's most significant skills that should be integrated, arguably, in the Algerian EFL context are summarised by Mitchell, Skinner and White (2010) as critical thinking and creativity in addition to leadership and teamwork. The current age differs significantly from earlier times due to the global presence of communication technology and the widespread dissemination of varied perspectives, including the potential for misinformation to spread rapidly through social media platforms. Throughout the day, numerous messages seek to inform, yet, in various settings - be it at home or outside, at the workplace or online, or in the marketplace - we are confronted with arguments and propositions designed to take advantage of those lacking a refined sense of critical thinking (Hardly and Boon, 2023) (see section 3.3). Consequently, the promotion of such skills creates a turning away from a memorisation-based education to an analytical, rational and meaningful learning experience that not only shapes the students' academic life, but also seeks long-

term benefits needed later in the workplace. Moreover, critical thinking should be developed in EFL students year by year as a good command of it requires graduate efforts to be built up. Barnaby (2016, p.40) asserts that 'students are expected to evaluate and interpret data in year one, critically analyse in year two and accurately deploy established techniques of analysis in year three'. And here lies the problem as EFL teachers find themselves dealing with students who lack critical thinking and autonomous skills as a result of the large reliance on the exam-centric education of previous educational levels, Benmoussat and Benmoussat (2018b, p. 35) comment 'As highlighted by numerous studies, it should be noted that the hegemony of the teach-to-the-test approach highly prevailing in Algerian EFL classrooms and overtly driving the curriculum has negatively affected the quality of English Language Education'. A quantum leap is, therefore, necessary in the Algerian EFL classes to move from reliance on rote learning and accumulated knowledge to be regurgitated in exams, to a more efficient way of knowledge acquisition which is based on analysing, evaluating and verifying information, and encourages questioning and generation of multiple interpretations.

The field of critical thinking has witnessed in the last decade a large growth of interest in the significance of integrating critical thinking worldwide (Dong, Li, and Chang, 2023), and Algeria is no exception. However, very little research has been carried out to investigate the position of critical thinking in the different Algerian educational levels. El Ouchdi-Mirali (2015), for instance, conducted a case study on fifth-grade primary school students to investigate the most implemented teaching approach. The findings revealed that the teaching and learning process is still dominated by rote learning, memorisation, and recalling of exact knowledge in exams. Hence, no traces for the cultivation of critical thinking, despite the fact that the competency-based approach which is adopted encourages the development of critical thinking skills.

Along similar lines, Belhamidi (2014) conducted a three-phase research study where the first phase involved distributing questionnaires to teachers to gather their conceptions about critical thinking; analysing fourth grade middle school textbook; and observing the teaching process and instructional practices. In phase two, an experiment was carried out where a model comprising of three core factors (collaborating, questioning, and encouraging students to engage in the process of thinking critically) was introduced. In phase three, the Cornell Class-Reasoning test (CCRT) was used to assess the effect of the treatment. The results of the first phase revealed that teachers are aware of the importance of critical thinking, yet are overwhelmed by the test-oriented approach hence very limited time, if any, was devoted to higher-order thinking activities. Moreover, after the textbook analysis, it appears that it doesn't relatively encourage the students to use their critical thinking.

However, the results of the experiment using questioning, collaborating and encouraging techniques seem to stimulate the students' critical thinking abilities.

Ameziane and Guendouzi (2015) examined the concept of digital competence in middle and secondary school textbooks, and its impact on the students' critical thinking. It was revealed that the acquired digital competence from the textbooks has no feasible effect on developing critical thinking skills. Another experimental research was conducted by Djamaa (2018) to examine the influence applying film literature course has on critical thinking skills of third-year EFL students. This study was intended to examine five critical thinking abilities: analysis, inference, evaluation, induction, and deduction. The results showed no significant difference between the control and experimental groups in critical thinking tests; however, the experimental group outperformed the control group only in the inference ability.

On their part, Abdaoui and Grine (2020) attempted to investigate the impact of university teaching under the LMD system on the development of critical thinking abilities of 28 first-year EFL students and other 27 third-year EFL students at Guelma University. They used the Watson-Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal Test (WGCTAT) to measure students' critical thinking skills. It was deduced from this study that the university teaching programme under the LMD system doesn't nurture the development of higher-order thinking skills.

In another investigation conducted by Melouah (2017), the primary emphasis was on exploring the impact of culture on the teaching and learning of critical thinking within the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) tertiary education in Algeria. The study exclusively employed interviews as its research tool. The findings suggested that Algerian cultural values might not provide a conducive environment for the cultivation of critical thought, potentially hindering the development and application of critical thinking skills. Moreover, the educational context itself may not be conducive to fostering critical thinking practices. The presence of traditional practices and values deeply rooted in Algerian culture could pose obstacles to the nurturing of abilities related to critical thinking

From the aforementioned studies, it is clear that there has been some examination of critical thinking, whether by investigating teaching approaches, examining the impact of activities presumed to enhance critical thinking, or assessing and reflecting on teaching materials. However, these studies seem insufficient, given that pedagogical issues persist without resolution and there has been limited change in the educational system in recent years.

In the Algerian context, there is a significant gap in research focused on critical thinking within university-level EFL classes. Most existing studies have concentrated on other educational levels, leaving a void in understanding how critical thinking is integrated and practiced at the university level. Furthermore, these studies have not utilised document analysis as a methodological approach. This study addresses this gap by being the first to examine university curriculum documents for evidence of critical thinking integration in Algerian EFL classes. By combining document analysis with semi-structured interviews and classroom observations, this research not only enriches the understanding of critical thinking integration but also offers methodological insights for future research. The study underscores the importance of examining curricular content to uncover the root causes of pedagogical challenges and highlights the limited attention given to this crucial educational objective within the higher education context in Algeria.

Consequently, there is a pressing need for extensive research on the concept in the Algerian context, particularly within the university setting where critical thinking is considered a fundamental educational objective. This highlights the importance of the present study in making a meaningful contribution to this area and addressing the dearth of research on such a pivotal matter.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

3.1. Introduction

This chapter reviews the relevant literature related to the topic under investigation. First, it starts with an attempt to demystify the concept of critical thinking from different perspectives highlighting the required skills and dispositions to engage in the process of critical thinking. After that, the importance of critical thinking in schools and workplaces, particularly to EFL students is also detailed. This chapter, then, tackles the most controversial issues in the field, starting from the possibility of teaching critical thinking to EFL students where it discusses the debate of whether critical thinking is a social practice or a skill which can be acquired. The different approaches to teaching critical thinking, activities and strategies to foster it in the students are also discussed. Moving to the issue of critical thinking assessment and the traps that educators need to consider when assessing critical thinking. This chapter ends by considering the barriers which lie in the way of developing critical thinking.

3.2. Defining the Concept:

While the increasing volume of critical thinking literature demonstrates its widespread acknowledgment, there exists a significant lack of consensus concerning the concept's definition (Fabian, 2015). Critical thinking has been always recognised as an unclear term to define, and a difficult concept to understand and to put into practice (Hadley and Boon, 2023). Halanon (1995) in supporting this point claims that 'critical thinking scholarship is in a mystified state. No single definition of critical thinking is widely accepted' (p. 75). On the same lines, Siegel (1988) affirms that 'despite widespread recent interest in critical thinking in education, there is no clear agreement concerning the referent of the term'(p. 5). Although there is no consensus among researchers on providing a uniform definition of critical thinking, it has received distinct definitions and interpretations. Ennis (1985), one of the major contributors to the critical thinking movement, defines it as 'reasonable, reflective thinking that is focused on deciding what to believe or do' (p.45). Similarly, Norris (1985), stressing the reasoning and rational foundation of critical thinking, explains that it is the ability to compare different arguments while operating one's own logic and reasoning. He states,

Thinking critically can be defined as rationally deciding what to do or believe...Being a critical thinker of course implies assessing the views of others and one's own views according to acceptable standards of appraisal. One must also be productive in the sense of conceiving of alternative courses of action and candidates for belief, before critically appraising which

alternative to choose. People must be able to produce reliable observations, make sound inferences and offer reasonable hypotheses. Finally, one must have the disposition to think productively and critically about issues, or else no amount of skill in doing so will be helpful.

(p.40)

In this sense, one should bring together different insights and perspectives, then reasonably analyse and deduce a conclusion to ultimately come up with an original view, Norris (1985) also highlights that having the skills to think critically isn't enough unless there is an inclination to put these skills into practice. Emphasising reasoning abilities, Siegel (1988), another proponent of the critical thinking movement, defines it as 'the educational cognate of rationality', and the critical thinker as 'the individual who is appropriately moved by reasons' (p. 25). Unlike Norris and Siegel's focus on reasoning, some researchers argue for the significance of communication and its positive correlation with critical thinking. In other words, improving students' communication abilities is crucial for enhancing their critical thinking skills. In parallel, possessing the ability to solve problems, to perceive things from different positions, and to form original views and arguments must result in a good communicator (Loacher et al, 1984 cited in Hay, Ellen A. 1987). Hence, the knowledge and critical thinking skills one may have will not be helpful unless there is an ability to communicate them.

Paul (1994) provides a distinct definition where he differentiates between two versions of critical thinking. Weak critical thinking involves mere theoretical learning of the skill without any real application. However, strong critical thinking entails putting that skill into practice and operating higher-order thinking such as analysing, synthesising, and evaluating in real life situations.

On his account, Davis (2015) notes that critical thinking means different things to different people; He also believes that the philosophical definition of critical thinking does not serve to develop a critical attitude or contribute to being a critical citizen. It rather seeks only to gain an understanding of that concept that is described by Williams as the 'most difficult one' (1976, p.74).

Davis (2015) notes that the teaching of critical thinking is as controversial as the concept itself. If teaching critical thinking considers developing the ability to think rationally, analyse arguments, and build up one's own judgement, Davis explains that that would be significant in education; however, he also states that 'educating for radical social and political change(i.e., "critical pedagogy") may be seen as less desirable' (2015, p.42). Surprisingly, he adds that others are not in favour of teaching critical thinking at all. For example, the Texas Republican Party opposes the teaching of critical

thinking because they conceive developing that skill as subversive and threatening to the 'fixed beliefs' and 'parental authority' (Strauss, 2012).

In his attempt to define the concept, Davis (2015) adapted the Delphi Report definition (Facione, 1990) - where the American Philosophical Association gathered a panel of 46 experts to come up with a conclusive definition of critical thinking. He points out two different categories of critical thinking: cognitive elements and propensity elements (outlined below), and then adds the term action as a crucial element to think critically, i.e., the practical engagement in an actual task.

In the cognitive elements, Davis (2015) identifies, on one part, critical thinking as arguments where he sees critical thinking as a skill that can be developed, and allows the students that are at the same time citizens to use an 'intellectual activity' (p. 49) to analyse, assess arguments, and be able to detect fallacies and bias. Furthermore, critical thinking is reflected in the ability of decision-making as decisions are made based on weighing, comparing, and interpreting arguments resulting in judgments which is fundamentally argumentation. On the other part, Davis identifies critical thinking as reflective thinking which refers to the process of thinking about one's own thought and knowledge, i.e. to reflect and be aware of previous and current experiences.

The second category of critical thinking is critical thinking as propensity elements. Davis (2015) states that propensity elements involve dispositions, attitudes, or inclination to engage in critical thinking that is totally different from being able to think critically. He suggests that dispositions are not the ability to identify, analyse and interpret arguments and then form judgments, it is rather a 'frame of mind which is necessary for exercising critical thinking' (p. 55), which includes one's will and intrinsic motivation to practise criticality.

Yet, according to Davis (2015), these approaches to defining critical thinking are still recognized as limited if there is no dedication to action, and so he further emphasises the importance of making a stand and being active in operating critical thinking.

Consequently, acquiring cognitive judgmental abilities, being ready and willing to practise these, and actually putting them into action is what is meant by critical thinking.

Brown and Keely (2007) took a different direction in defining critical thinking. They consider 'Critical Thinking as an awareness of a set of interrelated questions, an ability to pose and answer critical questions at appropriate times and a desire to actively use the critical questions' (p.2). This account of critical thinking might be perceived as limited compared to the preceding one because it tackles

merely the aspect of asking questions. However, as Davis (2015) notes 'one definition will never satisfy everyone' (p.48).

Halpern (1996) in his attempt to define critical thinking highlights the aspects of critical thinking outcomes and usefulness, and the role critical thinking plays in making rational decisions and dealing with problems, he claims that,

The use of those cognitive skills or strategies that increase the probability of a desirable outcome. It is used to describe thinking that is purposeful, reasoned, and goal directed—the kind of thinking involved in solving problems, formulating inferences, calculating likelihoods, and making decisions, when the thinker is using skills that are thoughtful and effective for the particular context and type of thinking task.

(p.06)

Similar to Davis's (2015) definition, Sternberg and Halpern (2020) are also advocates of stressing the fact that critical thinking is not a set of skills and abilities only, but is also the propensity and disposition to practise those skills. They argue that critical thinking includes the desire to take part in challenging tasks 'demonstrate flexible and open-minded thinking' (p.3), and maintain more productive strategies.

Reviewing some of the literature, it can be deduced that critical thinking involves the ability to recognise assumptions and question their validity, to separate between facts and views, to be able to evaluate and build up one's own judgments, and then reflect on them. It is not merely about cognitive abilities, however, it is also about the readiness and desire to exercise critical thinking in real-life activities. Critical thinking is not acquired intuitively: it requires deliberate planning and continuous training and practice. Thus, universities may consider moving forward from a superficial view of knowledge to more sophisticated forms of thought and higher intellectual processes by considering changes in the curriculum and infusing critical thinking in all subjects as an educational ideal.

This following discussion delves more into the distinction between critical thinking skills and dispositions.

3.2.1. Thinking abilities

Many scholars and theorists have identified lists of critical thinking skills as it is called by Facione (1990), abilities by Ennis (1991), or competencies by Fisher and Scriven (1997). These lists have some similarities, but they differ in terms of the conceptualization of critical thinking, and the targeted

educational level (Hitchcock, 2020). Before discussing critical thinking abilities, it is worth mentioning first critical thinking components from which critical abilities have emerged.

Anderson, Krathwohl and Bloom (2001) identify a model of critical thinking which is believed to clarify what general abilities constitute critical thinking. The components of this model are briefly explained below:

- **Knowledge**, Refers to the amount of knowledge one has through experiences, observation or research.
- **Comprehension**, the ability to grasp, or the process of understanding and making connections of the perceived knowledge.
- **Inference**, drawing good guesses on things about which one doesn't have sufficient evidence.
- **Application**, the ability to make use of the knowledge which one has.
- **Analysis**, the ability to see the different constituents of something; to break it up into pieces and to see how they connect altogether.
- **Synthesis**, how well one can generate conclusions by combining and merging ideas.
- **Evaluation**, making judgments about the appropriateness, validity and reliability of information.

Hitchcock (2020) proposes another set of critical thinking components which is slightly more sophisticated than the old model, which he describes as "mental acts and events". These components are: observing, feeling, wondering, imagining, inferring, knowledge, experimenting, consulting, identifying and analysing arguments, judging and finally deciding.

Moving to critical thinking skills which are generated from the aforementioned critical thinking components, Hitchcock (2020) introduces the following abilities:

Observational abilities, the ability to attentively and accurately observe and notice what is going on in the surrounding environment, not that only but also being able to express what has been observed. A good command of these abilities will remove the barriers in the way of reliable observations. Observational abilities are mentioned in Ennis's (1991) list.

Emotional abilities, emotions which are considered as a driving force in the process of critical thinking such as puzzlement and curiosity; and satisfaction at achieving a particular goal.

Questioning abilities, the ability to ask thoughtful and precise questions which are not based on pre-judgments and assumptions. This type is in Ennis's (1991) list as well.

Imaginative abilities, ability to imagine the most accurate explanation of a particular event or issue. These abilities are in Halpern's (1998) list.

Inferential abilities, the ability to generate conclusions using inductive or deductive reasoning. It is widely supported as a general critical thinking ability by a range of scholars (Ennis, 1991; Facione and Facione, 1990; Paul, 1992; Willingham, 2007).

Experimenting abilities, the ability to design and carry out an experiment is not only unique to experimental researches, but also are important in daily life. Experimental abilities are much more appreciated than observational abilities when developing knowledge (Ennis, 1991; Facione, 1990).

Consulting abilities, the skill of verifying the credibility and appropriateness of different resources when searching for information to solve problems, also included in Ennis's (1991) list.

Argument Analysis abilities, one of the most agreed on critical thinking abilities (Ennis, 1991; Halpern, 1998, Facione, 1990), it is the ability to identify and analyse arguments; to weigh evidence and draw one's own authentic conclusions.

Judging skills and deciding skills, being confident in one's ability to make reasonable judgments; and decision-making abilities.

The identification of critical thinking abilities will guide educators and academics in designing activities which focus on these skills, and hence fostering the process of critical thinking; it can actually help also in developing critical thinking tests as well.

3.2.2. Critical thinking dispositions

It has been always believed among scholars that critical thinking dispositions are as vital as critical thinking skills (Ennis, 1991; Dewey, 2017; McPeck, 1991; Norris, 1992; Paul, 1990). Critical thinking dispositions are habits of mind, propensities, inclination and willingness to engage in a certain way of thinking in different situations (Siegel, 1999).

Unlike critical thinking skills which have been investigated long ago and proved the possibility of being assessed using a number of tests, critical thinking dispositions have been always ignored because of the difficulty and ambiguity of their assessment. Furthermore, and despite the acknowledgement of the importance of critical thinking dispositions in thinking critically, some researchers claim that there are no proof for the existence of a particular mental basis responsible

for such propensities which take part in the critical thinking process, and assuming that is academically confusing and misleading (Bailin et al., 1999).

Currently, there are two standardised tests which claim to assess critical thinking dispositions: the California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) (Facione and Facione, 1992), and the Critical Thinking Disposition Scale (CTDS) (Soso, 2013). The CCTDI was designed to measure seven habits of mind which are: open-mindedness, truth-seeking, confidence, maturity, inquisitiveness, systematicity, and analyticity. Some academics, however, doubt the validity and reliability of that measurement (Walsh, Seldomridge and Bardros, 2007). The CTDS was developed to assess only two essential critical thinking dispositions: reflective scepticism and critical openness. This scale has received some positive feedback for being consistent and valid to some extent (Hogan, 2020).

A number of scholars in the field of critical thinking researched the concept of dispositions and came up with lists of critical thinking dispositions: some of them overlap and others differ (Ennis, 1996; Facione and Facione, 1992, Halpern, 1998; Jay and Tishman, 1993). However as Sarah et al. (2020) attempted to develop and check the validity of a new critical thinking disposition test called the Student-Educator Negotiated Critical Thinking Dispositions Scale (SENCTDS), they generated thirteen critical thinking dispositions which seem inclusive and quite interesting as it is very uncommon, if it ever happened, to involve students along with their instructors in the process of designing such a measurement (SENCTDS) by incorporating their opinions and reflections on what composes critical thinking. Therefore, a group of 31 students with 10 academics were gathered throughout four collective intelligence sessions using the Interactive Management Reflection to identify the following core dispositions adopted in the SENCTD scale:

Reflection, refers to the tendency to reflect on one's own thinking, perspectives, and attitudes; accepting that some problems may have multiple resolutions; that analysing and evaluating different evidence is necessary for making a good judgment.

Open-mindedness, it is the inclination to be flexible with opposing views; to avoid subjectivity and bias, to accept various kinds of feedback, positive or negative; to think about and change current knowledge based on new insights and experiences; to accept being wrong if proved by evidence.

Self-efficacy, it is basically the inclination to be confident and self-efficacious in thinking reasonably to resolve issues; to be confident in providing positive feedback or constructive criticism; and to acknowledge the importance of good reasoning in everyday life.

Truth-seeking, willingness to gain knowledge and information; to confront common claims and societal norms by questioning; to be able to confront one's own interest and beliefs, and even to modify them in the way of seeking the truth.

Organisation, tendency to be organised, systematic, focused; and aware of the context, evidence, reasons and time when targeting an issue or doing a task.

Resourcefulness, it is the desire to use internal or external resources to address problems; to make use of the available resources; to think about the possibility of something going as opposed to what is expected and reflect on that.

Scepticism, tendency to doubt information; to avoid making judgments in light of inadequate evidence; to take positions and change them with the availability of evidence.

Perseverance, motivation and willingness to progress; resilience in performing a task; resistance to difficulties and anxieties in the way of achieving a goal.

Inquisitiveness, inclination to be adventurous and curious to know different things, to get answers to problems,

Intrinsic goal orientation, inclination to be keen and willing to learn new things, and to tackle different and new tasks, to have intrinsic motivation for inquiries rather than extrinsic one.

Attentiveness, tendency to concentrate and to have a clear picture of the context, consequences, and possible barriers.

Creativity, thinking outside the box; and tendency to produce innovative ideas.

Clarity, willingness to seek comprehensibility and transparency.

From critical thinking dispositions, it can be deduced that critical thinkers are characterised by being willing and motivated to seek knowledge, and curious to discover new things, they don't believe whatever they receive, they are investigators, they analyse the information and verify its credibility and appropriateness based on evidence. Critical thinkers are not stiff individuals, they are open-minded to multiple interpretations and perspectives; they are confident to reflect on their own thinking as well as on others' by giving feedback. They are also flexible in the sense that they are open to changing their positions if proved to be inaccurate based on a critical analysis.

3.3. Importance of Critical thinking in EFL Classes

According to the American Council for the Teaching of Foreign Languages (ACTFL, 2018), literacy is no longer perceived as dealing with the basic four skills; it has increasingly included intellectual skills such as analysing, synthesising and interpreting Information, evaluating arguments and applying creativity. Undoubtedly, critical thinking is viewed as one of these essential learning skills in the 21st Century, and a vital outcome of education (Yang, Newby and Robert, 2005).

In today's media-rich landscape, characterised by the proliferation of misleading and fake news, and unreliable sources, the necessity of critical thinking skills extends beyond one's native language to the realm of language learning. According to Hadley and Boon (2023), our modern world faces a crisis of the mind, as the persistent flow of misinformation challenges our ability to distinguish truth from fallacies. Davies (2019) points out:

there is a sudden absence of any authoritative perspective on reality. In the digital age, that vacuum of hard knowledge becomes rapidly filled by rumours, fantasy, and guesswork, some of which is quickly twisted and exaggerated to suit a preferred narrative ... we inevitably end up placing more trust in sensation and emotion than in evidence. Knowledge becomes more valued for its speed and impact than for its cold objectivity, and emotive falsehood often travels faster than fact.

(p. xi)

Hadley and Boon (2023) illustrate the life-threatening consequences of poor critical thinking skills, citing examples during the COVID-19 pandemic where deficiencies in evidence-based thinking led to the rapid spread of conspiracy theories, fake cures, science politicisation, and non-expert proclamations, etc. These failures in critical thinking not only jeopardised the health and economic well-being of millions but also resulted in the tragic loss of hundreds of thousands of lives due to decisions influenced by flawed reasoning. They argued that, considering the transmission and consumption of uncritical and biased information and messages through various media forms reaching vast audiences, the incorporation of a critical thinking component is no longer a luxury solely in the students' first language; integrating critical thinking into language lessons is progressively gaining significance.

On his part, Tomayo (2013) believes that critical thinking is subject-specific and can be cultivated across all domains, and in different subject-matters, however, each subject has a different mode of thinking: each area of knowledge has specific principles or standards that define the way to judge the quality of thinking of that particular domain. For instance, the type of content and principles that

are relevant to physics is a distinct mode of thinking by physicists (González, 2006). Another advocate of subject specificity to critical thinking is McPeck (1981) who argues that there is no generalisability of critical thinking, and that all fields of knowledge have specific critical thinking norms and standards. For instance, the norms that are pertinent to solving a differential equation in mathematics are extremely different from those implemented to decide whether or not a painting is a genuine Picasso.

Hence EFL context as with any other educational setting is expected to foster students' critical thinking skills as an educational ideal and not an option. According to Arum and Roska (2011) '99 percent of college faculty say that developing students' ability to think critically is a very important or essential goal of undergraduate education' (p. 11).

To achieve this aim, Delmastrax and Balada (2012) assert that EFL teachers should have deep understanding of what critical thinking is to incorporate it in classroom activities, and to develop it in parallel with other L2 skills; this will result eventually in independent learners who are able to go beyond surface reception of knowledge to inferring meaning into real life situations, and are able to assess and reflect on their learning. On the same line, Putcha (2012) emphasises that tasks involving critical thinking activities such as decision-making and problem-solving are highly beneficial for EFL students in evaluating the consequences of their decisions. Thus the purpose of teaching and learning shifts from focusing on structure to meaning.

Joining university and starting an academic life requires students to read a large number of reading materials. In the EFL context particularly, reading comprehension is considered a serious challenge for students: this is because comprehension is not only regarded as possessing linguistic resources and automatic processing, it also requires applying higher-order thinking skills such as analysing, synthesising, inferring, and evaluating (Grabe, 2010). A study was conducted by Karimi and Veisi (2016) to explore the effect of teaching critical thinking on reading comprehension of 50 intermediate EFL learners. The findings demonstrated that critical thinking plays a vital role in students' reading comprehension. They explained that the positive relationship between critical thinking and reading proficiency is probably due to the classroom interaction and discussion that encourage the development of critical thinking skills where students approach the discussed topics based on prior knowledge, express their views as well as analyse others' critically, and take the responsibility for their own learning process. That in turn proved to have a positive impact on students' reading comprehension.

Marin and de la Pava (2017) investigated university English teachers' conceptions and attitudes towards the concept of critical thinking in the EFL context. Teachers emphasised the significance of critical thinking and the necessity to integrate it in EFL instruction as it does not merely allow learners to exploit the linguistic structures to communicate in L2, but it also develops learners' abilities to give reasonable arguments, make decisions and solve problems in real-life situations. Teachers also claimed that critical thinking enhances significantly students' communicative competence when they find themselves trying to explain and expand their arguments in their L2. Consequently, their second or foreign language becomes an efficient means to practise all critical thinking constituents (argumentation, problem-solving, decision making, etc.) in daily life.

On his part, Salmon (2013) emphasises the importance of critical thinking for college students as an essential aspect of success in their future careers. He highlights in particular the role critical thinking plays in preparing and training students to become philosophers and teachers of philosophy.

Similarly, in considering the valuable role of critical thinking in the workplace, the Association of American Colleges and Universities (2013) conducted an online survey where 318 employers participated to provide insights about the skills that they prioritise when hiring college students. The results revealed that the majority of employers (93%) seemed to agree on prioritising skills that surpass the candidates' abilities and specific knowledge in their field of expertise. According to them, 'a candidate's demonstrated capacity to think critically, communicate clearly, and solve complex problems is more important than their undergraduate major' (2013, p.1). In addition to that, employers recommended that more efforts should be made by universities to develop students' capacities to think critically, to prepare them to communicate successfully, and to handle all the challenges they confront in the workplace.

To conclude, it is worth mentioning that the cultivation of critical thinking especially in higher education is becoming a mandatory rather than a possible learning outcome regardless of what field of expertise or subject-matter it is. Integrating critical thinking in EFL instruction helps the students to become autonomous, creative and reasonable when expressing different views on any discussed topics in the classroom. It also develops the ability to analyse others' views, evaluate, and self-reflect on their learning. Infusing critical thinking allows students to go beyond accepting fixed bodies of knowledge to develop higher intellectual processes by referring to real-life practices, making effective decisions, dealing with different challenges, and thus preparing them to be good citizens and successful members of their future workplace. However, the task of integrating critical thinking

remains challenging and requires a lot of planning of how best to infuse it into the teaching materials, and training for teachers to be able to develop it in their students.

3.4. The feasibility of teaching of critical thinking

The confusion about critical thinking has not stopped on its definability: the issue of whether or not it can be taught, and the possibility of teaching it to L2 classes and in non-western countries have been similarly debatable. Amid this controversy, some scholars believe that critical thinking is too mystifying a concept, and too intricate a process to be taught (Simpson and Courtney, 2002), or it is more of a social practice that is acquired intuitively according to the culture in which someone has been brought up (Atkinson, 1997; Fox, 1994). Others rather emphasise the possibility and necessity of teaching critical thinking through the identification of a set of skills and behaviours to be developed thoughtfully in the learners regardless of their historical, political, and cultural backgrounds (Mason, 2008; Davidson, 1998).

To start with, it has been long believed by some scholars that critical thinking in itself is a Western concept, and thus teaching it in non-Western contexts, and L2 classes is a difficult - if not impossible - task. This belief was on the ground that Western countries have different cultural, traditional and societal foundations which better equip them to embrace critical thinking skills, assuming that non-Western students find it challenging to engage in critical thinking, or have defective critical thinking abilities (Atkinson, 1997; Ramanathan and Kaplan, 1996a). For Atkinson (1997), the West has specific social values and norms which form highly individualistic members who prefer individual conflicts and diversity of views instead of the East's collectivist nature, conformity and submission to authority. Atkinson (1997) believes that critical thinking is a socio-cultural practice that members of Western countries acquire in day-to-day life. In other words, critical thinking is an inherently socially-constructed practice and behaviour which is learned unconsciously by simply being raised and involved in Western culture, and thus it is not expected for non-Western countries, where critical thinking is absent in everyday life, to succeed in teaching it in schools. In support of this claim, Atkinson (1997) examined previous literature on critical thinking, and pointed out that the lack of consensus, and difficulty and confusion of educators and scholars on providing a clear definition of the concept, prove that critical thinking is not just a set of instructions or pedagogical practices, but rather a phenomenon that is composed primarily of cultural and social practices. He states that:

All the more interesting and troubling is the fact that academics, normally considered masters of precise definition, seem almost as unwilling or unable to define critical thinking. Rather, they often appear to take the concept on

faith, perhaps as a sort of self-evident foundation of Western thought such as freedom of speech.

(p. 74)

Ramanathan and Atkinson (1999) compared American and Chinese writing styles as an attempt to deduce potential differences in terms of the application of critical thinking. They analysed American composition textbooks, and they found that students are expected to take one position and powerfully defend it by providing valid evidence, and not only relying on personal experiences, they are also asked to analyse rationally given situations and to strongly stand for their points of view and argue against other views and hence emphasising students' individualities. These requirements according to Ramanathan and Atkinson (1999) are appropriate and acceptable to the American context, but would be quite challenging and problematic for L2 learners. They concluded that the American writing style clearly stresses more critical thinking, and this maintains again that critical thinking is a Western product which is not likely to exist in cultures that value social harmony, conformity, and submission to authority (Wen and Clement, 2003; Ramanathan and Kaplan, 1996b). In support of this point, Ho (1998) interviewed 20 university students in Taiwan to investigate their visions of what good writing looks like. The ability to retain quotes from ancient literature, and to use memorised proverbs or old sayings were very much appreciated over the ability to express one's own point of view when writing an argumentative essay.

Ramanathan and Kaplan (1996a) agree with Atkinson's perception that critical thinking is a socio-cognitive practice which has its roots in the culture in which one is brought up. Hence, it is difficult for EFL and ESL students and even educators who were raised and immersed in an extremely different culture characterised by different - if not opposing - socio-cognitive practices to cultivate such critical and analytical thinking which is more typical of the West. Ramanathan and Kaplan (1996a) argue:

L2 student-writers, given their respective socio-cultural and linguistic socialization practices, are more likely than native English speaking (NES) students to encounter difficulty when being inducted into CT courses in freshman composition classes; they are not "ready" for CT courses in either L1 or L2 writing classrooms.

(p. 232)

In order to explain more the challenges that non-Western - especially ESL - students encounter in adopting the process of thinking critically unique to the West, Atkinson (1997) identified three criteria which result in such cultural gaps. These are discussed below.

The concept of individualism, for instance, shapes the basis of Western societies which regard individuals as separate independent entities from each other who value individual goals and achievement, unlike non-Western collectivist societies which emphasise more group goals and interests. This Western behaviour of individualism underlies one of the principles of critical thinking. The second norm which characterises Western societies according to Atkinson (1997) is self-expression. Self-expression is considered as one of the fundamental means to critical thinking which is not highly appreciated in non-Western countries. In Asian countries, for example, people tend to value social harmony which is maintained by conformity, obedience and respect for authority (Wen and Clément, 2003; Stapleton, 2001; Davidson, 1998). In addition to that, in such cultures, it is commonly accepted that the teacher possesses a status of authority in the classroom - so do parents at home - while the students are expected to be submissive and respectful to people of authority, in such a way that they refrain from questioning what they are being taught (Yang, Badger, and Yu, 2006; Littlewoods, 2000). In light of this, developing a critical attitude becomes an elusive goal to achieve as critical thinking encourages students to analyse and evaluate the information they are exposed to, rather than blindly taking it for granted.

Furthermore, in Western cultures, language is considered as a means of discussing and expressing opposing views whereas in other cultures, silence is more valued. In China, for instance, people prefer to be silent as asking questions and voicing opinions are often interpreted as rudeness, impoliteness, and sometimes even aggressiveness (Harklau, 1994).

Atkinson (1997) highlights the fact that language educators should be very cautious when trying to adopt critical thinking in their classrooms as – in addition to the aforementioned reasons - ESL students rely primarily on memorisation in learning English language (Shahini and Riazi, 2011), they tend to memorise linguistic structures, language rules and vocabulary, then reproduce it when writing in English (Larkin, 2009), lacking the ability to analyse arguments and to construct their own meanings and judgments. Moreover, Atkinson (1997) believes that native speakers and non-native speakers have distinct modes of thinking, with different socio-cultural historical roots, consequently he assumes that ESL and EFL students are unlikely to be involved in the process of critical thinking ‘how might individuals from cultural systems that manifestly differ from mainstream U.S. culture respond to and benefit from thinking skills instruction?’ (p.79).

Atkinson’s assumptions were criticised on several grounds by Davidson (1998), starting with the argument that scholars were unable to come up with one clear inclusive definition, assuming

therefore that this concept is not simply a definable pedagogical practice, but rather an indefinable socio-cultural phenomenon. Davidson (1998) comments on that,

However, this is a little like saying that because a large number of professors do not know what the acronym TESOL stands for, then TESOL does not exist as an understandable acronym. The fact proves nothing more than a lack of understanding or clarity in some minds about what critical thinking is.

(p.120)

Atkinson (1997) examined some previous papers on critical thinking and highlighted the fact that scholars' definitions of the concept differ to some extent which indicates that they are uncertain of what it is, this according to Atkinson proves again that critical thinking is social practice. Here, Davidson (1998) states that 'Atkinson misses the forest for the trees' (p.120). He claims that the examined definitions are similar to a great extent, sharing the same core idea, but mostly with different wording. opponent

Davidson (1998) argues that critical thinking appears to be 'universally relevant', rather than a social practice that is applicable to a particular culture over another. He states that, while it might be true that in some cultures, critical thinking is not as highly encouraged as in Western cultures, this does not mean that it does not exist in such cultures. On his part, Ennis' (1996) major issue is basically when critical thinking should be taught, and how it can be best taught, but never whether it is appropriate to be introduced in the other part of the world. Davidson (1998) adds that even if critical thinking is not practised in community-oriented societies which value social harmony and obedience, this does not entail that critical thinking should not be taught to individuals of those cultures.

Moreover, Atkinson (1997) was criticised for seeing the picture from only one angle, in the sense that most studies claiming that Asian students lack criticality were conducted in Western contexts with Western topics, and here arises the issue of familiarity with the topic. Fox (1995) for instance notes that Japanese ESL students in an American university showed weak critical thinking skills, ignoring the fact that this study took place in an American university with American topics. There is great consensus among scholars and educators that topic familiarity and one's prior knowledge of certain topics play a significant role in the performance of thinking tasks and the ability to employ critical thinking skills (Kennedy, Fisher, and Ennis, 1991).

From the previous discussion, some scholars advocate for the Western possession of critical thinking where the latter has received considerable interest decades ago as an attempt to demystify and develop it; they believe that critical thinking is an unconscious socio-cultural practice and that

Western societies seem to be the right place for it along with individualism, freedom of speech, and empowerment of self-expression and voice; leaving the rest of the world with traditional approaches to knowledge such as memorisation and taking things for granted without asking; these societies according to them embrace more communalism, conformity, and supreme respect to authorities. Others reject that view, claiming that critical thinking is a teachable skill that can be developed in the East or the West, teachers need only to be careful in the process of cultivating it to overcome the barriers they may encounter. It can be concluded, however, that critical thinking is a universal intellectual process that can be acquired and developed in any part of the world, in Western contexts or EFL/ESL contexts; it is merely a question of the degree to which critical thinking is tolerated and encouraged that differs from one society to another - that is, it is accepted in some cultures that critical thinking is highly valued because of several cultural, political and historical factors. However, this does not legitimise the ownership of that concept, denying the benefits it may bring to individuals from other cultures where critical thinking does not receive much support in particular domains. Moreover, as critical thinking relies on the ability to weigh arguments and form accurate judgments through careful analysis of evidence, it is not reasonable to stereotype all Asian countries, for instance, as incapable of learning critical thinking simply because they value social harmony and conformity.

Furthermore, even if the judgment is that ESL/EFL students lack the necessary skills which allow them to acquire critical thinking, this does not mean that critical thinking should not be taught and introduced to them. Kubota (1999), states that 'characteristics of Japanese education described in the applied linguistics literature point significantly to less emphasis on creativity, self-expression, individualism, and critical thinking relative to U.S. education. However, many studies on schooling in Japan offer observations of the opposite' (p. 23). Likewise, Stapleton (2001) supports the idea that Japanese students have the ability and disposition to learn critical thinking, but they need guidance and instructions on how to foster that ability. Similarly, Davidson (1998) conducted a pilot study on Japanese university students in which the experimental group received additional critical thinking instruction while the control group was taught with regular academic English instruction. The result of the critical thinking essay test was that the experimental group performed better than the control group. Similarly, Sandhaya and Rahma (2014) investigated writing samples of 30 EFL students from Omani University: they compared their writing assignments before and after a semester of a critical reading thinking skills course. They found that as the students were trained to employ critical thinking skills while reading, they were able to transfer these skills to writing. When conducting a

quasi-experimental research on 40 intermediate Iranian students to analyse the effect of integrating critical thinking on speaking skills, Arfae (2019) concluded that teaching critical thinking has a positive effect on their speaking skill which proves again that critical thinking is teachable and beneficial for EFL students, and it only depends on the teacher enthusiasm and willingness to make efforts in choosing or designing tasks and activities that boost the students' critical thinking skills.

Lu and Xie (2018) conducted an experimental research on two EFL groups in a Chinese university to investigate the effect of instructional practices which develop students' critical thinking skills in an argumentative writing course. They implemented the International Critical Thinking Reading and Writing Test (ICTRWT) (Paul and Elder, 2006) to assess the results of the treatment, and interviews and questionnaires to gather data about students' attitudes towards that instructional programme. The findings revealed that the experimental group performed much better in the application of critical thinking skills in their writing than the control group which received standard teaching instructions. These studies suggest that EFL/ESL students are able to be taught and embrace critical thinking.

Other scholars such as Mckinley (2013) points out that critical thinking does indeed exist in different contexts; it is, however, the way of expressing it which differs from one context to another.

3.5. Approaches to teaching critical thinking

In search for the best approach to foster the development of students' critical thinking skills, scholars and educators have long been debating the effectiveness of teaching critical thinking as general skills in which generic critical thinking skills and dispositions are taught in separate courses, and teaching critical thinking as subject-specific where each domain is believed to have unique criteria which require critical thinking skills specific to that particular domain. The controversy of whether critical thinking skills are domain-specific or generic and domain-transcending has been strongly intertwined with the approaches to teaching critical thinking. Ennis (1989), an early proponent of the general view, identifies four main approaches to critical thinking instruction: general, immersion, infusion, and mixed approach.

a. The general approach

In the general approach, critical thinking is viewed as a set of generalised skills which are applicable in different domains and contexts, and thus can be taught separately in stand-alone courses. These courses aim to explicitly teach critical thinking skills and dispositions without the content of subject-

matter (Ennis, 1989). Proponents of the general view (e.g. Abrami, et al., 2008; Davis, 2013; Ennis, 1989; Pascarella and Terenzini, 2005) argue that critical thinking should be introduced in separate courses in order not to be eclipsed by the content of subject-matter (Siegel, 1988). Moreover, Ennis (1989) believes that despite the distinct content of domains, most of them share interfield commonalities which are the common basic principles that apply in every domain, and hence according to this view, general critical thinking skills are likely to transfer from one context to another. Halpern (2001) another advocate of domain-generality of critical thinking reviews a range of studies which employ the four critical thinking instructional approaches (general, immersion, infusion and mixed) as an attempt to analyse their effectiveness, and she concludes that the general approach has a great effect on the improvement of students' critical thinking.

b. The immersion approach

This approach attempts to integrate critical thinking within subject-matter instruction, but without explicit teaching of general critical thinking principles. It is argued in this view that being immersed in domain-specific knowledge is significant to promote the development of critical thinking, and to enable transfer across domains (Ennis, 1989; Moore, 2011). However, the immersion approach was criticised (e.g. Beyer, 2008; Davis, 2013) on the ground that transferability of critical thinking skills is likely to take place only when the teaching of general critical thinking principles is made explicit within subject-matter instruction.

c. The infusion approach

The infusion approach refers to the process of embedding critical thinking skills within thoughtful and well-constructed subject-matter instruction. In this approach, students are explicitly encouraged to think critically in the content of subject-matter using explicit general critical thinking principles (Ennis, 1989).

d. The mixed approach

This is a combination of the general approach and either the infusion or immersion approaches. It includes separate courses to teach critical thinking in a generic way, but in addition to that students are exposed to either explicit or implicit critical thinking instruction within each of their subject-matters (Ennis, 1989). In support of this approach, and on emphasising the notion of interfield commonalities, Ennis (1989) notes:

(a) Mathematics has different criteria for good reasons from most other fields, because mathematics accepts only deductive proof, whereas most fields do not even seek it for the establishment of a final conclusion; (b) in the social sciences, statistical significance is an important consideration, whereas in many branches of physics it is largely ignored; (c) in the arts, some subjectivity is usually acceptable, whereas in the sciences, it is usually shunned.

(p.8)

Indeed, fields diverge to a particular extent but according to Ennis, there are always overlapping critical thinking skills which are applicable in different contexts. Similarly, despite the fact that Facione (2000) designed the California Critical Thinking Skills Test which is considered a general test and not one that is directed to a specific subject matter, he also highlights the significant role domain-specific knowledge plays in the development of critical thinking skills and dispositions (Facione, 1999). Ennis (1989) extends the discussion on the notion of domain-specificity and offers a clear distinction between three versions of subject-specificity namely, empirical subject-specificity, epistemological subject-specificity and conceptual subject-specificity.

Before elaborating on the three versions, Ennis (1989) criticises the view that critical thinking is subject-specific on the ground that terms like field, domain, and subject suffer vagueness, noting that the term 'subject' can be used sometimes to describe some subject in school, or even more specifically a 'topic'. Accordingly, it is not appropriate to always intertwine critical thinking with school context only. He points out 'It is tempting, but a mistake, to infer from the fact that critical thinking is always about some subject (that is, topic) that critical thinking teaching can take place only in school subjects' (p.5).

McPeck (1990) - a notable proponent of subject-specificity - offers a counterargument that a number of concepts in Ennis' thesis, for instance, 'general critical thinking' and 'critical thinking skill' are themselves vague. He adds that this vagueness should not be inferred as confused hypotheses, but rather should be accepted as this is what constructs language plasticity. He emphasises that the focus should be put on the concepts' uses to determine their meaning, rather than looking for their precise definitions. McPeck (1981) attacks the view of critical thinking's generalisability and critical thinking courses which assume to teach general critical thinking. He believes that critical thinking cannot be isolated from a specific subject as there should be always something in particular to think about regardless of what that thing could be: topic, subject, field or domain, in school or out-of-school context. He states:

It is a matter of conceptual truth that thinking is always thinking about X, and that X can never be "everything in general" but must always be something in particular. Thus the claim "I teach students to think" is at worst false and at best misleading.

(p.4)

Yet, McPeck (1990) does not utterly reject the existence of very limited general thinking skills, but according to him the outcomes of general critical thinking instruction are not as promising as domain-specific critical thinking instruction. He argues that the more general the thinking skills are, the less beneficial they are. On similar lines, another advocate of subject-specificity, Willingham (2008) asserts that it makes no sense to detach critical thinking from contextual knowledge, and that teaching it in a generic way and out of domain-specific courses is trivial and ineffective:

If you remind a student to 'look at an issue from multiple perspectives' often enough, he will learn that he ought to do so, but if he doesn't know much about an issue, he can't think about it from multiple perspectives ... critical thinking (as well as scientific thinking and other domain-based thinking) is not a skill. There is not a set of critical thinking skills that can be acquired and deployed regardless of context.

(p. 21-22)

As noted above, Ennis (1989) classifies three versions of domain-specificity: empirical, epistemological, and conceptual domain-specificity. Ennis identifies three principles of the empirical version held by a number of researchers. First, there seems to be a consensus among scholars and researchers on the necessity and significance of background knowledge to foster critical thinking. The second principle is transferability, and most researchers are pessimistic regarding the possibility of critical thinking transfer across domains. Yet, they believe that transfer can take place only on the condition that students are exposed to critical thinking practices in a variety of domains and that instruction on transfer are made explicit to students. Finally, holding a strong domain-specificity position entails that teaching general critical thinking skills is meaningless and impractical.

The epistemological version of subject-specificity indicates that different fields require different critical thinking skills as each field has its own way to establish good reasoning which represents the interfield variation principle. In addition to that, this version shares with the empirical subject-specificity the principle that background knowledge is vital to thinking critically. This view was challenged by Ennis (1989) for the vagueness of the concept 'field', and for the existence of interfield commonalities as opposed to interfield variation.

The last and least appreciated version is the conceptual subject-specificity: for this view general critical thinking does not exist and critical thinking cannot take place except in the context of subject-matter. As McPeck (1981) argues, 'thinking is always thinking about something' (p. 3).

Having discussed the four major approaches to teaching critical thinking, and after reviewing some of the empirical studies which seek to explore the most effective approach for the acquisition and application of critical thinking skills in a variety of contexts, it appears that there is no consensus on the debate of whether critical thinking is domain-specific or domain-independent as the findings of these researches revealed inconsistency. Some of them concluded that embedded critical thinking instruction within the content of subject-matter (infusion and immersion approaches) is effective in fostering the development of critical thinking in a meaningful way. Others suggested the opposite and found that teaching critical thinking in separate courses has great benefits on students' ability to think critically. Each of the approaches seems to have strengths and pitfalls. Nickerson (1988) provides an example of the weaknesses which lie under each of the general and infusion approaches:

A risk of teaching a specific aspect of thinking only in a "content-free" way is that the student will acquire some understanding of that aspect but fail to connect that knowledge to the many situations in life in which it could be useful. A risk of teaching the same aspect of thinking only within the context of a [standard subject matter] course is that the student will fail to abstract from the situation what is really context independent and again will not transfer what has been learned to other contexts.

(p. 34)

It might seem that the mixed approach to critical thinking seems to be the most reasonable as it bridges the generic skills gained from the general independent courses with the specific skills embedded in subject-matters, and hence transfer across the different domains is more likely to take place. However, according to Harrell and Wetzel (2015), limited research has delved into effective strategies for enhancing the critical thinking skills of college students. In American universities, the predominant approach to teaching critical thinking primarily involves offering standalone courses (Green, 2015). However, given that content knowledge is necessary for the instruction of critical thinking within the domain of language teaching, research indicates that targeting critical thinking within subject-specific courses might be more efficient (Huber and Kuncel, 2016). Numerous studies have explored pedagogical approaches to develop students' critical thinking in language classrooms. The conventional method of teaching critical thinking often revolves around pro/con debates, grounded in the notion that "critical thinking consists of seeing both sides of an issue" (Willingham,

2007, p. 8). Recognising limitations in this traditional model, some researchers have introduced innovative approaches like "thick critical thinking" (Wendland, Robinson, and Williams, 2015) and argument mapping (Gelder, 2015). Moore (2017) proposes a model incorporating three approaches: the skills approach, the ethics approach, and the language of evaluation approach. Another model, named "TERRIFIC" (target, evaluate, routinise, reflect, inquire, fulfil, integrate, cooperate), has been suggested for integrating critical thinking into the language classroom (Sun, 2019). Professors instructing university-level courses in informal logic may exhibit varying inclinations in their teaching approaches. While some lean towards a general approach that emphasises logic and argumentation independently of specific subject matter, others opt for presenting pertinent skills within the context of a particular knowledge domain. There are also advocates for an exploratory approach that engages learners in intricate problem-solving situations. Notably, some argue in favour of a blended approach that incorporates elements from various types at different stages of the learning process (Ma et al., 2020). Since Ennis' (1989) taxonomy of critical thinking instructional approaches, there has been a substantial evolution in information and communications technologies. Emerging technologies, such as interactive simulations, social networking, and augmented realities, have become prominent. Concurrently, pedagogical approaches have also advanced, partly due to the integration of new technologies facilitating collaborative learning and simulations through games (Lee et al., 2016). These technologies, with their versatility, support a diverse range of critical thinking interventions, encompassing digital journals, role-playing exercises, simulations, storytelling, collaborative and cooperative learning, inquiry-driven strategies, problem-solving methods, and more. Furthermore, information and communications technologies offer flexibility and adaptability, allowing for effective combinations (Ma et al., 2020). While the suggested instructional strategies for critical thinking are theoretically robust and grounded in research, a definitive best method remains elusive, and consensus on an ideal approach is yet to be achieved. In creating critical thinking activities for the classroom, educators require creativity and flexibility. They may employ and blend diverse strategies innovatively or devise alternative methods tailored to their specific classes. Following an evaluation of a number of research-based teaching approaches to cultivate critical thinking in EFL classes, Zhao, Pandian, and Singh (2016) emphasise that the effectiveness of critical thinking instruction in EFL classrooms depends on teachers' intentional and sustained efforts.

3.6. Activities and strategies to foster critical thinking

Since critical thinking is not something we are born with, but rather a process we develop over time, then it is one of the teachers' main objectives in the classroom to cultivate this skill in their students. This does not entail telling them how important it is to be critical thinkers only; teachers need to model critical thinking in the classroom, and take them through the process of thinking critically by using some exercises and techniques which allow them to experience the process in itself, not only knowing about it. Brookfield (2012) in his book "Teaching for Critical Thinking" introduces an interesting selection of activities to foster students' critical thinking skills which are based on his own experiences in teaching. Some of these activities are discussed below.

Circle of Voices

Brookfield favours this activity as it allows every single student to contribute to the classroom discussion at least once, and second it teaches the students the benefits of active listening to develop and extend a discussion. Students are asked to form groups of five and are given three minutes of silence to think about what they want to say about the presented question. The three minutes of silence are crucial for students to analyse and conceptualise the question and then draw their opinions. Unfortunately, giving some time for thinking is uncommon as the usual scenario is to ask a question and expect responses immediately, this doesn't help the students to internalise the question and come up with a thoughtful argument. After the three minutes of silence, each student is given one minute to share something with the group without any interruption.

In round two, the rule dictates that students should comment on what they think about others' answers in the one minute monologue, they are not asked though to explain or elaborate in theirs.

The circle of voices is very important as it allows students to reflect on each other's views, and open up their minds to different perceptions; it helps to avoid the dominance of certain individuals by giving every student especially those who are shy and introverted an opportunity to participate in the discussion at least once.

Circular response

This activity is quite similar to the circle of voices with the same aim of maximising participation, hearing the voices of everybody in the room, and learning to listen and reflect on others' perspectives. The circular response works best with a number of 8-12 people and has two rounds as well. In the first round, students are expected to take turns in the one-minute monologue; the

difference is that when the first speaker finishes talking, the one next to him/her is supposed to comment or reflect directly on what has been just said in that one minute, and the circle continues until it arrives again at the first speaker who comments himself on the previous person's participation.

This exercise raises some sort of discomfort and anxiety as one should speak and connect immediately to the previous contribution. One way to help in that situation is by giving the person a few moments to think about what he/she wants to say. Another way according to Brookfield is to tell the students that it is fine to not be able to connect to a previous one's contribution, but in this case, the individual needs to explain why he/she found it difficult to follow up - reasons could be unfamiliarity, lack of experience, complexity of the argument, etc. In the second round, no rules are put forward and the discussion is open to asking questions, expressing opinions or commenting.

Chalk talk

This exercise, which was first developed by Smith (2009), is a silent and visual activity, with no speaking at all in the first phase. This activity starts with the instructor writing a question on the board. He/she then explains that it is a silent activity and everybody should be free to write whatever they want on the board whenever they are ready; this includes answering the question, commenting on others' posts, connecting some ideas, etc. The instructor can also participate in the same way: reflecting, commenting, posing sub-questions, and drawing lines between similar and opposing ideas in complete silence. When a long silence occurs without posting, the teacher then frees the discussion about what has been posted on the board.

This activity maximises the contribution and participation much more than a spoken discussion does. Besides it helps introverts to feel at ease while processing their thinking and forming their ideas.

Spot the error

In this activity, the teacher announces clearly that he/she will intentionally share something that is false, which could be a factual error, unjustified assumptions, biased information, or even simpler error. Then students are asked at the end of the session to write on a piece of paper what the error was in 30 seconds. The anonymous pieces of paper will then be handed to the teacher where he /she can share and comment on them.

This activity triggers the students' attentiveness and curiosity to spot the error, their willingness to seek the truth, and their consulting abilities by verifying what the teacher is saying.

The Appreciative Pause

Appreciation works wonders on students' self-esteem, hence it is important to demonstrate appreciation among students, if critical thinking is among the course objectives. The appreciative pause suggests that in each discussion there should be one minute devoted to peer feedback, students are only allowed to appreciate what they have gained from others' comments in that minute: it could be an acknowledgement of good questions, ideas which open new perceptions, or illustration or clarification which helps in the comprehension of some issues, etc.

Critical questioning approaches

Brookfield (2012) stresses the importance of asking questions as an essential technique to boost the process of thinking critically. Rhetorical questions or closed questions do not achieve much. It is the open questions such as asking to verify assumptions or asking to draw multiple perspectives which provoke the ability to think critically.

Similarly, other researchers (Haynes and Bailey, 2003; Hemming, 2000) emphasise the significant role the practice of good questioning plays in engaging students in meaningful active learning.

However, for the questioning practice to be effective and stimulating for the students' critical thinking, it needs to be carefully developed with the aim of achieving three essential goals: identifying assumptions, unearthing evidence to evaluate these assumptions, and generating multiple interpretations and perceptions. Furthermore, teachers should allow some time for the students to think about and formulate their ideas instead of expecting immediate responses, as good thinking requires some time to process. In fact, giving a few seconds of silence after a student's contribution helps as well in stimulating others' reflections and feedback where the latter is no less important in the process of critical thinking.

The principles of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) align seamlessly with the cultivation of critical thinking skills. In the CLT framework, language is not seen as a set of isolated rules to be memorised but as a tool for meaningful communication and language use in authentic contexts (Richards and Rodgers, 2001). Hadley and Boon (2023) explain 'critical thinking is actualised through problem-solving; it is activated first through our interaction with and creation of language. It then involves training people to question assumptions and conclusions in a more purposeful manner' (p.26). The activities outlined correspond with the fundamental principles of the CLT approach. The "Circle of Voices" and "Circular Response" activities, by encouraging active

participation and open discussion, contribute to the development of communicative skills. Similarly, "Chalk Talk" introduces a silent, visual component, reflecting the diverse ways language is expressed in real-world situations. "Spot the Error" aligns with CLT's goal of language as a tool for critical thinking by promoting active evaluation. "The Appreciative Pause" supports positive peer interactions, enhancing the collaborative nature of language learning inherent in CLT. Finally, the "Critical Questioning Approaches" emphasise open-ended questions, a key feature of CLT that underscores communication for various purposes. In essence, these activities not only foster critical thinking but also embody the communicative and interactive language learning nature emphasised by CLT.

3.7. Assessment of critical thinking

Considering the longstanding controversy among scholars on the definability and teachability of critical thinking, it is of no surprise that the assessment of critical thinking outcomes has been similarly a point of disagreement where those assuming that critical thinking is an innate socio-cultural practice which is not possible to define as any pedagogical practice, also assume that critical thinking is an abstract elusive concept which cannot be measured. However, from the previously discussed literature, it is clear that critical thinking has been able to be defined and hence should also be capable of being assessed. The assessment of critical thinking skills and dispositions has always been considered a challenging task yet as Ennis (1993) states, 'given our current state of knowledge, critical thinking assessment, albeit difficult to do well, is possible' (p. 179).

Most researchers agree on the possibility of assessing critical thinking, but they vary in scope, format and most importantly in purpose when designing tests or assessment forms. According to Ennis (1993), tests can aim to assess one aspect of critical thinking, or more than one, as it could be subject-specific critical thinking tests which aim to evaluate critical thinking in one particular area, or domain-general test which use general content from everyday situations on the condition that task takers are supposed to be already familiar with the content.

3.7.1. Purposes of assessing critical thinking

Ennis (1993) identifies the following set of possible purposes which educators should carefully think of prior to developing a test: these purposes which are listed below cannot be all combined in one assessment procedure.

1. Identifying the students' current critical thinking abilities. Doing this as a starting point will help to shed light on the students' strengths and weaknesses, allowing teachers to know where to put emphasis on their teaching.
2. Providing the students with feedback about their critical thinking skills. By highlighting the areas of strength and weakness, students will be guided on where they should focus their efforts.
3. Motivating the students to improve their ability to think critically. According to Ennis (1993), even though tests are not usually well-used as a motivational tool, they still can motivate students to work hard and learn about the content which is expected to be included in tests, resulting in developing their critical thinking if it was part of the content. If not, students will marginalise it (Smith, 1991).
4. Giving teachers feedback about the success of their approach in teaching critical thinking to students. Tests can be used as a self-evaluation tool to explore the effectiveness of their critical thinking instruction.
5. Conducting research on the various critical thinking teaching instructions and issues. Comparison between the different approaches and instructional practices is vital to answer some issues in critical thinking, and this comparison requires assessment to be achieved.
6. Helping in the decision-making of students' admissions to educational programmes. In some domains, students need to pass critical thinking tests to be admitted. This type of testing is called "high stakes" as it is highly dependent on the outcomes, such as the American College Test (ACT) and College Board Advanced Placement (AP) tests.
7. Revealing information about schools on their students' critical thinking prowess. In this type of assessment, schools and teachers are put under pressure as they are accountable for the level of their students' critical thinking skills. This purpose is also classified as "high stakes" testing.

3.7.2. Types of critical thinking assessment

The following discusses three main types of assessments for critical thinking, each varying in format and effectiveness: Published critical thinking tests, Written essays as assessments of critical thinking, and performance assessment.

3.7.2.1. Published critical thinking tests

There are large numbers of standardised critical thinking tests which vary in purpose, format and coverage. Some of them are developed to target one aspect of critical thinking, others aim to assess more than one aspect. The following are some of the standardised tests listed by Ennis (1993).

- **Tests assessing one aspect of critical thinking**

Cornell Class Reasoning Test: this test as the name entails is made for various forms of class reasoning, specifically for the range between 4-14 grades (Ennis, 1993).

Test on Appraising Observations: there are two versions of it, multiple-choice and constructed response testing. This assessment is designed for grades 7-14, and 'tests for ability to judge the credibility of statements of observation' (Ennis, 1993, p. 183).

- **Tests assessing more than one aspect of critical thinking**

The California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST): it is a multiple-choice test which is geared to university students, but can be used for high school students. It examines 'interpretation, argument analysis and appraisal, deduction, mind bender puzzles, and induction' (Ennis, 1993, P.183).

Watson-Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal (WGCTA): one of the oldest, most reliable and commonly used test, it was first created in 1937, after which came two new versions which were developed in the USA and UK in 1980 and 1991 respectively (Hassan and Madhum, 2007). It aims to test five criteria of critical thinking which are 'induction, assumption identification, deduction, judging whether a conclusion follows beyond a reasonable doubt, and argument evaluation' (Ennis, 1993, P.183). It is also designed for high school and university students.

Cornell Critical Thinking Test (CCTT): this multiple choice assessment consists of two levels, level X which is directed towards grades 4-14. It measures 'induction, credibility, observation, deduction, and assumption identification' (Ennis, 1993, p.183). Level Z aims at advanced test-takers, high school or university students. It tends to assess all the aspects included in level X in addition to fallacies inspection, prediction and experimental planning.

Ross Test of Higher Cognitive Process (RTHCP): this test includes 105 multiple-choice questions. It targets the three higher levels of Bloom's Taxonomy which are analysis, synthesis and evaluation (Norris, 1993).

As it can be noted, the majority of the above assessment tools are multiple-choice questions which are doubted to deeply reveal the students' critical thinking abilities. In addition to that, these tests are developed to assess critical thinking skills, but not critical thinking dispositions. Norris and Ennis (1989), in the Illinois Critical Thinking Project, investigated another method of testing as an attempt to cover more aspects of critical thinking skills and dispositions. They chose 20 multiple-choice questions from CCTT level X, and asked the students to provide written justification for each chosen answer allowing for a variety of students' background knowledge and interpretations.

3.7.2.2. Written essays as assessment of critical thinking

Another type of assessment which has been believed to be more efficient than the multiple-choice tests is assessing essays or passages written by the students. Lantolf (2006) points out that writing is a tool which reflects cognitive functioning like reasoning, inference, making judgments, drawing conclusions, etc. The Ennis-Weir Critical Thinking Essay Test is a testing and teaching material which can be used also for research purposes. It is appropriate for students from 7th grade (USA) to university students. The test is mainly about a presented complex argument where students are asked to analyse that argument and express their opinions in return with another well-formulated argument. This test aims to assess the ability to analyse and evaluate an argument, distinguishing reasons and assumptions, expressing one's views and defending them by formulating good arguments, and being open-minded to different angles and multiple perspectives. The Ennis-Weir test also covers areas that test takers should avoid: Ennis and Weir (1985) listed them as 'equivocation, irrelevance, circularity, reversal of an if-then (or other conditional) relationship, overgeneralization, credibility problems, and the use of emotive language to persuade' (p.1). According to Ku (2009), this test doesn't merely cover the students' cognitive abilities, but to some extent, it assesses even their dispositions to practise critical thinking.

3.7.2.3. Performance assessment

According to Ennis (1993), this type of assessment is the most reliable yet the most expensive and time-consuming as the grader is expected to take a considerable time observing each student. Students are required to perform the task by applying their knowledge and reasoning abilities to solve problems which are similar to real-life situations.

There are other recently developed critical thinking tests which use new formats for assessment, for instance, The College and Work Readiness Assessment which is a 90-minute task where students are required to analyse and evaluate real-life problems, and then try to formulate solutions. The River

City Research Project is an assessment programme for middle-school students which uses an interactive simulation environment to introduce real-life problems, and then the students are asked to solve the problems through experimental planning (Silva, 2008).

3.7.3. Traps and challenges in critical thinking assessment

There are some traps and challenges that researchers and educators should consider when trying to measure critical thinking.

- Most of the previously mentioned tests are designed to assess critical thinking skills, but very few aim at measuring dispositions and transfer of critical thinking to different contexts (Norris and Ennis, 1989).
- Multiple-choice tests are not believed to completely cover deep constructs of critical thinking. It is accepted that these tests are the easiest to use and evaluate, but they are the least valid because test takers can guess or randomly tick a choice, and still arrive at the correct answer (Ennis, 1993).
- In multiple-choice tests, the distinct background norms and beliefs between the students and test designers may result in different but justifiable answers (Norris and Ennis, 1989).
- Considering the fact that critical thinking takes a long period of time and considerable effort to develop, yet educators still can get significant results in a short period of time, then clearly this threatens the test validity (Ennis, 1993).
- The possible absence of a control group to be compared with the experimental group's pre and post-test, brings up the problem that results may be affected by external factors (Ennis, 1993).
- Topic unfamiliarity of the assessment can be an obstacle to eliciting critical thinking abilities: taking the example of the Ennis-Weir test which was developed for English language speakers, thus it may not be suitable for EFL/ESL learners. Stapleton (2001) agrees that the lack of familiarity with the topic may restrain the students from practising their critical thinking abilities.
- Performance-based testing limitations are costly in terms of expense, time consumption, and most importantly the danger of subjectivity (Silva, 2008).
- In high stakes assessments, test validity and results may be rendered questionable because students may get training in cram-schools to score well and pass those tests without them

acquiring or demonstrating any aspect of critical thinking skills. As a result, the test will fail to reveal the actual critical thinking prowess of the students.

To sum up, after establishing the testing purpose, critical thinking can be assessed using three major measurement tools that vary in coverage, purpose, and format. The first one is published standardised tests, primarily composed of multiple-choice questions grouped to assess one or more aspects of critical thinking. While cost-effective and straightforward, these tests are criticised for potentially not covering all critical thinking constructs. An alternative proposed by some scholars is a multiple-choice test followed by written justifications, a combination highly recommended for revealing students' thinking processes more comprehensively. Second, there is essay writing for critical thinking testing, requiring students to employ various aspects of critical thinking to formulate thoughtful arguments. Last but not least, performance-based assessment allows students to engage in real-life situations. While these last two methods are the most expensive and time-consuming, they are considered the most valid assessment procedures. Braun et al. (2020) posit that measuring critical thinking is best achieved through performance assessment, offering a more realistic and credible approach. This method, according to Lane and Stone (2006), Braun (2019), and Shavelson et al. (2019), can evaluate aspects of critical thinking that traditional assessments often fail to assess adequately or entirely.

The recognition of the significance of incorporating critical thinking skills is widespread across various fields, with particular acknowledgement in the domain of Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) (Hirai et al., 2022). Critical thinking is likely to be stimulated as EFL learners increasingly engage in reading documents in the English language, communicating, and participating in discussions with people worldwide. Despite this, there is a growing body of literature addressing how to nurture critical thinking skills among EFL learners, as evidenced by an increasing number of studies (e.g. Mineshima and Imai, 2017; Takeda, 2016). However, the discussion on critical thinking assessment for EFL learners remains limited, primarily due to the lack of consensus on critical thinking definition (Nicholas and Labig, 2013) and a shortage of assessment tools tailored for EFL learners (Reid and Chin, 2021).

The challenge of defining critical thinking constructs adds complexity to the assessment process, as noted by Ennis (2003). Another layer of complexity in critical thinking assessment arises from the debate on domain specificity. While critical thinking is often regarded as a general skill applicable across various contexts (e.g. Ennis, 2018; Kusumi, 2018), some contend that critical thinking skills

are inherently domain-specific, limiting the utility of general assessments (Rear, 2019). Hirai et al. (2022), providing an illustration of a non-western context, suggest that a student from Japan with high critical thinking skills but limited English proficiency may struggle to demonstrate these skills effectively in an English language context due to language barriers (Hirai et al., 2022). This means that domain-specific knowledge exerts an impact on the execution of critical thinking skills. In spite of these discussions, many standardised English critical thinking tests (discussed above 3.7.2.1) are still in use.

Although the standardised tests have proven valid and reliable in numerous studies, they appear inadequate in light of recent advances in validation approaches (Chapelle and Voss, 2021). According to Hirai et al. (2022), these tests have not explicitly delineated the scope for interpreting and utilising test scores, nor have they provided a clear understanding of the distinctions and relationships among intended factors. Consequently, using these tests for the validation studies of an English Critical Thinking Test would pose challenges. Moreover, these critical thinking tests are not suitable for classroom use given that the English and content used in them may be too challenging for EFL learners. The tests are designed for native speakers or highly proficient speakers. Additionally, obtaining these commercial tests from abroad is challenging (Stroupe, 2006), and it is expensive for a considerable number of students. Addressing these challenges, Hirai et al. (2022) developed an English Critical Thinking Test (ECTT) tailored for EFL learners, designed for secondary and university EFL students in Japan. The findings from this project demonstrated the validity and success of the test as intended. Although created in Japan, this study enables English teachers in various EFL contexts to assess students' critical thinking skills and measure the effectiveness of their critical thinking teaching.

3.8. Barriers to developing critical thinking

The importance of promoting critical thinking has been widely recognised in recent decades for successful academic and professional life. Researchers and educators are aware of the essentiality of implementing instructional practices and teaching strategies to develop students' critical thinking, but there appear to be several obstacles along the way which hinder the achievement of this goal. The following are some research studies revealing potential constraints on developing critical thinking.

Aliakbari and Sadeghdaghighi (2013) addressed 100 teachers from various schools and universities in Iran to investigate teachers' perceptions about the main reasons which hinder the development

of critical thinking, using Shell's Perceived Barriers to Teaching Critical Thinking (2011) survey. In this research, the majority of teachers regarded student-related issues such as lack of motivation to engage in tasks which require complex thinking, unwillingness to engage in active learning and the ultimate focus on getting good grades as major obstacles to implementing critical thinking. Then came the self-efficacy factor as the second highest barrier to implementing critical thinking. More than half of the teachers doubted their ability to teach critical thinking, or even their knowledge of how this could be manifested in the classroom. Moreover, the majority of teachers expressed that they did not feel ready or prepared to practise critical thinking.

Lack of knowledge of what critical thinking is, how to assess it, and how to cultivate it among students was perceived as the third major barrier. This could be an expected factor as teaching critical thinking requires teachers first to know what critical thinking actually means, second be aware of how best critical thinking can be taught, third be knowledgeable of the different teaching approaches and strategies that facilitate critical thinking development, and finally being capable to model critical thinking in the classroom. This entails that teachers need to gain competence through training or pre-service programmes to be able to teach critical thinking effectively to students. Other factors such as overloaded curriculum, inadequate time, and large classrooms were viewed as the least important constraints.

In similar research, Touati (2016) surveyed 16 EFL teachers from M'sila University (Algeria) to determine what factors impede the development of critical thinking despite the fact that it is considered among the most important goals in the new educational reforms. The questionnaire was divided into three main sections: teacher-related factors, student-related factors, and educational environment factors. Results showed that administrative support and students' characteristics were held accountable for hindering the implementation and development of critical thinking among students. More than half of the teachers regarded lack of support from administration, 'inadequate resource materials', 'additional workload' like supervision, 'large classes', 'lengthy syllabus' and 'mixed ability groups', as major barriers. Then came students' attitudes, 'lack of perseverance', 'discipline issues', and interest in obtaining good scores rather than improving their quality of thinking needed in school and beyond, in the workplace and in life in general. Teachers, however, seemed to disregard factors related to themselves such as 'teachers' attitudes' and 'teachers' lack of knowledge' of what critical thinking is and what teaching strategies are best to foster critical thinking.

Another factor was pointed out by Samarasinghe (2013), when interviewing a group of Omani students to reveal potential issues that might influence the development of critical thinking, which is socio-cultural compatibility. According to the results, Omani students' refraining from using critical thinking is not due to their inability, but this is rather because they have not been used to being involved in situations where they are asked to practise higher-order thinking skills whether in academic or social contexts.

In another survey carried out in a Turkish setting by Yildirim (1993), it was unexpectedly found that some teachers considered themselves responsible for fostering as well as for hindering critical thinking among students. Teachers even showed enthusiasm to enlarge their knowledge about teaching such higher-order thinking skills. However, others disregarded any teacher-related barriers, and highlighted a number of obstacles related to students' behaviours such as their interest in examination results, their lack of confidence in expressing their views and ideas, their expectations of the structure of the teaching/learning process, in addition to their lack of motivation to be involved in innovative teaching approaches.

In contrast to Alibari and Sadeghdaghighi (2013) and Tebb's (2000) findings which showed that teachers' lack of self-efficacy was among the main constraints to implementing critical thinking, Andrews' (2000) survey with 179 teachers in the USA revealed that teachers were aware of the significance of infusing critical thinking in their teaching, and the majority of them had a strong sense of self-efficacy in their abilities to teach it. According to Andrews (2000), teachers instead perceived time limitations, and interest in enhancing grades in standardised tests - rather than interest in preparing tasks which require complex thinking - as barriers to teaching critical thinking.

Ozkan-Akan (2003) conducted a survey on 522 high school teachers from four different regions in Turkey. The results indicated four major impediments to teaching thinking skills which are student-related, teacher-related, curriculum-related, and external factors.

As expected, student-related factors came first as the most reported constraints. Students' resistance to embrace critical thinking skills may be due to: (1) students' expectations that all questions have single absolute answers which do not leave room for multiple perspectives, (2) students' lack of confidence in their ideas, (3) students' preference for conventional ways of teaching and lack of interest in being involved in active learning, (4) students' perception that the teacher and the course book are the only sources of information and authority.

Most teachers perceived curriculum-related constraints as the second main impeding factor to critical thinking. The early study in New Jersey by Oxman and Barell (1983) found that teachers usually associate challenges of fostering critical thinking to the curriculum as well as the student-related barriers. According to the findings of this study, teachers expressed the belief that classroom teaching heavily relies on the content presented in textbooks. They noted that textbooks are often overloaded with various topics and a significant amount of information to be delivered to learners. The expectation is typically for this knowledge to be memorized, consequently leaving limited space for the cultivation of higher-order thinking skills.

When asked about teacher-related constraints, the majority of teachers disagreed with most of the statements. This is because, according to them, teachers are restricted by time to cover the whole syllabus which is considered as a primary aim, and there is no time for complex thinking in the classroom, nor to prepare activities which help in developing critical thinking. They also believed that even exams are not designed to trigger such thinking skills. Interestingly, 50% of teachers in this study believed that higher-order thinking skills are not meant for low-achieving students.

The least agreed constraints were external factors to the classroom together with teacher-related constraints. Teachers pointed out that inspectors give more importance to textbook coverage than to improve critical thinking. They added that they feel obliged to concentrate on finishing the textbook coverage to avoid administrative issues; half of them even expressed their concern about parental disapproval as they think that critical thinking is not socially desired.

To conclude, although developing critical thinking among students is becoming an inevitable aim for educators and course designers, practically speaking this is not an easily attainable task. There are many obstacles and challenges along the way to achieve such a goal; these obstacles need to be clearly identified to overcome and succeed in fostering such thinking skills. It is clear from the discussed literature that teachers have a vital influence on improving or inhibiting critical thinking among students, yet in many - if not the majority of - studies teachers tend to exclude themselves as responsible for hindering critical thinking, but instead they consider other constraints mainly related to students, curriculum and educational environment as discussed earlier. It is then recommended to avoid shirking responsibilities and to start working together towards practical solutions for instance, by providing pre-service programmes to teachers to gain knowledge about teaching critical thinking, also by avoiding a didactic way of teaching and to move to active learning. Moreover, administration and inspectors need to divert their full attention from content coverage

to the development of students' critical thinking, and for students to make some efforts in exploring new learning techniques and being open-minded to embrace innovative teaching approaches.

3.9. Summary

This literature review has provided definitions for critical thinking, focusing on both its cognitive skills and dispositions. The importance of critical thinking is widely recognised across various life domains, particularly in education. According to the literature, critical thinking plays a significant role in promoting ESL/EFL learning. Consequently, this study selected Algerian EFL university teachers as research participants.

Acknowledging the crucial role of critical thinking in education, it has been designated as a fundamental educational goal, with a specific emphasis on university education. Therefore, the study is situated within the university context. The literature review highlights that critical thinking is actively promoted and proven to be teachable in both Western and non-Western educational settings, despite varying degrees of societal acceptance.

Numerous teaching approaches and classroom strategies have been suggested to enhance critical thinking, including discussion on various assessment types. The literature underscores the pivotal role of teachers in cultivating students' critical thinking skills. However, it also acknowledges that teachers' decisions and practices related to critical thinking instruction can be influenced by multiple factors, particularly in Algeria, where critical thinking is not extensively taught and practised in society.

Numerous studies have examined various aspects of EFL classroom dynamics in Algeria, however, there is a significant gap in research focused on the role of critical thinking in higher education within this context. Specifically, there is a scarcity of studies exploring the concept of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes at the university level. Furthermore, existing research has not adequately examined the relationship between policy and implementation regarding critical thinking integration in these classrooms. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the current state of critical thinking in Algerian university EFL classes, highlighting the disparity between its recognition as an educational objective in the curriculum documents and its actual integration into pedagogical practices. This approach is crucial as it reveals that limited knowledge and practice of critical thinking among teachers are directly linked to the lack of opportunities presented in the curriculum documents. By highlighting this gap, the study underscores the perception among teachers that critical thinking is of low significance, resulting in minimal efforts to cultivate it. This research also

addresses the need for more studies on critical thinking within the MENA (Middle East and North Africa) region, an area that has been underrepresented in the broader discourse, which has primarily focused on Western and East Asian contexts. The inclusion of the Algerian context adds a valuable dimension to the existing body of knowledge.

In light of this, the review suggests a need for a comprehensive study that explores critical thinking representation in the curriculum document, delves into teachers' perspectives on critical thinking ,and investigates teaching practices within the Algerian educational context. This holistic approach aims to address the current state of critical thinking in Algerian education and offer valuable insights for its advancement.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

4.1. Introduction

In this chapter, the research methodology employed in my study will be discussed. It will start by identifying briefly the competing research paradigms or worldviews, then addressing the philosophical assumptions concerning ontology and epistemology underpinning the chosen research paradigm. I will then move on to discuss the chosen research approach, research design, and tools of data collection implemented in this study. Then, I will tackle the process of sampling and sample description. Finally, this chapter will consider the approach of data analysis and issues related to ethics.

4.2. Philosophical considerations

Educational research is a type of systematic inquiry based on collecting and analysing data related to the field of education. Ideally, it starts with identifying a problem, describing the aim of the research after reviewing the literature, gathering and analysing data, and finally interpreting it to reach a result which solves a problem or provides a better understanding of various educational phenomena. According to Newby (2010), educational research seeks primarily to investigate problems and find solutions, to improve academics' understanding of different issues, to examine and share policies for policymakers, and to enhance practice for teachers and practitioners in educational settings. On his part, Creswell (2002) identifies the following six possible purposes for educational research:

- Improve practice: research can result in an improvement in educational practices after being applied and tested in different contexts and on many individuals.
- Add to knowledge: educational research can add to existing knowledge and can suggest ways to facilitate the teaching and learning process.
- Identify gaps in knowledge: educational research can target issues where there is very little knowledge and investigations.
- Expand knowledge: research can enlarge our knowledge about things we know by tackling new perspectives.
- Replicate knowledge: research can be used to test the validity of previous research and confirm the results.

- Add voices of individuals to knowledge: research can address a variety of perspectives particularly those which weren't considered in the past to meet more diverse educational needs.

Stenhouse (1984, cited in Wellington, 2000) defines educational research as a 'systematic activity that is directed towards providing knowledge, or adding to the understanding of existing knowledge which is of relevance for improving the effectiveness of education' (p. 11). In an attempt to interpret this definition, three assumptions underlying research can be depicted: 'existing' refers to ontology, 'knowledge' refers to epistemology, and 'understanding' and 'improving' refers to research methodology, hence research paradigm in general.

A research paradigm is therefore composed of four main parts: ontology, epistemology, methodology and methods. The relationship between these philosophical assumptions which represent the basis of any research is directional. In the sense that one automatically leads to the other, as put by Hitchcock and Hughes (1995), where ontology is beliefs about the nature of existence which brings about epistemology. The latter reflects the way of investigating the nature of reality, and this knowledge brings about methodology which is the assumptions and rationale behind choosing methods. The last represents the research instruments used to collect data. In the following discussion, I will further elaborate on the aforementioned philosophical assumptions and the two major competing paradigms. Subsequently, at the end of this section, I will make my position clear regarding the research paradigm underpinning the current study.

What is ontology? Ontology refers to the beliefs about the kind and nature of reality. Ontology which Grix (2004) considers as the starting point in any research represents how we perceive the nature of things. Our beliefs of what reality is can determine the way of knowing about truth. Bryman (2008) proposes the concept of 'social ontology' which is a philosophical assumption dealing with social constructs as independent entities which can exist on their own without the intervention of individuals, or they are subjective entities which are socially constructed by individuals' experiences, views and interpretations. On similar lines, Ormston et al. (2014) suggest that social ontology reflects 'whether or not there is a social reality that exists independently from human conceptions and interpretations and, closely related to this, whether there is a shared social reality or only multiple, context-specific ones'(p.4). Hence, there are two broad types of ontology: realism and relativism (Pring, 2000). Realism entails that there exists only one objective reality which can be revealed by objective context-free experimental research, and findings can be generalisable. This type can also

be called objectivism. However, in relativism, multiple realities are embraced; there is no fixed reality *per se* as reality is yielded by social actors' experiences and interpretations. Unlike realism, reality from a relativist perspective is context-bound and, hence cannot be generalised but only transferred to identical contexts. To put it briefly, ontology is concerned with our beliefs of what is there to exist in the world that we can know about; it is also the way of viewing the kind and nature of reality and truth. This view can be referred to as constructionism.

Epistemology is the theory of knowledge or our beliefs of the nature and forms of knowledge, and the nature of the relationship between the researcher and what is being researched. For Crotty (1998), epistemology asks the questions: what is knowledge? what knowledge is possible to approach and what is not? how can we know and make sense of this knowledge? Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007) explain that epistemology deals with our beliefs about 'the very bases of knowledge – its nature and form, how it can be acquired and how communicated to other human beings' (p.7). There are a number of epistemological positions ,among them the major ones are: positivism which is compatible with ontological realism; and, interpretivism which is compatible with ontological relativism or constructionism.

Taking a positivist epistemology position where knowledge is regarded as objective, value and context-free and where reality exists independently without the intervention of individuals in the social world, this implies that the researcher should seek to discover the truth which already lies in objects. In other words, positivists in epistemology gain absolute knowledge about the world by discovering objective realities and meanings which already reside in objects that were waiting for the researcher to discover. Crotty (1998) clarifies:

A tree in the forest is a tree, regardless of whether anyone is aware of its existence or not. As an object of that kind, it carries the intrinsic meaning of treeness. When human beings recognize it as a tree, they are simply discovering a meaning that has been lying in wait for them all along.

(p.2)

In addition to that, positivist epistemology accepts the scientific methods of inquiry adopted in natural sciences to inquire and understand phenomena, methods such as hypothesis testing, cause-effect experiments and careful observation. According to this view, knowledge is tangible and can only be confirmed through our senses (Bryman, 2008; Ormston et al, 2014).

Moving to the interpretivist epistemology, knowledge is regarded as subjective, personal, and context-bound which can be understood through individuals' interpretations and perceptions of the social world. In this opposing view, the researcher should engage and be part of the research, he or she should not be distant from the research participants. Hence, both the research subjects' and the researcher's values, construction of meanings, and interpretations are embraced.

Unlike the traditional position, interpretivist epistemology rejects the scientific methods of inquiry of natural sciences when researching social phenomena. This is because social phenomena are not run by law-like regularities but rather are understood through the meanings and perceptions of the social actors (Bryman, 2008; Ormston et al, 2014; Al Saadi, 2014). The methodology then asks the question 'how can the inquirer (would-be knower) go about finding out whatever he or she believes can be known? (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p.108). This means that methodology deals basically with how we go about exploring social phenomena, it is the strategy or plan which informs the choice of particular tools (Crotty, 1998). In other words, methodology is a set of procedures, and associated rationale, which will be put into practice for the sake of understanding a certain phenomenon. Methods, on the other hand, are a 'range of approaches used in educational research to gather data which are to be used as a basis for inference and interpretation' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2003, p.108). Hence methods are simply the actual procedures, techniques, or tools which are used to collect and analyse data in a research process.

4.2.1. Research worldviews

Research paradigms are, 'ways of looking at the world, different assumptions about what the world is like and how we can understand or know about it' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Therefore, a paradigm or a worldview as the name indicates is a way of perceiving the world, a set of principles, and a system of beliefs about the way of perceiving knowledge which shapes our way of seeking answers to research questions and finding solutions to problems. A research paradigm is characterised by ontological, epistemological and methodological considerations. A number of research paradigms are discussed in the literature (Pring, 2015; Creswell, 2013; Lather, 2004) - for example: positivist, interpretivist, critical, emancipatory, pragmatic, constructionist, advocacy/participatory, and empirical-analytic. Among these, the most popular and widely used paradigms are: positivism and interpretivism which are discussed below.

4.2.1.1. Positivism

The positivist paradigm can be historically traced back to the nineteenth-century French philosopher, Auguste Comte, who was the first to use the term positivism as a philosophical approach and who was also behind considering sociology as a separate discipline (Beck, 1979 cited in Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.10). According to Comte, experimental and statistical techniques are crucial to uncover knowledge. Ontologically, this view believes that there is one single reality which is external to individuals and can be uncovered through empirical observational procedures of the scientific method. Epistemologically, in this view, there is a clear line between facts and values, and thus the researcher's values and influence are detached from the object to be known. Methodologically, what counts in positivism is the measurement of elements, quantification of statistical data, and direct observation of variables. Positivists believe in generating theories and laws to make predictions which make it possible to investigate the social world (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Grix, 2004; Seale, 2000).

The positivist position has been subject to criticism and rejection since the second half of the nineteenth century on the grounds that scientific methods are not able to investigate social phenomena. Concepts such as inner experiences, attitudes, thoughts and perceptions which characterise human behaviour are abstract conceptualisations. These qualities are neither tangible nor observed through our senses and therefore are not possible to be measured using the traditional objective approach of inquiry (Hammersley, 2013). As such, positivism proves insufficient for this study, positivism's limitation in acknowledging the subjective nature of human interpretations hinders its suitability for exploring the depth of understanding and the significance teachers ascribe to critical thinking in their teaching, and the realities of critical thinking implementation in Algerian university EFL classes . Teachers' perceptions are inherently subjective and shaped by their unique experiences, an aspect that aligns more with an interpretivist approach which is elaborated upon in the subsequent section. Another criticism highlighted by Pring (2015) is that positivism fails to consider the human's great potential to interpret personal experiences and give meanings to different issues and phenomena, hence neglecting a great deal of truth about reality. 'How we make sense of the social world resides in our distinctively human nature, and we have to take account of this in recognizing that the social world is not the same as an object of science' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018. p. 15). Therefore, positivism does not align with the study's emphasis on delving into the lived experiences, beliefs, and reflections that influence instructional decisions; and thus understanding the practices reported by participant teachers and the challenges they encounter.

Finally, results which are generated from the positivist approach are often seen of little value and practicality, especially for those concerned such as educators, practitioners, managers, etc. (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This is because findings are very likely to be deterministic, unnatural and laboratory-like which is very far from what social world phenomena really embody. These principles does not serve the context-specific nature of the current study; and does not acknowledge the subjective interpretations and meanings that teachers and educational stakeholders ascribe to their experiences within the unique cultural and educational context of Algerian higher education. These criticisms have given rise to an opposing view namely interpretivism which is likely to be pertinent to social sciences.

4.2.1.2. Interpretivism

The interpretivist or constructivist approach is more human-based: it is grounded in the belief that reality is multi-layered and that individuals are socially active and are able to construct and interpret social reality. Interpretivists approach the social world in its natural settings, no intervention or testing is involved. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2003) state that the 'social world can only be understood from the standpoint of the individuals who are part of the ongoing action being investigated' (p.19). Both the researcher and the research participants' values and interpretations are involved in this view. The researcher approaches the social world with some thoughts and values in which he/she believes are not enough to understand a particular phenomenon because of the various, changeable, and unexpected ways of what is perceived as reality (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). The researcher instead builds on prior knowledge and collaborates with the participants' perspectives to interpret and shape socially constructed knowledge. This is why the interpretivist researcher is compared by Denzin and Lincoln (2008) to a bricoleur: 'interpretive bricoleur understands that research is an interactive process shaped by his own personal history, biography, gender, social class, race, and ethnicity, and by those of the people in the setting' (p.9). Ontologically, Interpretivists hold a relativist view which implies that reality is perceived differently from one individual to another (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Hence reality is viewed as a socially constructed process (Pring, 2000). Epistemologically, interpretivists hold that knowledge is subjective and personal and that knowledge develops through the interaction of individuals within a specific context (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007).

Methodologically, interpretivists aim at understanding and exploring the social world through the subjects' perspectives and viewpoints (Creswell, 2009). Examples of methodologies are case studies, ethnography and phenomenology. Generalisation however might be considered absent in the

interpretivist paradigm as findings are usually context-bound and based on personal subjective constructions, and hence might not fit in different contexts (Neuman, 2000). Unlike positivism's theory testing which precedes data (deductive approach), theories in interpretivism develop and emerge from data (inductive approach) (Creswell, 2003).

4.2.1.3. The chosen research paradigm

The interpretivist paradigm serves as the foundational framework for exploring critical thinking representation in EFL curriculum documents in Algerian higher education. Guided by a social constructivist ontological stance, critical thinking representations are socially constructed by diverse stakeholders. The interpretivist lens allows us to move beyond surface-level document analysis, facilitating a nuanced understanding of the meanings attributed to critical thinking within the specific cultural and educational context. Qualitative methods, inherent in interpretivism, such as document analysis and interviews, enable a rich exploration of multifaceted perspectives shaping these representations.

Aligning with the study's aim of understanding how teachers incorporate ministry guidelines into practical strategies for critical thinking, the interpretivist epistemology proves instrumental. This approach unveils the tacit knowledge, beliefs, and contextual factors influencing teachers' decisions. The interpretivist paradigm underscores the importance of subjective meanings, enabling a comprehensive exploration of the intricate interplay of individual interpretations within the social context, essential for translating policy into practice.

Adopting an interpretivist paradigm is particularly apt for delving into teachers' perceptions of critical thinking. Acknowledging that these perceptions are shaped by individual experiences, beliefs, and social interactions, unravelling subjective meanings attributed to critical thinking by teachers. This approach facilitates a nuanced exploration, recognising diverse ways teachers conceptualise and value critical thinking in their teaching practices.

Identifying the practices teachers employ to foster critical thinking skills and uncovering the challenges they encounter is approached through the interpretivist paradigm, offering a holistic understanding. Acknowledging that practices are influenced by individual perceptions and contextual factors, this paradigm navigates the intricacies of the teaching environment. The interpretivist lens encourages an in-depth exploration of teachers' lived experiences, bringing to light tacit knowledge and personal reflections influencing instructional decisions. In essence, the interpretivist paradigm serves as the theoretical backbone for this study, aligning seamlessly with

each aim by emphasizing the social construction of knowledge, subjective meanings, and contextual intricacies that shape the phenomenon under investigation.

4.3. The chosen research methodology (qualitative) and approach (inductive)

The current study is designed to answer the following main research questions:

1. To what extent does Algerian higher education encourage the teaching of critical thinking skills?
2. To what extent has critical thinking moved from theory to actual educational practices?
3. What are university EFL teachers' perceptions of critical thinking, and the importance of its integration in their teaching?
4. What practices do EFL teachers enact to, or consider would, foster EFL learners' critical thinking abilities?

Therefore, the research aims at:

- Investigating the extent of critical thinking representation in the curriculum document communicated by the Ministry of Higher Education to universities, i.e. identifying any evidence of infusing critical thinking and considering it as an educational objective.
- Observing the extent to which teachers attempt to implement the ministry guidelines, and their translation of these guidelines into practice in regard to the infusion and development of critical thinking among students.
- Exploring teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking, what they know about it, and how important they think it is to integrate critical thinking in their teaching.
- Identifying potential practices teachers perform to develop critical thinking skills, and highlighting the challenges and barriers they perceive on the way of delivering it.

The focus of this study is to gain an in-depth understanding of the state of critical thinking in Algerian Higher education between theory and practice: that is, introducing it as an educational objective only, or actually considering it in practice through an investigation of teachers' thoughts and perceptions, and observation of actual classroom educational practices. Considering the two major research paradigms in the field of education namely quantitative and qualitative, I have decided that the scientific methods of natural sciences which fall under quantitative research do not fit in this research, and therefore the current study embraces a qualitative paradigm, which is elaborated upon in the following section.

4.3.1. Characteristics of qualitative research

There has been always an ongoing debate about the most appropriate paradigm for educational research: quantitative or qualitative. Quantitative research - as the term indicates – is concerned with the quantification and analysis of data in numerical form. Unlike quantitative research's emphasis on numbers and on gathering large quantities of data from a large sample, qualitative research's focus lies on words, thoughts and feelings (Bryman, 2008). Qualitative research aims at understanding and interpreting knowledge and reality as it is perceived by different individuals in its natural settings. It is defined by Macmillan and Schumacher (2006) as an inquiry in which data is gathered through direct interaction between the researcher and the research participants in their natural context. Similarly, Creswell (2007,) provides the following definition:

Qualitative research begins with assumptions, a worldview, the possible use of a theoretical lens, and the study of research problems inquiring into the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. To study this problem, qualitative researchers use an emerging qualitative approach to inquiry, the collection of data in natural setting sensitive to the people and places under study, and data analysis that is inductive and establishes patterns or themes.

(p. 37)

The outcomes of a qualitative inquiry involve a combination of participants' thoughts, views and voices, researcher's reflection on his/her own per-conceived assumptions, in-depth description and interpretation of the phenomena and the problem under study. Its significance can be either in enlarging the literature in the area being investigated, or it can serve as a call for making a change and action.

Hammersley (2013) suggests an inclusive definition of qualitative research, which he defines as:

A form of social inquiry that tends to adopt a flexible and data-driven research design, to use relatively unstructured data, to emphasise the essential role of subjectivity in the research process, to study a number of naturally occurring cases in detail, and to use verbal rather than statistical forms of approach.

(p. 12)

Drawing on these definitions and a comparison between LeCompte and Schensul (1999), Marshall and Marshall and Rossman (2006), and Hatch (2002) definitions, the following common characteristics of qualitative research are discussed by Creswell (2007, pp. 37-39):

‘Natural setting’: in qualitative research, data are collected in face-to-face interaction, the researcher tends to get in touch directly with the participants in their natural settings. Individuals are not brought into specific labs, and tools are not distributed to them to complete, instead, they are being observed and talked to in their context.

‘Researcher as key instrument’: the whole process of data collection in qualitative research necessitates that the researchers gather data by themselves, they analyse documents, interview individuals, and observe their behaviours.

‘Multiple sources of data’: qualitative researchers use a rigorous approach to data collection, they don’t rely on a single instrument, they adopt multiple sources of data such as document analysis, interviews and observations. They interpret information, organise and generate themes to create meaning out of all the data collection tools.

‘Inductive data analysis’: qualitative researchers use an inductive research approach, they organise data into categories and themes to come up with a meaningful set of themes in a ‘bottom-up’ process.

‘Participants’ meaning’: throughout the entire qualitative inquiry, the researchers’ ultimate focus is put on the meaning that the individuals under study have towards the problem, it is not however the meaning that the researchers hold, or read in the literature.

‘Emergent design’: in the way of reaching information in qualitative research, the researchers enter the field with an initial plan which may change later as the research progresses. The process of qualitative data collection is flexible, and there is always a possibility of changing and modifying the research questions, the fieldwork, or the research sample, or shifting the data collection forms. A rigid research process is avoided as it stands in the way of exploring new directions in case a change in situations occurs, or an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon develops over time.

‘Interpretive inquiry’: qualitative research is based on the researchers’ interpretations of the collected data from different forms which cannot be detached from their historical and contextual backgrounds, or their prior knowledge. The readers and participants will then give their own interpretations of the study, resulting in different views of the problem under study.

‘Holistic account’: qualitative researches commit to establishing a rich, complex and in-depth picture of the issue. The researchers’ main focus is not to discover cause-effect relationships, but rather to shed light on the complex interactions of various factors.

Most of the above-mentioned characteristics can be related to the current study, as I aimed to provide a holistic picture of the state of critical thinking in Algerian higher education using multiple

methods of data collection in natural settings. The interpretation of the collected data from interviews, classroom observation, and document analysis yielded a thorough and in-depth picture of the overall situation. I intended to let the data inform the study, that is, meaning is constructed through the data, instead of deductively testing an established theory to confirm or reject it. Hence this study follows an inductive approach which best matches qualitative research (Creswell, 2015; Robson and McCartan, 2016). I deliberately chose to adopt a data-driven and inductive approach rather than employing a theoretical framework. The central focus was on exploring the state of critical thinking within the Algerian higher education context, particularly its integration into the curriculum and the perspectives and practices of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers. Given the absence of a well-established theoretical foundation specific to critical thinking in the Algerian context, opting for a data-driven and inductive methodology allowed the study to organically unfold, drawing insights directly from the data collected, ensuring that the findings are contextually relevant and grounded in the experiences and perspectives of EFL teachers. The research questions were carefully formulated to explore the conceptualisations, challenges, and teaching approaches related to critical thinking without the need for a predetermined theoretical framework. The findings demonstrated a nuanced understanding of the curriculum objectives, teachers' perceptions and practices, and obstacles hindering the development of critical thinking among EFL teachers. By relying on a data-driven approach, the study successfully addressed its objectives, showcasing the effectiveness of this method in capturing the complexities of Algerian higher education concerning critical thinking in EFL classes.

4.4. The chosen research design: Case study

Denzin and Lincoln (2011) state 'each practice makes the world visible in a different way' (p.7). Of the various approaches within qualitative research, the focus of this study is definitely not to explore the stories of individuals' life to develop a narrative about it (narrative research), is not to provide a description of how a culture-sharing group works (ethnography), is not either to describe the essence in individuals' experiences in a particular phenomenon (phenomenology), and is not to generate a theory model (grounded theory). The focus of this study is to develop an in-depth and holistic description of an issue through an exploration of a case. Hence, I choose case study as a research design to approach this research. To start with, some like Stake (2005) view case study as only the choice which the researcher makes of what is to be studied (or 'sample' of the study). However, many others introduce it as an approach, a research strategy, a methodology, a type of research design or a research outcome (Creswell, 2007; Denzin and Lincoln, 2005; Merriam, 1998;

Yin, 2003). This study adopts case study as a research design or an approach to qualitative inquiry. Arriving at a single definition of the case study is not an easy task, Creswell (2007), for instance, defines it as a qualitative approach which seeks to explore a 'bounded system' or 'multiple bounded systems' through a period of time using multiple data collection methods (e.g. interviews, documents, audio-visual materials, and observations) to develop an in-depth analysis and description of a case. Yin (2009) does not agree on the term 'bounded system', he describes the case study as a study which investigates a phenomenon in its natural context where the boundaries between the phenomenon and the context are not clearly apparent.

A case study is, therefore, a type of research design which allows exploring a phenomenon through describing and analysing individuals' views and interactions, or events to develop a rich, detailed and holistic view using a rigorous approach of data collection to gather information in multiple forms within particular temporal and geographical boundaries.

Drawing on these definitions, case studies have several characteristics. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) consider the vivid and rich description of the whole situation or events in a case, 'a case study provides a unique example of real people in real situations, enabling readers to understand ideas more clearly than simply by presenting them with abstract theories or principles' (p.376). Case studies involve the analysis of many variables in a single case, thus to examine these variables, adapting more than one research method is necessary to collect multiple forms of evidence (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Case studies can accept both quantitative and qualitative data, hence can be adopted in mixed methods research, but can also be limited to quantitative research; case studies can blend description, explanation, analysis, and illustration (Yin, 2009). Hitchcock and Hughes (1995) argue that there is often a compatibility between case studies and interpretive inquiries, and that the less control and manipulation of variables, events, and individuals' behaviours, the more valuable the case study is. Another distinguishing aspect of case studies is highlighted by Verschuren (2003), he emphasises case studies' 'holism' rather than 'reductionism' where his conceptualisation of 'holism' does not necessarily mean analysing the whole situation, group, or institution, but rather looking at specific areas of interest in a case.

According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018), researchers in case studies can establish causal relationships as they observe causes and effects in real-life contexts, but they need to deeply understand the case to do justice to it.

Using case study is particularly important for this research as it allows the triangulation of data from different methods (interviews, observation, and document analysis) where I can listen, observe,

examine and then interpret. Triangulation of data - which Yin (2014) considers a unique characteristic of case study - helps in checking and maximising the research outcomes.

4.4.1. Types of case studies

There are many types of case studies which are classified based on different criteria. Denscombe (2014, p. 57), for instance, suggests two main types of case studies based on the purpose of the study: 'discovery-led' purposes which involve describing, comparing, explaining, and exploring, and 'theory-led' purposes which involve illustrating and experimenting.

Following Denscombe's 'discovery-led' classification, Yin (2014) identifies three major categories of case studies based on the research outcomes:

- Exploratory case studies can contribute to form research questions, or to develop hypotheses to be tested in larger-scale studies, be it qualitative or quantitative. However, Adelman, Kemmis and Jenkins (1980) reject the claim of adopting case studies only as preliminaries to other studies, and argue for the significance and legitimacy of the existence of case studies as a stand-alone sufficient research design which aims to explore a phenomenon and provide a rich analysis of situations where there is no single set of outcomes.
- Descriptive case studies provide narrative accounts by describing a particular phenomenon as it occurs in its real-life context.
- Explanatory case studies can be used to test theories, and explain causal relationships. Types of research questions which ask 'why' and 'how' are more likely to fit in explanatory case studies.

Echoing Yin's (2014) classification of case studies, the current study is exploratory in nature as all of the research questions ask primarily the 'what' type of questions: 1. To what extent does Algerian higher education encourage the teaching of critical thinking skills? 2. To what extent has critical thinking moved from theory to actual educational practices? 3. What are university EFL teachers' perceptions of critical thinking, and the importance of its integration in their teaching? 4. What practices do EFL teachers enact to, or consider would, foster EFL learners' critical thinking abilities?

4.4.2. Issues underlying case studies

According to Creswell (2007) and Denscombe (2014), one of the issues that the researcher may encounter when conducting qualitative research using case study design is to clearly identify what Creswell calls 'the bounded system': selecting and realising the boundaries of what exactly to involve in a case whether an individual or individuals, an institution, a programme, or as an activity is often

a daunting task. Another issue which is identified by Creswell (2007) is the choice of whether to study a single case or multiple cases as according to him including more than one case can affect the depth, focus and richness of the study. On the other hand, considering a single case gives rise to the issue of generalisability - the most notable concern when conducting case studies. Ruddin (2006) suggests that there is no need to introduce generalisability as a requirement for case studies at all as generalisability falls under the positivist philosophy, and hence has very little meaning for interpretive and qualitative research. To Yin (2014), when considering the limitation of generalising from case studies, one may ask the question of whether it is possible to generalise from a single experiment: he points out that 'generalisations in science is rarely based on a single experiment, they are usually based on a multiple set of experiments that have replicated the same phenomena under different conditions' (p. 20). The same could apply to case studies.

In support of this claim, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) state that just as experiments, case studies can be generalisable by the replication of multiple case studies 'contributing to greater generalisability' (p.380). However, Yin (2014) proposes that case studies embrace 'analytic generalisation' rather than 'statistical generalisation', he argues 'case studies, like experiments, are generalisable to theoretical propositions and not to populations or universes' (p.21). Statistical generalisation implies extrapolating from a sample to a broader population based on the size of the sample, frequencies, and statistical significance, whereas analytic generalisation aims at expanding and generalising to broader theories (Yin, 2014). According to Thomas (2010), despite the uniqueness and singularity of case studies, they offer 'exemplary knowledge' (p.576). Simons (2015) suggests that case studies are generalisable as the reader can relate and connect his/her own experiences and understandings to those in the case study. Hence, case studies can offer 'universal significance' (p.181). She also notes that the reader can apply this universal understanding in his/her own situation. Pring (2015) questions the idea that case studies need to consider generalisability in a scientific way at all as they can 'alert one to similar possibilities in other situations. They, as it were, 'ring bells'' (p.56).

An analytic argument needs to be built based on the research outcomes and the reviewed literature. Therefore, the current study remains hopeful that it would be possible to demonstrate how the resulting analytic argument which reveals the actual situation of critical thinking in the Algerian University can theoretically be expanded, generalised, be related, and alert to situations other than the chosen one.

4.5. Data collection tools

As mentioned earlier, the current study adopts a qualitative approach where a range of methods was chosen to seek triangulation of data. The aim behind triangulating the data through two or more research instruments is to achieve consistent findings, to compare the data gathered through different methods, to spot any potential interesting differences, and to check and confirm the results (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007). Patton (2002) highlights the rationale for using different sources of data 'studies that use only one method are more vulnerable to errors linked to that particular method . . . than studies that use multiple methods in which different types of data provide cross data validity checks' (p. 188). Similarly, Adeyemi (2008) argues that combining multiple research tools reduces the risk of bias in the research outcomes, minimises threats to the validity and reliability of the research findings, and hence maximises the trustworthiness of the study. Creswell (1998) notes that:

There are four basic types of information to collect: observations (ranging from non-participants to participants), interviews (ranging from semi-structured to open-ended), documents (ranging from private to public) and audio-visual materials including materials such as photographs, compact disks and video tapes.

(p. 120)

Three of the of the abovementioned forms of data collection - analysis of the curriculum documents, observation of classroom events and practices to explore the translation of the teaching guidelines into real practice, and semi-structured interviews with teachers - were employed in the current study. Regarding the order in which the three research tools were utilized, I began with document analysis. This initial step set the foundation for the study by providing an overview of the state of critical thinking in the curriculum documents, allowing me to examine how these documents might influence teachers' understanding and practices. Following this, I conducted interviews to delve into teachers' understanding of critical thinking and their practical expertise in its application. Lastly, I used classroom observations to verify whether the teachers' reported understanding and practices were reflected in their actual classroom behaviour. It is important to acknowledge that conducting classroom observations before the interviews could have offered further insights into teachers' practices. However, this approach would have been challenging and potentially infeasible. I assumed that building a good rapport with teachers through interviews was necessary before requesting to observe their classes. The data collection process was difficult due to the COVID-19 circumstances,

and directly asking teachers to observe their sessions without first establishing trust through interviews would have made even more challenging. In the following discussion, I will look specifically at these research instruments.

4.5.1. Interviews

Interviews are the most powerful and commonly used data collection instruments in qualitative research (Kumar, 2005).

According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018), the interview is not only a practice to gather data, but also 'a social, interpersonal encounter' (p. 506) which enables an interchange of ideas and viewpoints between two or more people about a particular topic of mutual interest. Yet, it is important to note that the interview is not a daily, ordinary conversation as it requires careful planning and adequate preparation, it is usually based on constructed questions, and it aims to gain evidence and information which renders it different from events and conversations that occur naturally. The interview seeks to explore both the interviewer's and interviewee's worldviews and interpretations of different situations and events in which they live.

Lichtman (2006) and Bernard (2000) identify three common types of interviews. In the unstructured or informal interview, the interviewer has great freedom and flexibility in guiding the content and structure of the interview. This type requires experienced interviewing skills as the interviewer has to develop, adapt and generate follow-up questions relating to the purpose of this study as the conversation proceeds. The unstructured interview can also serve as a preliminary activity at the beginning of an interview to establish rapport with the interviewee or interviewees, and to make them feel at ease and not being interrogated. This type of interview is best known to be used in ethnographic studies. In the structured, standardised interview (Lichtman, 2006; Bernard, 2000), the interviewing procedure is rigid where the researcher is supposed to ask an exact pre-determined set of questions with the same wording and order to each participant. The structure of the interview is prepared in the form of a schedule with pre-established response categories similar to the structure of a questionnaire, which is why it is sometimes referred to as a verbal questionnaire (Ribbins, 2007). Limiting and constraining the participants' answers to categories is considered one of the drawbacks of the structured interview as respondents may feel that they have to fit their perceptions, experiences, and thoughts into categories established by the researcher. In the semi-structured interview - often viewed as the most convenient and effective form of data collection (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009) -, the researcher has more freedom and flexibility compared to the structured interview, despite the pre-set open-ended questions which are scheduled to cover particular

themes, the researcher still has the possibility to customise and tailor the wording and sequence of questions according to the flow of the interview. Furthermore, the researcher can introduce follow-up questions and probe the participants' views and meanings to elicit more elaborate answers (Lichtman, 2006; Bernard, 2000). The semi-structured interview is often regarded as the most favourable type of all interviews, as it enables the interviewer to capture hidden and complex issues related to the participants' perspectives and experiences. Gillham (2000) also argues that this type of interview is the most significant and probably the most productive if carefully planned and properly carried out.

Considering the issue of power relations when interviewing, although Mason (2002) notes that the interviewer is usually the one who possesses power over the interviewee, in the case of the elite interview, the interviewee undoubtedly has the power over the conversation content.

For the purpose of this research, I opted for the semi-structured interview based on the following rationale. First, the semi-structured interview, although guided by a schedule, is flexible, in the sense that the researcher can adapt the pre-set guide and extend the interview based on the flow of the conversation. As such, the interviewer is allowed to generate additional questions, change the sequence of the questions, or even change the style and wording of the questions to disclose important and hidden facets of a situation. As Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007) point out, the use of the semi-structured interview allows me to probe the participants' answers and to develop follow-up questions, to seek clarification about critical and unexpected responses. According to Denscombe (2007, p. 176), interviews can 'develop ideas and speak more widely on the issues raised by the researcher'. Second, unlike the structured interview which limits the interviewee's answers to pre-established categories, the semi-structured interview is characterised by open-ended questions, and therefore allowing the interviewee or interviewees to freely express themselves, and provide answers in their own terms using their own language and ideas, enabling both sides of the interview to ask for clarification, and hence maximising the construction of knowledge. Third, the semi-structured interview consumes less time compared, for instance, to the unstructured interview, as the latter does not have a guiding script or pre-set questions and probes to direct the conversation (Kumar, 1999), whereas the semi-structured interview is organised by a schedule to frame the flow of the interview and reduce bias. Emphasising this point, Freebody (2003) and Kumar (1999) argue that following the prepared list of questions may increase the reliability of the interviewing process. As such, The interviews were carried out with ten EFL university teachers from a department of English language in Algeria. I purposely chose EFL teachers who teach at different

university levels to gather diverse views about the topic under investigation, particularly, to explore whether critical thinking is considered at any stage in higher education.

Before the phase of recruiting participants, permission for data collection was sought from the head of the department. Potential participants were then contacted first via email, a consent form and a participant information sheet were attached to provide an overview of the topic. Teachers were then approached individually to arrange appointments and were promised anonymity and the right to withdraw. For each scheduled appointment, I arrived at the location chosen by each participant well in advance. I waited in close proximity until the interview time to ensure punctuality. Before the interviews commenced, participants were once again briefed on the interview's purpose, the utilisation of an audio recorder, their access to interview transcriptions and analysed data, and the potential use of collected data in publications. Additionally, they were reassured about the anonymity and confidentiality of both their identities and any data they might contribute.

During the interviews conducted with the use of an audio recorder, I tended also to take notes on aspects that I found particularly intriguing. While this approach could potentially disrupt the natural flow of the interview, it served as a demonstration of my keen interest and attentiveness to their expressions. Furthermore, the act of note-taking during the interviews appeared to encourage participants to express themselves more freely, possibly because they perceived that their ideas were being acknowledged and deemed valuable to the research. It is important to acknowledge that the language used in all the conducted interviews was English. Consequently, there was no need for translation of the interview transcripts. This significantly reduced the potential for misinterpretation or distortion of the data that can occur during translation. By conducting and analysing the interviews in the original language, the study ensured that the nuances, idiomatic expressions, and specific terminology used by the participants were preserved. This approach enhanced the accuracy and reliability of the data interpretation, thereby strengthening the overall trustworthiness of the research findings.

Following each interview, I made an effort to document essential insights for potential enhancements in subsequent interviews. This involved capturing thoughts on areas that could be improved and noting concepts that required further clarification in future interviews. This reflective practice aimed to refine the interview process and ensure that subsequent interactions were more effective and insightful.

4.5.1.1. Stages of planning an interview

Based on the guidance provided by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009), I followed the seven stages that qualitative researchers need to go through in planning to conduct an interview, and these are discussed below

Thematizing: this is the introductory stage of an interview which is mainly about setting the major purpose of the study which is to offer a comprehensive understanding of the state of critical thinking in Algerian university EFL classes; this stage involves also highlighting the rationale for selecting interviews as a research tool which is to collect varied accounts from teachers regarding their conceptualisations and practices. The intention is also to enable a thorough comparison with the results obtained from the other research tools employed in this investigation.

Designing: at this stage, I planned the interview schedule, particularly, I transformed the research objectives and questions into actual questions to reflect the aims of this study. I also had to decide about the question format and the response mode. Robson and McCartan (2016) propose what might be covered in the interview schedule for the semi-structured interview '- Introductory comments (probably a verbatim script); - List of topic headings and possibly key questions to ask under these headings; - Set of associated prompts; and - Closing comments.' (p.291).

Interviewing: refers to the actual process of interviewing which is based on a list of questions to guide the flow of the conversation. I began by explaining the conduct of the interview, and assuring that the participants will remain anonymous, and that their responses will strictly be kept confidential, and that they have the right to interrupt at any time to ask for clarification. I then asked for participants' permission to record the interview to aid the analysis. I continued with the known protocol of interviewing, to ask questions and hopefully receive thoughtful answers (Robson and McCartan, 2016). However, I was flexible and made some amendments to the interview guide, added some questions when necessary, skipped ones, and changed the sequence of certain questions based on the flow of the interview. This adaptability is particularly applicable to the semi-structured interview, which is why it was selected for this study.

Transcribing: this stage is described by Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) as critical in the interviewing process for 'there is a potential for massive data loss, distortion and the reduction of complexity' (p.523). Consequently, when transcribing an oral, interpersonal encounter into written form, there is a risk of data losing its depth and richness, along with the omission of non-verbal messages.

Analysing: after the transcription of the data collected from the interview, comes the stage of analysing and interpreting these scripts and organising them into themes and codes using particular approaches of data analysis (see section 4.6).

Verifying: checking the validity, reliability and generalisability of the research outcomes - though generalisability is not the aim of the current study (see section 4.8).

Reporting: communicating the results is generally based on the type of interview. For instance, conducting structured interviews is likely to yield numerical data which might be presented in the form of tables and graphs, however, open-ended interviews which is the case in this study yielded word-based data, and hence qualitatively reported.

4.5.2. Observation

Since people's actions and behaviours are core aspects in real-world research, a natural and effective strategy is 'to watch what they do', to record this in a particular form, to describe, and then analyse and interpret what has been observed (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.319). According to Marshall and Rossman (2016), observation does not entail just looking. It is, however, looking systematically and documenting carefully events, activities, and individuals' behaviours, routines, etc. A unique characteristic of observation as a research tool is that 'it offers an investigator the opportunity to gather first-hand 'live' data' from events or situations which naturally occur in the social world. (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Hence observation allows the researcher to obtain direct and authentic data about what is actually going on in the situation rather than counting on second-hand data. In many cases, what people declare they do, does not necessarily reflect what they actually do in real-life situations, and observation offers a reality check (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Observation allows the researcher to collect data on:

- The physical setting (e.g. the physical environment and its organisation);
- The human setting (e.g. the organisation of people, the characteristics and make-up of the groups or individuals being observed, for instance, gender, class);
- The interactional setting (e.g. interactions that are taking place, formal, informal, planned, unplanned, verbal, non-verbal etc.);
- The programme setting (e.g. resources and their organisation, pedagogic styles, curricula and their organisation).

(Morrison, 1993, p.80 cited in Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 543)

According to Robson and McCartan (2016), approaches to observation can be classified into two dimensions: structure and formality dimension; and the role of the observer dimension. In its turn, the former can be divided into formal and informal observation. In the informal approach, the

researcher is free to a great extent in deciding what information to collect and examine, and how to record it. And because the type of information in this approach is unstructured and hence difficult to collect, the observer is expected to perform multiple tasks to synthesise, abstract, organise and describe the data. In the formal approach, the observation process is highly structured, there is a considerable emphasis on sticking to the pre-structured aspects to be observed. As such, the researcher has to pay attention only to these pre-set categories, and has to regard anything else as irrelevant.

The second dimension concerns what role the researcher takes in the situation he/she is observing. Particularly, this involves the degree of the researcher's participation in that situation. Robson and McCartan's focus was on two extreme positions. In the first one, the researcher tends to completely participate in the studied situation and become a member of the group. This role is referred to as the participant observer. Whereas in the second position, the researcher tends to be detached from the group, and hence be a pure observer.

In addition to Robson and McCartan's dimension of the observer role, Cooper and Schindler (2001), on their part, add two more dimensions: direct or indirect observation; and overt or covert observation. In the direct observation, the researcher is required to be present in the observation process. Thus, the observer in this case is the research tool. In the indirect observation, the researcher uses other instruments to record the situation, for instance, cameras. Overt observation implies that the researcher makes his/her role clear and known from the beginning, and informs the individuals under study that they are being observed. In covert observation, the subjects do not know that they are being observed, and the researcher doesn't reveal and make him/herself known to be an observer.

4.5.2.1. Types of observation

Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) identify three main types of observation lying on a continuum from highly structured to unstructured. A highly structured observation involves categories of what is exactly to be observed. These are organised in an observational schedule. This type generally yields numerical data which, in turn, facilitate the calculation of frequencies, incidences, and patterns, and help the researcher to compare between different situations.

A semi-structured observation involves the use of a less structured agenda of issues, the observer then is expected to collect data to enlighten these issues in a less systematic and structured way. An unstructured observation is quite vague when it comes to what exactly the researcher is looking for. The researcher is to enter a situation and record all the events and behaviours which are taking place

to decide later what aspects are important to the purpose of the study. Generally, structured observation is hypothesis-testing, in the sense that it has a hypothesis worked out in advance, and the data gathered from the observation is meant to confirm or reject this hypothesis. On the contrary, semi-structured or unstructured observation is hypothesis-generating, where the observer provides a clarification for the situation under study after reviewing the observational data.

Similarly, Robson and McCartan (2016) emphasise two extreme types of observation: participant observation which is linked to the flexible qualitative approaches to research; and structured observation which is mainly based on the quantification of behaviours, patterns, trends, etc. Therefore, it follows a quantitative approach of data collection using coding and category systems, and checklists as recording forms.

Through the use of participant observation, the researcher becomes a member of the community, in that he/she dives into their social life, learning about their ways of verbal and non-verbal communication, their interactions with each other, and their habits and social conventions. Being involved in the group, the researcher is the instrument of interpreting the subjects' experiences and subjective meanings in a situation which might give rise to the issue of subjectivity, and hence the researcher is required to possess some personal skills and considerable sensitivity to avoid any potential bias. Furthermore, with participant observation, analysis occurs at the same time of data collection, unlike most of the other research methods where data analysis comes after data collection (Robson and McCartan, 2016). According to Dewalt and Dewalt (2002), participant observation can be strengthened in terms of validity by the use of other complementary research methods, as is the case in this study.

For this study, unstructured classroom observation was chosen to look at any evidence of the incorporation and development of critical thinking by university teachers, this included: lesson plans, teacher's practices and activities, types of questions, and teacher-student interaction; and to check whether the participant teachers do translate into practice the aspirations of the Ministry of Higher Education guidelines regarding the development of critical thinking among students - this is in case the document analysis reveals that critical thinking is indeed considered as an educational objective, and there are elements which encourage the teaching of critical thinking. For this research, and due to time constraints and the challenges posed by the COVID-19 period, I could only conduct ten one-time observations for each participant teacher. To facilitate this, prior arrangements were made with teachers to position myself at the back of the classroom during each session. In maintaining a non-participatory role, ensuring ethical considerations, and avoiding any disruption to students, I took

the stance of an observer as participant. This role entails that I should be known and overt to the participants as an observer, but without taking any part in the activities of the group. Yet, Robson and McCartan (2016) question the idea of considering the researcher as passive and taking no part in the group activities, while being known as the researcher, they argue that 'their role is now one of the roles within the larger group that includes the researcher' (p.327).

As such, I declared at the very beginning that I would not participate in the classroom activities. I was introduced as a postgraduate student researcher to establish transparency and maintain the trustworthiness of the research. As for the recording approach, I used field notes solely (see Appendix F for an example of the field notes) as recording with other tools such as taping, mobile phones, or video cameras could increase the reactivity effect (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Furthermore, if one might question the data, two extra methods will be used in addition to observation: document analysis and semi-structured interviews, and this will strengthen the validity. Throughout the observation phase, I recognised the challenge noted by Merriam (1998) that 'where to focus or stop action cannot be determined ahead of time' (p. 97). To ensure a comprehensive record, my approach was to document all unfolding events from the teacher's entrance to the end of the session. This inclusive strategy, unconstrained by specific events, aimed to prevent the oversight of any unexpected but significant events. Consequently, I recorded various aspects, including general circumstances, the physical environment, activities, student-teacher interactions, etc. I maximised every available opportunity to collect extensive data that could significantly contribute to addressing the research questions.

Similar to interviews, following each observation session, and during my commute home by bus or car, I engaged in reflection. This practice involved writing down any additional notes that time constraints prevented me from elaborating on during the session.

4.5.3. Document analysis

Document analysis is a form of qualitative inquiry which is concerned with the examination and interpretation of documents to elicit meanings and gain understanding and knowledge about the phenomenon under investigation (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). Bowen (2009, p.27) defines document analysis as 'a systematic procedure for reviewing or evaluating documents -both printed and electronic (computer-based and Internet-transmitted) material'. Documents generally include texts (words), but they can also be extended to include videos and images. According to Creswell (2003), documents can take different forms, for instance, agendas, journals and Diaries, newspapers, institutional reports, minutes of meetings, letters, and books; and non-written documents such as

pictures, films, maps, etc. Sometimes the context of the study determines what type of documents should be examined, studies on educational institutions or schools, in particular, include: 'written curricula; course outlines, and other course documents; timetables; notices; letters; and other communications to parents' (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p. 352).

It is unusual, but still possible, for document analysis to be the only research tool in a particular study, as it is often combined with other additional methods as a means of triangulation. Through the use of multiple sources of evidence alongside document analysis, the researcher can corroborate all the findings from the data gathered and thus increase the credibility of the research (Bowen, 2009). Hence, obtaining data from a single tool may increase the potential for bias. With regard to this, documents may be analysed and interpreted according to the researcher's own reflections which, as a result, gives rise to a potential researcher's bias and subjectivity. This is why, it is not advisable to rely on document analysis as a stand-alone method, but rather as a complement to other methods (Bowen, 2009).

Document analysis can fit in mixed methods studies, in which it can be combined with both qualitative and quantitative tools, as it can fit in qualitative inquiries, in particular case studies. Bowen (2009) notes that 'as a research method, document analysis is particularly applicable to qualitative case studies- intensive studies producing rich descriptions of a single phenomenon, event, organisation, or programme' (p.29).

4.5.3.1. Uses of document analysis

There are a range of purposes for using document analysis (Bowen, 2009). First, document analysis can provide information about the context of the study. Such information can clarify the background and historical roots which may have affected the phenomenon being studied. Second, document analysis can help to generate questions to inquire about when designing interviews, and can suggest some aspects to pay attention to in participant observation. Third, document analysis can provide rich knowledge and insights about the phenomenon under investigation, and hence can work as a supplementary source of data to other methods, such as interviews and observation. In addition to that, when studying a document which has been through several amendments over time, document analysis can serve as a tracking tool for the development and changes of that document. Last, document analysis can be used as a means to verify the findings from other methods. If the evidence gathered from the document analysis contradicts the other tools' findings, the researcher has to inquire further into the issue. However, if the findings are converged across multiple sources of data, the trustworthiness of the study will increase.

4.5.3.2. The analysis of documents

O'Leary (2014) suggests two major techniques to analyse documents. In the first one, the researcher treats the document as an interviewee or a supplier of Information, in which he/she asks questions and then highlights the answers within a passage. In the second one, the researcher quantifies the frequency of occurrences of particular concepts or elements - this is content analysis. Bowen (2009) points out that some qualitative experts object to content analysis as they believe that it obscures the interpretive processes. However, Bowen (2009, p.32) - even though he thinks that quantitative content analysis is helpful, in some cases, in giving an overall picture of a particular phenomenon - excludes the use of content analysis as a quantification tool of the frequency of terms for example, but rather he recommends its use as a 'first-pass document review' to identify the relevant information and data to the study. In addition to content analysis, documents can be analysed using a thematic analysis. The latter entails the identification of patterns within a passage. After carefully reviewing and evaluating the document, themes which are meaningful and pertinent to the purpose of the study emerge as a result of the coding and categorising processes. Bowen (2009) highlights the possibility of using pre-set codes across supplementary tools, meaning that codes generated to be used in interview transcripts can be used in the document analysis.

As for the purpose of my study, document analysis was employed to provide clear background information about the extent to which critical thinking is integrated into the university educational guidelines, if at all; it could also help me to modify or generate new questions in the semi-structured interview schedule, or draw my attention to some aspects which needed to be observed in the participant observation. To obtain the curriculum document, I approached the head of the department. While seeking permission to commence data collection, I also requested the curriculum documents. The head of the department graciously agreed and informed me that he would send them to my email. Consequently, I received the three curriculum documents which are: Licence curriculum, Master's curriculum for Teaching English as a Foreign Language major (Didactics), and Master's Curriculum for Literature and Civilisation major. The three curriculum documents were originally written in English, which eliminated the need for translation. This was advantageous as it ensured that no meaning was lost or altered through the translation process, allowing for a more accurate and reliable analysis. Working directly with the original English texts allowed for a precise examination of the language and content, which was crucial for identifying any explicit or implicit references to critical thinking. The curriculum documents were, therefore, analysed and interpreted to investigate whether or not they present critical thinking as an educational objective. In other

words, it sought to explore the extent to which Algerian higher education encourages the development and promotion of critical thinking among students. To avoid any potential bias, and to increase the research's credibility and trustworthiness, document analysis was not used as the primary and only research tool: it was, however, a complement to the other additional tools, which are semi-structured interviews and observation.

4.6. Data analysis

After the collection of 'raw data' from the three different research instruments in the current study - interviews, observations, and document analysis - the next step is to understand, analyse, and make sense of these data to present them in the form of meaningful findings (Bloomberg and Volpe, 2012, p.134). Since all the data gathered from this study are qualitative in nature, qualitative data analysis is, therefore, required to move from the raw data or information to understand, explain, and interpret the phenomenon under investigation (Taylor and Gibbs, 2010). Qualitative data analysis is an ongoing, non-linear, reflexive process between data collection, analysis, and interpretation in which the researcher can move backwards and forwards and make the necessary refinement, assembly, and combination of the segments, units, or categories to create meanings and then draw conclusions. Thus, it involves:

Organizing, describing, understanding, accounting for, and explaining data, making sense of the data in terms of the participants' definitions of the situation (of which the researcher is one), noting patterns, themes, categories and regulations, all of which are the task of the qualitative.

(Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 643)

That said, it could be deduced that data analysis plays an essential role in the process of conducting any research. According to Robson and McCartan (2016), there are three main different approaches or methods to qualitative data analysis which one chooses among based on the 'fitness for purpose' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.725). In other words, there is no right or wrong way to do qualitative analysis, it all depends on the purpose of the study. These approaches are: quasi-statistical approaches, thematic coding approach, and the grounded theory approach.

Of the three approaches to qualitative analysis, thematic analysis or more specifically, reflexive thematic analysis was chosen to analyse the descriptive data set gathered from the three research tools employed in this study. 'Reflexive thematic analysis' - the newly preferred term by Braun and Clarke (2019) - was developed to accommodate various frameworks, and to answer quite more varied research question types. For example: it can be suitable for questions in relation to understanding and representation of a particular phenomenon; it can be suitable for questions in

relation to people's perceptions, opinions, and experiences; as it can suit questions related to the construction of meaning. In addition to its flexibility, accessibility, and applicability with all qualitative data and in a wide variety of disciplines and fields, reflexive thematic analysis was also opted for in the current study as it can be approached using different ways: inductive/ deductive, semantic/ latent, and realist/ constructionist (Braun and Clarke, 2019).

An inductive approach entails that themes are generated from the data itself; a deductive approach, on the other hand, entails that themes are developed from existing concepts or theories. In a semantic approach, themes are identified within the explicit meanings of the data where the researcher does not go beyond what the participants have explicitly articulated; in a latent approach, themes are developed to report the underpinning assumptions and conceptualisations which lie behind the semantic content of the data. A realist approach describes 'experiences, meanings, and the reality of participants'; whereas a constructionist investigates, 'the ways in which events, realities, meanings and experiences are the effects of a range of discourses operating within society' (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p. 467).

Further, unlike the grounded theory approach which aims at generating a full, useful theory grounded in the data, in thematic analysis 'researchers need not subscribe to the implicit theoretical commitments of grounded theory if they do not wish to produce a fully worked-up grounded-theory analysis' (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.8). Yet, it is worth noting the distinction between full grounded theory, and 'lite' grounded theory. Full grounded theory implements specific grounded theory procedures and seeks at developing a full theory from the data. Whereas the 'Lite' version of the grounded theory involves the implementation of particular procedures of coding and generation of broader patterns - in this case categories instead of themes - very much similar to the thematic analysis without having to commit to a theory development (Braun and Clark, 2006).

It is important to highlight that the document analysis employed a combination of inductive and deductive approaches. The inductive aspect involved initial open coding. Subsequently, the deductive component utilised Bloom's taxonomy and its revision as a guiding framework for analysing the curriculum documents. This choice was made due to the fundamental role that Bloom's taxonomy plays in shaping the structure of formal educational curriculum documents.

Bloom's original taxonomy of educational objectives was first introduced in 1956 by a group of university educators under the leadership of Professor Benjamin Bloom, to provide an educational framework, structure learning objectives, design activities and assessments, and provide a language

for teachers to use to discuss their curriculum developments, and to describe the outcomes and objectives that they expect from their students. Each level in the taxonomy builds upon the level below it, knowledge lies at the basis of the taxonomy, above it comes comprehension and application, and then analysis, synthesis, and at the top of the pyramid, evaluation – in the higher stages of learning, critical thinking becomes actively involved (Zohar and Dori 2003). The taxonomy has witnessed subsequent improvements, the most well-known and widely recognised revision was introduced in 2001 by David Krathwohl, Bloom's colleague who was involved in 1956's original taxonomy, and Lorin Anderson who was Bloom's student. The new formulation of Bloom's taxonomy was renamed A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing, and the terminology of the cognitive processes changed from nouns to action verbs. As such: comprehension, application, and analysis were changed to understand, apply, and analyse, respectively, and synthesis to create. In the revised taxonomy, categories of the cognitive process may overlap as a hierarchy along a continuum. For instance 'the subcategories that define the limits of the understand category are allowed to overlap apply' (Anderson and Krathwohl, 2001, p. 120). Unlike the original taxonomy where moving to a more complex ability requires the mastery of a less complex one in a commutative hierarchy.

Critical thinking skills are an integral part of Bloom's revised taxonomy. The latter is not in itself a definition of critical thinking, however, given the fact that it is a taxonomy, this means that it provides a ranking to classify cognitive abilities from lower to higher. Thus, it has been commonly considered that higher cognitive activities encompassing: analysis, synthesis, and evaluation are clear expressions of critical (that is, higher-order) thinking skills (Duron et al. 2006). When comparing these higher cognitive actions to the definitions and the commercial tests of critical thinking, an apparent congruence can be noted. For that reason, critical thinking has often been associated with Bloom's taxonomy. Additionally, since the emphasis of the document analysis is on the educational objectives, Bloom's revised taxonomy seemed a useful framework to guide the analysis of the curriculum documents. More precisely, it helped me to explore how each educational objective corresponds to which taxonomy level, and as a result explore the incidences of critical thinking, and the extent to which these documents encourage the teaching of critical thinking. According to Bowen (2009, p.32), the process of document analysis involves three main stages 'skimming (superficial examination), reading (thorough examination) and interpretation'. As previously discussed, thematic analysis was used to understand the documents and provide a picture of the state of critical thinking in these documents with regard to Bloom's revised taxonomy.

Reflexive thematic analysis is, therefore, a generic approach to analysing large amounts of qualitative data by identifying key features and patterned meanings, organizing them using codes and themes, and then describing and analytically reporting them in rich detail. Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest six phases of doing thematic analysis; these phases do not need to be followed rigidly, as the process of thematic analysis is not linear, but rather a reflexive, recursive process allowing the researcher to move back and forth as required. The six guidelines for carrying out a thematic analysis which were followed in this research are discussed below.

Phase 1: data familiarisation

As a first step, I immersed myself in the data and became familiar with it. By Immersion, I mean that I carefully read the entire data looking for patterned meanings before the coding phase. It is at this phase that any verbal data will need to be transcribed into written texts to allow the practice of thematic analysis. Although the transcription process may seem expensive in time and not enjoyable, it provided me with a great opportunity to familiarise myself with and understand more thoroughly the data. Consequently, the three points I have considered in this phase are: familiarising with the data through active reading; transcribing the verbal data into written form using interpretive skills; taking notes of any initial thoughts and ideas.

In the case of interviews, reading the data during the transcription process allowed me to begin identifying patterns and connections across the transcripts. As for the observational data, I reviewed the handwritten field notes multiple times, maintaining a broad perspective without delving into details. The same approach was applied to the curriculum documents. Before transitioning to the formal analysis phase, wherein the documents allowed for direct analysis, I read them repeatedly to establish a solid familiarity with the data. This process facilitated the generation of tentative codes as I engaged with the three datasets. It is important to highlight that throughout the data collection process, I employed a diverse set of skills, including listening, reflection, interpretation, note-taking, concentration, and analysis. My engagement with the data extended beyond the transcription stage, it persisted during and after the entire data collection phase as I continuously familiarised myself with the events in the field. Therefore, in this study, data analysis was not confined solely to the formal analysis stage but was an integral part of the entire data collection process.

Phase 2-3: generation of initial codes and search for themes

These two stages were intertwined as they occurred concurrently in my analysis process. Generating initial codes and searching for themes took place after having thoroughly familiarised with data, and established an initial list of ideas which are thought to be important and interesting. These two phases, therefore, begin the systematic production of initial codes where a code refers to: 'the most basic segment, or element, of the raw data or information that can be assessed in a meaningful way regarding the phenomenon' (Boyatzis, 1998, p.63). Unlike the theory-driven approach guided by specific questions, which shapes code production, I adopted an open-minded stance. The themes developed in the subsequent stage were data-driven, informed directly by the data itself (refer to Appendix H for an illustrative example of the process of identifying themes).

I initially used the Nvivo software package for data analysis, but I later found that using papers, typed documents, sticky notes, and highlighters worked better for me. It is advised at this stage to code as many potential themes and patterns as possible - sometimes what does not seem important might turn out to be interesting and relevant when proceeding with the analysis -, and to avoid neglecting inconsistencies as all data have contradictions. As such, I examined the data looking for expected and unexpected events, in addition to any inconsistencies. After extensively reviewing the substantial volumes of gathered data that appeared pertinent to the aims of the study, I initiated the coding process. During this process, I carefully examined each interview, field note, or document separately. Adjacent to each text, I provided descriptions and interpretations of the data, drawing connections with other sets, particularly the interviews and observational data related to the teachers' classroom practices.

This phase proved to be the most extensive and time-consuming in the entire thematic analysis process. The creation of codes held a central position in the data analysis. Once patterns were organised into categories, my aim was to interpret the meaning conveyed by these categories. I also aimed to establish connections between different codes, grouping them into distinct themes. In some instances, certain coded items had to be reassigned to different themes as the analysis became more detailed compared to the initial stages. At this stage, I started to make sense of the relationships between codes, sub-themes, and broader themes, therefore, I organised codes into broader themes, bringing together relevant coded data under potential overarching themes. Some codes were merged to form comprehensive themes, while others were identified and evolved into subthemes.

Phase 4-5: reviewing, defining and naming themes

By this phase, I had a collection of candidate themes which needed next to be reviewed. This phase is, therefore, concerned with the refinement of the developed themes where some may hold as they are as overarching themes, others may be combined together, and others may be divided into separate themes. There are two levels which characterise this phase. In the first level, I reviewed the coded data extracts. This involved re-reading all the combined extracts under each theme, and checking whether or not they form a coherent pattern. When the themes did not seem to fit, I tended to consider the themes themselves, for example, by creating new ones, locating the extracts which seemed not working under a particular theme to another, or discarding them. In level two, I considered the validity of the candidate themes in relation to the entire data set. The representation of the set of themes and sub-themes in a table was quite helpful in this. As such, I re-read the whole data set - as mentioned before - to ensure that the themes work well in relation to the data and to code any missing interesting meanings.

After I had reviewed the list of themes and sub-themes, I moved to give comprehensible, concise, and straight to the point names. This entailed also identifying the essence of each theme and the aspect of the data which each theme represents. As such, I wrote down a detailed analysis of the story behind each single theme which I later used in the final phase, namely the production of the report.

Phase 6: production of the report

Having analysed the data, and labelled the themes directly from the participants' own statements or my interpretation based on my literature review. I presented the analysed data and backed them with examples of participants' quotes as a means to mitigate potential subjectivity in the data analysis process (Creswell, 2013). This presentation aimed to enable readers to make informed judgments regarding the credibility of this study.

4.7. Research participants

The appropriate selection of the methodology, instruments, and sampling strategy determines the quality of research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Sampling is, therefore, considered an inevitable aspect of any research topic and in different fields. It allows us to obtain information and then establish judgements about people, settings, institutions, and other things based on evidence collected from a small group or a subset of the total population, where gathering data from an entire

population is not often possible due to some constraints such as accessibility, expense, and time (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Robson and McCartan, 2016). Sampling, then, is a strategy used by researchers to systematically select a portion or a small representative group from the whole of a population to be the subject and the source of knowledge for the study. Robson and McCartan (2016) and Walliman (2011) point out that the term 'population' does not necessarily refer to the number of people only, but it can be extended to include non people-related units such as situations, events, places, or generally the quantity of things which are selected to be the subject of the study. Broadly, there are two major techniques of sampling: probability sampling, and non-probability sampling.

In probability sampling, also known as random sampling, all participants of the wider population have equal nonzero chances of being selected. It is described more clearly as a procedure where the probability of selecting each individual in the population is known, that is inclusion or exclusion from the sample is merely a matter of chance. Due to the randomised selection of the sample in probability sampling, it is possible to make statistical inferences and generalise to the wider population (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Robson and McCartan, 2016).

In non-probability sampling, it is not possible to specify the probability of including each unit in the sample. Non-probability sampling is commonly used in ethnographic studies, case studies, and in any small scale studies where there is no great concern to make statistical generalisation from the sample under study to the entire population (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Hence, non-probability sampling is a sampling technique where the chances of selecting each individual or unit of the wider population are unknown. The researcher does not randomly select the sample, however, he/ she purposely decides who to include and who to exclude in the sample based on particular criteria appertaining to the purpose of the study.

Probability sampling is most frequently used in quantitative enquiries as it seeks representativeness, and therefore generalisability of the findings. However, non-probability sampling is often employed in qualitative inquiries where the focus is placed on a particular phenomenon or group of people. Hence, the sample represents itself and not the wider population.

In the process of recruiting participants for this study, I opted for the two most commonly used types of non-probability sampling: purposive and convenience sampling.

In purposive sampling or judgement sampling, the researcher deliberately picks the participants based on his/ her judgement of their possession of the certain qualities being sought in the study. Simply put, the researcher decides what he/ she wants to investigate and then selects units for the sample that are most likely to be a rich source of information for the purpose of the study, and are also willing to take part in the study. Convenience sampling, on the other hand, or as it is sometimes called opportunity sampling involves the selection of individuals or units because of their willingness to participate, their convenience, and easy accessibility. It is mainly the process of selecting people who are geographically near and accessible when conducting the study, and continuing that process until reaching the required sample size (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

This study, in line with a qualitative research design, made use of purposive and convenience sampling for the semi-structured interviews and classroom observation, where data was gathered from ten EFL university teachers. This study took place in the faculty of letters and languages, specifically, in the Department of English Language. At this university, I graduated with both bachelor's and master's degrees, this is a total of five years of studies there. Hence, conducting this research at a university where I once was a student makes accessibility more convenient.

Purposive and convenience sampling allowed me to choose my participants based on the following pre-established criteria. The selected sample is all EFL university teachers who are willing to take part in this study as the research's focus is examining EFL university teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking, their perspectives of the development of critical thinking in their students, and their translation of the educational guidelines into practice. It aimed mainly to present the teachers' conceptualisations and pedagogical practices in relation to critical thinking, if there are any. In addition to that, purposive sampling allowed me to choose teachers teaching students majoring in English from different levels including bachelor's and master's years to explore if the teachers are considering the incorporation of critical thinking in their teaching at any particular stage in university. Purposive sampling also allowed me to exclude teachers who are in charge of subjects which might not highly require the use of higher-order thinking skills such as grammar or phonetics, as these do not seem to provide a rich insight into the phenomenon being investigated.

In terms of classroom observation, I employed opportunity or convenience sampling. I seized the opportunity and asked the purposely selected sample for semi-structured interviews, requesting permission to conduct a classroom observation. They agreed to participate in the classroom observation also and granted me access to their sessions. Consequently, I conducted ten classroom

observations to delve into the teaching approaches, dynamics of teacher-student interactions, employed teaching approaches and practices, and types of questioning. The observations aimed to assess the extent to which educational objectives were adhered to, particularly in fostering critical thinking skills. Additionally, the observations served to cross-check the teachers' accounts from the interviews regarding their classroom practices.

4.8. Ensuring rigour- research trustworthiness

Ensuring rigour in research is one of the major concerns that the researcher encounters, and without it 'research is worthless, becomes fiction, and loses its unity' (Morse et al. 2002, p.14). Nonetheless, and given the different philosophical assumptions about the nature of knowledge, quantitative and qualitative research use different terminologies to describe the techniques and procedures of ensuring the quality and rigour of research. Some researchers (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Morse, 1999) appropriate the use of validity and reliability for both fixed and flexible inquiries. However, many qualitative researchers avoid the use of such terms, and Lincoln and Guba (1985) suggest the term trustworthiness instead which includes four criteria: credibility, confirmability, dependability, and transferability. These four criteria were employed to evaluate the quality and worth of this study.

4.8.1. Credibility: the term 'credibility' is used in qualitative research as a substitution for internal validity. It refers to the extent to which the research findings truly reflect the context of the study and the participants' experiences and answers (Whittemore, Chase, and Mandle, 2001). Credibility, therefore, is the confidence in the truth of the study results when it is linked to reality. Credibility is viewed as the most important criterion in establishing the trustworthiness of this study (Pilot and Beck, 2014), consequently, quite a variety of techniques are available to reinforce it compared to the other three criteria. These techniques can be triangulation (Creswell, 2013; Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña, 2014), member-checking (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), verbatim transcriptions (Guest, MacQueen, and Namey, 2012), peer-debriefing (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), thick description of the whole research process (Silverman, 2006), and establishment of good rapport with the research participants (Arksey and Knight, 1999). Some of these strategies were addressed in this study to ensure credibility.

To begin with, I made use of triangulation which helps to improve the research validity and reliability (Creswell, 2014; Morse, 2015). Triangulation is a valuable technique which involves the use of multiple data collection methods (data triangulation), the use of more than one observer (observer

triangulation), the combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches (methodological triangulation), or the use of multiple theoretical perspectives (theory triangulation) (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

In order to enhance the research rigour, to obtain an in-depth comprehensive and well-developed finding, and to shape a holistic picture of the phenomenon under scrutiny, data triangulation - as was discussed previously - was used in this study through the use of three research instruments: document analysis, semi-structured interviews, and classroom observations.

Each method was described in detail, explaining the aim and reason behind the selection of these methods which are believed to capture various interesting accounts about the state of critical thinking in an Algerian university setting at a theoretical and a practical level. For instance, while I obtained basic data from the document communicated by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research which set the background for this study, interviews provided fundamental information about the teachers' perspectives and lived experiences, then classroom observations helped in witnessing the teachers in their natural settings and in checking certain aspects that were raised during the interviews. As such, examining the dimensions of the phenomenon through the use of different sources compensated for the limitations of the methods and exploited their benefits.

Second, purposive sampling along with convenience sampling helped me to easily access participants who were anticipated to provide rich information which could also apply to similar contexts.

Third, another important strategy that I implemented to boost the research credibility is member checking' (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Silverman, 2013). I provided the participants with transcripts of the interviews in which they took part to consider whether what they said and was recorded matched their intentions, to correct errors if there were any, or to add information if necessary. Further, according to Rallis and Rossman (2009) peer review or the consultation of a 'critical friend' (p. 269) can help to ensure the credibility of a research. Therefore, feedback from and reflections of my supervisor, my fellow PhD researchers, and other academics were welcomed and taken into consideration throughout the various stages of my research. Moreover, I used peer- debriefing where I asked one EFL university teacher with whom I had a good relationship to review the relevance and coherence of the themes in conjunction with their extracts(Guest, MacQueen, and Namey, 2012).

Finally, establishing a good rapport with participants (Arksey and Knight, 1999), and familiarising them with the research aims, procedures, and data collection tools is also one way to assure the research credibility. I, therefore, provided the participants with a description of the entire research process, and gave each single participant in the study the opportunity to discontinue their participation in the study at any point in the process.

4.8.2. Transferability: used to replace 'external validity' in quantitative research. It refers to the extent to which the research findings apply to other contexts and other participants (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Brown, 2014). There has been an ongoing debate about the possibility of transferring the findings of qualitative research to a wider population, as the aim is usually to provide rich context-bound information about a limited number of individuals, or a specific phenomenon within a particular environment. Erlandson, Harris, Skipper, and Allen (1993) note that many interpretivist researchers believe that it is quite difficult for generalisability to take place as all observations happen within a specific context. However, many other researchers hold an opposing view, suggesting that transferability should not be wholly excluded as, even though each case is unique, it is still an example within a wider group and can inform of potential similar situations (Denscombe, 1998; Ritchie, Lewis, Nicholls and Ormston, 2003). In order to achieve transferability in this research, I have provided a comprehensive detailed and thick description of the whole research process, starting from the research context, sample, data collection tools, data analysis procedures and interpretation, up to the writing of the final report. This will help other Algerian researchers and readers to compare and contrast the circumstances which defined the current research context against their own contexts.

4.8.3. Confirmability: the concept of confirmability deals with the researcher's concern about objectivity (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2011). According to Brown (2014), confirmability in qualitative research refers to 'the verifiability of data upon which all interpretations in the study are based' (p.122). That is to say, Confirmability is the process of verifying that the research findings reflect the participants' views and experiences, rather than the researcher's own predispositions - consequently the researcher's bias (Anney, 2015).

Therefore, to achieve confirmability in this research, I made sure that the generated data truly represented the participants' worldviews, and not my own views and preconceptions. Another way to address this concern according to Miles and Huberman (1994), is the extent to which the researcher admits his/her own predispositions. Hence, I explained in detail the methods adopted,

and the justification of the decisions made to choose these. Moreover, the strengths as well as the weaknesses of each method were acknowledged. Furthermore, Lincoln, Lynham, and Guba (2011) emphasise the role of triangulation in ensuring the research confirmability. Using data triangulation in the current study helped to reduce the researcher's bias.

This study made use of external audit (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), which involves seeking external validation and feedback from individuals who were not directly involved in the study regarding the research process, findings, and interpretations. I obtained this validation through participation in research conferences and events like the UWS Research Festival. These external forums offered opportunities to present research, engage with peers, and receive feedback, contributing to the overall trustworthiness of the research.

4.8.3. Dependability: - used in qualitative research to replace reliability, dependability refers to the extent to which the research findings are stable and consistent over time (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In other words, it is concerned with the potentiality of achieving similar findings if the research is to be repeated with similar participants and in similar contexts (Anney, 2014). Lincoln, Lynham and Guba (2011) argue that dependability is closely tied with credibility, and that ensuring the former can help in illustrating the latter. Hence, dependability can also be achieved through the use of multiple data collection methods. Dependability can also be reinforced by providing a thorough description of the different data collection processes to enable potential future researchers to replicate the study. Yet, qualitative inquiry is not meant for replication, as it aims to present in-depth rich data generated by participants within their specific contexts at particular points in time. In this regard, Shenton (2004) claims 'the processes within the study should be reported in detail, thereby enabling a future researcher to repeat the work, if not necessarily to gain the same results' (p. 71). Therefore, in this study I addressed dependability through a detailed thick description and explanation of: *a.* the research design and the implementation of the adopted methods; *b.* all the phases of the research processes from data collection to analysis and interpretation; *c.* the operational details about what was planned to do and what was actually completed in the fieldwork. This is mainly to demonstrate transparency and aid those who might wish to replicate this research in their respective contexts.

4.9. Positionality and reflexivity

Conducting this qualitative research, I was 'a central figure who influences the collection, selection, and interpretation of data' (Finlay, 2002, p. 531); therefore, my influence as an insider ,being a

former student, and a current researcher on the whole research process could not be ignored pretending it had not been there, but rather it had been accepted and dealt with. This recognition underscores the significance of reflexivity. And here lies the significance of reflexivity. According to England (1994), reflexivity is described as a 'self-critical sympathetic introspection and self-conscious analytical scrutiny of the self as a researcher' (p.82). On his account, Mann (2016) suggests that 'reflexivity involves examining yourself as a researcher and also your research relationships' (p.27).

In other words, reflexivity refers to the researcher's rigorous self-evaluation of his/her own beliefs, perceptions and practices throughout the whole research process, and consciousness of how these may influence the research decisions and procedures. Reflexivity involves directing the researcher's investigation lens towards him/herself, and positioning his/her role as part of the research process. This constant internal dialogue between the researcher and his/her relationships with the researched, the setting, and the research outcomes is expected to increase the research's trustworthiness and hence the research rigour (Finlay, 2002; Angen, 2000).

In this study, I was reflexive on my involvement at every step of the research process such as the context under investigation, the chosen participants, the procedures of data collection and analysis, and the writing-up process (Gray, 2008). As such, I examined my feelings, beliefs, and perceptions, and disclosed my philosophical assumptions which determined and justified the selection of the research methodology and the research design of this study.

In this study, my role as a researcher, an interviewer, and an observer was explicitly revealed to the participants with whom I shared many aspects. I acknowledge that I was part of the research context, I was a student there for five years and I graduated with both bachelor's and master's degrees. Having prior relationships with some of the participants helped to gain relatively convenient access, especially to carry out classroom observations, yet it could have had an influence on the data gathered from interviews (Garton and Coplan, 2010). Consequently, I was constantly reflexive on this by examining my thoughts and feelings.

As far as power relations are concerned, the interviewer is usually in a position of power. However, as some of the participants were my former teachers, and despite the fact that my status changed from being a former student to a researcher and future colleague, I was a bit cautious, paying great respect to them. Such a relationship could have restricted my perception of the data collected, leading to a predetermined interpretation. However, practising reflexivity and being aware of my own stance helped to maintain good and less biased research conduct.

I was also aware that the major aim of the current study is not particularly to criticise the educational system, or to criticise the decision makers and teachers, but rather the ultimate goal is to surface the position of critical thinking in Algerian university as it is conveyed by documents, pedagogical practices, and teachers' beliefs and experiences. Thus, the interviews aimed to gain knowledge, and not to underestimate or cause any kind of discomfort.

Undoubtedly, the benefits of conducting this study in a context which is familiar to me outweighed the potential drawbacks.

4.10. Ethical Considerations

Carrying out a research project requires the researcher to constantly think about the ethical aspects surrounding the issue being investigated. Paying careful attention to ethics is not an endpoint, but rather a continuous process throughout the stages of research. Ethics refer to a set of rules, principles, or a code of conduct by which the researcher should abide in order to meet the obligations of good research conduct (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

This research adheres to the University of The West of Scotland code of ethical practice and, thus, follows the British Educational Research Association (BERA) code of conduct. The BERA ethical guidelines are set up to endorse researchers in social sciences, especially in the field of education. Educational researchers, therefore, are expected to comply with these underlying principles and values to ensure professional and ethical research conduct (BERA, 2018).

Before starting the data collection phase, a research ethics application form had been submitted and approved by the School of Education & Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland. The latter's role is to consider general ethical issues in the application. After obtaining the ethical approval, I have provided the participants with:

- A participant information sheet which contains: an outlining of the entire study and its aims, what participation involves, who are the participants, when and where data collection will take place, the participants' rights to withdraw, how anonymity and confidentiality will be maintained, and contact details.
- An informed consent form (which will be discussed later) to be signed in the event they agree to take part in this study.

I made sure that no participant was coerced to participate whatsoever: as such all participants were informed that they have the total freedom to withdraw at any time of the process for a reason or no reason.

As part of anonymity and confidentiality which are considered to be among the most important issues in ethical considerations to protect the recruited participants (Wiles, Crow, Heath, and Charles, 2008), I have informed the participants that their identities will be kept anonymous. I used pseudonyms to replace their full names. Additionally, I have promised and assured the participants that their data will be handled with total confidentiality, and disposed of, following the completion of the doctoral process. I have also sought the teachers' permission and consent to tape-record the interviews.

As a researcher, I was expected to be thoughtful of any harm the research may cause to the participants, and it was my responsibility to avoid any kind of it, be it physical or psychological, though it is believed that physical harm is not likely to occur in educational research (Neuman, 2012), and that psychological harm such as stress or anxiety are likely to exacerbate only when the topic is socially sensitive, or when the researcher deals with vulnerable groups (Robson and McCartan, 2016), which is not the case for the current study. It was also vital to treat all participants with respect and equity and to refrain from prejudice, stereotypes and any other social or cultural discrimination. In this research, students could be involved indirectly when conducting classroom observations. Thus, an informed consent by the class teacher only – that is the main focus – might not be sufficient, and a consideration of providing information and an explanation of the research, and obtaining an informed consent by students might be necessary as well (BERA, 2018). As such, I briefly explained the research project to the students in the observed classes and invited them to sign an informed consent.

Informed consent

For research to be ethical, participants have to be given the freedom and self-determination about deciding whether to take part in the research or not, and to make that decision, the researcher must provide adequate and pertinent information about the study and what it entails in order to help the participants to understand and consider what they are getting involved in. That participants' permission is what is called 'informed consent' (Walliman, 2005, p. 346). Diener and Crandall (1978) define the term consent as 'the procedures in which individuals choose whether to participate in an investigation after being informed of facts that would be likely to influence their decisions' (p. 57

quoted in Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018, p. 122). As such, the participants have the opportunity to consider whether to accept or refuse. As part of the participants' freedom, informed consent can also be informed refusal, and participants should receive no penalties for their decisions to withdraw (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). As much as providing fair and salient information about the study to the participants before actually interacting with them is necessary, it is also problematic in deciding how much information to give. Ruane (2005) argues that disclosing too much information about the research purpose may affect the participants' answers and behaviours, and bias the results; on the other hand, providing partially insufficient information may be considered a violation of the informed consent principles. Nonetheless, participants have to understand:

- Who is doing the research?
- What the research is about?
- What are its aims and objectives?
- What the participant is being asked to do and why?
- What will happen to the results and how they will be disseminated?
- What steps are being taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity?

(Walliman, 2005, p. 346; Wiles, 2013, p. 25)

Based on Boynton (2005) steps to obtain consent, I took the following procedures:

- I answered all of the above questions using an information sheet which was attached to the consent form, and which explained what it entails to take part in the study. In addition to that, I tried to provide them with the sufficient information they needed to know verbally.
- I allowed time for the participants to think about their decision to participate. According to Boynton (2005), it is advised to allow at least 24 hours to reflect on participation.
- I provided the participants with a signed copy of the consent form which is considered a permanent record for the participants in case anything goes wrong about consent.
- I ensured that the participants fully understood what they were consenting to. Boynton (2005) suggests that it is a good practice to ask the participants if they have any concerns, and check their well-being during and after the research process, especially in case of sensitive topics.

To sum it up, before the beginning of the research, permission had been sought and obtained from the Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland. Participants were aware of the requirements before agreeing to take part in the study. They were provided with a consent form and

a participant information sheet which included all the information they needed to know about this study. All participants were treated with respect and were aware that they could withdraw their involvement at any stage without having to provide an explanation. Considering the educational nature of the current study, and that all participants were adults, No physical or psychological harm was anticipated. Finally, confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the whole research process, pseudonyms were used instead of the participants' real names, and all data were securely stored on my personal computer and were exclusively accessed by myself.

4.11. Summary

This chapter outlined the essential elements of the current study and the selected methodological procedures for obtaining the necessary data. It offered a comprehensive account of the methodological components employed in this thesis, with the goal of ensuring that readers understand the reasoning behind each choice and the execution of the study. The chapter also delved into the philosophical considerations of the research, covering the ontological and epistemological stance, along with a discussion of the qualitative research approach for data collection. An in-depth discussion was undertaken regarding the research instruments, procedures, and the overall research process. The following chapter presents the findings of the three research tools.

Chapter 5: Analysis of the Findings

5.1. Introduction

In the current study, the main aim of analysing the university EFL curricula was to explore these documents for any evidence of critical thinking integration in Algerian higher education. It also aimed to analyse data gathered from a number of university teachers regarding their conceptualisation and understanding of critical thinking. Further, it sought to investigate their views on the importance of incorporating critical thinking in their teaching. Moreover, this study aimed at exploring teachers' educational practices in relation to critical thinking, and their translation of the general guidelines set by the Ministry of Higher Education. Chapter five presents the findings of the data gathered from the three research methods employed to answer the research questions. The first section is devoted to the findings related to the document analysis (EFL curriculum documents). Then, results from the semi-structured interviews are considered. The final section is concerned with the data obtained from the classroom observation.

5.2. Critical thinking representation in the Algerian higher education curriculum

This section reports the findings of the analysis and interpretation of the English language curriculum documents at the university level. The process of data collection and analysis was carried out with regard to the first research question:

To what extent does Algerian higher education encourage the teaching of critical thinking skills?

The main purpose of the analysis of the curriculum documents was to reveal whether or not critical thinking and its various components are emphasised in the objectives of the higher education curricula of the English language. For this purpose, I employed thematic analysis in reference to the widely used framework of cognitive skills: Anderson and Krathwohl's revision of Bloom's taxonomy (see section 4.6). As discussed in chapter 4, I followed Braun and Clark's (2006) six stages of conducting thematic analysis beginning with data preparation and ending with the report of the findings:

- Familiarising with data
- generating initial codes
- searching for themes
- reviewing the themes

- defining, naming, and comparing themes to Bloom's framework
- producing the report

Initially, I introduce the curriculum documents communicated by the Ministry of Higher Education. Subsequently, I explore in depth the presence of any critical thinking elements in the educational objectives of each subject at a semantic level (explicit), as well as at a latent one (implicit). As such, this exploration is not confined solely to explicit mentions of the term 'critical thinking.' Instead, it adopts a dual approach, scrutinising the semantic level for clear and explicit indications of critical thinking, while also applying a more nuanced analysis to unveil any implied aspects that may contain underlying references to critical thinking. This twofold investigation ensures a thorough exploration of both the explicit and implicit dimensions of critical thinking within the stated educational objectives.

The following are the three official curriculum documents issued by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research for the English language course:

Licence curriculum

Master's curriculum for Teaching English as a Foreign Language major (Didactics)

Master's Curriculum for Literature and Civilisation major

5.2.1. Licence Curriculum:

To start with, university teaching programmes are suggested and validated by a number of governing bodies on which the Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research relies to execute the implementation of the training policy and the strategy underlying this policy. The teaching structure following the LMD is divided into three training cycles: Licence degree, Master's degree, and PhD degree. The ministry develops the plan and guidelines of the national curriculum of higher education, higher education institutions propose their training offers and research policy based on the data they have and the potential of their environment. Then, the National Commission for Empowerment (CNH) with its subdivisions the Regional Assessment Commissions (CRE) evaluate and authorise the proposed courses from academic institutions to issue the corresponding diplomas, to other educational and scientific bodies of evaluation namely: the National Council for the evaluation of Scientific Research and Technological Development (CNER), and the National Pedagogical Sector committees (CPND) to evaluate research activities and the fulfilment of national teaching and research programmes (National Report, 2019).

Upon analysing the Licence curriculum, it became evident that the document was mainly about the organisation of modules, teaching units, evaluation systems, and some amendments in the credit system and coefficient of the subjects in each semester. Furthermore, the document featured several tables containing the names and signatures of teachers representing various universities across different cities in Algeria. The document contained also several evaluation grids for licence and master's programs in English Language at various universities. It included criteria and observations regarding different aspects of the programs, such as the title, content, credit calculation, ethical considerations, and approval from the relevant academic bodies with the entries 'conform' or 'non-conform' suggesting that the program aligns with the specified criteria according to the committee involved in the evaluation process.

Credits are a measurement unit of a student's work (course, homework, TD (travail dirigé), personal work, etc.). Credits can be capitalised and compensated from one term/subject to another within a particular cycle. For a Licence degree, a student has to obtain 30 credits in each semester that is 180 credits for the whole cycle. Given that each academic year has 2 semesters, an additional 120 credits have to be collected to get the Master's degree.

There were four teaching units in the document for each semester, presented in the form of tables. These tables included each subject's credits, coefficient, hourly volume in 15 weeks (1 semester), and the evaluation mode percentage (exam/continuous evaluation). Each teaching unit with its modules is presented as follows:

- Fundamental units (70%): written comprehension and expression, oral comprehension and expression, Grammar, phonetics, introduction to linguistics, literature, and culture/civilisation.
- Methodological units (20%): study skills for university, and study of texts.
- Discovery units (10%): introduction to translation, human and social sciences.
- Transversal units (10%): foreign language (usually French).

Evidently, there was more focus on written and oral expression, grammar, and study skills as the highest number of credits and hours were devoted to these modules with 45 hours in 15 weeks for each, compared to only 22 hours and 30 minutes for every other module. The emphasis on these modules may be attributed to the expectation that students graduating from secondary schools possess only superficial knowledge and basic skills in the English language. This is due to the limited exposure, typically one to two English language classes per week, during their middle and secondary

school years. As argued by Benmoussat and Bouyakoub (2019), EFL students joining universities lack communicative and analytical skills due to the teach-to-test approach where tests do not actually assess such skills. As a result, curriculum designers and teachers might feel compelled to follow the same path, exposing students to basic skills and knowledge that they believe are within the students' grasp at that level and which allow them to perform well in exams.

The document showed that the teaching programme for the first semester (described above) was the exact one applied in semesters 2, 3, and 4 (same teaching units, modules, coefficient, teaching hours, etc.), however, there were some amendments in the third year's teaching programme (semester 5 and 6), new modules were introduced such as: introduction to didactics (TEFL), introduction to ESP, methodology (research techniques), ICT, and cognitive psychology. Other modules such as grammar, phonetics, and study skills were eliminated. At this level, studying about the language and gaining knowledge about linguistics, literature, and civilisation were a top priority over practising the language teaching units.

The examination of the first curriculum document issued for the licence cycle revealed that none of the following was included: general educational goals or expected outcomes, specific objectives to be considered by educators when designing their course plan, the sequence in which these objectives should be achieved, a brief content, teaching materials, nor the type of activities that should be used. The complete absence of what a curriculum often includes made it extremely vague, bringing up questions instead of answering ones.

In terms of the main aim behind the document analysis, which was to investigate the presence of any elements of critical thinking, this License curriculum document did not provide sufficient information to answer the research question. To allow a proper analysis, a document should contain certain elements, among these elements are the teaching objectives which are the main focus of this research, however, this document did not provide any content to be analysed.

5.2.2. Critical thinking in the curriculum of Teaching English as a Foreign Language

5.2.2.1. Master 1: TEFL major

Unlike the License curriculum, Teaching English as a Foreign Language curriculum included comprehensive details of all modules along with their educational objectives. This inclusion enabled an in-depth analysis that can effectively address the research question. First, to uncover whether or not the term 'critical thinking' is explicitly mentioned in the curriculum, I reviewed the educational

objectives of each of the following teaching units. The Master's cycle involves four semesters. The teaching units (modules) of the first semester are:

- Methodology of teaching English as a foreign language
- Language acquisition
- Educational psychology
- Pragmatics
- Applied linguistics
- Research methodology
- Statistics
- Reading skills and strategies
- English for specific purposes (ESP)
- Legislation

The teaching units of the second semester are the same as those of semester one except for three modules: Pragmatics, reading skills and strategies and Legislation, which were replaced by Discourse analysis, Academic writing, and Entrepreneurship, respectively.

Having reviewed each of the objectives of the above-mentioned modules, it seemed that there was no explicit mention of the term 'critical thinking'. Looking for explicit incidences of critical thinking was not enough, therefore, to obtain a clear picture of the integration of critical thinking in the curriculum of TEFL, I started the coding process by classifying each objective by the action verb used as the structure of the teaching outcomes and objectives is mostly: 'students are expected to...', 'this course seeks to...', 'this will allow students...', 'students should be able to...', or 'this course is designed to...'. Although identifying verbs was useful, the coding process was not done mechanically, as such I interpreted the intended meaning of the educational objective (the whole sentence) as a whole and not only the operational verbs. The following are the main themes which emerged from the generated codes of the first year Master's programme which were then compared to the cognitive abilities of Bloom's revised version to explore which level most of the objectives are on: lower-level thinking skills or higher-order thinking skills. The themes are:

- *Expanding students' knowledge*
- *Raising students' awareness*
- *Developing students' understanding and application*
- *Developing students' higher cognitive skills*

Before discussing the emerging themes, it is worth mentioning that the teaching objectives of most of the first semester's modules were not changed in the second semester, except for six modules: three of them were the newly introduced subjects in semester two, and the other three are the same modules of semester one but with different objectives.

a. Expanding students' Knowledge: analysis of the curriculum document revealed that a large number of objectives were set to address the aspect of knowledge which according to Bloom's framework lies at the bottom of the learning process. This stage of learning is aligned with the operational verb in the revised version, *remember*.

This instructional objective according to Anderson and Krathwohl (2001) requires two associated cognitive processes, *recognising* and *recalling* which means that students at this level are asked to memorise basic facts, events, dates, information, etc., and to retrieve that knowledge when necessary, for instance, in modules like ESP (English for Specific Purposes), the aim of the course was mainly to consolidate students' knowledge of the term ESP and concepts related to it 'At this level, students are supposed to *expand their knowledge* with regard to the teaching of ESP by introducing them to the notions of course, syllabus and curriculum in ESP' (p.46).

In applied linguistics, the main aim was stated as 'applied linguistics is introduced at this level to *enlarge students' knowledge* in the field of linguistics..., the course seeks to equip students with pertinent information about applied linguistics origins, foundations and scope...' (p.29).

Another example, the objective of teaching legislation was to provide students with information about the Algerian legislative system, the executive power, the legal system, employment policies, etc. 'The teaching of this module should help the students *to have an idea* about Algerian legislative system, especially legislations regulating the teaching/learning activity' (p.35). The structure of the majority of objectives seemed to target lower-level skills where students are expected to absorb and accumulate knowledge to be reproduced when needed.

b. Raising students' awareness: of all the modules, the term raising awareness was mentioned in two modules: Methodology of teaching English as a foreign language_ one of the core modules in TEFL major _, and entrepreneurship. Although the structure of The objective of TEFL course did not specify what exactly are students supposed to do with the knowledge they are exposed to, it is stated that 'students are expected to develop an awareness of the underlying principles of the existing language teaching approaches/ methods..., and how each of the learning skills is taught effectively'

(p.36). This might entail that since various teaching approaches are introduced, students are required to compare traditional teaching approaches to new ones, and to identify similarities and differences. *Comparing* along with *recognising*, *describing*, *classifying*, *expressing*, and *explaining* are sub-processes to perform the cognitive skill of *understanding* in Bloom's revised framework. Therefore, two categories of the cognitive process overlapped: *remembering* (knowledge) and *understanding* which both correspond to lower-level skills. In the module of entrepreneurship, the main objective was also to provide the students with some basics of starting a business and to give them an idea about what English for Business, and English for Occupational Purposes (EB, EOP) mean which again reflected the emphasis on knowledge 'the teaching of this module should help the students to develop some awareness about the essentials of starting a business in relation to their major, particularly language schools and institutions. It also aims at introducing them to the main concepts and notions of English for Business and English for Occupational Purposes' (p.48).

c. Developing students' understanding and application: the term *understanding* was explicitly stated as the main aim in the following three modules: educational psychology, language acquisition, and statistics. The last two modules had the same objectives in semesters 1 and 2. In educational psychology, the aim of the course in the first semester was 'to develop an *understanding* of different personality aspects (especially during adolescence period)...' (p.27). This objective targeted primarily the skill of *understanding* where students are supposed to develop comprehension of the various personality development theories they are exposed to. In semester two, the objective was amended to include the operational verb *use* alongside *understanding* where students are supposed to understand and use appropriate methods and strategies learned from the course of educational psychology to ensure effective teaching in their future teaching careers. Based on Bloom's revised taxonomy, the cognitive skill *use* corresponds with the category of *Apply*. *Applying* is comprised of the sub-processes of *executing* and *implementing*, these reflect the application of procedures or strategies to familiar and unfamiliar tasks (Anderson and Krathwohl, 2001). Similarly, the module of statistics aimed to encourage the development of students' comprehension and application of statistical tools in their dissertations. The module of language acquisition emphasised the idea of introducing the students to the main theories of first and second language acquisition 'making learners *understand* the difference between first and second language acquisition' (p.37), and helping them understand the neurological and psychological factors influencing those processes which fall under the categories of *knowledge* and *understanding*.

The course of academic writing was primarily meant to stress the cognitive process of *application*, more precisely, its subcategory *executing*. *Executing* occurs often in conjunction with *understanding*, this is because students are supposed to know the proper procedures to use in a situation after being confronted and familiarised with a similar situation. The course objective of academic writing was stated as ‘the course gives students an opportunity to practice and improve their writing skills in the target language. It focuses on *absorbing* and *producing* academic language for practical, mainly, writing dissertation...’ (p.45). therefore, after being exposed to the stages of writing a research paper, features of abstracts, referencing, etc., students are expected to comprehend the received knowledge and produce it in similar contexts.

d. Developing students’ higher cognitive skills: of all the modules in both semesters, some higher-order cognitive skills appeared explicitly only twice. Those skills are analysing and evaluating which are part of the higher level of Bloom’s revised taxonomy, and which are also considered skills of critical thinking. The objectives of research methodology and discourse analysis modules combined lower and higher cognitive skills: *identifying, determining, distinguishing, and evaluating*. Research methodology, for example, aimed to enable students to identify and evaluate research problems, to determine the rationale, to identify research questions, to evaluate the appropriateness of a research methodology, and to distinguish between different research designs. In discourse analysis, the objective was structured as follows: ‘The students are expected to be able to analyse, understand and use different types of discourse, both oral and written’ (p.39), hence three stages of the learning process were overlapped: understanding, applying, and analysing.

In the module of reading skills and strategies, there were no explicit mentions of higher-order thinking skills, however, the objective of the course was primarily to develop students’ ability to read quickly and efficiently. Reading efficiently may imply that students should go through a number of processes such as: scanning, skimming, comparing and contrasting, and analysing.

Through the analysis of the first year’s curriculum, it can be noted, first of all, that critical thinking as a concept on its own was not clearly established as a goal. In fact, critical thinking was not even explicitly mentioned once. The analysis revealed a great emphasis on lower-level thinking skills mainly *knowledge* and *understanding*. In some instances, these skills were accompanied by application. The incidences of higher-order cognitive skills in comparison to those of lower-level thinking skills are very low. The higher-level cognitive skills, analysis and evaluation, which are often

considered key abilities in the process of critical thinking appeared only twice in both semesters as explained earlier.

5.2.2.2. Master 2: TEFL major

Moving to the second part of the curriculum document, I also examined all the objectives of the second year's modules. While semester four is basically devoted to thesis writing, the teaching units found in semester 3 of the Master's training are:

- Course books in the foreign language class
- Culture in foreign language class
- Educational psychology
- Applied linguistics
- Research methodology seminars
- Statistics
- Presentation skills and strategies
- English for specific purposes
- Work ethics and professional conducts

Reviewing all of the above modules, I found that there is only one explicit mention of critical thinking in one of the subjects, as shown below. However, there was no guidance or clarification on how students actually develop the capacity to do this, and notably, there is no guidance provided to teachers on how to facilitate this process:

Course books in the foreign language class: 'Through this course, students are expected to think critically about textbooks. They are expected to be able to evaluate textbooks and adopt instructional materials to the needs of students with different levels and backgrounds' (p.49).

To gain a better understanding of the teaching and learning objectives, I classified them into the following themes:

- *Developing students' knowledge about research conduct*
- *Raising students' awareness about aspects in their future careers*
- *Developing students' higher-order thinking skills*

a. *Developing students' knowledge about research conduct*: research methodology seminars, educational psychology, statistics and English for specific purposes emphasised primarily the importance of exposing students to the principles of the research process and methodological issues.

For example, by the end of the course of educational psychology 'students are expected to become familiar with research in educational psychology, and be able to process data in this area' (p, 51). Familiarising entails presenting knowledge and allowing students to recognise and identify different aspects of research in the field of educational psychology, recognising and identifying falls under the category of remembering (knowledge) and understanding. However, this objective is twofold, in the second part, students are required to process information which may involve examination and analysis. In the module of ESP, the aim was to present and describe aspects and characteristics related to the subject matter, and students were basically asked to digest what was exposed to them 'at this level, students will be exposed to different writing genres..., the focus will be on describing the characteristics and the main principles of academic genres' (p. 56).

Research methodology seminars and statistics modules aimed to develop students' knowledge about the research process and statistical tools which might be helpful in the development of their research topics, hence students are supposed to apply what they learned in the process of writing up their dissertations which reflects the category of applying in Bloom's revised version, i.e., students are expected to execute the information learned in a familiar situation. Yet, there was no clear articulation in the objectives of how students are supposed to be engaged in the learning process, except for being exposed to knowledge which would help them in the future.

b. Raising students' awareness about aspects in their future careers: modules like culture in foreign language class, applied linguistics, and work ethics and professional conducts are generally focused on developing future teachers of English by exposing the students to knowledge they would need in the future, and raising their awareness about issues in their future profession, in this case, teaching English in particular. The objective of applied linguistics which is a follow-up to Master's 1 aimed 'to review and *intensify students' knowledge* about the application of the discipline in foreign language teaching by introducing some new relevant concepts...which would offer some insights for their research works and at the same time prepare them for a future career in teaching' (p.52).

Similarly, in the module of culture, students are expected 'to develop an awareness of the interrelationship language/culture...' (p. 50), by exposing students to the definition of culture, how it can be taught, its importance in foreign language teaching, and how it can be integrated into the foreign language curriculum. The aim of teaching work ethics and professional conducts is also to raise 'students' awareness about the different forms of corruption, and how to fight it in their professional practice' (p. 58). Therefore, providing the students with knowledge about the

phenomenon, the issues related, and the solutions as well. Echoing on Bloom's framework, there seemed to be an overlap of three cognitive abilities: remembering, understanding, and applying, as students are expected to receive a set of information to be applied later in similar situations.

c. Developing students' higher-order thinking skills: as previously mentioned, developing students' higher cognitive skills was considered once in the module of coursebooks in the foreign language class where students are expected to deal with textbooks using a critical eye, analysing, and evaluating, and deciding whether these textbooks cater to the needs of the students, or there is still a need to adopt other materials. This was a long-term objective as students are introduced to the following content: benefits and drawbacks of using a textbook, authentic Vs created material, teachers' degree of freedom in adopting materials, and criteria for textbooks to be invested later in teaching.

Analysis of second year Master's curriculum for TEFL students did not differ much from that of Master 1 regarding the great emphasis on the lower cognitive skills over the higher cognitive skills. It was clear that the programme prioritised the fact that students have to prepare for the Master's dissertations to graduate, as a result, it targeted aspects they would need to achieve this goal. Aiming to prepare students for their future professions (particularly in teaching) was second in priority. Yet, the objectives were not precise on how, if ever, higher-order thinking skills might be integrated and developed, or to what extent will students be actively participating in the learning process, as most of the objectives were focused on students' reception of knowledge and expectations of its application in the future.

Reviewing all of the 29 objectives set for the entire Master's training programme, TEFL major, there were only three incidences of higher-order thinking skills, the rest were related to lower cognitive skills. In those three incidences, critical thinking was explicitly mentioned once, and the other two were components which constitute the process of thinking critically, these are analysing and evaluating. As such, those objectives revealed very little interest in the development and integration of critical thinking.

5.2.3. Critical thinking in the Master's curriculum of Literature and Civilisation

5.2.3.1. Master 1: Literature and Civilisation major

Similar to the TEFL curriculum, this document provided the educational objectives for all modules, which proved valuable as the primary focus was on scrutinising these objectives for any indications

of the integration of critical thinking. The following are the modules of Master 1 Literature and Civilisation which were first examined for any explicit mentions of critical thinking:

Semester 1:

- Britain: the making of the modern world (MMW)
- USA: the making of a nation (TMN)
- Literary criticism (LitC)
- Literary theory (LitT)
- Methodology of research (MoR)
- Teaching English as a foreign language
- Reading skills and strategies (RSS)
- Cross-cultural communication (CCC)
- Legislation

Semester 2:

- History of British literature (HBL)
- History of American literature (HAL)
- Contemporary developments in Britain (CDB)
- America's rise to globalism (ARG)
- Methodology of research (MoR)
- Teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL)
- Writing skills and strategies (WSS)
- Computer-assisted language learning (CALL)
- Entrepreneurship

There was one explicit mention of critical thinking in the teaching and learning objective of the following subject area:

Cross-Cultural Communication (CCC): ' By dealing with western perceptions of the Arab world and vice-versa, this course aims at making the students aware of misconceptions and distortions that arise among differing cultures; thus, it provides them with the necessary tools that intellectually stimulate and improve their *critical thinking*' (p.29).

Clearly, the concept of critical thinking, in general, does not seem to be introduced as a mandatory skill in all subject areas, yet as previously mentioned I analysed each objective to capture any

embedded integration of critical thinking. After the review of all the objectives of the Literature and Civilisation curriculum, I found that the emergent themes are similar to some degree to the themes in the TEFL curriculum, the difference is mainly in the frequency of and emphasis on some skills. The themes are:

- *Developing students' knowledge and understanding*
- *Developing students' higher-order thinking skills*
- *Improving students' basic skills*

a. Developing students' knowledge and understanding: knowledge and understanding continue to be the most frequent and essential skills set in the teaching and learning objectives which come at the bottom of the learning process according to Anderson and Krathwohl's (2001) revised taxonomy. In the first semester, it was expected from the module of Britain: The Making of the Modern World (MMW) that 'at term, the student will be able to understand the basic narrative of modern British history (1815 to 1914)...address the major events, ideas, and transformations in British religious, social, cultural, political and economic history' (p. 21). In USA: The Making of Nation (TMN) module, major concepts, themes, and events in American history from the pre-Columbian period to the end of Reconstruction are introduced to students, as such the course aims 'at providing the students with the necessary *background knowledge for understanding* today's American culture' (p.23). Literary Criticism (Lit C) and Literary Theory (Lit T) share the same objective which emphasises the importance of familiarising and raising students' awareness of schools of thought 'The course is meant to familiarise the students with the completely new outlook that the twentieth-century theoretical orientations bring about' (p.24). Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL)_ which is introduced in both semesters_, legislation, and Entrepreneurship are modules included in the curriculum of both streams TEFL and Literature and Civilisation. As in the TEFL curriculum, the module of TEFL in LIT and CIV curriculum seeks to provide the students with knowledge about the teaching of English and the four skills, particularly in middle and secondary schools. Similarly, the modules of legislation and entrepreneurship, aim at giving the students an idea about the Algerian legislative system, specifically legislations regulating the teaching process, and providing them with the basics of starting a business, as well as introducing them to concepts in relation to English for Business and English for Occupational Purposes. As can be noted, these objectives mainly target lower cognitive skills which are reception of knowledge and comprehension, and are more about what the teacher is expected to do, for example: demonstrate, familiarise, develop, and provide the

students... rather than what the students are expected to accomplish or put into practice which may imply that students perform a small role in the classroom.

b. Developing students' higher-order thinking skills: Having analysed all of the objectives of Master's 1 LIT and CIV curriculum, I found that some of the higher-level skills were considered in the objectives of the following modules: methodology of research, cross-cultural communication, contemporary development in Britain, America's rise of globalism. Cross-cultural communication aims at stimulating students' critical thinking by allowing them to identify, compare and differentiate between views and stereotypes of different cultures, specifically the clash between the Eastern and Western cultures. Apart from the aim of introducing the students to theories and appropriate methods and techniques for doing original research, the module of research methodology aims to 'enhance their ability to collect and analyse data and formulate research projects' (p. 26). Regarding the module of contemporary development in Britain, the aim is to encourage the students to critically analyse events, figures, outcomes, and generally the knowledge exposed to them concerning the major developments in British contemporary history 'More than dates, figures and names, the student should be able to approach them critically and analytically' (p.33). In the module of America's rise of globalism and considering Bloom's framework, there was an overlap of low and high-level skills where the aim was to provide the students with in-depth knowledge of American social, cultural, economic as well as political history as it has developed from 1865 to the present time, so that by the end of the course 'they will be able to analyse and discuss complex ideas at an advanced level' (p.34).

c. Improving students' basic skills: Notably, some modules in the LIT and CIV curriculum stressed the importance of enhancing students' basic skills, particularly reading and writing. History of American literature module sought to improve students' reading and fluency in the English language by being exposed to different literary texts, the aim was also 'To help learners *know* about the historical contexts of American literature and major trends and authors, *understand* the American society and its culture as reflected in the literary works' (p.32). As can be noted, three cognitive abilities of Bloom's revised taxonomy can be spotted in this objective, remembering (knowledge), understanding, and applying.

Similarly, in the module of history of British literature, the aim was to read and understand British literary texts, and to be able to apply this knowledge in discussions and presentations related to literary topics. This course aimed to help the students '*...understand and employ* the meanings of

basic literary terms in discussions over and oral presentations of literary topics' (p.31), emphasising again the cognitive skills of understating and applying. The statement of these objectives did not seem to leave room for higher-order thinking skills like analysing, evaluating, and creating since students are expected to understand a set of knowledge to be then used as it is in discussions, presentations, exams, etc.

Reading skills and strategies and writing skills and strategies are modules designed primarily to reinforce students' effective reading skills particularly reading historical and literary texts given their major; and to teach them about the process of writing, writing foundations, note-taking, structure of an essay, etc., which is a part of preparing the students to write their Master's dissertations. Effective reading and analytical writing may impose the use of some higher-level skills such as: examining, distinguishing, comparing and contrasting, evaluating, criticising, weighing argument, etc. however, this was not clearly indicated in this teaching objective.

Having reviewed first-year Master's Lit and CIV curriculum, it appeared once again that expanding knowledge, developing understanding, recalling and applying information were the most repeated cognitive skills in the educational objectives. Critical thinking and other higher-order thinking skills such as analysing were considered in four modules, however, critical thinking was explicitly mentioned only one time, without offering any guidelines on how students are expected to develop critical thinking skills, nor was there any guidance on how teachers are supposed to stimulate these skills in their students.

5.2.3.2. Master 2: Literature and Civilisation major

The second part of the LIT and CIV curriculum involves modules of semester 3 only. By the end of the third semester, students should have written proposals for their Master's research projects as semester 4 is dedicated to thesis writing in all specialities. Semester 3 modules are:

- British and American government: a comparative approach (BAG)
- Islamic foundations of Western civilisation (IFWC)
- Postcolonial literature (PCL)
- Introduction to comparative literature (ICL)
- Research methodology seminar
- Presentation skills and strategies (PSS)
- Teaching culture in the EFL class (TC)
- Work ethics and professional conducts

The themes which emerged from these modules are similar to those that emerged in the previous semesters, this was due to the fact that many modules are introduced in both specialities and in all semesters. The themes are: stem

- *Stimulating students' analytical thinking*
- *Developing students' knowledge and awareness*
- *Developing students' research and presentation skills*

a. Stimulating students' analytical thinking: Although there were no incidences in which critical thinking was explicitly mentioned in the teaching and learning objectives of the above modules. Some higher-level thinking skills which contribute to the process of critical thinking were emphasised. For instance, the module British and American Government: a comparative approach aimed, first, to enhance students' understanding of British and American governments and politics, policy-making, political parties...by explaining to them related concepts and mechanisms. This objective might promote students' analytical thinking. The objective behind introducing the module of Islamic foundations of Western civilisation was to open students' minds and encourage them to explore and reflect on Islamic thought contributions to Western civilisation as acknowledged and debated in writings in English 'this class aims at opening a new window from which the student looks at and appreciates his own civilisational heritage' (p.41). In introduction to comparative literature module, the history and critical theories of comparative literature are introduced to students, as such 'this course aims at providing them with the necessary tools that permits them to investigate parallel texts from different national origins, eras and disciplines critically' (p.43). As can be seen and drawing on Bloom's revised version, these objectives combined both lower-level skills like knowledge and understanding and higher-level skills like investigating, reflecting, questioning, relating, etc.

b. Developing students' knowledge, understanding, and awareness: Knowledge, understanding, and application were stressed in modules such as: postcolonial literature, Teaching Culture in the EFL Class, and work ethics and professional conducts. The objective of postcolonial literature was to introduce students to writings in English from diverse cultural and historical backgrounds about postcolonial theories and writers aiming to bring the students 'to an *understanding* of the complex nature of identity and culture' (p.42). In teaching culture in the EFL class, students are expected to gain an idea about the interrelationship between culture and language, and how to incorporate the teaching of culture in EFL classes. The module of work ethics and professional conducts aimed to

raise students' awareness about the types of corruption, reasons and consequences of corruptions, and ways to fight corruption, particularly in the teaching profession. There was no indication of including higher-order thinking skills, the aim of these modules was to deliver knowledge and expect it to be useful for the students in the future.

c. Developing students' research and presentation skills: Research methodology seminar aimed at discussing issues related to the research process and methodology to help students develop their research proposals by the end of the third semester. Presentation skills and strategies aimed to provide the students with easy tools and strategies to use for the best impact in presentations, how presentations work, and how to cope with stress, etc. These objectives also seem to emphasise the reception of knowledge and application in similar situations.

Analysis of the first and second year's LIT and CIV curriculum revealed that of the 27 teaching objectives, critical thinking with other higher-level skills was considered 7 times where the term critical thinking was mentioned only one time as an objective in itself, the other mentions were mainly targeting the skill of analysing. Promoting higher-order thinking skills did not appear to be a priority compared to lower-level skills such as knowledge and understanding. The consequences of the low emphasis on critical thinking in the curriculum documents and its impact on the broader framework of critical thinking integration in EFL classes will be elaborated upon in the subsequent discussion chapter.

5.3. EFL University teachers' conceptualisation of critical thinking, their instructional practices, and perceived barriers

5.3.1. Introduction

In this section, data gathered from interviews is presented and analysed to explore teachers' understanding of the concept of critical thinking and its importance, and further to identify potential approaches and strategies that teachers employ to incorporate it in their pedagogy, if there are any, highlighting the challenges and barriers they perceive in the way of developing it. This section aims to answer the following research questions:

- *What are university teachers' perceptions of critical thinking, and the importance of its integration in their teaching?*
- *What practices do EFL teachers enact to, or consider would foster EFL learners' critical thinking?*

An interview schedule was used to answer these research questions, and additional follow-up questions were asked when appropriate with some participants. As discussed in chapter 4, thematic analysis was employed following Braun and Clarke’s (2006) six stages of analysing qualitative data. As such, I started with a coding procedure by searching for patterns which were then categorised into themes, then analysed and discussed in detail. The data analysed were organised into the following four broad sections, and major themes and sub-themes were developed under each section.

Figure 1: EFL University teachers 'conceptualisations of critical thinking, their instructional practices, and perceived barriers

5.3.2. Teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking

5.3.2.1. Components of critical thinking

To discover the teachers' conceptions of critical thinking, participants were asked to explain what they understood by the term critical thinking. After analysing the answers given, it was revealed that the participant teachers perceived critical thinking as a process which involves a set of cognitive skills. Their accounts were centred on the following sub-themes: *the ability to analyse, synthesise, and evaluate; questioning and truth-seeking; criticism; and problem-solving.*

a. The ability to analyse, synthesise, and evaluate: Four of the participants indicated that critical thinking is a skill which includes a number of cognitive sub-skills. According to Reem's point of view 'critical thinking means critical, let's say, reasoning, employing, or using procedures like: evaluation, analysis, synthesis'. Similarly, Ali considered critical thinking as a fifth skill after speaking, listening, reading, and writing, he added that critical thinking involves the use of 'receptive and productive skills', and the ability to analyse, synthesise, evaluate information, and form conclusions after inferring and making connections.

b. Questioning and truth-seeking: Omar highlighted the importance of questioning and having an open mind to explore different ideas as aspects of critical thinking, he stated that 'critical thinking is the ability to think, let's say out of the box, to have a divergent thinking...' (Omar). In a similar vein, Lina emphasised questioning as a powerful tool to foster critical thinking:

So, critical thinking is always about raising questions, about why and how and when, and what if. So, these questions can help you in developing the critical thinking which will open and widen your views about the world and what you are dealing with.

(Lina)

c. Criticism: Some participants used criticism as a synonym to critical thinking. Adam, for example, defined critical thinking as the ability to criticise the information that one receives. He then continued to describe it as 'the ability to contrast and compare between objects, ideas...and the ability to discover flaws, advantages, pros and cons, and the hidden and said, flaws and limitations in anything that I learn' (Adam). Comparing and contrasting ideas, analysing arguments, and seeking facts and flaws to reach sound judgment are indeed elements of critical thinking, however, it is important to highlight that critical thinking and criticism should not be used interchangeably.

Another four teachers seemed to share the view that critical thinking means mainly criticism in their definitions 'to criticise what have been handed to you, for example, what is told to you by people

who have, let's say, supervision over you like your parents, your teachers...' (Omar). On her part, Lina mentioned the difference between hard and soft sciences, and how important it is to be a critical thinker in social sciences, unlike concrete sciences where facts are determined based on rules. She perceived critical thinking as the ability to criticise and ask questions, she stated that 'critical thinking is always about criticising and thinking critically about the theories that we have' (Lina).

Another participant, Mia, did not provide a precise definition, but she argued to the fact that students should not only absorb the information they receive from teachers 'they need to show agreement and disagreement' (Mia). She added that students need 'to react' and criticise what they are exposed to, otherwise, the teaching process would not be effective.

d. Problem-solving: Djamal, although he admitted at the beginning that he does not have much knowledge about critical thinking, and that he only uses the concept in a general sense, he offered an insightful answer 'being able to invest what you have to come with solutions, to come up with new ideas, to come up with your own analysis and judgment' (Djamal), he mentioned the aspect of problem-solving as one element of critical thinking where students use knowledge critically, think about the data they receive, and evaluate the situations to effectively solve problems. He added that he urges his students to use the knowledge they acquire in real-life situations, to think critically about it, and not to take it for granted. This view was also shared by Nora who defined critical thinking as a 'skill encompassing several sub-skills including, for example, the ability to analyse, synthesise, solve problems, and not take things for granted' (Nora).

However, two participants, Mustafa and Salim, seemed to avoid answering the question and providing a precise definition of the concept. Mustafa stated that he has an idea about it as he has recently done research on Bloom's taxonomy which is according to him related to 'thinking skills' and 'creative thinking'. Salim also did not provide his understanding of critical thinking, he stated that critical thinking is a metacognitive skill which needs to be possessed by students, but he added that he does not believe that all students are capable of practicing criticality 'truth to be told, not all students have this property, the metacognitive skill, because it requires training and exercises and practice so that we can develop it in the students with low or with average levels' (Salim). This implies that Salim believes that critical thinking is a skill that high-achievers or gifted students already have that average and low-ability students do not, and he added that it is the teachers' responsibility to develop that skill in those students by choosing the right type of exercises.

The participant teachers viewed critical thinking in terms of its components as involving an element or a set of cognitive skills, however, their answers seemed to lack elaboration and precision, some of them avoided answering the question directly, and also in some instances, critical thinking was confused with criticism and creative thinking. Therefore, it might be deduced that there might be a lack of understanding and knowledge about the concept of critical thinking among teachers.

5.3.2.2. Importance of critical thinking

Of the 10 participants who were interviewed, there seemed to be a consensus that critical thinking is a crucial skill that should be developed not only for academic purposes, but for life in general. Three sub-themes on how critical thinking is useful were identified: *everyday life, research and academia, EFL leaning*.

a. Everyday life: On his part, Mustafa noted that critical thinking is not only important in the school context but also outside, in real-life situations. He explained that teaching the language is not the ultimate objective as they aim also to prepare future citizens who are able to make contributions to their society and their country. Supporting this point, Nora stated that ‘incorporating critical thinking in any kind of teaching is of crucial importance given its relevance not only to classroom activities but also to real-life situations and tasks’ (Nora).

b. Research and academia: Djamal claimed that developing critical thinking is of central importance for him, and that the purpose of his teaching is how to make use of knowledge, particularly, in conducting research, he commented:

Knowledge or information or the amount of knowledge is not the most important thing, it is how to use that knowledge, how to develop your understanding of certain concepts, and how to be able to discuss things and eventually do research and write something about those topics. So for me, I look for that, I try to achieve that... and not only take information or knowledge, memorise it and then forget about it, but to invest it.

(Djamal)

Another participant, Adam, highlighted the significant role that critical thinking plays in preparing students for academia and in forming successful future researchers. And as an attempt to integrate it into the curriculum, he suggested (informally) to his colleagues introducing it as a separate module at university. According to him, this suggestion came as he noticed the absence of critical thinking in the students’ answers in class, in exams, and even in their master’s dissertations, he commented ‘I don’t see critical thinking in their essays, right, they just copy paste’ (Adam). When asked about his

colleagues' attitudes towards his suggestion of integrating critical thinking as a separate module, he said that there was a consensus over the importance of critical thinking, but there was a disagreement about its applicability as according to some it is very difficult to put the concept into practice.

c. EFL learning: Reem did not elaborate much on how or in what ways she perceives the importance of critical thinking, she only commented that 'if we want learners to develop a certain proficiency in the target language, they have to make use of critical thinking, especially for advanced learners' (Reem). Mia, also, believed that critical thinking is really important because the main aim of the teaching process is to produce autonomous and active learners, students who are able to reflect on and to make use of knowledge to solve problems '...we need to have critical thinkers, not just receivers of knowledge' (Mia). Lina and Omar, on the other hand, emphasised the significance of critical thinking in the field of social sciences. Lina pointed out that given the importance of this topic, teachers should rethink their teaching approaches and question whether or not they encourage their students to critically think about the information they receive, she commented '...so we need to reconsider the way we transmit the information to the students' (Lina). Omar, similarly, believes that students at university level in general should be introduced to critical thinking, particularly, students in the field of social sciences as according to him the latter needs 'students' who are able to think critically, to always challenge let's say old ideas, and to have their own ideas and express them in a free way' (Omar).

Surprisingly, Salim and Reem both mentioned the idea that critical thinking is only appropriate for advanced students, and introducing it at early stages might not be convenient. Salim stated that critical thinking is indeed important and that teachers have to think about adopting types of questions and types of evaluation which stimulate students' critical thinking, however, he believed that it is a complex topic to be presented to beginners 'starting from intermediate or up to intermediate levels we can think of incorporating critical thinking tasks and critical thinking problem-solving exercises' (Salim).

From the analysis of the participants' answers, it seemed that the teachers were aware of the significance of critical thinking inside and outside the classroom. They all agreed that integrating it into the teaching process is quite useful. Yet, some of them believed that critical thinking is an intricate concept, and it might be more reasonable to introduce it in later stages of learning. That is,

for instance, it might be appropriate and more relevant to introduce it to master's students than to students in a bachelor's program, this is further discussed in the following chapter.

5.3.2.3. Teachability of critical thinking

When asked about their ability to teach critical thinking and whether they think that critical thinking can be taught, most teachers argued that they can teach critical thinking, but this happens only implicitly. Seven out of the ten teachers claimed that critical thinking is implicitly considered in their educational practices, for example, in their tasks, exercises, interactive games, questioning, and feedback.

According to Ali, critical thinking cannot be taught explicitly and one does not need to tell the students about it. He suggested that critical thinking is implicitly introduced in certain types of activities, he commented 'I think it is implied...you cannot teach it directly, for example, problem-solving, you can put situations and then ask them questions, maybe to see their reactions' (Ali).

Similarly, Reem admitted that usually the aim is not to practice or develop critical thinking, she said 'sometimes, we do this spontaneously, we do not have the intention', she added 'in some tasks and activities, learners are going to think critically' (Reem), assuming that in many cases students spontaneously engage in the process of critical thinking. Lina, explained that to infuse critical thinking in her teaching, she always tends to ask students to clarify their answers 'whenever they say something, I say why?' (Lina).

Another participant, Omar, advocated for the possibility of teaching critical thinking implicitly but not explicitly. He noted that critical thinking can be implicitly taught through the type of tasks teachers design for students, their feedback, and classroom interaction in general. He explained that if a teacher, for instance, has a strict attitude towards his students' answers in the sense that he does not accept diverse views and expects only what he delivers to students, this would indirectly hinder them from expressing new ideas.

Although Mustafa and Mia seemed positive about the possibility of teaching critical thinking, they provided very brief and confused answers. Mia claimed that she usually uses interactive games as a way to promote students' higher-order thinking skills. And Mustafa confirmed his ability to teach critical thinking, however, when asked about the ways which he uses to infuse it in his teaching, he did not seem to be able to answer the question. This might entail a gap between the teachers' cognitions of critical thinking and their pedagogical practices, he said 'yes, of course, we can and we

have to' (Mustafa), and when I asked him to elaborate on how he could possibly incorporate critical thinking in his teaching, he commented:

Well, concerning how, there are many methods of course, so we have to put learners in situations where...or situations that require higher level thinking, let's say operations and skills. So, we need to incorporate various methods and techniques like: brainstorming, evaluating their own outcome, etc. There are many many techniques.

(Mustafa)

Adam, likewise, believed that he is capable of introducing critical thinking, but pointed out that he is unsure of how difficult that would be, especially when considering teaching it as a separate module, and given the fact that he only has some knowledge of reading about it but not practising it. He added that this skill is important and should not only be taught at university, but even in early school years.

Salim and Djamal believed that critical thinking is teachable, but they were not sure about its applicability, as they pointed out that there are factors which should be taken into consideration. These factors will be tackled in detail later in this chapter (see section 5.3.5). Salim claimed that 'sometimes we find some problems when the students' cognitive awareness is low compared to the input is exposed to them' (Salim). He once again highlighted the idea that students' levels might be a problem given the complexity of critical thinking. Djamal also seemed to believe in the teachability of critical thinking, but he also seemed fully aware that developing this skill requires a long-term process, it cannot be taught in a short period of time. He also assumed that the process of teaching critical thinking might be successful for some students more than others.

Nora, similarly, maintained this view 'yes, I believe I can teach critical thinking to some extent, depending on the subject taught and the aims of the course' (Nora), and the aims of most subjects unfortunately involve aspects other than critical thinking.

To sum up, all participant teachers seemed to agree on the possibility of teaching critical thinking only implicitly, one of the participants even used the term 'spontaneously'; it should be noted that there is no such thing as spontaneous when it comes to critical thinking as it requires careful selection and preparation of activities and very thoughtful planning.

5.3.2.4. Teacher's role in promoting critical thinking in students

As previously presented, many participants consider that the teacher plays the most significant role in developing critical thinking in students. Hence, participants were asked to elaborate on how they try to effectively instil critical thinking in students and adapt their classroom practices to go beyond learning the language itself and focus on skills that are required to face the challenges of the 21st century. The participants in this study suggested three ways in which teachers can make an impact on students regarding the development of critical thinking: *classroom activities, teaching approach, and supervision.*

a. Classroom activities: Five participants believed that they do play an important role in cultivating critical thinking in their classes by creating opportunities for students to think critically through classroom tasks and activities. Reem, for instance, claimed that she tries to introduce critical thinking in her classes using some activities which are expected to make students reflect on their learning. She gave an example of an activity where all students are asked to observe a group of students modelling a particular teaching approach after they had a lecture about it, then students are expected to reflect on the group's performance and compare it to the knowledge they received in the lecture, to see whether or not they applied the principles of that teaching approach. Salim, on the other hand, described his role in the classroom regarding the integration of critical thinking as being 'subject to the challenges raised in my teaching process as a whole' (Salim). Salim seemed to recognise the importance of the issue and seemed to be aware of his role in this regard, but he was also concerned about the feasibility of introducing critical thinking given its difficulty and the many challenges imposed by the context, he stated:

It's not easy to teach critical thinking and it is not impossible, well my role is that, I mean the will and the determination is there, the syllabus and the course design or the lesson plan must be is always made up of elements that would stimulate or that would stir critical thinking.

(Salim)

On his account, Omar admitted that teachers play a crucial role in making their students become critical thinkers, not only through classroom activities, but also by considering it when setting objectives, and preparing exam questions and assignments 'the teacher can promote critical thinking in the activities by focusing on the things I said earlier, means encouraging the student to always challenge and criticise and bring his own perspective' (Omar).

According to Lina, the problem with students graduating from university is that they find themselves unable to think, or at most think in similar expected ways, take the same path, do not think in a divergent way, do not try to create multiple solutions to the very first issue they face. For that reason, Lina added that she considers that her role is mainly to recommend students to think critically and try to create opportunities out of the difficult situations faced in real-life.

b. Teaching approach: In this study, two participants perceived their role in developing critical thinking as primarily adopting an appropriate teaching approach. Djamal, for instance, claimed that nurturing critical thinking in university students is supposed to be the teacher's major aim, this is because students at this stage are not aware of the concept nor how to use it. Students enrolling in university settings are not aware that the purpose of learning is not to accumulate knowledge but how to make use of it, for example, to solve problems. Djamal emphasised this point and further explained that 'teachers should focus more, their main job should be to monitor the learning process, they should help learners to think critically, I mean, and it is not to think about the content' (Djamal). This means that the emphasis in the learning/teaching process should not be put merely on transmitting the knowledge, as in the new digital world knowledge can be found everywhere. Djamal suggested that if students 'do some research, they will find richer content than what we provide' (Djamal), therefore the emphasis should be placed on what to do with the knowledge.

c. Supervision: Interestingly, Two participants pointed out that they tend to encourage critical thinking in supervision, they think that master's students who are preparing their graduation dissertations should be aware of critical thinking at this stage. Adam explained that he attempts to engage his students in critical thinking tasks 'to some extent', but he accentuates more the importance of using higher-order thinking skills in the writing of the master's students 'I always ask my supervisees to write not only descriptive dissertations, but also critical' (Adam). This might imply again that Adam perceives critical thinking as a skill more appropriate for advanced students. Mia shared a similar view as Adam's regarding their role in raising master's students' awareness about critical thinking as they are expected to complete their dissertations to graduate, she admitted though that she gives little attention to critical thinking in other modules that she is in charge of, she stated:

...I'm not giving that much focus on critical thinking, I do give focus, but not that much. Because, because I think that it would be better when my students who are in their master level, it would be better for them to be taught how to be critical thinkers, because at that time, they need to write

dissertations, they need to analyse information, they need to analyse the relationship between variables, between aspects.

(Mia)

It is worth noting that introducing critical thinking at very late stages to students and expecting them to perform accordingly is not expected to generate successful results (Biggs and Tang, 2011; Byrnes, 2012). Critical thinking needs to be gradually and consistently developed till students become good at it. Mustafa admitted that he is still not confident about infusing critical thinking in his teaching, he stated 'well, I do my best, but I know it is not it is still not enough, it is still not enough, we hope that we can improve through time, yeah, it is not it is not enough' (Mustafa). Nora also shared her concern that to embrace such a concept a number of reforms need to take place at several levels 'I think much remains to be done in this respect at all educational levels' (Nora).

5.3.3. Teachers' educational practices and implementation of critical thinking

5.3.3.1. Criteria of critical thinking activities

Data were collected regarding the teachers' knowledge of the characteristics that contribute to the development of critical thinking skills in an activity, and whether or not they implement classroom activities which particularly trigger students' ability to think critically. Some of the teachers' answers regarding the characteristics of critical thinking enhancement activities can be categorised into the following: *encouraging students' voice, requiring solving problems, requiring making connections, encouraging reflection and self-evaluation.*

a. Encouraging students' voice: some of the teachers' answers were ambiguous as they seemed unable to provide clear answers to the question. Taking Omar's point of view, for instance, at the beginning, he appeared to be confused 'I don't know what to say...', but then he suggested that for an activity to be improving to the students' critical thinking, it needs to encourage the students to go beyond the knowledge they receive, to be open-minded and to express different opinions, he stated:

Activities that ask the students to create, for examples, to challenge what has been provided in the classroom in way or another, and to bring his own perspective in the answer I mean, so when asking them about something, you should encourage personal opinions, for example, personal reflections on things.

(Omar)

Nora also shared this view, she pointed out that one of the characteristics of critical thinking enhancement activities is 'among other things... viewing matters from a variety of perspectives' (Nora). Djamel declared that he tends sometimes to redirect students' thinking to something he/she did not think of, and to consider other possibilities as 'there is not a right or wrong answer, all answers are acceptable either way' (Djamel).

On encouraging students' voice, Omar maintained that activities that might develop students' criticality should allow them to express their views freely even if they are opposed to the teachers' views. Omar stated that in the research methodology module, for instance, he asks the students to come up with a research problem, identify the various variables and then propose the research method they believe is appropriate. He pointed out that this might develop their higher-order thinking skills:

Giving the student a chance to choose the method that he believes is appropriate, even if the recommended method, for example, by the teacher is, let's say, an experimental study, but we encourage the student to use a method that he thinks is more appropriate, is more flexible, I do not know, is more needed, even if it's not recommended by the teacher, So I believe this is critical.

(Omar)

b. Requiring solving problems: Mia and Reem suggested that the aspect of problem-solving is what characterises an activity which promotes critical thinking, but their answers were quite short lacking any sort of elaboration or illustration which once again might reflect a lack of knowledge about the applicability of critical thinking. When asked to provide examples of activities they implement to integrate critical thinking in their teaching, Mia admitted that given the fact that she is a novice teacher, she still does not have the adequate knowledge to put critical thinking into practice 'well, Because I don't have that much experience as a teacher of English at the University, I do not have much knowledge about the implementation of critical thinking' (Mia).

c. Requiring making connections: other teachers suggested that what characterises an activity that develops the ability to think critically is encouraging the students to make connections between what they learn and to link classroom learning to real-life situations. Reem, for example, stated that 'activities that urge students, let's say, to make links or connections between real-life activities'. Ali also commented 'maybe activities which make the students make connections, like matching activities'. Ali seemed unable to provide a clear and detailed answer, he noted that due to the

changes and restrictions caused by Covid-19, his focus was not put on improving students' ability to think critically, his focus was rather on covering the whole curriculum, although the question asked was in a general sense and did not specify the period of the Covid-19. He stated:

This year, this year no because of the pandemics, just I aim to cover the material or to deliver the content. But before yes, I do not remember exactly the example in detail, but I guess when I taught my students, second year students, about induction and deduction. It was like giving them providing them examples on the board and asking them to make connections by deduction and induction and see the difference.

(Ali)

On similar lines and on the criterion of making connections, Djamal expressed his lack of awareness of the types of activities which help in the development of critical thinking. He added that he tries always to link what he teaches to real-life situations for a more meaningful teaching and learning process, he explained:

... I give examples about their (the students) own process of learning in their daily life. And even when I teach the other module, which is TEFL for master students, I try to give examples. I start with myself, and with other teachers... I mean, this is interesting, if you teach them something just for the sake of teaching them that thing. It would not work I mean, you should always link it to something.

(Djamal)

D. Encouraging reflection and self-evaluation: the last criterion identified by teachers is the criterion of encouraging reflection and self-evaluation. Lina noted that it is any activity which helps the students to criticise and build their knowledge, and most importantly to evaluate and reflect on their learning. She stated:

... If we take the example of written expression, now when I ask the students to write a paragraph, here there are different tasks and activities we follow most of the time we follow the type of writing and ask them directly to write but before we write, we should develop for them: What is a paragraph, what makes a paragraph, what is and what is not a paragraph. So, asking them to write a paragraph then teaching them the paragraph and asking them to decide whether the paragraph they have written is a paragraph or not, such evaluation or self-evaluation can help them to retake always of what they are doing.

(Lina)

Mustafa seemed unsure of how to answer the question and requested some time to think about it, he then suggested that an activity that develops critical thinking skills should encourage the students to evaluate one own learning, and also to evaluate and reflect on others' ideas, and he gave an example 'to evaluate each other and to evaluate themselves like, for instance, recording their own performance and later on, ask them to make a reflection on their own performance and to evaluate their own performance for instance' (Mustafa). Similarly, Djamel noted that he sometimes tries to make the students reflect on their own work and consider other ideas or perspectives. He stated:

Sometimes they work in pairs and in groups, even individually, and they try to see what they have written, and I try to direct their thinking by asking, for example, don't you think that it is going to be interesting if you consider that? I mean, what about this?

(Djamel)

5.3.3.2. Teachers' approaches and educational practices to develop critical thinking

Teachers shared the classroom practices they usually arrange in the classroom that they believed could be developing to the students' critical thinking. The data gathered revealed that the teachers' answers were centred on the following types of activities: brainstorming and questioning, projects and presentations, and group or pair work. Yet, some teachers admitted that sometimes the teacher-centred approach seems to dominate the classroom implying that sometimes there are no tasks or activities performed by students in the classroom.

Djamel, for example, explained that sometimes the classroom practices depend on the module itself, whether it is skill-based or content-based. When the module is skill-based, Djamel said that he usually uses brainstorming, questioning, group work activities, he also assigns students to prepare small papers and present it. However, in content-based modules, he stated that the aim is usually to deliver the content, yet he tries to get the students engaged in the discussion, he said:

For the content modules, which I teach for master students, generally, it is lecture, traditional lecturing. However, I try to involve my students, I try to ask them questions, I try to raise their interest, I try to find knowledge or pieces of information they have deep down in their minds, but they don't know. I try to get that and try to link things.

(Djamel)

He also believed that using questioning to check the students' understanding at the end of each session can develop the students' critical thinking by asking them 'to reproduce' what they have learned. Reproduction of information, if anything, does not reflect the practice of critical thinking, reflecting little knowledge about what the concept actually means. he commented:

Sometimes, before presenting the point, I ask them questions, or I direct their thinking towards something, or for instance, another strategy that I use, sometimes I introduce something and by the end, okay, about the use or about the significance of something, and I try to make them reproduce what they have learned, to see or to monitor our learning, and to see if they understood and to see if they are thinking.

(Djamal)

Lina, on her part, stated that since she is in charge of lectures, she does not manage to get the students involved in any activities. She added an interesting point claiming that in order to draw the students' attention and interest, she often tends to ask questions without providing answers, and then informs them that those questions might be part of tests or exams, she commented:

Most of the time I do lectures which means I do not have the opportunity to involve tasks apart from trying to raise the discussion of the students and ask them to reconsider the points that they have, I most of the time leave open questions without answering and threatening that they will be the exam, so they can find the formation and try to discuss that.

(Lina)

Mustafa, for instance, noted that the only activity that he usually practises in the classroom is brainstorming, he stated that he does not start lecturing directly, but he first allows time for the students to brainstorm the topic. He perceived this as a way of developing critical thinking.

Reem specified that she arranges debates and presentations for master's students usually in the form of a group work activity where they are expected to receive questions from their peers and herself. This according to her would engage the students in discussions which would stimulate their critical thinking 'presentations followed by debates, when one group of students or even one student presents something, and then he receives questions and comments, these questions raise issues of critical thinking' (Reem). Yet, she added that sometimes there is no time for practice, and therefore she only tends to deliver the content planned.

Omar and Adam stated that one way to engage the students in the learning process is through classroom discussions about the subject matter. Omar gave an example of the module of methodology, he said:

depends on the module in particular, when we talk about methodology, research methodology, usually the activities are about, let's say, research problems about identifying relationship between variables and raising research questions that matter and this is usually in pair work, that's what we do.

(Omar)

Another participant, Nora, mentioned that she frequently organises communicative activities like think/pair/share activities, reflective activities, and project work. On the other hand, Mia, who admitted to her limited knowledge of implementing critical thinking due to her limited teaching experience, mentioned that she has begun incorporating tasks such as writing essays and games, which she believes can improve students' critical thinking skills

It was revealed from the answers that the teachers employ various educational practices which are engaging and interactive, and seem to create an active learning environment where it is possible for critical thinking to be considered and cultivated, however, this does not mean that the teacher-centred approach with the traditional lecturing is no longer adopted, as admitted by some teachers. It should be noted also that all the above-mentioned activities could be performed without any particular focus on critical thinking. Classroom practices will be further examined in section 5.4 of this chapter, where these activities will be observed in practical application.

5.3.4. Teachers' awareness about Critical thinking representation in the EFL university curriculum

5.3.4.1. Critical thinking 'is not actually part of the agenda'!

The participants in this study believed that the educational system does not play any role in the integration of critical thinking in EFL classes. And that the curriculum of English language does not contain any instructions about the implementation of critical thinking within classroom practice. The teachers' answers were centred on these two sub-themes: *LMD system merits, and teacher's responsibility*.

a. LMD system merits: most participants argued that they have never received a document from the Ministry of Higher Education which represents critical thinking as an educational objective, examples of this from their accounts are:

'I haven't come across any document so far regarding the way how we should or how it is important to raise learners, learners' critical thinking' (Mia).

'That's not actually part of the agenda, I mean, decision makers, from the ministry or the board of teachers, they are not talking about these things' (Omar).

'There is no specific emphasis or objectives concerning critical thinking... ' (Djamal).

'I have I had to look at the Canvas which is the part of the national curriculum of English, but I have never read something like about critical thinking or something like that, right' (Adam).

However, some participants perceived this as something to be taken for granted when the LMD system was adopted. They argued that although there is no clear evidence that the implementation of critical thinking is supported by policymakers and as such government documents, it is actually among the aspirations of the LMD to promote learners' skills such as autonomy and critical thinking. They added that even the approach which is applied in the LMD system namely, the Competency-based approach, is meant to redirect a great deal of time and effort in the classroom from the teacher to the students dissimilar to the traditional approaches. Hence, students get immersed in the learning process and become active participants rather than passive recipients of knowledge and instructions, or at least theoretically this is -along with other distinctive principles- what the competency-based approach is expected to bring about. On his account, Mustafa stated that:

To my knowledge, I didn't really see a document which mentions critical thinking because we know that the system adopted here is the LMD system, and it is somehow based on the competency-based approach. So, the competency-based approach for instance, is an approach that encourages the development of creative thinking. So, on paper, it does. Well, what's written on paper, we can say that it does, but in reality it does not. In reality, like I said previously, the hindrances, the major problems, because we do not have the means to really incorporate techniques to develop critical thinking.

(Mustafa)

In the same vein, Mia claimed that critical thinking does not seem to be included in any curriculum documents. However, it should be noted that it is mentioned twice in the curricula and the principles of the LMD system emphasise the promotion of students' critical thinking skills and autonomy where the role of the teacher switches from the only provider of knowledge to a facilitator, and where the student becomes the core of the learning process and the one in charge for his/her own learning.

Unfortunately, this remains ink on paper as according to her things get complicated when it comes to practice, she said:

When it comes to the actual practice inside the classroom, this is definitely hard to be done or to be conducted simply because the students still depend on the teacher as the source of information, students are considered just as receivers of knowledge, Ok. They I have noticed that they don't really want to think or to bother themselves even to think about the information.

(Mia)

Djamal agrees with Mia and Mustafa that there might be some interest in the concept informally. That is, critical thinking might be talked about between teachers or in informal meetings, but it is by no means being executed in actual pedagogic practices, and this might be due to a number of challenges which will be discussed later in this chapter (see section 5.3.5). He stated 'probably they say that, probably many, many, many responsible individuals Say that, but into practice! It's a different story, it's a different story' (Djamal). Lina, similarly, highlighted the fact that despite the absence of instruction or guidance in the curriculum documents regarding the development of critical thinking, she believed that this is actually among the outcomes anticipated by the application of the LMD system, she explained:

If we say that the LMD system is encouraging students to work outside the classroom and working outside the classroom means doing research, and the more you do research, the more you feel that you are lost, when you are lost, you try to rearrange and find the way to go out and you feel that you are, we are recommending or asking the students to think critically about what they are doing and what they are learning implicitly.

(Lina)

b. Teacher's responsibility: other participants pointed out that the teacher is mainly the party held accountable for deciding whether or not to incorporate critical thinking in the teaching/learning process 'I believe that it's all up to the teacher, not higher authorities' (Nora). Reem highlighted that they do not receive any communications from the Ministry of Higher Education regarding the implementation of critical thinking neither as a separate subject nor integrated into the different subjects, she added that it all depends on the teacher or group of teachers to design the syllabus, but taking into account the Ministry's general guidelines. She said:

The advantage perhaps at the university level is that it means it is the teacher or the group of teachers who design the syllabus. Ok, when a group of

teachers design the syllabus, and then even when a new teacher comes, he may add, he may adapt it, modify it according to the students.

(Reem)

Omar also agreed that there are no specific objectives communicated from higher authorities, and that it is all up to the teacher to decide what and how to teach, and whether or not to incorporate higher-order thinking skills. Djamal similarly emphasised the role of the teacher in the implementation of critical thinking, and how this topic has been neglected by policymakers, he stated that 'it is the role of the teacher, not only the content, how to present the content, how to make it interesting how to make it useful, and how to promote critical thinking' (Djamal). However, one participant Salim, pointed out that one can guess that the subjects and the courses' headlines of 'a Canva or a syllabus which is presented to you and it comes from the ministry require critical thinking' (Salim). Interpreting a headline though may vary from one teacher to another, and if one teacher guesses from the title of a subject that it requires and encourages promoting critical thinking as an outcome or a tool to fully grasp that subject, other teachers may not guess the same, unless critical thinking was clearly articulated at least in the general objectives. Moreover, It could not go unnoticed that Salim mentioned that 'the Canva or syllabus' is prescribed by the ministry, while other teachers indicated that it is developed by 'the teacher' or 'a group of teachers' and therefore can be adopted as it is, or amended according to the students' needs, abilities, etc. this might imply that the teachers are unsure of the actual source of the curriculum and syllabus, and whether it is designed at the level of the Ministry of Higher Education or the level of the school. In addition to that, since all teachers confessed that there is no explicit mention or instruction about critical thinking in the ministry's general objectives or guidelines, this might be interpreted that critical thinking is not a priority in higher education, and therefore teachers may opt to integrate it in their teaching or not.

5.3.4.2. Critical thinking as an educational objective

The analysis of the data showed that although there seemed to be a consensus among teachers about the lack of focus and guidance on the implementation of critical thinking at the level of the Ministry of Higher Education, most of the participant teachers claimed that when designing their lesson plans, they do consider critical thinking to be among their educational objectives, although some stated that they do not necessarily write it down as a course objective, but they take it into consideration in the classroom. Mia, for example, explained that although the LMD system adopted by the Algerian universities embraces the integration of critical thinking and considers it a vital skill

to be developed in higher education, curriculum designers and documents do not. And this was the reason why Mia did not prioritise critical thinking when setting her educational objectives. She argued though that she takes into account the development of critical thinking implicitly during the lecture using questioning strategies. She stated:

Well, when I design my lesson plan, I don't really give importance to critical thinking, but when I go to the classroom, and when I start teaching, I do really try to raise learners' critical thinking, Okay, this is done via asking questions and getting their responses. So, when I ask questions and get their responses, I try to stimulate their critical thinking, okay, in a kind of debates... I do not perceive it as a priority maybe because of policymakers, they do not emphasise the implementation of critical thinking. Although it is mentioned that critical thinking is very important as a part of the LMD system and it has to be implemented. Here in Algeria, we are teaching based on the LMD system, so it is important to implement, or it is important to encourage students to think critically. Okay, for some other teachers, not me, they try to develop their students' critical thinking based on doing projects, Okay. So, through doing projects they are supposed to solve problems.

(Mia)

Omar also argued that he does take into consideration critical thinking when he plans for his lecture since he teaches methodology and according to him this module requires critical thinking skills more than other modules as students are expected to do research in the future and write up a dissertation to graduate. Another participant, Salim, advocated for considering the development higher-order thinking skills among the classroom objectives, but he believed that this would be more necessary for master's students, he stated:

Yes, especially when I teach master's classes, the nature of the modules already requires let's say a high cognitive load, okay. A high cognitive load is the amount of the theoretical foundations in the module to be taught and the student has to level up with that input, so that divergent or critical thinking will be enacted or activated.

(Salim)

On the other hand, Ali and Nora indicated that it is all depending on the module itself which means that sometimes the nature of the module does not necessitate integrating critical thinking as a classroom objective. Ali explained that in modules related to literature, the objective is usually to deliver the content, whereas in study skills module, for example, the aim is to develop students' different skills along with critical thinking but in an implicit way. He said:

Well, when it comes, for example, to teaching in literature, I focus more on the content of the literary materials, but with study skills, it is like it is an objective because I aim to provide my students with the needed, let's say, information through which I guide them to prove their skills, self-management skills, time management skills, and even communication skills and critical thinking is related, It is implied.

(Ali)

Reem's answer did not differ from others, she stated that even though she does not set critical thinking as an objective nor prepare to develop it in advance, she feels that it is integrated into her teaching spontaneously as the ultimate goal of the course according to her is to develop future teachers, and as such critical thinking without doubt is needed. Adam, Mustafa, and Lina admitted that although they think that introducing critical thinking as an educational objective is of great importance, it is not always convenient to achieve this goal.

5.3.5. Factors affecting the development of critical thinking in EFL university students

The analysis of the findings regarding the challenges perceived by teachers as impediments to the development of critical thinking revealed the following five six themes: pedagogical factors, contextual factors, curriculum-related factors, student-related factors, teacher-related factors, and sociocultural factors. The participants highlighted several issues under each category as shown in the table below.

Table 1: Participants' perceptions of the factors that influence students' critical thinking development

Pedagogical factors	-Teaching approach -Focus on language skills
Contextual factors	-Class size -Teacher's training -Time constraints/length of syllabuses
Curriculum-related factors	-The system's marginalisation of Critical thinking.

Student-related factors	-Students' Motivation and interest -Language proficiency/student level -Focus on exams
Teacher-related factors	-Lack of knowledge -Assessment -Negative feedback
Socio-cultural factors	-Obedience to authority -Lack of Confidence

5.3.5.1. Pedagogical factors

The pedagogical factors perceived by the participants include *the teaching approach and the focus on language skills*.

a. Teaching approach: one of the challenges that most teachers admitted having a significant impact on the cultivation of critical thinking in EFL classes is the dominance of the exam-centric education or what is called the teach-to-test approach. They seemed to be aware that this approach of preparing students for examination does not promote students' thinking but rather encourages rote learning. This approach in the Algerian context is a consequence of years of prioritising good scoring at all educational levels, rewarding the reproduction of knowledge, and thus encouraging memorisation. Salim, for example, considered the application of this approach as the major problem in education in Algeria, he stated that:

This issue is striking really, and the fact of giving knowledge or conveying knowledge to the student for the sake of, of reproduction. And reproduction here is just done by learning by heart, the students just learn by heart without making sense of the knowledge that they learn...this is the big problem here in the Algerian educational system.

(Salim)

Similarly, Lina shared her concern explaining that even classroom activities are used mainly to grade students, thus students act accordingly. To demonstrate this point, she claimed that when she uses presentations as tasks to evaluate the students on their work inside the classroom, other students who are not part of the group presenting show no interest because they are aware that they are not

being assessed but rather the members that are presenting, she added that even when they are asked to ask questions to open up a discussion, they just refrain from participating. This implies that each group just prepare the topics assigned to them without bothering themselves to check others' topics to at least be able to follow in the classroom, this indicates again that the ultimate focus in classrooms is on grades. Lina further explained:

When we ask the students to ask questions about that presentation, they refuse to ask the questions, so I end up asking the questions myself, and when I ask the questions, students take it personally, I said, forget about the mark, and let's learn, no, you are asking us because we are the group who presented well, they, we do not have that culture of learning the information that we may not use it here in class, but we use it after 20 years.

(Lina)

This lack of student interest in peer feedback can be linked to the teach-to-the-test approach for several reasons. First, when teaching is heavily focused on exam preparation, activities that are not directly assessed, like peer feedback, may be perceived by students as less valuable. This perception can lead to disengagement, as students prioritise tasks that are explicitly linked to their grades. The lack of familiarity with peer feedback, could also contribute to this disengagement. In the Algerian educational context, particularly prior to higher education, peer feedback might not be a common practice. As a result, students may not be accustomed to its use or understand its value, which further contributes to their lack of interest.

In his account Adam raised an interesting point, he argued that because the exam-centric teaching approach has been deeply rooted in the educational system, students believe that reproducing the exact information they were given is what good learning means. As such, recalling information as it is and being unproductive and voiceless would seem acceptable if not appropriate following this approach. Adam said:

I will tell you something very important, students do that on purpose, because they believe that what a good mark, they believe that some teachers want them to copy paste what they have taught them in the classroom based on their discussion with students, etc. Right, so this is one thing that pushed them not to think critically... So, I think that those tests, which do not engage students in that critical thinking mode are really unproductive. Right, so usually, the test pushes the students to think in a non-creative, non-critical way.

(Adam)

b. *Focus on language skills*: According to Ali, another problem that accompanies the exam-centric approach in the teaching of English at university is the focus on teaching the language itself. This implies that teachers tend to transmit all aspects of the language, but they neglect the ultimate goal that every university across the globe aims at: to teach the students *how* to think critically about the knowledge they receive and not only *what* to think about. Ali argued ‘...we still struggle in Algeria, officially speaking, we don't talk about critical thinking as our focus, we still focus just on language learning and teaching, how to make students learn the language not to think critically’ (Ali). Omar shared a similar view:

They focus on mostly on basic language skills, from one part, and on the content of the different modules that they are teaching. Okay, so they focus on information, delivering information to the learners and getting that information back in exams and tests. Yes, I believe that they focus on language skills, like grammar, etc.

(Omar)

Djamal also perceived the focus on the content and the four skills as one of the factors affecting the teaching of critical thinking, he stated ‘...unfortunately, it's not the thing we focus on. I mean, we should, but we are limited by other factors, the other skills and content’ (Djamal).

5.3.5.2. Contextual factors

The various contextual factors the participants referred to were grouped into the following three categories: *class size, teacher's training, time constraints/length of syllabuses*.

a. *Class size*: six participants perceived large class size as one of the major issues that hinder the promotion of critical thinking. Ali, for example, related the large number of students to the classroom layout. He expressed his dislike to the traditional classroom arrangement, but given the number of students, circle or U-shape sitting would not be possible. Reem, similarly, believes that teaching a large class size makes it very difficult if not possible to ensure that all students are engaged in any activity let alone an activity which targets students' criticality. In support of this claim, Adam and Mia stated:

Really the number of students, right, the number. So, yeah, I may, for example, design activities, which can engage students in a critical thinking or critical thinking mode, but when I want to put into practice, it is so difficult to get all students engaged in this in this critical thinking, right. So, the number of students is, we have problem with this one right.

(Adam)

Because of the large number of students in each group, it would be very hard for the teacher to organise activities about critical thinking, you try to imagine a classroom of or a classroom which is made up of up to 40 students, how are you going as a teacher, how are you going to control or how are you going to involve all of them in activities, or in problem solving activities?

(Mia)

Interestingly, Lina noted that dealing with a great number of students does not allow her to evaluate the students based on their ability to think critically about the information, assess it, or solve complicated problems. She asserted that:

One of the problems in implementing critical thinking is the number of the students because as I said for the presentations, we just give the opportunity to just to evaluate it is not a presentation to evaluate the students of what they are saying, if we are really doing a critical thinking, we will ask the students to think and to reflect his way of thinking about what he presented, but vis a vis, the number of the students, we are going to give four students 20 minutes, every student 5 minutes, we cannot see that the students have read the article or had done research, and he can present the information.

(Lina)

According to the statements above, there appear to be two implications. First, the issue of large class size can affect teachers' selection of the types of activities as some activities require a small number of students to be executed during the time set for a session, and too many students require a lot of time. Second, the criteria of evaluation might also be determined by the number of students, a relatively small number of students allows teachers to pay close attention to more complex skills.

b. Teachers' training: five participants believed that for teachers to be able to develop critical thinking in students, they need first to gain knowledge about it and how it can be put into practice. Thus, according to them, teachers should receive training during their careers to be able to provide the best learning experience to their students. Djamal explained the importance of teachers' training by noting that some people get their degrees in fields that have nothing to do with teaching, yet find themselves in a teaching career, he stated:

We speak about teachers' training, I mean, you know, that when you finish your study, you finish your degree, Magister, or doctorate you can be appointed to a teaching position, but some people have been trained in educational psychology, some in topics of critical thinking, and some people have done something that is completely different, literature and civilization,

they don't have a background in teaching. And even any, any training that is done at the level of the university, it is a matter of formality.

(Djamal)

This means that to teach students how to think critically, teachers need to be critical thinkers themselves, they need to model it to their students first to instill it in them, and to manifest its importance.

c. Time constraints/ length of syllabus: some teachers view time as one of the serious challenges if they consider integrating critical thinking as according to them there is a syllabus that needs to be covered in the academic year. However, if teachers focus on skills that require time and effort to prepare and execute, they would fail to cover the content. Djamal although appearing to be aware that teachers are required to cover the syllabus content in the allocated time, he believed that this should not be the priority, particularly at the university level, He explained:

Once we start working with that on our learners, and once they start to think critically, we do not need to worry about the content we need, we do not need to worry about syllabus, we do not need to worry about if I am going to finish or not. Just teach them to think critically and give them the lessons. They will do the work themselves. Yeah. And you can intervene occasionally. So, teach them the skill first, of thinking critically of thinking of analysing.

(Djamal)

Ali admitted that he recently tended more to adopt teacher-centred approaches to be able to deliver the prescribed content. He pointed out that before the pandemic, his teaching approach was task-based where he used to try to create an interactive environment for learning. This according to him was affected by the Covid-19 circumstances and the new administrative arrangements where the number of teaching hours was reduced. He stated that ‘...because of the pandemic, you know, we rely on the teacher-centred approach more, because we are short of time, and we need to cover lots of materials’ (Ali).

5.3.5.3. Curriculum-related factors

The system's marginalisation of Critical thinking: some participants attributed ‘the real situation of the poor critical thinking in Algeria’ as described by Lina to the educational system as the primary factor hindering critical thinking. They seemed to believe that teachers and even students should not be held accountable for the current educational issues as they were brought up in a system where rote learning and recall dominated, and where success was related to good scoring. The

system though proved to be successful in achieving its basic aims but missed the major aim of education to produce a future citizen capable of facing modern life challenges. Omar agreed on this stating that ‘this system in general does not promote life skills. It is all about having greater rates of success among students, but teaching students how to be critical is not really part of the agenda’.

Other participants like Adam and Mia believed that the reason why critical thinking has not been seriously taken into consideration by teachers is the absence of explicit instruction from higher authorities. Mia claimed that ‘there is no official document given to the teachers, official documents written or issued by the ministry, ok, and given to the teachers to indicate that raising or improving learners’ critical thinking is a must’. Adam also viewed the system as encouraging to memorisation, inhibiting to productivity. He stated:

I think it is not productive at all, right, it is not productive at all. Like, you have to memorise some stuff, and then you know, I'm going to tell you something which is so important: there is no explicit policies that we have to teach critical thinking in any in any, I would say, in any field in any speciality.

(Adam)

5.3.5.4. Student-related factors

The student-related factors the participants mentioned involved: *students’ motivation and interest, focus on exams, language proficiency/student level, and lack of confidence.*

a. Students’ Motivation and interest: four participants referred to two types of motivation believed to be affecting students’ critical thinking development: intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Two participants shared an interesting idea, they argued that students might lose interest and motivation when they get challenged with activities that stimulate higher-order thinking skills. Ali stated that if he would attempt to give students activities that require them to think critically, only a few students would be willing to participate ‘for example if you have 30 students, you can find like 15 or more students that are not interested in this, this kind of activities’ (Ali). Mustafa highlighted that students tend to resist making efforts in the learning process, they would prefer ready-made information instead of searching, analysing, evaluating, and then coming up with an authentic product, he said:

Students’ lethargy, they are indifferent, they do not want to work, even if you give them ,for instance, a project work that would require the engagement of higher-order thinking skills, they resist, they would just go and copy and paste things from the internet. Sometimes we encourage them,

we tell them that we want your own product, something you do yourself, it does not have to be perfect, it has to be yours, so that you would develop through time, but they resist, unfortunately.

(Mustafa)

On his account, Salim proposed that the absence of digital technology learning environments which engage students in interactive activities can hamper the development of critical thinking, he stated that:

Low motivation, ok, Lack of extrinsic, let's say, extrinsic motivation or equipment, such as language labs, and an interactive, let's say, learning strategies so that the student will break that boredom in the classroom, and so would the teacher, ok. So, this is what I think I think that there must be equipment that must be special logistics that will, let's say at least help in the, in the teaching of critical thinking.

(Salim)

Interactive activities might indeed promote students' engagement and performance in the classroom by stimulating their interest and participation. It might also help students to activate and apply their knowledge, question, analyse, solve problems, and thus be more active and responsible for their own learning, which might not be the case using conventional lesson materials.

b. Focus on exams: some participants regarded students' obsession with grades as one of the major hindrances to the development of critical thinking. They seemed to perceive students' attitudes towards scoring well as the reason behind the lack of criticality, and not a consequence of an educational system or a teaching approach. According to Ali, students go to schools with a purpose in mind, and this purpose does not include building knowledge and developing thinking 'the student has only the exam in mind, not to understand, they came here prepared like am here to score, it is a paradigm' (Ali), he actually added that sometimes when they discuss a relatively complex topic, students tend to ask whether they might have that as an exam question. Mia shared a similar view 'the first reason is that the students' passion towards grades only, instead of giving importance to the knowledge they gain'. Djamel explained that students' thinking, willingness and openness to learning are the major factors responsible for hindering or promoting higher-order thinking skills. Even when he tends to encourage them to focus on themselves, exams seem to be the only concern they care about. This indicates a notably uncritical attitude, suggesting that students have been conditioned to memorise and reproduce information for tests and exams. Therefore, constructing

their own knowledge appears daunting. This is possibly attributed to a curriculum that does not encourage the cultivation of critical thinking. Djamal gave an example:

I finished the curriculum today, I finished the content of the course with my students, and I suggested something: I told them, what if I asked them a question to summarise to recapitulate the whole semester and I told them what if I give this question as an exam question, the majority of them said no because it was an analytical question. They did not have the answer in the handouts. They have certain things, but the conclusion should be their own based on what I told them, they refused, you know and they asked about the exam type of question, are we going to have an essay? It is the exam and not nothing else. Despite the fact that we speak about other things, the doctoral entry exam requires you to write an essay to be critical to be analytical, to synthesise, etc., but no, they just study for the exam.

(Djamal)

c. Language proficiency/student level: most of the participants associated students' language proficiency and their linguistic and cognitive abilities with critical thinking. Their notions appeared to regard high-achievers as more likely to embrace and practice critical thinking whereas low-achievers or as Reem and Lina called them 'poor students' are deemed incapable of practising criticality. Reem explained that given students' abilities in the English language, she does not expect her students to engage in critical thinking at all. She believes that they are at the bottom of the learning process in Bloom's taxonomy, she stated that:

Sometimes, the students' level itself sometimes I mean, we have, let's say, poor students, I mean, that we cannot develop it, a student who is unable to write, let's say, a correct or coherent paragraph, you cannot expect him to think critically, that is it, it is sometimes we are in Bloom's taxonomy, we are still in a bit of a knowledge and comprehension, perhaps application, but not synthesis or analysis or evaluation. So, we are still in the lower level of thinking skills.

(Reem)

It should be noted though that a low level in English language could be a barrier for students to get engaged in critical thinking activities by affecting their ability to convey ideas properly, but this does not reflect a dearth in their thinking processes.

Ali, also, explained that given the students' high dependence on the teacher, their level, and unwillingness to read, he always finds himself obliged to do the work for them, hence 'instead of making connections, interpretations, and try to address issues of critical thinking, I focus on

delivering the summary of the novel, and then I summarise themes, symbols, motifs' (Ali). In a similar vein, Lina believes that students' level plays an important role in the possibility of fostering critical thinking as according to her one cannot always get 'the best students', and therefore when asking questions, she tends to be considerate to that. Again, Lina seemed to believe that introducing critical thinking is appropriate only for high-achievers. She explained:

...We need also not to neglect the poor students. So for that reason, there are different parts for the questions, when we ask them about something that they need to think, they do not accept it, they say, 'ask direct question'. And this is the reason I said they have the information but they didn't build knowledge with information. So, if you say, if you present it on a yellow paper, they recognise it, you put it on a black paper, they say it is completely different. I always believe ending up with two people is much, much much better than nothing.

(Lina)

Adam also expressed that one of the reasons why critical thinking is not being embraced by teachers is 'the level, academic level of our students is not that good, I mean, at least most of them' (Adam).

5.3.5.5. Teacher-related factors

The teacher-related factors the participants mentioned fell into the following four categories: *lack of knowledge, assessment, negative feedback*.

a. Lack of knowledge: four participants pointed out that teachers' lack of knowledge about critical thinking and most importantly about its application in the classroom, and their lack of awareness about the significance of its integration could be the reason critical thinking has been overlooked in the Algerian EFL classes. Mia, for example, suggested that teachers are reluctant to change, they still follow the traditional teaching approaches with the same educational objective in mind that is to transmit knowledge and prepare students for exams 'the teachers as well need to forget about the traditional way, they have to change the traditional way of teaching. We are teaching under the LMD system, we have to depend more on active pedagogy' (Mia). Another participant, Lina also highlighted that teachers could only have heard about the concept of critical thinking in a general sense, but most teachers do not have a deep understanding of it:

Not all the teachers are aware, not all of the teachers have updated the information about it, not all the teachers have the detailed information, they may have some generalities, but they do not have, how to use the task or how a normal task can be turned to critical thinking task.

(Lina)

And here comes the role of teachers' training in raising awareness of the necessity to adapt new teaching approaches and strategies, rethinking the dynamics of the teaching/learning process, redirecting the focus towards skills that are needed to keep up with the challenges of the modern world. Although emphasising the importance of the teachers' training particularly for inexperienced teachers, Djamal noted that in most cases the university training is merely 'a matter of formality', and teachers should work on themselves to be able to provide the best learning experience. In addition to that, it is worth noting that if a teacher lacks criticality, there is a high chance that his/her students might tend to mimic their behaviour particularly given the large dependency of students on the teacher.

b. Assessment: three participants admitted that when evaluating students' work, they tend to focus on the basic skills which are usually the major concern in language classes. Lina, for example, expressed that time is very limited to assess complex aspects like critical thinking, besides the number of students is large, and it is very difficult for her to assess each single student. Giving little attention or no attention at all to the assessment of students' thinking might lead the students to think that aspects like criticality do not matter, and therefore devote their time to memorising and recalling. Additionally, two participants believed that the teacher's responsibility to cover the whole syllabus during an academic semester affects critical thinking instruction. This indicates that teachers prioritise completing the content to prepare students adequately for assessment (exams) over working on improving students' thinking because they view the development of critical thinking as time and effort-consuming. Ali added that the nature of the module also might not facilitate the infusion of critical thinking 'sometimes, the restriction of the module, because the nature of the module sometimes doesn't give you a chance to teach everything' (Salim).

c. Negative feedback: one participant stated that the cultivation of critical thinking cannot take place if the teacher's personality tends to be dominant in many aspects in the classroom. Omar argued:

the subjectivity of the teacher and his teacher-centeredness in teaching in terms of the content, in terms of the methodology, in terms of many things, so the teacher who focuses on, I mean, on the way you, you treat the answers and the way you give feedback, all can be a hindrance, if you focus on your own point of view as a teacher and you dismiss or disregard learners' points of view and the way they challenge your ideas the way they think, their creativity in answering even if it is false, even if it is false, we have to encourage.

(Omar)

To develop thinking skills, teachers need to create a safe free environment for students to allow them to air their opinions, and to challenge the knowledge they receive. Giving the students the opportunity to express their views, criticise and explore ideas in an unthreatening supportive atmosphere would help the students to develop their criticality.

5.3.5.6. Socio-cultural factors

One participant argued that there are socio-cultural factors that affect the cultivation of critical thinking in students. Adam suggested that this issue runs deep in society and particularly in families where children are raised to be respectful and submissive to people in authority like parents and teachers. Growing up in a society that values conformity to authority results in individuals who do not appreciate voicing opinions, challenging ideas, and disagreeing with authority:

Sometimes even from home. I mean, children, they are socialised not to disagree with anyone, especially those authority. I mean, be they parents, their peers, or even their teachers in the classroom. Right, so it is something which is not only educational, but like social, maybe social...because at home, they are afraid if a child disagrees with his parents, he will be penalised, he will keep up with the same theme that goes to the classroom. So, he would think that if I disagree with my teacher, if I critically discuss my ideas, if I disagree with him, that he may or there is a high likelihood that he may be penalised, maybe, form bad opinion about me. So, there is this kind of I am afraid to disagree, I am afraid to be critical.

(Adam)

Lina raised an interesting point about learning and retaining information only to be used for a short-term purpose and then clearing the slate, for example: submissions or passing tests. Lina stated 'Because here in Algeria, we always have the tendency to wipe once we finish, we submit, we completely ignore that stage of reading. From the draft to submission, always the first draft is the final product we submit'. This could imply that it might be a cultural phenomenon that is also promoted by the educational system to prioritise the product over the process, which means what matters most is the completion of the task, whereas how or what tools and skills the student uses to come up with the product are neglected.

Adam mentioned that students tend to be afraid to voice their opinions in the sense that they perceive the knowledge that was spoon-fed to them as the ultimate truth that should be taken for granted, he stated:

So, they are always afraid to think critically about these pre-conceived already existing ideas...I mean usually I feel that my students are afraid to voice their opinions, they think themselves as unable or they don't have the right to critically discuss anything.

(Adam)

He noted also that students believe that reproducing the exact knowledge received by teachers in class is the right and appropriate thing to do which eventually discourages them from thinking critically. If students think they get rewarded for memorising and regurgitating knowledge as it is in exams, and for accepting everything to be true without trying to analyse or seeking evidence and disagreeing if some information lacks enough evidence for instance, then one must consider that students might act in that particular way as a result of their experiences throughout all the schools years, and their behaviours might have been shaped based on the environment's, schools' and teachers' expectations.

Another participant also believed that this teaching approach is imposed by society in the first place, and this can be clearly reflected by the widespread of private lessons at all educational levels. In these private lessons, teachers prepare students for exams by practising a great number of tasks and questions which are expected to be part of exams. Indeed, students observing the efforts made and resources provided by their parents to achieve the best results by practising expected exam questions might instil in them the idea that good learning equals good marks, which might inhibit the development of critical thinking skills.

5.4. Critical thinking pedagogical practices of Algerian EFL university teachers

This section addresses the last research question which aims to investigate teachers' actual educational practices in the classroom in relation to the development of critical thinking. Data from 10 classroom observations were gathered and analysed to answer the last research question and also to cross-check the findings from the interviews. I used field notes to collect data from the observation sessions. My field notes were not focused only on the teachers' pedagogical practices; I tried to observe all that could possibly be observed in the classroom to provide a clear picture of the situation. The field notes then were analysed and organised based on their significance and relevance to the study. It should be noted that this was a one-time observation for each participant, therefore, repeating this study using multiple observations may yield different results. All the observation sessions' field notes were summarised and coded, patterns were identified and then organised into themes. The main findings which emerged from the observations were centred on

the following themes: teaching approach, classroom physical environment, Students' classroom behaviours, and classroom activities. These are presented below.

5.4.1. Teaching approach

The teaching approach that largely dominated the class time is teacher-centred. Teachers were the sole source of information in the classroom, and students were mainly listening and taking notes. Although I entered the field with a pre-constructed knowledge of how things work in the department based on my experience as a former student, I was mindful of my familiarity with the context in that I did not take any aspect of this research for granted, and I tried to 'make the familiar strange' (Mercer, 2007) to avoid potential researcher bias or reaching premature conclusions. When I was a student there, teachers used to leave handouts and lessons in a stationery store located near the University for students to make photocopies. In the period just before exams, particularly, this stationery store becomes crowded by students who want to make photocopies to the point that one cannot pass through. However, I did not want to take my experience as the ultimate reality as things might change over time. I tried to investigate this with some students in informal discussions after some of the classroom observations. It appeared that this was still happening, and teachers would either leave lessons in the stationary or send them via the department platform. Consequently, students receive ready-made knowledge in two ways: note-taking during teachers' lecturing, and handouts prepared by teachers.

Most of the participant teachers started their sessions by asking the students to provide a recap of the previous lecture, but then they ended up doing the recap themselves when faced with total silence by students. The students' inability to provide a review of the previous lesson might indicate that the students take notes only to review them when they anticipate a test. This was also maintained by Mustafa when he noticed that the students were unresponsive 'you don't seem that you are revising your lectures, you have to revise your lectures, you have a test next week' (Mustafa). Even during the class, and although teachers tended to encourage students to participate when they asked display questions or referential questions (the latter were very few as most questions were just to check the students' understanding), one or two students only would respond, if any. Teachers in most cases would provide the answers themselves, or would call on names randomly from the students' list to answer. When students were given opportunities to ask questions, they would ask for more clarification about what they did not understand from the teacher's explanation. For instance, in Mustafa's session, students were allowed some time at the end of the session to review their notes and think of any questions they might have, meanwhile, the teacher left the class. As he

came back, one student had some points that he did not understand, Mustafa explained them and gave examples, he did not allow other students to think about those questions, nor did he give them the opportunity to answer or discuss them. However, this might be attributed to the shortage of time. Another student even asked the teacher to check the accuracy of the notes she took during the lecture. Overall, no challenging or thought-provoking questions were asked from both sides.

Teacher/student rapport seemed good, there was some sense of humour in some sessions, and teachers tended to encourage the students to participate, and provided them with positive feedback when they did. However, there were some instances where the teacher's authoritative character came into play. For example, more than half an hour was wasted at the beginning of Mia's session: first, because she was late 15 minutes, and second because students did not print and bring with them the handouts related to the topic of the lecture as advised. The teacher was angry and yelling at students. One of the students suggested that they have the lecture on their phones, but the teacher insisted that they should have printed the lectures and that they were not allowed to use their phones. The teacher ended up asking one of the students to print the lecture for the whole class which took him a considerable time given the relatively large number of students. The classroom atmosphere appeared somewhat uncomfortable, and the students seemed less motivated, inattentive, and uninterested. The learning environment did not seem particularly conducive on various levels, potentially making the development of higher-order thinking skills more challenging. Another incident which took place in Djamal's session, although his attitude seemed very friendly and kind throughout the session, there was one moment when he asked the students to read summaries he assigned them to write, one student for some reason found difficulty to read her own handwriting, the teacher's reaction was intense and as the student tried to interrupt perhaps to explain, the teacher said 'do not speak, when I speak you listen!'. This was an awkward reaction in which I felt very uncomfortable and I was just an observer. This incident actually may have affected that student's confidence to speak in class again. However, apart from this incident which represented the teacher as a highly authoritative figure, the lecture was not monotonous and the students were active to some extent compared to the other sessions that I observed.

Obsession with examination appeared in many instances during the sessions observed. Students seemed extrinsically motivated to learn for the sake of filling out the exam sheets and getting good marks. Similarly, teachers seemed to value examination-driven education by helping the students to absorb as much knowledge as possible without having to go deep and think critically about what they are learning, limiting the entire learning/teaching experience to preparing students for exams.

This actually was prevalent when teachers designed classroom activities for the sole purpose of grading the students. As explained earlier in section 1, each module has an exam and a TD mark, TD is an acronym for the French word *travail dirigé* which means continuous evaluation of students' work in the class. In the classroom activities that I witnessed, teachers would generally hold a list of students' names, and as a student finishes the task he/she was assigned to, the teacher would ask for the student's name, provide minimum feedback such as: 'very good' or 'you can do better', and then would write down the grade. At the beginning of Omar's session, for example, two students from another group approached the teacher and asked for his permission to attend and present in the last 20 minutes as they were absent in their session which was the last of the semester. Knowing that part of the continuous evaluation grade is based on presentations, those students had to take from the time devoted to another group, presented very quickly, and mainly read from the slides just for the sake of getting a grade. When the students finished their presentation, the teacher was holding the students' list, he asked for their names and seemed to grade them. There were no comments or questions or any discussion from either the teacher or the students. Similarly, Salim asked his students by the end of the session to read the reports which were assigned as homework. The students were reading their reports one by one in their places, the teacher gave some very brief feedback that did not seem quite effective or constructive, such as: 'good', and then he asked for their names to grade them. I noticed that many students were not interested in each other's reports, as they did not seem to listen attentively, instead, they were either chatting or preparing themselves to read their own reports, and some were using their phones. The teacher did not initiate discussion, neither did he invite other students to give feedback or comments. Mia, also, emphasised the importance of grades, she advised her students that she would send them a number of activities to do at home which will be part of their TD mark. When I attended Adam's session, it started as observed in the other sessions that I attended with a review of the previous session, the teacher then moved to the new lecture, he was lecturing and the students were taking notes. As we reached the mid-session, the teacher started a revision to the lectures of the whole semester, in most cases he asked questions then impatiently jumped to providing answers, he also dictated to the students the topics which would not be in the exam and explained how the TD mark will be calculated. Adam advised that the next session will be dedicated to further revision and activities to prepare for the exam. Mustafa, also, advised his students that they should revise their lectures as they were expected to have a test in the following week. The teacher provided this advice probably because the students were not responsive when he tried to review the previous lecture and commented 'you

are not revising your lectures!'. This value for examination was also manifested by students in many incidents when they asked about the date on which they would have a test, and whether what they were learning in a particular session would be tested in the exam. In Djamel's session, for example, a student asked about the test in the first session of the semester, the teacher was astonished and said that 'it is literally the beginning of the semester and you started to worry about the test?', it was mentioned many times in the interviews data that grades are all that matter to the students.

5.4.2. Classroom physical environment

The classroom seating arrangement in most of the sessions that I observed was in the traditional format. Students were sitting in rows next to each other in rectangle tables and mobile chairs, facing the whiteboard with their backs to one another, and with a small space between rows to pass through. Three sessions of the observed classes were held in an auditorium. Ali mentioned this issue in the interview and expressed his dislike for this seating arrangement, which actually might seem determined by the large number of students. Although the traditional seating arrangement seemed useful in accommodating all students, it had many shortcomings. It was difficult for the teacher to move around the classroom, particularly in group work activities. If a teacher intended to check the students' progress in a group work, students would move to clear the way for him/her to pass through, which resulted in some noise and distraction to the students. The Classroom interaction also seemed to be affected by such seating, on many occasions students in the back rows seemed disconnected from the rest of the class. Students in the front rows seemed to be to some extent more attentive. This seating arrangement seems compatible with the teacher-centred approach as it puts the students in a position of listening while the teacher presents information. Thus, it discourages discussion between the students, and results in uneven distribution of interaction in the classroom.

One of the things that caught my attention as well was the rooms' temperature. In almost all the sessions that I attended classrooms were very cold, students were sitting with their coats on. This might distract the students from their learning, and affect their academic performance.

Some of the sessions that I observed took place in an auditorium, the number of students was small compared to the vast space of the room. This actually caused an issue in hearing the teacher well. I could barely hear what the teacher was saying, particularly when the teacher sat at his desk lecturing instead of moving on stage.

It was expected that since the lecture was held in the auditorium, there should be some facilities such as an LCD projector, screen, and an audio system which would help the voice to be distributed

in the room. However, in the three sessions that I attended, only a whiteboard was available. Salim, for example, used the whiteboard and his personal computer to deliver the lecture. He sat at the desk reading from his personal computer, sometimes making eye contact with the students and explaining, sometimes standing up to write an important idea or an example on the board. As explained earlier, on many occasions I found difficulty in hearing the teacher, which might be the case for some students who were not sitting in the first rows. Students did not seem engaged with the teacher, probably because he was mainly sitting and using his personal computer, his interaction with the students was restricted mainly to asking them if they had any questions, or needed a further explanation on any point. Later, the teacher advised that he would send the students the PowerPoint presentation he used in the lecture. This, actually, leads us to tackle an important aspect of the classroom which is the teaching materials.

The only teaching materials that teachers seemed to employ in the observed classes are: the whiteboard and handouts. Computer-assisted learning, audio-visual aids, and language laboratory are teaching and learning materials which are expected to keep the students engaged, and active, challenge them, and create a joyful learning atmosphere. These, however, were not available in the sessions that I observed. Data show was used in two sessions by students in their presentations. Most teachers used some papers which helped them in their lectures. Mia, for instance, in her written expression session was using papers to guide her lecture which was about comparison and contrast essays. At the end of the session, the teacher advised that she would send the students a list of conjunctions which they may use when writing a comparative and contrast essay.

5.4.3. Students' classroom behaviours

From what I observed in the classes that I attended, students were generally well-behaved, and there were no crucial issues. However, I noticed some disruptive behaviours which occurred from time to time like chatting with their peers while the teacher was lecturing, using their phones under the tables, arriving late, and not doing what teachers expect them to do. Another striking behaviour that I noticed on many occasions is the students' reticence and lack of motivation which was manifested in a notable absence of nods, a lack of raised hands for questions, and limited participation, observed in only few students. These behaviours might not seem to have a direct impact on the development of critical thinking, however, if happening repeatedly, this might affect the learning process, and divert the students' attention from the primary purpose of attending classes. It might also affect the teacher-student relationship, thereby indirectly impeding the development of higher-order thinking skills. The teacher-student relationship is crucial for fostering higher-order thinking skills as a

positive and supportive relationship creates an environment where students feel comfortable and motivated to engage deeply with the material, and to freely express their opinions. When students are disruptive, inattentive, or unmotivated, it can strain this relationship, making it difficult for teachers to foster an interactive and engaging classroom atmosphere. In such an environment, students may be less likely to ask questions, participate in discussions, or take intellectual risks, all of which are essential for developing critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills. Conversely, a strong teacher-student relationship, characterised by mutual respect and engagement, encourages students to think more deeply, participate actively, and apply higher-order thinking in their learning processes.

In Lina's session, which was held in an auditorium, very few students were actually paying attention to the teacher, these were mainly first-row students who were taking notes while the teacher was explaining. A group of students were having a test at the back because they missed it, some students sitting in front of me were chatting and scrolling in their phones. When the teacher gives her back to the students to write something on the board, the noise would even get louder. The teacher seemed to ignore such behaviours, this is probably because she did not view this as a major distracting factor to the learning/teaching process, or she was committed to cover the lecture in the allocated time, therefore paying attention to such behaviours might be a waste of time.

The majority of students were noticeably silent in the sessions that I attended, the classroom participation was usually dominated by two or three students. Mia, in her written expression session, for instance, seemed to be affected by my presence as she asked the students about what it means by critical thinking and why it is important, students were completely silent, she kept encouraging them to give ideas as she said that they discussed that the other day, but the students were still unresponsive. The teacher then was obliged to move on and re-explain the concept again and how this is related to the topic of the lecture. It is important to note though that this reactive effect was experienced only once in Mia's session, and only in the incidence described above.

The silence and lack of motivation to participate was a pattern in almost all the attended sessions. In Reem's session, students were expected to comment or ask questions after a group presentation, however, this did not happen which led the teacher to call on names to share their opinions. A similar act took place in Nora's session as an attempt to sort out the issue of students' reticence. In her research seminar session which was a module for master's students to discuss the progress of their dissertation writing, each student was supposed to talk about his/her topic in front of the class, and given that students were reluctant to discuss their topics after every single presentation, the teacher

then opted for an option which seemed to motivate the students to comment and give feedback about each other's work, she took the students' names list, and whenever a student participates, she would add a mark next to his/her name which then with the presence would make their TD mark (the grade for the student's work in the classroom), those who do not participate are deemed to have very low grades. The teacher, then, seemed to use grades as an extrinsic motivation to push the students to interact in the classroom. This, actually, seemed to work as many students were participating either by providing a suggestion, a question, or feedback about the topic as a whole.

5.4.4. Classroom activities

The main activity which dominated the observed classes was lecturing. Most of the class time, if not all, was devoted to delivering knowledge by the teacher in a unidirectional way. Students' role in the classroom was typically listening to the teacher and taking notes. The attended classes included various courses, such as linguistics, study skills, sociolinguistics, research methodology, written expression, etc. Therefore, in addition to the teacher's lecturing, there were some types of activities: individual work, pair/group work, presentations, and questioning. These were not necessarily developing to the students' criticality and were only performed in some classes. That is, these activities were not frequent and were not taking much of the lecturing time. Each activity was witnessed only one time, apart from questioning. Some of the observed sessions did not involve any activity.

The following are examples of these activities which I related to Bloom's revised taxonomy (2001) of the cognitive domain to assess the level of learning these activities actually target, and their association with the development of critical thinking.

5.4.4.1. Individual work

The only individual work that I witnessed in the observed classes was in the form of a written assignment. The students were required to write a report as homework about their experiences with children with learning difficulties. When they came to the classroom, they were required to read their reports to the whole class in their places. The students read their reports one by one. However, I noticed that there was clearly no attention among the students about each other's reports, and no interaction or peer feedback afterwards. And apparently, they were not encouraged by the teacher to do so. Each student read his/her topic, the teacher would then ask about the student's name to write down the grade. Meanwhile, other students held their reports and appeared to be preparing themselves for their turns. When all students finished reading their reports and were graded, the teacher then asked the students to prepare another task for the next session. They were asked to

write an 'introspective' report expressing their views about the different accents in Algeria, and whether or not their views changed after the lecture they had that day.

In these writing activities, the students' cognitions were expected to be stimulated to reflect on their own experiences, reflect on the information they received in the lecture, and put that in the form of a report. Therefore according to Bloom's revised taxonomy (2001), students were asked to recall the types of learning difficulties they learned about in the lecture (remembering), identify and explain an experience they have been through (understanding), demonstrate their understanding by using their knowledge and draw connections to their experiences (applying and analysing), reflect on their experiences and evaluate the way they dealt with that family member who suffered a learning difficulty (evaluating), create the report and generate new ways on how individuals with learning difficulties should be treated (creating). Given that analysing, referring, and creating are aspects which constitute the process of critical thinking, if this activity was executed as planned without resorting to copying from the internet as some teachers complained when interviewed, this activity could actually be claimed to be developing to the students' critical thinking. Given that analysing, referring, and creating are essential aspects of critical thinking, this activity could indeed foster students' critical thinking skills if executed as planned. However, some teachers complained during interviews that students often resorted to copying from the internet, which undermines the activity's potential to develop these skills.

5.4.4.2. Pair/group work

From the observed sessions, pair work and group work were used once in Djamel's session and Ali's session, respectively. Before having the students do an activity in a pair work, Djamel explained well the lecture which was about taking notes, paraphrasing, quoting, and summarising. He gave them the following example about paraphrasing:

Extract:

A. there has been much debate about the reasons of the industrial revolution happening in the 18th century in Britain, rather than in France or Germany. (Bailey, 2011)

B. Why the industrial revolution occupied in Britain in the 18th century, instead of the European countries, is the subject of considerable discussions. (Bailey, 2011)

After writing these two sentences on the board, the teacher asked about the difference between them. Students seemed reluctant to answer at first, then started answering all together with separate words without requesting the teacher's permission to talk. There was one student who seemed more active and tended to always answer any question first, thereby dominating the

classroom discussion. This behaviour seemed to restrict the teacher-student interaction to primarily that one student, limiting engagement with the rest of the class. The teacher then outlined the points of paraphrasing between the two statements, noting that 'industrial revolution' is a keyword and cannot be paraphrased. After the teacher's explanation and illustration, he gave them other sentences and asked them to paraphrase them in pairs. Students were expected to share their paraphrasing with the class. When the teacher asked: 'who wants to start first?' none of the students raised his/her hands. This situation imposed on the teacher to call on names randomly to read their paraphrasing. And when the teacher asked about the students' opinions after each other's paraphrasing, they were totally unresponsive, which again imposed on the teacher to give feedback himself. This was also maintained in the interviews when Lina noted that if someone or a group of students presents something in front of the class, and then the teacher would try to open up the discussion and ask the audience to share their views or ask questions, they would resist doing so. Therefore, all the feedback given or questions asked would almost always be from the teacher.

According to Bloom's revised taxonomy (2001), this activity seemed to promote the students' cognition in terms of knowledge, comprehension, and application. Students were required to recall the tips and principles of paraphrasing (remembering), understand how these can be applied to the task given to them, and identify the points that need paraphrasing (understanding), actually apply these strategies and principles to produce their own paraphrasing (applying).

Group work was done in Ali's session, the students were asked in groups to pick up keywords from a text. He allowed them time to search for these words. During the group work. I noticed that students were using English and the Algerian Arabic dialect for communication. The teacher also used the Algerian Arabic dialect when emphasising important points during the lecture. When the time was up, the teacher asked the students to share the keywords they found in the text, and he then explained them. As they came across a difficult word, the teacher asked them to use their phones to find the meaning of that word. Again, he allowed some time and then explained the word to the students. Asking the students to search for the meaning themselves might be seen as an attempt by the teacher to involve the students in the learning process, however, this activity could be more beneficial if he gave the students the opportunity to share their understanding of the keywords, instead of explaining these directly to them.

This activity, therefore, seemed to target the students' ability to recall their knowledge about English vocabulary (remembering), identifying the words that seem significant in a text (understanding), according to Bloom's revised version (2001) of the cognitive skills. These activities seemed to

promote the students' lower-level skills: knowledge, understating, and application, hence the development of critical thinking was not likely to take place.

5.4.4.3. Presentations

In her TEFL class, Reem assigned topics about the different traditional and modern teaching methods for her students to present in groups. Students were asked to prepare their PowerPoints to present in front of the class. This activity was expected to be followed up by a class discussion. During this activity, I noticed that the group presenters were only reading from the slides which might have led the audience to lose attention and interest. After the presentations, the teacher asked the students in the audience to raise questions about the topic, or give feedback or comments about the presenters' performances. Students were unresponsive, this behaviour happened repeatedly on many occasions in the observed classes. The teacher was holding the students' names list to give grades to the students presenters, as this activity as explained before was intended mainly to give grades to the students. This was actually admitted by Lina when interviewed. Given the students' resistance to participate, hence resistance to open up the discussion, the teacher started to call on names asking them about their opinions about the presentations. When called on, one of the students had a question for the group about the topic of the presentation, the group presenters seemed a bit stressed and started searching for the answer in the papers they used in the presentation. This might imply that the students were not quite aware and invested in what they prepared confirming Adam, Mustafa, Djamal, and Lina's claim in the interviews about the students' turning to plagiarism when doing homework or projects. The teachers complained that no matter how much they try to convince the students to come up with something authentic that reflects their own efforts and remind them that their work does not have to be perfect, students would still copy and paste from the internet.

In a similar activity done in Nora's session, not only the presenters were graded, but the students in the audience were also graded for their participation, meaning those who did not participate after the presentations would get very low grades. What seemed interesting was that once a student raises his/her hand, the teacher would immediately write a mark on his name, indicating that raising one's hand to participate, therefore getting a grade is more important than what one has actually to add to the discussion.

According to Bloom's revised taxonomy (2001), this type of activity was expected to develop the students' cognition in terms of understanding, analysing, evaluating, and creating. The presenting group was expected to gather information and analyse it, compare the pros and cons of each

teaching method and create a presentation about it, and the students in the audience were supposed to evaluate their peers' presentations. However, as discussed earlier, things did not seem to work as planned, therefore the likelihood of developing critical thinking skills seemed very low.

5.4.4.4. Questioning

Questioning was found in almost all the sessions that I observed. However, it is important to specify what types of questions were frequently used, and whether or not these have an effect on promoting the students' higher-order thinking skills. To begin with, as mentioned above the students' participation in the classrooms was quite limited, this was raised by many participants who complained that the students rely on the teacher to do everything in the learning process. This means that when a teacher asks a question which is usually directed to the whole class, very few students would interact and try to answer (sometimes as few as one or two students). And in some cases, when the teacher insists on the students to participate, students would avoid raising hands, and would rather throw separate words without asking for the teacher's permission to talk. Questioning was used mainly for two different purposes. Some questions were display questions, these were posed by the teachers for the sole purpose of recalling existing knowledge or checking the students' understanding of previous lectures. The other type of questions was analytical to some degree. The problem with the latter type of questions lay in the students' reaction, students in many cases would remain silent when a question seems a bit demanding to their analytical thought. It should be noted that these questions were very few.

In her ESP session, Lina tended to frequently ask rhetorical questions which are closed and only require a yes or no, for example:

The teacher: when can one teach ESP? Can students specialised in civilisation teach ESP?

The students: No

The teacher: No, because they did not have training about what ESP is.

Lina continued to ask questions without expecting the students to answer. The teacher asked again questions like: 'what is the role of the teacher?', 'what is the task of a course designer?', and she followed each question with an immediate explanation, indicating that she was not asking for the students' input.

Mia, in her written expression session, like most of the other participant teachers asked the students questions which required the students to remember what they received in previous lectures. Similarly, Ali posed the question 'why taking notes is important?', 'can you remember?' obviously it

was something that they already had and were expected to recall. Still, the teacher jumped to answer that question as the students remained silent.

Teaching the same lecture to another class, Djamal took another approach to questioning, allowing the students to deduce the answer by giving examples and asking questions which were related and connected to the students' real lives. The teacher, for example, captured the students' attention by saying 'in this session, you will be taking notes, why do you think that note-taking is important?', he then allowed time for the students to answer and discussed with them the process of taking notes, its importance, and the understanding they get through the process. The teacher highlighted that note-taking is different than writing, in that one cannot use abbreviations and acronyms in formal writing, and gave them an example about the master's dissertation they will be writing next year, and asked what they would use. The students suggested that they would use paraphrasing instead, and the teacher added to their answers that they would need to paraphrase, summarise, quote, and come up with ideas. Furthermore, Djamal asked the students if they had watched the movie 'anonymous', and one student responded that he had seen it, the teacher then asked him to try to give a summary of the movie, therefore illustrating an aspect in the lecture by an actual practice before jumping to give the rule directly and what a summary means.

'Why is speaking prior to writing?' this was a question posed by Mustafa in his linguistics session which required the students to make use of the knowledge they received by weighing arguments and providing evidence to explain the statement. However, none of the students attempted to answer, the teacher again allowed a few seconds, then explained the statement himself. Other than that question, Mustafa repeatedly asked the students to think of an example each time he explained an aspect of the lecture which was about 'language functions', but the same scenario seemed to happen as very few -if none- students responded, as such the teacher continued to explain and give examples.

A similar example was captured in Adam's session when he asked his students about the interpretation of the following expression: 'a language is an accent with a navy and an army', students were unresponsive, and the teacher moved to explain it himself.

The teachers asking questions and not expecting answers from students, the students recognising that the teachers' questions would be followed up by answers and explanation by the teachers themselves seemed to be an accepted behaviour that both students and teachers get used to. Consequently, the students have learned that they do not necessarily need to answer the questions at all.

In some sessions and apart from lecturing, there were no activities or questioning at all, except for that question where the teacher asks the students if everything is clear, or if they have any questions. The students' type of questioning on the other hand was only requesting the teachers to explain more the aspects they did not understand well or missed taking notes about it.

Clearly, according to Bloom's revised taxonomy (2001), two types of questions were employed in the observed classes. The most frequently used questions were to elicit and recall previous knowledge and to check whether or not the students understood the content of the previously taught lectures (remembering and understanding). Questions that seemed to promote greater abilities of thinking (analysing and evaluating) -which were very few- were not effective as they were confronted by the students' resistance and unwillingness to make efforts to answer these types of questions. Overall, questioning did not seem to stimulate the students' higher-order thinking skills.

5.4.4.5. Summary

The analysis of the three curriculum documents: Licence, Master's TEFL, and Master's Literature and Civilisation revealed that the mentions of critical thinking were very few, which indicates that the integration of critical thinking does not seem to be supported by curriculum designers. The Licence document did not contain any educational objectives or course content, therefore there were no data to analyse in this document. Critical thinking was mentioned explicitly only once in the other two documents. Enlarging students' knowledge, and developing their understanding seemed to be on top priority at all levels. Some higher-level thinking skills like analysis and evaluation were mentioned, but their frequency was very low compared to lower-level thinking skills. Overall, the university curriculum documents did not seem to encourage the development of critical thinking skills as the focus was more on developing knowledge and understanding. Further, these curriculum documents did not seem helpful to the teachers regarding the implementation of critical thinking as they did not include any definitions, activities, or guidelines that would help them in integrating critical thinking into their pedagogy.

The participants in this study, although their answers were short and lacked elaboration, they perceived critical thinking as a skill which consists of several cognitive sub-skills including, the ability to analyse, synthesise, and evaluate; questioning and truth-seeking; criticism; and problem-solving. The importance of critical thinking was acknowledged in all the participants' answers. They conceived it to be an important skill not only for the students' academic success and future research, but they also recognised its importance in producing successful and effective citizens. All participants held positive views regarding the teachability of critical thinking. They all concurred that this skill is

teachable, yet some of them believed that introducing it to students is particularly pertinent in later stages of learning.

The participant teachers conceived their role in developing critical thinking in three ways, through incorporating critical thinking in their teaching approach, when supervising projects like master's dissertations by encouraging the students to critically analyse and discuss information, and also through integrating critical thinking implicitly in their usual classroom tasks.

However, several challenges that come in the way of achieving this goal were identified. According to the participant teachers, critical thinking is not part of the educational agenda and the curriculum documents. They claimed that since there are no communications from the Ministry of Higher Education to consider critical thinking among the educational objectives, it is then the teachers' decision to implement it in their teaching or not. This marginalisation from policymakers and curriculum designers made the development of critical thinking the first thing to be neglected by teachers when other hindrances like time constraints and length of syllabuses are encountered. Another striking issue that was perceived to impede the development of critical thinking is dominance of the exam-centric education. The participants seemed to be aware that most of the teaching and classroom activities were designed mainly to pass tests and exams and achieve good grades.

Some participants believed that one of the reasons that hinder the development of critical thinking is the students' level and lack of motivation. They believed that students with low level in English language are not likely to engage in critical thinking activities, therefore they tend to focus their efforts on the development of the four basic skills. Other participants, however, claimed that society and the way children were raised in their families is one of the reasons critical thinking is overlooked. They believed that since individuals grew up respecting people in authority and valuing conformity, they become afraid to voice their opinions or to disagree with their teachers for example, and therefore critical thinking is less likely to take place. It can be deduced that there are many issues regarding the development of critical thinking in the Algerian university where each issue if not sorted out is likely to generate other problems.

The analysis of the observational data in this study developed four main themes, namely, teaching approach, classroom physical environment, students' classroom behaviours, and classroom activities. The teaching approach which dominated the observed classes was teacher-centered, students seemed to rely on the teacher to do everything in the classroom. Thus, they did not seem

to take any responsibility for their own learning. Moreover, obsession with examination was prevalent on many occasions in both the teachers' and students' acts. Teachers even used grades as an extrinsic motivation for the students to participate and frequently assigned activities for the purpose of grading only. Observing the classroom physical environment revealed that the large number of students might have an implication on the seating arrangement, along with the teaching approach and the choice of activities. As such, the large number of students imposed the traditional seating arrangement and teacher-centeredness. Another aspect which could affect the learning process is the room temperature, as the classrooms were very cold. There were no varieties in terms of the teaching materials, only the whiteboard and handouts were used in the sessions that I observed, this also might have an impact on the students' engagement.

Regarding the students' behaviours in the classroom, students were overall behaved, but there were some disruptive behaviours like late attendance and chatting. Students' reticence and lack of motivation were also quite evident. For example, on many occasions, the students would remain silent when the teacher asks a question which could be attributed to the students' assumption that their teachers would eventually answer the questions themselves.

The main activity which was observed in the classes and which occupied most of the learning/teaching process time was lecturing. On a few occasions, some activities were employed in some sessions. Many of them promoted the students' ability to understand and recall knowledge. There were also some attempts which were expected to involve higher cognitive levels, these did not seem quite effective as they were encountered by some impeding factors.

In the next chapter, the findings from the three research tools will be triangulated and discussed in relation to the literature review.

Chapter 6: Discussion of the Research Findings

6.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to provide insights into the most important findings that emerged from the three research tools used in this study, with related literature. As such, methodological triangulation is used, drawing on the three research tools when relevant, and relating the findings to the research questions. This chapter is organised based on the order of the research questions. That is, the first section is concerned mainly with the findings from the analysis of the three university curriculum documents of English language course communicated by the Ministry of Higher Education, which are: Licence curriculum, Master's curriculum for Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) major, and Master's curriculum for Literature and Civilisation (Lit and Civ) major. The analysis of these documents was to investigate the integration of critical thinking into the courses' objectives. In this section, I also discuss the teachers' interview answers regarding their knowledge of the representation of critical thinking in the educational agenda. In the second section - drawing mostly, but not exclusively, on the interview data - I discuss the findings related to the second research problem. That is, the teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking, their attitudes towards the development of critical thinking in their teaching, and their perceptions about its applicability in EFL classes. In the third section, I discuss the findings related to both research questions three and four. Research questions three and four are discussed together as they both tackle the teachers' instructional practices, one from the teachers' theoretical perspectives, and the second from the observational data of their actual practices. Therefore, I discuss the participant teachers' accounts of the educational practices they think might develop critical thinking skills. I also consider the participant teachers' approaches and classroom activities regarding the development of critical thinking as found in the classroom observation sessions to cross-check and compare their cognitions with their actual pedagogic practices. I conclude the chapter by discussing the challenges and hindrances that the participant teachers highlighted as impeding to their attempts/aspirations to implement critical thinking in their teaching.

6.2. Research question 1: to what extent does Algerian higher education encourage the teaching of critical thinking skills?

This question aims to find any evidence for the integration of critical thinking in the EFL curriculum documents mentioned above. More specifically, the curriculum documents were analysed to investigate whether critical thinking is set as one of the courses objectives. It also aims to explore the extent to which this concept is emphasised compared to other aspects of the teaching/learning

process. Although the document analysis was inductive, Bloom's revised taxonomy (2001) of learning, teaching, and assessing was used as a guide in classifying the educational objectives found in the documents.

The results of this study show a very limited emphasis on fostering critical thinking within the university curriculum documents communicated by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. The participant teachers demonstrated an awareness of this deficiency, and attributed part of their marginalisation in the development of critical thinking to that.

As regards the first curriculum document which is developed for the Bachelor's programme (Licence), it was found that the document does not include any general guidelines, or educational objectives. These are normally expected to be among the necessary aspects that a curriculum document should contain, besides being the focus of this research (Wiggins and McTighe, 2005). This document, however, includes the teaching units, evaluation system, credits, and module coefficients. In the teaching units, subjects are grouped within four main teaching units, Fundamental unit which addresses English language skills like oral comprehension and expression, written expression, grammar, etc.; Methodological unit which is mainly aimed to equip students with the necessary methodological skills needed in the field of research; Discovery unit where students are introduced to new subjects in different fields to enlarge their knowledge; and lastly Transversal unit where students are usually introduced to another language. Regarding assessment, the evaluation system involves a predetermined percentage for both exams and continuous evaluation. In terms of credits, students are required to attain 30 credits per semester, valid only for the Bachelor's degree. To obtain a Master's degree, an additional 120 credits are necessary. Importantly, credits can be capitalised and transferred. The Licence document includes also a consideration for module coefficients as well, emphasising the significance of each module within the overall curriculum structure. These elements were found in the three research documents, however unlike the Licence curriculum, the other two documents namely, TEFL and Lit and Civ curricula include educational objectives set for each subject. Under each subject's objective, there are general guidelines of the content that should be covered during each semester.

As for the TEFL curriculum, the findings showed that there was only one explicit reference of critical thinking in the whole document including first and second year's learning objectives. Most of the objectives for the Master 1 teaching units were related to lower cognitive skills. As such, enlarging the students' knowledge and developing their understanding of the different subjects seemed to be

the primary goal of education at this level. In a general sense, these objectives displayed a lack of emphasis on the enhancement of students' higher cognitive skills. When considering skills like analysing and evaluating as higher-order thinking skills which constitute the ability to think critically, there were only two objectives which addressed these skills. However, it should be noted that implicitly referencing critical thinking in the objectives may not always be interpreted by teachers in the intended manner of the educational objective. This was acknowledged by Erikson and Erikson (2019) as they provided an illustration of using verbs such as 'criticising' to develop critical thinking in students, they argued:

including verbs such as 'criticize' will not promote critical thinking unless the teacher interprets them in such a way, and steers students in such directions. Otherwise, the ability to criticize might just as well be a matter of reproducing a critical discourse found in the literature or even uncritical acceptance of a critical discourse presented by the teacher, where attempts to gainsay these positions as a result of students' own critical thinking may even be rebutted.

(p. 2298)

The same applies to using verbs like 'analyse' and 'evaluate' in the curriculum documents: the teachers' interpretation of these skills might be that students are required to analyse and evaluate ideas or topics based on the input provided and discussed by the teacher in the classroom. That is, the teacher's interpretation of these objectives might be limited to the students' abilities to analyse and evaluate ideas based on the information presented by the teacher. In a similar vein, one of the participant teachers claimed that although critical thinking is not explicitly mentioned, one can infer its necessity from the statement of the objective, the teaching outcome, or even from the title of the lecture. It should be noted though that different teachers have different interpretations, therefore, assuming that critical thinking is required without mentioning it or its components may not be accurate. Erikson and Erikson (2019) pointed out that 'different teachers will have different disciplinary understandings and thus may have different interpretations of the same learning outcome (including setting different standards for when a learning outcome have been reached)' (p. 2296). This may indicate also having different measures or criteria to assess whether an objective or a desired outcome has been successfully attained. That is, diversity in interpretation can lead to distinct teaching methods, assessment criteria, and expectations for students, resulting in a range of educational experiences within the same curriculum. This emphasises again the role of individual interpretations in shaping the practical application of a curriculum within the teachers' distinctive classroom settings.

The objectives outlined for the Master 2 programme did not differ much. Unexpectedly, these objectives did not progress to include more advanced cognitive skills. Despite the slight shift of focus from that of the first year towards equipping the students with the necessary tools that enable them to write the master's dissertation, the formulation of these objectives remained primarily aiming to develop students' knowledge and occasionally included the skill of application, neglecting the development and integration of higher-order thinking skills.

Equipping the students with the knowledge needed in their future professions, especially those pursuing careers in teaching, was the secondary priority. However, while aiming to achieve this goal, integrating and cultivating higher-order thinking skills remained blurred as again the educational objectives were largely centred on the students' passive acquisition of knowledge and the anticipation of its future application. As such, offering limited clarity on the extent of active student engagement in the learning process, how students are supposed to deal with the knowledge they are exposed to, or what they are required to do.

Therefore, as mentioned earlier, critical thinking was explicitly considered only once in the Master 2 programme, and the entire TEFL curriculum, indicating little interest in the cultivation of critical thinking among students.

6.2.1. Importance of knowledge in scaffolding the students' critical thinking skills

The focus on the acquisition of knowledge at the early stages is not only acceptable, in fact, it is also necessary as many researchers and scholars have emphasised the significant role that a solid base of knowledge plays in paving the way to more advanced skills (McPeck, 1990; Willingham, 2007). Thus, it helps in scaffolding the students' critical thinking skills. This means that students need a foundation of information to be able to engage in an effective and critical analysis, they need something to think about critically. Byrnes (2012) asserts that introducing and aiming to develop basic reasoning skills when designing the introductory levels of the curriculum is required, and helpful for students to be able to exercise higher-order thinking skills in subsequent phases. Hence, gradual integration of critical thinking in the curriculum is required (Biggs and Tang 2011). That is, the formulation of the objectives should start by expecting the students to develop skills like 'describing', 'identifying' or 'explaining', then eventually progressing to higher cognitive skills in later stages like 'analysing' or 'criticising'. The findings from the document analysis in the study, however, did not show a similar process: there was no noticeable shift of focus from lower to higher cognitive abilities. This limited acknowledgement of higher-order thinking skills in the educational objectives

results in minimal attention to critical thinking, and therefore little improvement of students' critical thinking skills.

Regarding the educational objectives found in the Master's curriculum document of Literature and Civilisation major, it was revealed that aiming to develop the students' critical thinking skills was considered again only once in the whole document. The subjects' objectives for first-year Master students who major in Lit and Civ, similar to those within the TEFL curriculum, primarily emphasised expanding the students' knowledge across various subjects, and developing their understanding of the material. The formulation of the objectives outlined mainly the expected actions on the part of the teacher, such as demonstrating, familiarising, developing, and providing students with information, etc. In contrast, there is a notable absence of emphasis on what students are expected to do, or how they are expected to be actively engaged in the teaching/learning process, which implies a limited role for students within the classroom dynamics.

Some objectives aimed at developing basic skills by fostering the students' comprehension and facilitating the application of knowledge, where students are expected to recall and employ the acquired information in discussions, presentations, tasks, exams, etc. Therefore, leaving no room for the development of students' higher-order thinking skills.

There were four modules in which higher cognitive skills were taken into consideration. Critical thinking was mentioned only once in the whole document in the Cross-Cultural Communication module; the other three instances targeted the skill of 'analysis' which once again, as discussed earlier, relies on the teachers' interpretations which are often to provide the students with predetermined knowledge to use in their analysis, instead of allowing independent analysis and critical thinking. In the Master's two objectives, in addition to the consistent focus on enlarging the students' knowledge, understanding, and awareness, and developing the students' research and presentation skills through exposing the students to a set of content and strategies and expecting their application in similar situations; there was also a combination between lower and higher cognitive skills in three instances.

6.2.2. Critical thinking as an objective in skill-/content-based modules

As can be noted, the findings of this study revealed that the Lit and Civ curriculum places slightly more emphasis on the development of higher-order thinking skills compared to the TEFL curriculum. This distinction may be attributed to the content of the module: skill-based modules are more likely to develop basic skills, like speaking, listening, reading, and writing, whereas content-based modules

which mainly constitute the Lit and Civ curriculum are more likely to equip the students with knowledge of the cultural aspects of English-speaking countries, in this case the US and UK, and also provide an opportunity to students to develop their English skills. The inclusion of cultural elements in content-based classes offers a rich environment for fostering critical thinking skills. This is achieved by exposing students to unfamiliar cultures that may bear similarities or striking differences to their own. Students have the opportunity to delve into the variations of 'western civilisation' and 'Islamic civilisation'. Through engaging in cultural comparisons and contrasts, students can cultivate a critical perspective of their own culture, as well as those of others, gaining insights into themselves and the world. Furthermore, since critical thinking is widely practised in Western countries and perceived by some scholars as a Western possession (Atkinson, 1997; Ramanathan and Kaplan, 1996), exploring it as part of cultural comprehension in such contexts holds significant value. According to Brown (2014), this type of subjects offers a meaningful input which stimulates students' analytical thought to come up with a critical output. This perspective aligns with Richards and Rodgers' (2000) and Crocker and Bowden's (2011) assertion that language learning becomes more engaging and motivating when students direct their focus towards topics beyond language itself, and further when those topics are related to their lives. This was opposed by some of the participant teachers in this study who argued that it might be possible for them to develop critical thinking in skill-based modules such as Study Skills, but not in content-based modules where their primary focus is to deliver the predetermined content to students. There are also studies which advocate for the teaching of critical thinking skills in skill-based courses (Nguyen, 2017). This indicates that both content-based and skill-based modules can be appropriate to nurture critical thinking, however, the teachers in this study shared their concerns about the possibility of developing this skill at all because of a number of constraints which will be discussed later in this chapter.

Broadly speaking, the findings from the document analysis in this study revealed that the emphasis on lower-level skills overshadowed the development of higher-order thinking skills in students. This reflects the marginalisation of critical thinking in the curriculum documents within higher education. The Findings from the participant teachers' answers in this study regarding the representation of critical thinking seemed to be to a great extent consistent with the content of the curriculum documents, all of them pointed out that they have never received a document or any communication from the Ministry of Higher Education that encourages the teaching and integration of critical thinking as an educational objective. Despite the very few instances in which critical thinking and its constituent skills were mentioned in the documents (which were not acknowledged by teachers,

probably because they were not as common as those aiming to develop knowledge and understating), all participant teachers agreed on the marginalisation of this concept when it comes to the planning and the general teaching guidelines communicated by the ministry as some of them expressed that ‘critical thinking is not part of the agenda’. Considering that curriculum designers and individuals responsible for establishing the general guidelines and educational objectives do not allocate significant attention to critical thinking, teachers tend to eliminate the cultivation of critical thinking skills as the first thing to do when confronted by various challenges such as time constraints, workload, and large class size, as reported by some of the participants in this study. This brings us to the notion of ‘the ceiling’ where educational objectives become as a ceiling for teachers’ ambitions.

6.2.3. Obscuring critical thinking: the impact of the educational objectives

Erikson and Erikson (2019) suggested that ‘the wall of outcomes might conceal from the student the need for critical thinking and related issues’ (p. 2300). They proposed this notion to describe the effect that learning outcomes may have on limiting the students' potential and ambitions. Given that both learning outcomes and educational objectives are established to articulate what students are expected to achieve or demonstrate as a result of the learning process, the notion of the ceiling can be applied also to the context of this study as most of the statements in the analysed curriculum documents are related to the development of lower cognitive skills. This can divert the teachers’ attention from the real goal of higher education and their academic responsibility. In this case, the educational objectives did not only exclude critical thinking from the picture, but also were like a ceiling which obscures critical thinking skills from the teachers’ vision, limiting their ability to recognise the value of critical thinking in the process of learning and teaching . As such, even though teachers may have the desire and ambition to develop students’ higher-order thinking skills, they find themselves compelled to conform to what the guidelines dictate; and as a result, diverted from the bigger picture where ‘the system hardly supports students trying go the extra mile and teachers are hardly encouraged to reward students who go outside the box’ (Erikson and Erikson, 2019).

6.2.4. Promoting critical thinking within the LMD system and CBA framework

While the study participants acknowledged the lack of explicit emphasis on critical thinking in official communication from the Ministry of Higher Education, they pointed out that critical thinking is recognised as a fundamental principle of the LMD system and a core aspect of the competency-based approach.

The LMD system, which was adopted to adapt to the fast-changing world and the increasing globalisation, aimed primarily to foster the development of students' autonomy and life-long learning skills. Not only that, the LMD system also aimed at enhancing the students' critical thinking skills which are core requirements nowadays worldwide to succeed, particularly at university level (El Ouchdi- Mirali, 2015). This was an attempt to deliver quality education and to enhance the international recognition of Algerian diplomas (Saad et al., 2005). The LMD system places significant emphasis on the role students should play in the classroom, assigning them responsibility for approximately 70% of the workload and the overall classroom efforts (Talbi, 2015). This system then is supposed to promote the shift from the traditional classroom format where students are only expected to consume information which is transmitted in a unidirectional way from the only person of authority in the classroom, that is the teacher. Despite these merits, the LMD system in the Algerian context was criticised on several grounds: mainly because the adoption and application of this system focused merely on the formality rather than the essence, therefore it has not succeeded in achieving its aspirations (discussed further in chapter 2.2) (Metatla, 2016; Talbi, 2015). The participants in this study also agreed that the LMD system has not succeeded in achieving the intended goals, and that these aspirations remain ink on paper as in practice there is an extremely different story. The LMD system, along with the competency-based approach, seemed to exist primarily as a set of principles in a document, instead of a tangible impact on practice. Ball's insight, though originally addressing policy, resonates with these principles, as they share a parallel function in prescribing specific approaches and actions within the educational context, emphasising that both remain incomplete until they are implemented and translated into action. he argued 'policy is both text and action, words and deeds, it is what is enacted as well as what is intended. Policies are always incomplete insofar as they relate to or map onto the "wild profusion" of local practice' (Ball, 1994, p. 10, cited in Trowler, 2003, p. 96).

The participant teachers reported that the adoption of the LMD system was accompanied by the Competency-Based Approach which was intended to replace the prevailing teacher-centred approach with the student-centred approach. The CBA has several features, among them the most distinct one is the prior needs analysis of students before designing the syllabus (Richards and Rodgers, 2001). This aspect indicates that there is no prescribed syllabus and that the competencies encompassing both the knowledge and skills are determined based on the students' needs and current competencies. However, this characteristic cannot be put into practice as the content and syllabus to be taught in the context of this study across the different levels is ready-made by the

responsible bodies at the level of the Ministry of Education (ME) and Ministry of Higher Education (MHE) and which the participant teachers reported that they are committed to cover.

Another unique characteristic of this approach is that it is not time-bound, which means that what determines the progression from one lesson to another is the students' competency development and mastery of the skill and not the time allocated for the lesson. Sturgis and Patrick described it as 'the transformation of our education system from a time-based system to a learning-based system' (2010, p.1). Therefore, moving to a new lesson is possible only when the competencies of a lesson are accomplished regardless of how much time it may actually take. Again, this characteristic is not feasible in the context of the current study, the participants shared their concern about time constraints as one of the major challenges. They expressed feeling compelled to cover the prescribed content before the end of each semester, and as such lacking the sufficient time to spend on the development of students' critical thinking skills. This seemed acceptable to them since as explained earlier critical thinking is not part of the educational agenda, and consequently they are not required to teach it or integrate it in their classroom pedagogy. This aspect of the competency-bound approach, which is lacking in Algerian universities, is also expressed by O'sullivan and Burce (2014) who stated 'so, while most colleges and universities hold time requirements constant and let learning vary, competency-based learning allows us to hold learning constant and let time vary' (p. 72).

Taking the learning process beyond the classroom is also what distinguishes the CBA from other traditional approaches. This aspect goes hand in hand with the principles of the LMD system where the central role of the teacher is no longer to be the ultimate source of information and the most active and authoritative figure in the classroom, the teacher's role becomes more of a facilitator of the learning interaction. The teacher is mainly expected to prepare tasks that meet the students' needs which were identified before the commencement of the course, to provide effective feedback and construct appropriate assessment procedures. The students' role then shifts from consuming knowledge to generating knowledge with peers. Thus, instead of receiving information from the teacher and recalling it, students are expected to make efforts, be active, engaged, and responsible for their own learning (Richards and Rodgers, 2001; Sturgis and Patrick, 2010). This, as the other features, seemed unattainable according to the findings of the current study. The participant teachers reported that the students mostly rely on the teacher to take control of the whole learning process, complaining that even beyond the classroom when students are asked to do homework

using their own efforts, they would just copy and paste from the internet without attempting to come up with something authentic.

As mentioned earlier, the participants expressed that despite the limited representation of critical thinking in the EFL curriculum documents, critical thinking is one of the desired outcomes of both the LMD system and the CBA. However, in practice, these aspirations did not seem to see light as the teacher-centred approach is still dominating EFL classes. These results are supportive to Abdaoui and Grines's (2020) findings on the hegemony of the teacher-centred approach, and the students' lack of autonomy within the framework of the LMD system. And given that learning autonomy and critical thinking have a significant positive correlation (Nosratinia, Abbasi, and Zaker, 2013), it might be inferred that the little interest in the development of critical thinking in the curriculum documents might be the reason behind the students' lack of autonomy.

Other studies in the Algerian context (Ahouari-idri, 2005; Talbi, 2016) attributed the unsuccessful application of the LMD system not only to the teachers' lack of knowledge, but also to the students' ignorance of what this system entails. Their findings indicated that students are not aware of the underlying principles, objectives, and the expected positive outcomes of this system; they rather have only a negative attitude towards it in terms of the responsibility and the large number of subjects they are expected to have. Failing to achieve the merits of the LMD system and the CBA, and consequently overlooking the cultivation of critical thinking (given that teachers considered critical thinking as one of these merits) brings us back to the idea that both the LMD system and CBA were adopted merely as a form rather than a substance. This could be the reason why teachers struggle to put these into practice.

An implication which can be drawn from the results of the first research question is that the limited implementation of critical thinking (which will be discussed later in this section) could be attributed to the limited representation of critical thinking in the curriculum. This finding corroborates Alagözlü's (2007) argument that the lack of critical thinking is related to the lack of opportunity and explicit reference in the curriculum to cultivate it.

The following section discusses the teachers' knowledge and understanding of the concept of critical thinking, and their views about its importance and teachability.

6.3. Research question 2: what are university EFL teachers' perceptions of critical thinking, and the importance of its integration in their teaching?

Given the long controversy about the meaning of critical thinking worldwide, particularly in the western context, it has been always difficult to come up with a single agreed definition as 'critical thinking in higher education is a phrase that means many things to many people' (Davis, 2015, p.41). That is why, it was necessary that one of the questions guiding this research aims to explore EFL university teachers' understandings of critical thinking, its importance and teachability, in a non-western context where research in this regard is very scarce. Exploring The teachers' accounts would also provide insights into the degree of critical thinking integration within their instructional practices.

6.3.1. Teachers' perceptions of critical thinking

This study found that the participant teachers agreed on the importance of making critical thinking an integral part of the curriculum and classroom pedagogy, however, they appeared to have a basic limited understanding and knowledge about critical thinking, and how to incorporate it in their teaching. Their definitions were centred on having a set of cognitive skills like analysis, synthesis, evaluation, reasoning, and problem-solving, in addition to questioning assumptions, most of these notions accord with those mentioned by a number of scholars (Facione 1990, Brookfield, 2012, Halpern,1998, Ennis, 2011). However, their lack of knowledge was evident through the brief and non-elaborate answers they provided, some participants even avoided answering the question. Furthermore, it was noticed that criticism and critical thinking were used as synonymous sometimes, despite the distinctive meanings of these terms. It is important to note that critical thinking involves effective analysis, questioning, reflection, and evaluation of evidence, among other aspects. On the other hand, criticism can be considered a component of critical thinking when it is based on objective analysis of presented arguments. Nevertheless, poor criticism may arise from biased judgments and preconceived notions, and here lies the difference between the two concepts.

Moreover, critical thinking is a process which involves mainly two different things, skills and dispositions and they are equally important. The findings disclosed that the participant teachers conceptualise critical thinking in terms of skills only, none of them mentioned critical thinking dispositions. The latter play a fundamental role in engaging the students in the process of using higher-order thinking skills, and contribute to putting the critical thinking skills one has into actual practice. Many scholars (Ennis, 2011; Davis, 2015; Halpern, 2014; Paul and elder, 2012) emphasised that teaching critical thinking requires more than developing cognitive skills and competencies. It

also involves developing new habits of mind and metacognitive awareness. In other words, students need to develop an attitude to regulate and constantly improve their thinking, they have to demonstrate a willingness to evaluate their own thinking, recognise biases and limitations, and engage in the process of reconstructing it. The relatively limited understanding of critical thinking among the university teachers in this study is similar to that reported by Zhang, Yuan, and He (2020) who investigated Chinese university EFL teachers' perceptions, and the influence the latter have on their practices.

The teachers' limited conceptualisations of what critical thinking actually means could be due to its intangible construct which makes it hard to assess and practise as expressed by one of the participants that despite the theoretical knowledge that he developed reading about critical thinking, he does not know how to teach it. It could also be due to the teachers' lack of adequate awareness and practice in their previous years of education, this was reported by one of the participants who was a novice teacher. This could suggest that the teacher's previous education and the recent curriculum do not adequately prepare students (future teachers) to develop critical thinking skills - as evidenced by the curriculum document analysis. Lastly, it could be due to the lack of attention and support from the educational institutions for the teachers' training programmes and professional development. This is in line with the findings in Buphate and Esteban (2018), and Prommak (2019).

6.3.2. The impact of Teachers' modelling on the development of critical thinking

Considering the teachers' limited familiarity with critical thinking in this study, it is very unlikely that they would be able to cultivate it in their students. Sufficient knowledge and expertise about what the concept entails are required for teachers to be able to teach it to students. They need to be critical thinkers themselves, before attempting to develop critical minds (Hager and Kaye, 1992; Paul, 1990). Another important aspect that has a direct and significant impact on the development of critical thinking is the teachers' behaviours. Teachers need to model critical thinking to students: their behaviours must support the practice of critical thinking. Given that the findings from the observation sessions in the current study revealed a high dependency on the teachers to make most of the efforts in the teaching/learning process, students are likely to be influenced by the teachers' lack of critical thinking qualities. Teachers in Prommak's (2019) study believed that students need their teachers to exemplify how to be a critical thinker. The concept of 'modelling' seems to be related to the ZPD (Zone of Proximal Development) in Vygotsky's sociocultural theory where the teacher is viewed as the most knowledgeable and influential member who models and demonstrates

critical thinking skills and attitudes. The teacher's modelling which could be in the form of: effective questioning techniques, evidence evaluation, argumentation, or reflection serves in guiding and scaffolding the students' thinking processes. Through observing and being part of these modelling experiences, students would gradually move from their current understanding to engage in more advanced critical thinking processes. Using modelling as an instructional strategy to develop critical thinking is also endorsed by various scholars in the field (Brookfield 2012; Costa 2006; Facione 2000).

6.3.3. Misconceptions in teachers' perception: English Language Proficiency and Critical Thinking applicability

Despite the limited knowledge exhibited by the participant teachers about critical thinking, all of them acknowledged that developing critical thinking would bring successful results to the students' learning process in classrooms and beyond, in the workplace or academia. This supports the findings of many research studies, as explored in section 3.3. For instance, a survey which included not only teachers but employers and policy makers was conducted in the U.S. on the importance of teaching critical thinking revealed an agreement that students graduating from universities should be equipped with critical thinking skills and dispositions, emphasising that this should be a fundamental outcome of higher education (Tsui, 2002). However, the current study revealed that there were some misconceptions about its innateness and teachability. Interestingly, some teachers believed that students' proficiency level significantly influences their ability to engage in critical thinking processes, assuming that students with low proficiency level in English language might not be capable of thinking critically. They perceived a lower language proficiency as a barrier to the cultivation of critical thinking skills. Additionally, they believed that the teaching of critical thinking would yield more successful outcomes exclusively for students with higher language proficiency levels. Hadley and Boon (2023) described EFL teachers' objection to the teaching critical thinking as what they called 'false dilemmas':

False dilemmas are 'either/or' forms of binary thinking that position only two possibilities when many options are in fact available. Here the objection could be restated as: 'Either my students should be able to study critical thinking in English as easily as they could in their native language, or they shouldn't be asked to learn it at all during their English language classes.' The first thing that should be remembered is that, depending on their education and other life experiences, beginners in the second language may already have well-developed CT skills, and simply need instruction on how to express their arguments in the target language

(p.7)

Furthermore, one participant in the study inferred that critical thinking is an inherent skill possessed by certain individuals, particularly high-achievers, while those with lower abilities do not naturally possess it and require practice and training to develop it. It should be noted that having a high level in English language or any subject does not necessitate being good at thinking critically, conversely, having a low level in English language does not deem one less capable or incapable to engage in critical thinking. Many studies advocated that integrating critical thinking into EFL or ESL classes can simultaneously enhance the students' critical thinking skills and language proficiency (Dong, 2017; Liaw, 2007; Yang, Gamble, and Tang, 2012).

Another notable finding is that some teachers perceived the introduction of critical thinking as appropriate at advanced stages of education, rather than at earlier stages. For instance, some of them expressed their attempts to focus on fostering critical thinking skills among master's students, given that they are expected to produce master's dissertations as a requirement for graduation. According to existing literature, critical thinking is universally acknowledged as a skill that can be nurtured in all students, starting from introductory levels, parallel to other skills, and progressively integrated throughout their academic journey (Byrnes, 2012). The development of Critical thinking cannot occur suddenly or within a short period of time. This means that it cannot be introduced at later stages and expect the students to be good at or to become ingrained as a habitual practice. Some participants however held the belief that critical thinking is an intricate concept that can only be possessed or developed by intermediate or advanced students. Research has proved the feasibility of fostering critical thinking among language learners not only for intermediate or advanced levels, but also for beginners (Brumfit et al, 2005; Yamada, 2010). In line with this perspective, Hadley and Boon (2023) emphasised the possibility of designing critical thinking activities and lessons tailored for individuals with lower levels of proficiency in the English language. They argued 'we should remember that we do not have to teach such beginners or low-intermediate learners everything about CT. It is possible to teach some of the simpler aspects of critical thinking for students at this level' (p.8).

It is important to remember that we do not have to teach such beginners or low-intermediate learners everything about critical thinking, and demonstrated 'It is possible to teach some of the simpler aspects of critical thinking for students at this level. The Pathways series of textbooks (e.g., Chase & Johanssen, 2012).

6.3.4. Implicit vs. explicit teaching of critical thinking

Although the participant teachers realised the importance of the implementation of critical thinking in their classes, they seemed sceptical and self-conscious about their ability to teach critical thinking and questioned its prioritisation in their classroom pedagogy. The majority of them believed that critical thinking is teachable, but only implicitly. In the literature, scholars hold different views regarding the implicit and explicit instruction in teaching critical thinking. Both approaches proved to strengthen the students' cognitive development and improve their thinking skills (Halpern, 1998). Kennedy et al. (1991) concluded that using instructional interventions that specifically target the development of critical thinking has shown positive outcomes. On his part, Ennis (1989) suggested four possible approaches to teaching critical thinking (see section 3.5), among these is the general approach which involves direct instruction in critical thinking as a stand-alone course. Gelder (2005) supported this approach to critical thinking teaching as according to him students require opportunities of 'deliberate practice' in enhancing critical thinking skills. However, by implicitly, the teachers in this study seemed to mean 'spontaneously' or 'unintentionally' - as mentioned by some of them - which suggests that according to them critical thinking can be developed implicitly without making specific targeted efforts towards this aim. This might imply a lack of understanding and awareness regarding the implicit teaching of critical thinking as well. Along similar lines, Gann's (2016) examination of how critical thinking is manifested in various global English language textbooks highlights a significant concern regarding critical thinking in English Language Teaching (ELT) coursebooks. Gann (2016) pointed out that despite many textbooks asserting the promotion of critical thinking, the actual incorporation of critical thinking elements is often subtle to the extent of being nearly 'invisible'. Gann concluded that the implementation of critical thinking in ELT materials appears to be insufficient in the majority of cases.

Promoting critical thinking is an effortful process which is hardly possible to be effective and successful only if it is well-planned and prepared for thoughtfully. Furthermore, as almost all participant teachers advocated for the implicit approach (did not perceive it explicitly at all), one participant completely denied the possibility of teaching critical thinking explicitly and advocated only for the implicit approach through certain types of activities or tasks, arguing that teachers do not need to tell the students that they are trying to develop their critical thinking skills. This contradicts with Dwyer, Hogan, and Stewart's (2014) argument that clear and adequate instruction is required to improve the students' critical thinking abilities. This corroborates with the findings in

Higgins (2015) that students who were taught critical thinking explicitly outperformed those who were taught implicitly.

A degree of inconsistency emerged from the teachers' accounts regarding their ability to teach critical thinking. While some claimed to be capable of teaching critical thinking, they struggled to provide elaborations or examples of how they would do so. Despite their awareness of its teachability, some teachers admitted a lack of concrete pedagogy for putting critical thinking into practice. The teachers' lack of a well-defined pedagogy for fostering critical thinking was evident during the classroom observations. In most instances, the classroom activities and interactions appeared to focus on students' comprehension and memorisation rather than nurturing their critical thinking abilities. This will be discussed further in the following section. Moreover, it was reported that critical thinking is teachable to some extent, but it mainly depends on the subject and the aim of the courses. And from the document analysis, it was revealed that the development of critical thinking was not an objective in the majority of courses.

Considering that teachers' perceptions significantly influence their practices where the latter is highly dependent on and shaped by the former (Paul, 1995; Borg, 2003), this means that a good understanding and conceptualisation of critical thinking reflects better recognition of critical thinking pedagogies. Therefore an implication of the findings in this study could be that the limited understanding of critical thinking and the absence of critical thinking behaviours and dispositions among teachers hinder the effective implementation of critical thinking in their teaching. The following section discusses the teachers' cognitions regarding the development of critical thinking in their students and its integration within the classroom pedagogy and how these relate to their actual practices.

6.4. Research questions 3 and 4: What practices do EFL teachers enact to, or consider would foster EFL learners' critical thinking? To what extent has critical thinking moved from theory to actual educational practices?

Question three aims to investigate the teachers' integration of critical thinking, more specifically, it explores the teachers' perceptions of the instructional practices they use to promote it in their classes. It was also important to investigate the teachers' actual practices to see whether their perceptions of their integration of critical thinking in their subject matters are consistent with their teaching practices. For this sake and to answer the fourth research question, classroom observation sessions were conducted. The findings revealed that despite the teachers' narrow conceptualisation

of critical thinking and lack of a clear vision concerning the pedagogy of teaching critical thinking, they listed questioning, brainstorming, presentations, and group/pair work as the most frequent teaching techniques and activities they employ to develop the students' critical thinking skills. However, there was a gap between the participant teachers' perceptions of their teaching of critical thinking and their actual classroom practices. The observational data revealed that although the teachers believed that they were implementing critical thinking to a certain extent in their teaching, in practice, almost all their teaching strategies and activities did not seem to be stimulating or enhancing to the students' criticality.

6.4.1. The relevance of critical thinking across various subjects

All participants claimed that despite the absence of explicit instruction to implement critical thinking in the curriculum, they tend to consider it in their teaching practices; even though they do not formally include it as one of the stated objectives when designing lesson plans. They highlighted that sometimes the nature of the module itself does not necessarily mandate the incorporation of this type of thinking. This finding is contrary to previous studies which have suggested that critical thinking can be taught in different subjects across all fields (González, 2006; Tomayo, 2013). Similarly, proponents of subject specificity of critical thinking believe that it can be cultivated in all modules and domains, the difference merely lies in the specific principles and standards that determine how the quality of thinking of that particular subject is assessed. This was discussed further in section 2.4. Furthermore, as discussed earlier critical thinking should not be left to implicit expectations, the findings from Abrami et al.'s (2008) study reaffirm the necessity of establishing explicit objectives and instruction to develop both critical thinking skills and dispositions.

6.4.2. Teachers' dominant teaching Methodologies

According to the interview data, it was found that the participant teachers attempted to integrate critical thinking in their teaching through three primary approaches: their teaching methods, supervision, and classroom tasks. Some teachers expressed their concerns about the students' knowledge and awareness of what critical thinking means, and their readiness to engage in it. They believed that students tend to adhere to conventional thought patterns, overlooking the fact that the goal is not merely to accumulate knowledge but to effectively make use of it. A possible explanation for this might be that the way through which knowledge is disseminated has an impact on the students' ability and willingness to think critically. This aligns with McPeck's (1990) and Williams and Burden's (1997) views that students adopt learning approaches that reflect how their teachers instructed them to learn, which means that they are influenced by the way teachers

manage their classrooms. Duron, Limbach, and Waugh (2006) argued that the prevalence of lecture-based mode of teaching in higher education is one of the impediments of the students' active engagement in critical thinking. According to Choy (2003), many teachers still maintain that students require direct instruction before they can actually learn. To cultivate critical thinking skills, teachers need to reconsider their perception of the learning process, that direct instruction is the only way for students to learn in the classroom.

In the current study, the participant teachers emphasised that it is the responsibility of teachers to encourage and guide students to become critical thinkers, by actively monitoring the learning process and fostering an environment that encourages the expression of diverse perspectives. This accords with Bailin et al. (1999) who suggested that successful and effective critical thinking instruction requires 'providing an environment in which critical thinking is valued and students are encouraged and supported in their attempts to think critically' (p. 299). However, in the observed classes, this was not translated into practice. Despite the recent reforms of the educational system and the teaching approaches, it was found that the prevailing pedagogical approaches in English university classes continue to be rooted in traditional teacher-centred methods. These practices reinforce a hierarchical view of teachers as the sole authority on knowledge, with an emphasis on transmitting information through rote memorisation rather than encouraging active and reflective learning. It seems possible that this finding, as indicated by some research studies (Prommak, 2019; Thamraksa, 2003) is attributed to the teachers' sense of pride in their power. Potentially even without their awareness, teachers might be afraid to lose their power status as the central figure in the classroom, that students need to conform to their authority. In addition to that, the students' over-reliance on the teacher might also feed in the teacher's potential egocentricity. This might explain the teachers' resistance and fear to change their teaching method. Consequently, the teachers' adherence to the teacher-centred paradigm might leave little room for the development of critical thinking. As such, I observed that lecturing remains the dominant mode of instruction, leading to passive student participation during classes. This finding is supported by Marmah (2014) who claimed that despite the emergence of new teaching methodologies that encourage active learning, traditional lecturing remains the most favoured and prominent mode of instruction in higher education. The persistence of teacher-centred pedagogies, among other challenges which will be discussed in the following section, might impede the effective incorporation of critical thinking. In the observed sessions, active learning and student-teacher interaction was very limited in the sense that the teacher was responsible for most of the work in the classroom. It should be

noted though that some teachers as expressed in the interviews made some attempts to engage the students in the learning process, but in most cases, silence seemed to dominate the classroom (see section 5.4.3). The participation varied slightly from one class to another, but was generally very limited. Such an instructional approach aligns with the conventional lecture format which does not encourage the cultivation of critical thinking. However, It is important to acknowledge that generalisation is not sought in this regard as it was a one-time observation for each participant. Yet, there were patterns across the observed sessions that implied that this might be the way lectures are held very often.

6.4.3. Critical thinking as an end product not a process

Few participants perceived their role in promoting the students' higher cognitive skills to be bound and particularly important for students pursuing a master's degree, primarily to equip them to proficiently compose their dissertations. Notably, one of the participants emphasised this point, as according to him the master's dissertations which are produced by students lack analysis and criticality. This might imply that they viewed critical thinking as an important skill solely aimed at completing academic assignments – master's dissertation in this case - rather than recognising its broader applicability as a lifelong skill. This finding is similar to Gunawardena and Wilson's (2021) who argued that the deficiency in critical thinking development may be attributed to the teachers' perspective of critical thinking as a static product that students are required to demonstrate in a task or an assignment rather than a developmental process. This implies that teachers should not regard critical thinking as an end product, but rather as an activity that students engage in on a daily basis, creating the habit of critical thinking and dispositions. However, a contrasting perspective emerged from another participant who claimed that the opportunities to foster critical thinking skills in master's students are very limited given that most subjects are content-based, consequently, they rely on traditional lecturing. As previously indicated in section 1, content-based modules offer a suitable foundation for the cultivation of students' critical thinking abilities (Brown, 2014; Crocker and Bowden, 2011; Richards and Rodgers, 2000).

6.4.4. Teachers' classroom strategies to develop critical thinking

Furthermore, it was also found that the participant teachers perceived their responsibility in developing the students' critical thinking skills by practising classroom tasks and strategies, which encourage reflection and self-evaluation, and enable the students to connect their learning in classes with real-life situations. To this end, they reported that they use presentations: questioning strategies, brainstorming, and group/pair work. It was revealed, however, from the observational

data that these practices which were very few and occupied very limited time of the sessions were not necessarily developing to the students' critical thinking skills. However, as mentioned earlier, these are one-time observations with minimal occurrences of classroom activities, which may not necessarily be indicative of typical teaching practices. This finding is consistent with that of several research studies in different contexts (Al- Balushi and Osman, 2013; Al-Kindi and AL-Mekhlafi, 2017; Alwehaibi, 2012; Choy and Cheah, 2009; Ouslimani, 2021, Zhang, Yuan, and He, 2020,) in terms of the teachers' failing to integrate critical thinking in their instructional practices. For example, brainstorming was suggested as a technique to stimulate the students' cognitive abilities, where students are expected to solve problems and to generate ideas and share them with the group before the teacher delivers the information. In the observed sessions, when the teacher attempted to get the students to brainstorm the topic at the beginning and even during the session, students were unwilling to guess or share their thoughts. The teacher then ended up rushing into regular lecturing. Again, this could indicate that this was an accepted behaviour in the classroom interaction, where students expect the teacher to provide them with the knowledge and materials they need to know and use in their examination and that their input is not necessary. The teachers' reaction rushing to spoon-feed information seemed to affirm that. This was further evident in the teachers' offers to send the students the slides used during the sessions, and also in providing the option to access lecture notes to make photocopies in preparation for exams. This unidirectional structured teaching approach seemed to discourage active pedagogy and the development of critical thinking in students. This finding corroborates with Duron, Limbach, and Waugh (2006) argument that although delivering content and knowledge to students is important in higher education, it often impedes active learning of critical thinking skills and dispositions.

Another finding is that most participants concurred that to encourage students to think critically, they tend to ask intricate questions. Questions that enhance the students' criticality should go beyond mere fact recall and memorisation. This finding is supported by many scholars (Brookfield, 2012; Haynes and Bailey, 2003; Hemming, 2000) who emphasised the importance of asking complex and open questions in the development of the students' critical thinking skills. The teachers' modelling of thought-provoking and analytical questions might assist the students in formulating analytical questions themselves. Elder and Paul (2004) pointed out that teaching students to actively generate questions is a crucial component of fostering critical thinking. The greater their ability to question, the more they can enhance their learning. When teachers pose advanced questions that require lengthier and more intricate answers, students are motivated to engage in complex thought

processes and are inspired to seek knowledge independently. The field notes gathered during the classroom observation sessions unearthed some inconsistencies. The teachers' questioning practices predominantly lacked thought-provoking elements and were primarily aimed at checking the students' comprehension and knowledge retention. Furthermore, they mainly used display questions, such as requesting students to recapitulate previous lectures or inquiring whether they required further explanations on any lecture aspect. Notably, one participant, highlighting the importance of questioning, stated that he tends to ask the students at the end of each session to reproduce what they have learned. However, this is a strategy to check understanding rather than to stimulate the students' critical thinking skills. There were very few incidents where the participants formulated complex questions that required the students to go beyond yes/no answers (these are elaborated in section 5.4.4.4). It should be noted that regardless of whether the questions were analytical or display, students exhibited a tendency to show reluctance in engaging with them. As explained earlier, The students' resistance to engage could be due to their awareness that teachers are likely to provide them with the answers anyway. And it could be possible also that teachers feel forced into the role of knowledge supplier because of the students' reticence. Another interesting observed behaviour is the time allotted for students to answer the teacher's questions. The participant teachers did not seem to allow sufficient time for the students to think, instead they immediately answered the questions themselves. This behaviour may contribute to students maintaining the habit of being totally dependent on the teacher in the classroom. On this issue, Brookfield (2012) emphasised the importance and necessity of wait time to allow the students to think and formulate their answers.

Projects and presentations were among the instructional activities used by the participants to cultivate critical thinking skills in their students. They claimed that engaging in research projects and delivering presentations fosters an environment where students interact with their peers, facilitating discussions on diverse subjects, exchanging viewpoints, and posing questions. Additionally, these activities promote active participation, thus enhancing the development of students' critical thinking abilities. In practice, the observed presentations did not appear to contribute to the development of students' critical thinking skills, as the primary objective behind these presentations seemed to be focused solely on assessment and grading. There was minimal interaction and participation from the audience, forcing the teachers to intervene by calling on students to ask questions or provide comments on the presentation. The teachers' feedback was very limited and primarily centred on grading without offering personalised guidance for improvement.

Furthermore, despite the teachers' positive perception of the potential impact of group and pair work on fostering students' critical thinking, this belief was not effectively translated into practice. Group work and pair work were only implemented one time, and they did not seem to promote the students' critical thinking skills. During the group work activity, students were instructed to identify keywords in a passage, but no subsequent discussion took place as anticipated. The teacher merely asked the students to share the identified keywords, after which he himself provided explanations for those keywords, thus leaving little room for the students to think or guess the meaning from the context. In the pair work activity, students were asked to paraphrase sentences following the teacher's example. After sharing their paraphrasing, the teacher again provided only limited feedback. Moreover, at the end of one of the observed sessions, students were given the opportunity to read their writing assignments. However, this exercise did not contribute significantly to the enhancement of students' critical thinking skills (see section 5.3.4.1) as each student read his/her report without showing interest in others' reports, and there was no peer feedback or discussion facilitated. Additionally, the teachers' feedback was restricted to superficial praise without specific guidance on what was done well or in need of improvement. Furthermore, students were neither given the opportunity nor encouraged to provide comments or reflections on each other's reports. Research indicated that providing students with feedback on their learning process, along with creating opportunities for them to reflect, assess their own work and review their peers' work, contributes to the enhancement of critical thinking skills (Duron, Limbach, and Waugh, 2006). The lack of active engagement and constructive feedback, in the current study, might hinder the development of critical thinking skills. It should also be noted that in some observed sessions, lecturing was the main activity as there were no tasks or activities employed.

These findings suggest that the teachers may think that they are cultivating the students' critical thinking skills by implementing the aforementioned activities and strategies, however, they are actually developing the students' knowledge comprehension and ability to memorise; an objective that aligns with the primary aim outlined in most of the modules in the curriculum documents, as revealed in the document analysis. This implies again that the teachers' cognitions and practices are interrelated, the lack of the teachers' knowledge of critical thinking and the qualities of being a critical thinker which was revealed in the findings of the second research question, i.e. the absence of modelling critical thinking behaviours might be the reason of the insufficient instructional practices to incorporate these skills in the classroom. In addition to that, this study revealed a

number of challenges that hinder the teachers' attempts to implement critical thinking in their teaching, these are discussed in the following section.

6.5. Challenges of implementing critical thinking

Drawing on the findings of the interviews and observations, several challenges were identified. The research findings revealed that the limited, almost non-existent practice of critical thinking cannot be attributed to a single entity. Rather, it emerges as a result of complex interplays involving multiple parties including: policymakers and curriculum designers, teachers, students, the educational context, and the wider societal norms.

Having established in the previous section that the teachers' lack of knowledge of critical thinking hinders its implementation. The participant teachers attributed the lack of theoretical and practical pedagogy for teaching critical thinking to the absence of training opportunities and professional development. If teachers are not well-trained and qualified to go beyond basic language teaching, it would be very difficult for them to nurture critical thinking in students as they cannot teach something that they themselves are not familiar with. This finding was also reported in Al-Kindi and Al-Mekhlafi's (2017) study as one of the major impediments to the development of critical thinking. The implementation of critical thinking instruction by educators is significantly influenced by the extent of training they receive. Sodoma and Else (2009) conducted a study highlighting that teacher training contributes to raising their confidence in navigating new challenges, particularly when engaging in new practices. Teachers need to receive explicit guidance on the methodologies of teaching and fostering critical thinking. According to Al-Nabahini (2010), if critical thinking is implemented by teachers who are adeptly trained and equipped with comprehensive insights into the underlying principles of critical thinking tasks and strategies; the classroom experience becomes more engaging and enjoyable for both students and instructors. Teacher training offers opportunities for teachers to transform and innovate their teaching methods and to change the monotonous standardised practices. Instead, they can create an environment where students learn to think critically and develop important life-long skills (Lauer, 2005).

The present study further revealed that time limitations and the obligation to cover the prescribed syllabus emerged as significant impediments encountered by university teachers in their endeavours to foster critical thinking within their instructional practices. The process of integrating critical thinking into pedagogy is an effortful process that necessitates an investment of considerable time. Consequently, the participant teachers seemed to be under pressure to deliver the content in its

allotted time, rather than diverting attention to the enhancement of students' critical thinking skills. This was also found in the observed sessions, where the urge to complete the lesson before the end of the session was evident. This practice afforded minimal opportunity for students and teachers to engage in intellectually stimulating discussions. This result is in line with the research done in different contexts by Al-Kindi and AL-Mekhlafi (2017); Hamzah, Zhaffar, Razak (2018); Ouslimani (2021); Hashim (2015); Omar (2015); Prommak (2019) which highlighted the problem of syllabus commitment.

Moreover, the reliance on traditional teaching methods which was prevalent in the classroom observation sessions seemed to create a passive learning environment limiting the classroom interaction and opportunities for students' active engagement. This was also found to be among the hindrances of implementing critical thinking. The large class size, an issue most teachers complained about, coupled with time constraints made critical thinking the first thing to be overlooked. This could explain why lecturing is the dominant teaching method. Khan and Akbar (1997) pointed out that lecturing is the primary and preeminent pedagogical teaching approach in many developing countries, and even worldwide (Marmah, 2014). This might not be surprising, given that this method of teaching is cost-effective, allowing the teacher to manage a large number of students and to cover considerable materials within constrained timeframes. Besides, the lecture method does not require the use of digital technologies and equipment. This aspect aligns with the observation of El Ouachdi-Mirali (2021), who pointed out the limited availability of ICT resources in Algerian universities, stating that 'teaching ICTs in the LMD system is evaluated through an exam and a TP mark. Yet, no computers are available in our department to support learning' (p.5). Numerous studies highlighted the benefits of the rational incorporation of technology, including improved academic performance, increased motivation and self-confidence, and the cultivation of critical thinking skills among students. Furthermore, such integration fosters greater student engagement, participation, and positive attitudes towards learning in general (Arat, 2011; Balanskat, Blamire, and Kefala, 2006; Donmuş and Gürol, 2014; Uluyol, 2011).

The emphasis on syllabus coverage could be attributed to the dominance of the exam-centric culture ingrained in the Algerian educational system, as explored in section 2.4. Teachers appear to acknowledge and accept that the teaching/learning process is geared heavily towards test and exam performance only. This, in turn, compels teachers to instruct students in a manner conducive to passing exams effectively, ultimately prioritising the end product - academic achievement and grades - over the learning process itself. Teachers seemed aware of their focus on content delivery

and exam results, and students seemed to succeed without any particular focus on critical thinking. This suggests that even the assessment criteria primarily evaluate students' ability to regurgitate knowledge rather than assessing their ability to apply the acquired knowledge effectively. This finding was also reported by Nguyen (2017) indicating that teachers had to select a teaching approach and instructional practices that would better assist their students in the exams. Similarly, Choy and Cheah (2009) indicated that on some occasions there is a misalignment between the teachers' expectations of the students' development of critical thinking skills and the methods they use to assess it. Their argument suggests that teachers might primarily assess students' grasp of the material rather than their ability for analytical thinking that extends beyond the content. Consequently, given that the students' achievement is not evaluated in terms of their ability to demonstrate critical thinking skills, two implications might be deduced. First, students might come to believe that critical thinking is not required at all to succeed, and second that their teachers do not value the act of thinking critically and going beyond the information they have given. They may think that it is not desirable or teachers might not be comfortable with students expressing disagreement with them, as indicated by Andrews (2015).

Moreover, when the participant teachers discussed the barriers to implementing critical thinking, they often attributed these challenges primarily to specific traits they perceived in their students. According to some researchers, the issue is less about a deficiency in ability and more about the absence of a 'lack of questing attitude ... or inclinations in thinking critically' (Zin and Eng, 2014, p. 61). Teachers frequently reported that students' conception of learning appeared to be securing good grades and passing tests and exams. This brings us to another finding, which is that the teachers perceived that students' attitudes and mindsets resist activities that may require them to think deeply or make efforts. These traits are: lack of motivation and interest, lack of autonomy and total reliance on teachers and handouts, and students' reticence. They noted that students tend to lose motivation when faced with activities that demand the application of higher-order thinking skills. This aligns with the findings of Hansen and Stephens (2000), who argued that passive students often exhibit a 'low tolerance for challenge' (p. 43).

Furthermore, the participant teachers expressed that the easy and immediate access to information through technology nowadays has created in them an anticipation of rapid achievement. Such a mindset has contributed to diminishing the students' processes of learning and cognitive engagement. Students then prefer to copy content from the internet over making serious efforts to get the work done. This point resonates with Carlson's (2005) view that 21st-century students tend

to be impatient and inclined to anticipate immediate success with the very minimum effort. This finding corroborates with that of Prommak's (2019) study.

As stated by Allamnakrah (2013), it may seem tempting to attribute the current state of education to students' cognitive abilities and traits; nevertheless, it is possible that students have grown accustomed to this approach to learning over the preceding years of their education, where teachers used to expect standard answers and reproduction of the knowledge transmitted by them, while students play a minimal, if any, role in the classroom. According to Stedman and Adams (2012), students are capable of engaging in critical thinking using their own cognitive skills. Similarly, Fisher (2011) argued that critical thinking is an effortful activity in which individuals may have varying proficiency levels. However, an enhancement of these skills requires an investment of the teachers' time and efforts in planning activities which stimulate and improve students' critical thinking skills. This implies that the students-related issues as hindrances to the development of critical thinking might be attributed to the limited practice and opportunities in the classroom. The results of this study revealed also that the teachers lacked confidence in their students' abilities and readiness to develop critical thinking skills. Some teachers perceived their students as hesitant to share their thoughts and as having limitations in expressing themselves effectively due to language constraints. Black (2005) proposed that creating an open and inclusive classroom environment characterised by high expectations, where students feel comfortable and encouraged to share their thoughts, opinions, and ideas without fear, is crucial for the successful cultivation of critical thinking skills. This is also supported by Bailin et al. (1999) who pointed out that successful implementation of critical thinking could be an outcome of 'providing an environment in which critical thinking is valued and students are encouraged and supported in their attempts to think critically' (p. 299).

Lastly, although it was not an aspect that was not largely considered by the participant teachers, Algeria's cultural traditions and values, deeply ingrained in society, may pose challenges to the cultivation of critical thinking skills. These cultural aspects encompass values such as respect, conformity, and obedience to authority figures like parents, to the extent that questioning their actions or statements is often perceived as disrespectful. Avoiding generalisations, these are prevailing features in Algeria and many Arab countries (Alazzi, 2008; Al-Omari, 2008). This suggests that critical thinking may not be widely embraced within family dynamics and may not hold significant social value. These socio-cultural characteristics could influence how students perceive their teachers, leading them to regard educators as authoritative figures with whom they should avoid disagreeing. This attitude toward teachers may impede students' active engagement with

critical thinking. It could also explain students' lack of confidence in expressing their views as highlighted by the participants in the interview data, and the students' reticence and lack of participation as evidenced in the classroom observation. The socio-cultural dimension of critical thinking was discussed further in section 3.4. This finding aligns with the conclusions of Melouah's (2017) study, which explored the cultural influences of the Algerian context on the teaching and learning of critical thinking. According to Melouah, the prevailing culture in Algeria, much like many other cultures in the Arab world, adheres to a conservative and collectivist framework. From a young age, individuals in these cultures are instilled with the principle of valuing the group over individual perspectives. These societies emphasise respect for authority figures, such as parents and teachers, adherence to established rules and conventions, and conformity to group norms. Criticism or questioning is typically perceived as disrespectful behaviour and is contrary to established norms. Furthermore, expressing one's thoughts and challenging established beliefs and values is often discouraged or not readily accepted. This suggests that Algerian socio-cultural norms and values, which are not highly encouraging of critical thinking, may pose challenges to the development of this skill. Opposing this argument, Hadley and Boon (2023) argued that 'the West does not have a corner on the critical thinking market'. They added that observing a debate on a 24-hour news network or briefly scanning comments on social media within the Anglophone world would suffice as evidence for this claim. He also contended Orientalist attitudes claiming that 'the portrayals of Western as opposed to Eastern thinking can be grossly stereotypical; they overlook the diversity of individuals operating within these cultures. There is no one 'Asian' or 'Western' culture in any meaningful' (p.13). This implies that making generalisations about stereotyping and attributing cultural features to an entire community can be unjust, as what occurs, for instance, in one family may differ in another family.

6.6. Conclusion

In this chapter, I have discussed the most important findings in relation to the literature. As demonstrated, the findings of this study have shed light on the state of critical thinking within the English language university curriculum documents and how teachers perceive and implement critical thinking in their classroom pedagogy. A comparison between teachers' perceptions of critical thinking-related classroom practices and their actual practices unveiled inconsistencies between their cognitions and actions. Several factors were identified as interacting in the development of critical thinking. Therefore, instead of attributing the lack of critical thinking practice to a single party, it appeared to be an outcome of a cycle of issues in which each problem generated others. In light

of all the challenges discussed above, it might not be reasonable to expect teachers alone, who themselves lack adequate knowledge and expertise, to introduce it and cultivate it in students. Thus, there is an urgent need for collaboration at various levels to bring about transformation in: educational guidelines, curriculum content, teaching methods, assessment criteria, and more.

In the final chapter, I will conclude this study with a summary of the findings and main implications, highlighting the theoretical and practical contribution, and proposing recommendations for future research in the field.

Chapter 7: Conclusion

7.1. Introduction

The final chapter consists of six main sections. Following the introductory section, I initially summarise the research aims, research questions, methodology, and main findings. In the third and fourth sections, I elaborate on the implications and recommendations of this research at different levels. I then state the study's theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions. In the sixth section, I acknowledge the limitations and based on these, I provide recommendations for future research. A reflection on my PhD journey marks the end of this chapter and the dissertation.

7.2. Summary of the study

The purpose of the current study was to investigate the state of critical thinking in Algerian university EFL classes. This study aimed to develop a holistic understanding of Algerian EFL university teachers' perceptions and actual pedagogical practices concerning critical thinking development. Additionally, it sought to examine the presence of any evidence of critical thinking in the educational objectives outlined in the curriculum documents provided by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research for bachelor's and master's degrees in both majors: Teaching English as Foreign Language and Literature and Civilisation. By delving into the teachers' conceptualisations and practices, and assessing the alignment between the educational objectives outlined in the curriculum documents and the actual manifestation of critical thinking in classroom practices, this study aimed to bridge the gap between theoretical intentions and practical implementation. To guide this investigation, the following four research questions were formulated:

1. To what extent does Algerian higher education encourage the teaching of critical thinking skills?
2. What are university EFL teachers' perceptions of critical thinking, and the importance of its integration in their teaching?
3. What practices do EFL teachers enact to, or consider would foster EFL learners' critical thinking?
4. To what extent has critical thinking moved from theory to actual educational practices?

An interpretative paradigm was maintained in this qualitative case study design. This paradigm was chosen as it aligns with my belief that social phenomena are best understood through the individual perspectives within a specific context. The focus of the study on exploring teachers' subjective

meanings, perspectives, and experiences regarding the state of critical thinking in Algerian higher education reflects a commitment to understanding the participants' views rather than discovering an objective reality. Therefore, I concluded that this approach would be the most effective in achieving the research aims. The data were collected using methodological triangulation, encompassing the analysis of three curriculum documents, ten semi-structured interviews, and ten classroom observations. Inductive thematic analysis was employed for both the semi-structured interview data and observational data. For the document analysis, however, inductive thematic analysis and Bloom's (2001) revised taxonomy of educational objectives were both used. The main findings that address the research questions are summarised below.

The results of this study indicate (License, Master's TEFL, and Master's Literature and Civilization). This finding suggests that curriculum designers have not placed significant emphasis on integrating critical thinking into the educational agenda. Notably, the License document lacked any educational objectives or course content, resulting in a lack of pertinent data for analysis. In contrast, the explicit mention of critical thinking appeared only once in the remaining two documents. Across all levels, the predominant focus of the curriculum documents revolved around expanding students' knowledge and fostering their understanding. While some higher-order thinking skills, such as analysis and evaluation, did make occasional appearances, their occurrence was significantly overshadowed by lower-level thinking skills. The overarching implication of the curriculum documents findings could be that the development of knowledge and comprehension is prioritised over critical thinking. Furthermore, these documents offered little support to teachers seeking to implement critical thinking within their pedagogical practices. They lacked any form of guidelines designed to facilitate the integration of critical thinking. This dearth of supportive resources and the apparent neglect of critical thinking in the curriculum documents seemed to divert the teachers' focus and endeavours away from cultivating critical thinking skills in their students. In fact, considering the prevailing focus of the curriculum documents on knowledge transmission, this might further discourage the promotion of critical thinking in teaching. Notably, The study participants pointed out that although there is no explicit instruction to integrate critical thinking in the official documents communicated by the Ministry of Higher Education, they highlighted that critical thinking is acknowledged as a fundamental principle within the LMD system and an integral aspect of the competency-based approach.

With regard to the participants' conceptualisations of critical thinking and its importance in classroom pedagogy, the findings revealed that the participant teachers had limited knowledge

about what the concept entails. They provided brief, less detailed, but varied responses. However, they shared a common perception of critical thinking as a multifaceted skill encompassing cognitive sub-skills such as analysis, synthesis, evaluation, questioning, truth-seeking, criticism, and problem-solving. It was evident that the responses provided by the teachers indicated that they viewed critical thinking as a set of static cognitive skills, rather than recognising it as a dynamic process that involves not only cognitive abilities but also the development of certain dispositions, traits, and a willingness to engage in critical thinking practices. The participant teachers recognised the significance of critical thinking not only for students' academic success and future research but also for fostering successful and effective citizenship. Furthermore, all participants expressed a positive view regarding the teachability of critical thinking but had concerns about their self-efficacy and ability to stimulate students' critical thinking skills. Moreover, while all participants agreed on its teachability, some of them were uncertain of students' readiness to be introduced to such higher-order thinking skills and suggested that introducing it might be particularly relevant in later stages of education. Concerning the teachers' role in fostering critical thinking and even though they had limited knowledge of the relevant theory and specific pedagogical methods for teaching critical thinking, the participant teachers identified three primary approaches: integrating critical thinking into their teaching approach, promoting critical analysis and discussion in projects like master's dissertations, and incorporating critical thinking implicitly into their daily classroom activities.

This study found that there is a gap between the teachers' perceptions of critical thinking and its teaching and their actual pedagogical practices. The teachers identified questioning, brainstorming, presentations, and group/pair work as the most frequent teaching techniques and activities they employ to develop students' critical thinking skills. However, when examining the observational data, it becomes apparent that these strategies, despite the teachers' beliefs, did not effectively stimulate or enhance students' critical thinking abilities. The prevalent teaching approach observed throughout the classrooms was predominantly teacher-centred. This meant that students heavily depended on the teacher for all aspects of their learning experience, indicating a limited sense of responsibility for their own learning. Additionally, a strong emphasis on assessment was evident in both teacher and student behaviours, with teachers often employing grades as a means to motivate student participation, sometimes assigning activities solely for the purpose of grading. Concerning students' behaviours within the classroom, there was a lack of motivation among students and a tendency toward reticence. For instance, students often remained silent when teachers posed questions as they expected teachers to provide the answers themselves, which they did. These

practices seemed to reinforce the teacher's authoritative role within the classroom, with traditional lecturing being the primary activity occupying a significant portion of class time. Overall, although classroom activities such as group work, projects, discussions and questioning were occasionally incorporated, many of them focused on lower-order cognitive skills, emphasising understanding and recall of information.

This study not only offered insights into prevailing classroom practices and dynamics, but also shed light on the challenges faced in promoting critical thinking. These challenges encompass a variety of factors. Firstly, the physical classroom environment was found to have a significant impact. The presence of a large number of students often led to traditional seating arrangements that discouraged engagement and promoted a teacher-centred approach. Additionally, the limited availability of teaching resources and digital technologies may have hindered student engagement further. Furthermore, given that the curriculum documents lacked clear guidelines and direct objectives regarding the incorporation of critical thinking, teachers tended to believe that academic success could be attained without any specific focus on critical thinking. Commitment to cover the whole content with time constraints, along with the prevalence of an exam-centric educational approach further exacerbated the issue. Student's level of language proficiency and motivation posed additional barriers to the development of critical thinking skills. Moreover, societal norms that prioritise conformity and obedience to authority figures were identified as influential factors. These norms contributed to students' reticence and lack of confidence in expressing opposing opinions and participating in critical thinking activities.

In summary, the lack of awareness regarding the theoretical foundation and practical application of critical thinking is a result of an accumulation of various issues and challenges; addressing these challenges would require significant reforms within the Algerian higher education system. Providing support and guidance to teachers to effectively integrate critical thinking into their pedagogy is also essential for fostering a culture of critical thinking and inquiry among students. The following section provides a more detailed discussion of these implications.

7.3. Implications of the study

Drawing on the findings of this study, particularly on what was found in the curriculum documents, the hindrances and challenges stated by the participants and also observed in the classroom observation, the following implications were generated.

The study's findings have profound implications for higher education in Algeria, particularly in the domain of English language teaching and the cultivation of critical thinking skills. Firstly, the study shed light on a critical factor contributing to the limited emphasis on critical thinking development: the absence of opportunities within current curriculum documents. As such, the merits of the LMD system and the CBA proved challenging to attain on the ground, which can be attributed to the particularities of the context. This emphasised a significant gap between the theoretical importance of critical thinking and its practical integration into educational frameworks, indicating a lack of serious support for and effective integration of critical thinking in both curriculum and practice.

The study's implications extend to the roles of policymakers and curriculum designers, revealing a dearth of awareness and offering a compelling case for recognising critical thinking as a fundamental educational objective, particularly at the university level. This has broad implications for the overall structure and focus of higher education in Algeria. The predominant emphasis on developing students' knowledge and basic skills, even at advanced stages, not only suggested a deprioritisation of higher-order thinking skills but also underscored the exclusive focus placed on advancing students' language proficiency.

Furthermore, the teachers' negative attitudes towards the students' cognitive abilities in practicing even less demanding activities implied their lack of confidence that their students could learn to think critically on their own. Although creating an environment characterised by high- expectations fosters student expression of thoughts, and is essential for the successful implementation of critical thinking in the classroom (Black, 2005), many of them perceived their students to be unwilling to share and lack the command of language to express their thoughts well. For instance, teachers presumed that students do not have the answers to their questions, leading to a tendency to provide responses without encouraging independent thought. Conversely, students anticipated that teachers will provide answers, discouraging them from offering their own insights. This suggested that both teachers and students held negative assumptions about each other. Consequently, this dynamic results in minimal cognitive engagement and criticality.

In terms of classroom pedagogy, the study showed that despite the supposed shift to a student-centred approach, the teacher-centred approach remains the preferred teaching methodology, implying again that given the contextual constraints , it might be difficult for teachers to adopt alternative methods. Furthermore, the teachers' urge to cover the content and to provide all essential learning materials suggested a highly structured teaching approach. This has implications

for classroom dynamics, student-teacher interactions, and the overall learning culture, suggesting a need for a gradual shift from teacher-centred approaches to methods that empower students to take on more active roles in their learning process.

Moreover, the teachers' limited theoretical knowledge and practical pedagogy indicated a need for professional development that would improve teachers' understanding of critical thinking and would help them innovate their teaching approaches. This would further enhance teachers' critical thinking skills and their ability to model and teach these skills effectively in the classroom. The study's findings also revealed that there is a common sense that success can be attained without the development of higher-order thinking skills, with students predominantly asked to reproduce prescribed knowledge. This suggests the importance of incorporating critical thinking into language/course assessments, and moving beyond linguistic proficiency measurement to assessments that genuinely challenge and evaluate students' critical thinking capabilities.

Although the socio-cultural factor in Algeria, where critical thinking may not be widely appreciated in everyday life, was not widely scrutinised in this study, it still endorsed the findings of Melouah (2017) that it poses a unique challenge. This suggests that Algerian society might not widely recognise or appreciate critical thinking in the positive sense it is supposed to convey. In other words, there seems to be a lack of acknowledgement and positive regard for the importance of critical thinking within the cultural and societal context of Algeria. In summary, These implications emphasise the need for a fundamental re-evaluation and restructuring of higher education system in Algeria to effectively integrate and prioritise critical thinking skills in both curriculum and practice.

7.4. Recommendations

Based on the findings and the implications of this study, the following recommendations are proposed for policy, CPD, and classroom practice.

7.4.1. Recommendations for curriculum designers and educational authorities

Drawing on the literature and the findings of this study, teaching critical thinking in a non-Western context, particularly in the field of English language teaching, may present some challenges. Students are expected to simultaneously develop language proficiency and critical thinking skills, which can be a demanding task. However, it is important to note that while this presents a challenge, it is by no means an impossible one. Numerous studies (Dong, 2017; Hadley and Boon, 2023; Liaw, 2007; Yang, Gamble, and Tang, 2012) have advocated for the benefits of integrating critical thinking into EFL or ESL classes, suggesting that this approach can enhance both students' critical thinking abilities

and their language proficiency. Having established through the findings of this study that one of the reasons why critical thinking is not implemented is the absence of affordances within the current curriculum documents, an intensive revision of the curriculum documents by curriculum designers might be highly recommended. Additionally, policymakers should recognise the fundamental role of critical thinking in higher education. Critical thinking should be integrated as a core educational objective (Davis, 2011; Salmon, 2013; Yang, Newby and Robert, 2005), if not the primary one, particularly at the university level. Prioritising critical thinking from higher authorities would inspire and sensitise teachers of the necessity to incorporate it in the teaching and learning process. That is, by placing importance on critical thinking at a higher level, there is an expectation that this emphasis will permeate down to teachers, influencing them to incorporate critical thinking more actively in their educational practices. Therefore, policymakers and curriculum designers should consider critical thinking an integral component throughout the entire educational journey, not only in higher education. This perspective aligns with Bemmoussat and Bouyakoub's (2019) observation that students' approaches to learning are significantly shaped by their preceding educational experiences (section 2.4). Initiating the cultivation of this skill from primary school is particularly crucial as it will instil positive attitudes towards critical thinking in children and cultivate the dispositions and habits of mind required to practice criticality from a young age. Hudgins et al. (1989) stated 'the end goal for teaching children to become critical thinkers is the development of a disposition to do so' (p. 329).

Another recommendation for higher educational authorities is concerned with critical thinking instruction. While opinions on the best approach for teaching critical thinking vary, both direct explicit instruction and implicit instruction have shown significant positive results (see section 3.6). Therefore, a mixed approach to developing critical thinking skills can be highly effective as it combines the advantages of the general, infusion, and immersion approaches (Kennedy et al., 1991). In this mixed approach, the introduction of a stand-alone course on critical thinking may yield significant benefits (Ennis, 1989; Gelder, 2005). Such a course would serve to expand students' understanding of the concept of critical thinking and raise their awareness of its relevance not only within the confines of academia but also in their everyday lives. In the context of Algerian university education, adopting a mixed approach to critical thinking development could prove beneficial. A specialised course covering explicitly the fundamental principles of critical thinking, as suggested by Ennis (1989), might be considered at least to all first-year university students. This explicit instruction is essential as it may not be feasible for some teachers to integrate critical thinking into their lessons

due to time constraints as expressed by many participants. The necessity for this course is further emphasised as critical thinking may not be sufficiently valued and practised in students' daily lives. However, in addition to the stand-alone course, the mixed approach should also incorporate the infusion or immersion approaches to critical thinking teaching across various subjects (Ennis, 1989; Gann, 2013; Nicholas and Raider, 2011). The infusion approach entails encouraging the students explicitly to think critically about the content of the subject matter, whereas the immersion approach involves the integration of critical thinking within the subject matter without explicit instruction (Ennis, 1989). This would provide students with considerable opportunities to put their critical thinking skills into practice. Without rigorous practice, students may erroneously perceive that critical thinking holds little significance or relevance for them.

Both the direct explicit instruction approach in a stand-alone course and the infusion or immersion approaches should seek not only to enhance students' critical thinking skills but also to cultivate their critical thinking dispositions. Therefore, it is crucial to clarify the significance and relevance of critical thinking, along with the expected learning approach from students. This is mainly because students may require evidence that they are engaged in meaningful learning, or they may need to understand the purpose and potential benefits of critical thinking in their learning. In summary, within the university setting, it could be advantageous to consider a compulsory first-year course on critical thinking, along with an infusion or immersion approaches across different subjects.

To ensure that teachers can effectively instil these skills in their students and become critical thinkers themselves, customised professional development would be required. Policymakers, at the level of higher education, should take more serious actions regarding teacher training programmes. Given the significant role that modelling critical thinking by teachers plays in fostering the students' critical thinking, continuous professional development is highly required for teachers to self-reflect on their current teaching practices and to enhance the students' learning experiences. If a drastic change is sought at the level of the teaching pedagogy, sustainable teacher training is emphasised for teachers to innovate their classroom practices, assessment criteria, and classroom management. Additionally, training workshops could be beneficial to equip in-service teachers at all educational levels with critical thinking knowledge, effective teaching strategies, and assessment procedures.

The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research might consider extending its efforts beyond promoting critical thinking solely within curriculum documents, educational guidelines, objectives, and policies. It could further emphasise its importance in national workshops, conferences, and

public speeches to broaden its impact beyond the education sector and reach society at large. The development of critical thinking skills should be a central focus on the national agenda, aspiring to transform Algerian society into one that values and embodies critical thinking principles. Fostering critical thinking not only within school subjects but also throughout society will equip individuals with the capacity for improved problem-solving, informed decision-making, and will raise awareness of societal issues. This approach goes beyond challenging established norms and strives to cultivate a more innovative, adaptable, and democratically engaged society.

Given the significant role that digital technology can play in enhancing students' active engagement, participation, and motivation and in providing a joyful environment for learning (Arat, 2011; Balanskat, Blamire, and Kefala, 2006; Donmuş and Gürol, 2014), the Ministry of Higher Education in accordance with schools' principles might consider providing digital resources including access to the internet, computers, readings materials, etc. Additionally, as suggested by Hamzah, Zhaffar, and Razak, (2018), School administrators and heads of departments should address the management issue of the predominantly large class size and teachers' heavy workloads. This could be particularly important as university teachers often run multiple responsibilities simultaneously. As such, reassessment of the heavy workload that forces teachers to discard paying attention to the core goals of teaching is essential.

Lastly, despite the LMD system and the Competency-Based Approach guidelines emphasizing the importance of fostering critical thinking, numerous studies (Metatla, 2016; Talbi, 2015), including this one, have revealed a significant gap in their effective implementation. The disparity between theory and practice suggests that, unless these policies are seriously integrated and put into action, they will remain mere words on paper. To ensure proper and effective execution of these guidelines, especially those aimed at promoting critical thinking within the teaching/learning process, it is necessary that they are explicitly and comprehensively outlined in the curriculum documents.

7.4.2. Recommendations for teachers

In addition to the educational authority's recommendations, the findings and implications of this study have also generated the following recommendations for teachers to improve their classroom practices regarding for the development of critical thinking.

Incorporating critical thinking in language/course assessment: as stated by many scholars (Brown (2004); Chamot (1995), Tung & Chang, 2009), language learning should not only be limited to linguistic proficiency but should also include the development of higher-order thinking skills. One

way to develop critical thinking is through assessment criteria. An effective language assessment, particularly at higher education, should extend beyond measuring mere language proficiency. It should encompass tasks and assessment items designed to challenge learners' critical thinking capabilities. Drawing on the findings of this study regarding the focus on the students' regurgitation of knowledge in tests and exams, language assessment should provide opportunities for learners to practice and apply critical thinking skills. Teachers may assess students' ability to think critically in the target language through tasks involving text analysis, argumentation, or evaluation of media and everyday issues. Additionally, in classroom teaching, employing techniques that encourage critical thinking, like discussions exploring diverse perspectives on complex topics, can shift the emphasis from rote memorisation to deeper comprehension and analysis, empowering students for critical thinking in real-world situations.

Furthermore, including critical thinking assessment as a compulsory element in university degree exit exams can act as an effective incentive for students to actively focus on improving their critical thinking skills. By integrating critical thinking in high-stakes assessments, students will be more inclined to recognise it as a valuable skill deserving of development.

Teacher expertise and modelling of critical thinking: Teachers play a pivotal role in fostering critical thinking. It is not enough for them to be proficient in the subject matter; they must also be skilled in pedagogical strategies that allow them to act like critical thinkers themselves and then promote critical thinking in students (Al-Kindi and AL-Mekhlafi, 2017). This means that teachers must be aware of critical thinking principles and strategies and model it themselves to students. This can be displayed through knowing how to ask questions effectively, being curious and open to different perspectives, designing activities that encourage deeper thinking, and creating a classroom environment where students feel comfortable expressing their ideas and questioning assumptions. By emphasising these aspects and providing opportunities for students to witness criticality, teachers can guide students toward becoming independent and critical thinkers.

Fostering questioning and inquiry habits: having established in the literature (see section 3.3) that critical thinking dispositions are as important as critical thinking skills, a fundamental aspect of promoting critical thinking in the classroom is instilling a culture of questioning and inquiry among students. As opposed to some participants' perceptions, regardless of their educational language proficiency level, students have the capacity to develop critical thinking skills. Hence, teachers should facilitate this process, emphasising not just what to think but also how to think critically. Encouraging

students to question, probe, and explore various perspectives is essential in fostering their critical thinking abilities and nurturing in them a habit of critical inquiry that extends beyond the classroom.

Providing effective feedback and encouraging self/peer assessment: the finding of this study revealed the limited use of feedback, the absence of self-regulation and reflection among students, and the teachers' limited promotion of peer feedback following activities and presentations. Effective feedback is a powerful tool that teachers should use to foster critical thinking in students (Duron, Limbach, and Waugh, 2006). When teachers provide detailed, specific, and personalised feedback on exams, assignments, and classroom activities, they help students understand their areas of strength and weakness. It also helps them to develop deeper comprehension and thinking beyond rote memorisation and encourages students to identify and focus on the areas that need improvement. Self-assessment and peer assessment take this a step further by requiring students to evaluate their own work and that of their peers. These practices require higher-order thinking skills as students must not only identify errors but also provide reasoned justifications for their evaluation and judgments. This process would enhance their critical thinking abilities significantly.

Classroom pedagogy: while the findings of this study indicated the prevalence of teacher-centred approaches, it may seem reasonable considering the necessity to manage a significant number of students within time constraints. However, teachers should be mindful and attentive to reduce the potential hindrances posed by this teaching method on the cultivation of critical thinking. Given that critical thinking is not widely practised in society, it may seem even more challenging to reform deeply ingrained classroom conventions and traditions that have persisted for generations. These classroom cultural practices, as shared by many participants, include students heavily relying on teachers as the only source of knowledge within the classroom, which runs counter to the principles of critical thinking. Yet, it is essential to recognise that change is not an impossible task. Teachers can actively contribute to changing the classroom dynamics by providing students with opportunities to become more autonomous. They should encourage students to assume more active roles in the learning process and provide them with autonomous tasks that foster their self-confidence. This challenges the traditional 'banking model' of education, as criticised by Freire (2017), which dehumanises learners into objects, controls thinking, and limits creativity and critical thinking by portraying teachers as the sole authorities and knowers. By narrowing the significant gap between teachers and students, often seen as mere recipients, students can enhance their abilities to engage in critical analysis, evaluation, and even questioning and challenging what is taught by the teacher. Teachers can gradually make change in the students learning culture by infusing critical thinking into

their lessons, strategies, and activities. It is equally crucial to convey to students the importance of critical thinking and how it will benefit them in the long run. This approach empowers students to interact with the content of the subject matter in a manner that nurtures critical thinking. Moreover, it is important for teachers to actively contribute to fostering critical thinking in students, avoiding the assumption that these skills will 'spontaneously' develop through assigned tasks and activities.

Scaffolding critical thinking as a process: the participants in this study held the belief that critical thinking is mostly applicable to advanced students, especially those pursuing master's degrees, where they are required to develop critical thinking skills for their dissertations. However, drawing on the literature, critical thinking necessitates consistent and gradual integration as it cannot be developed in a short period of time (Biggs and Tang, 2011; Byrnes ,2012). Therefore, to ensure students develop a strong basis for critical thinking skills, teachers must view critical thinking as an ongoing process rather than a static learning outcome. This perspective acknowledges that students need ongoing support and guidance to become proficient critical thinkers. Teachers could progressively introduce critical thinking in the very first years of education. By scaffolding this process, educators ensure that students continually build on their critical thinking skills throughout their educational journey. This approach ultimately equips students with the ability to think critically in various contexts and enhances their problem-solving, decision-making, and analytical skills.

7.5. Limitations and future research directions

Reflecting on the literature, it was found that the socio-cultural factors have a significant impact on the development of critical thinking. The scope of the current study did not focus on the socio-cultural aspect which affects the development of critical thinking as it was not a recurring theme in the findings. It might be useful for future research to investigate in depth the socio-cultural dimension, and how society, family relationships, and individual traits in the Algerian context might play a role in hindering the development of critical thinking. Furthermore, given that Algeria is a large country with cultural values and traditions that differ from one region to another, and the fact that critical thinking is culturally influenced, further studies could explore EFL university teachers' conceptualisations and pedagogical practices from the different large regions in Algeria to investigate how teachers 'cognitions and practices could vary and be affected by the regional cultural factors, and the local interpretations of the curriculum.

In addition to that, since critical thinking is also subject-specific, further research needs to be carried out in other disciplines in higher education. This is because teachers in different disciplines might

have distinct conceptions and classroom practices regarding the cultivation of critical thinking specific to their subject area. Conducting research in different disciplines might also be pertinent to investigate whether the limited understanding and implementation of critical thinking is exclusive to language classes where the primary objective is typically to improve students' language proficiency, or it extends to other disciplines. Moreover, although the possibility of developing students' linguistic skills and higher-order thinking skills simultaneously was evidenced in the literature, the impact of students' language proficiency in fostering critical thinking in the context of TEFL was expressed by many participants. This raises the question of what factors may hinder critical thinking development in other fields where there is no language barrier, particularly when communication occurs in one's native language. Delving deeper into this issue could shed light on potential barriers to critical thinking that transcend language constraints, and it may offer valuable insights into the broader factors influencing critical thinking across various academic domains.

Studies, including the current one, often rely on teacher experiences or research conducted by teachers on their students, while students' perspectives and experiences have been overlooked. In this context, incorporating student viewpoints can significantly enhance understanding and contribute to the development of critical thinking within the teaching/learning process. This study aimed to capture the state of critical thinking from different dimensions by investigating the representation of critical thinking in the curriculum documents, the teachers' perceptions, and the actual classroom instruction and classroom practices; however, in many instances throughout the data analysis, I realised the need to hear the students' perspectives on the classroom dynamics, on their teachers' practices, and their opinions on the reasons behind of the prevalent students' reticence and many more. Thus, repeating this study and involving the students' part of the story would provide richer data concerning the state of critical thinking in Algeria.

The duration of the study was constrained by external factors, and it was imperative to adhere to a predefined timeline. The data collection phase in this study took place during the COVID-19 period and because of the government restrictions, the new regulations and measures at that time, and time restrictions, I could only conduct 10 one-time classroom observations. Although the data generated was rich and highlighted many frequent patterns on what is going on in classrooms, alerting of similar practices, a longitudinal study using multiple classroom observations may yield different data or confirm the findings of this study.

7.6. Contribution

This study brings several noteworthy contributions to the field: theoretical, practical, and methodological. Notably, there is a scarcity of studies exploring the concept of critical thinking in the Algerian context in general, and in EFL classes at higher education in particular. By delving into this unsearched area, this study offers valuable insights for language researchers and teachers interested in integrating critical thinking into language classrooms. Furthermore, this study addresses a significant gap in research by examining the relationship between policy and implementation regarding critical thinking integration in EFL classrooms, with the objective of promoting high-quality education. While previous studies in Algeria (e.g. Adder and Baghi, 2020; Belit, 2021; Benaissi and Guerroudj, 2015, Bennacer, 2021; Korichi and Bahloul, 2021; Labeled, 2015; Rahmani and Makhoulouf, 2023) have mainly explored and focused on topics like EFL classroom interaction, bilingualism, code-switching, motivation, approaches to developing speaking and listening skills, communication strategies, etc., the role of critical thinking in higher education has received limited attention. Hence, this research makes a vital contribution by understanding the actual state of critical thinking in the context, highlighting the disparity between considering critical thinking as an educational objective and actually integrating it into pedagogical practices. Additionally, addressing this gap and responding to the dearth of research in this area contributes to the call for increased research on critical thinking across various domains and educational levels. Furthermore, concerning the context, the majority of research on critical thinking has been carried out in Western and, more recently, East Asian settings (e.g. Abrami, et al., 2008; Bailin et al., 1999; Ennis, 1991; Dewey, 2017; Lu and Xie, 2018; McPeck, 1991; Norris, 1992; Paul, 1990; Ramanathan and Atkinson, 1999; Siegel, 1999; Yang, Badger, and Yu, 2006; Yang, Newby, and Robert, 2005; Zhang, Yuan, and He, 2020). Consequently, this study offers a valuable addition to the existing body of knowledge related to the state of critical thinking within the MENA (Middle East and North Africa) region.

Another notable contribution of this study lies in its methodological approach. Employing methodological triangulation, this research utilised document analysis to scrutinise three university curriculum documents of English language, conducted semi-structured interviews to explore teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking, and employed classroom observation to investigate teachers' educational practices. This comprehensive approach helped in gathering and cross-checking data on critical thinking perspectives and pedagogical practices of Algerian EFL university teachers, consequently enabled the generation a multidimensional picture of the phenomenon under examination. While interviews and observations have been widely employed in critical

thinking research in the EFL context, this study stresses the value of document analysis as a method. This method helped to bring to light one of the most important reasons why critical thinking plays a negligible role in the Algerian university. In that, it was evident that the very limited knowledge and practice of critical thinking were the result of the lack of opportunities in the curriculum documents. Consequently, teachers have formed the perception that critical thinking is of low significance and, as a result, they have not felt compelled to invest time and effort in its cultivation. This insight can be beneficial for future researchers interested in using document analysis to seek richer data. This multifaceted approach stands out as a unique contribution, as to the best of my knowledge no prior studies have employed this methodological design for a similar investigation in the Algerian context. In fact, I could not locate any research that analysed higher education curriculum documents. The use of document analysis in the three curriculum documents of higher education adds an innovative dimension to the exploration of the state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes. The classroom observation, similarly, has proved to be very effective as it revealed that many aspects of the teachers' perceptions regarding their classroom practices were not reflected in reality.

In terms of practical contribution, this study offers evidence-based implications and recommendations that if taken into consideration could significantly enhance the quality of education. This study amplified the teachers' voices and shed light on the challenges and hindrances associated with the incorporation of critical thinking, such as limitations within the curriculum documents, assessment criteria that focus on the reproduction of knowledge, and teachers' lack of knowledge and expertise, often coupled with a lack of professional development, students' traits like reticence and over-reliance on teachers, etc. this study not only identifies these challenges but also offers implications and recommendations into how teachers could navigate them for more effective implementation. The findings may inform decision-makers, curriculum designers, teacher trainers, and teachers in the field of TEFL or other subjects to develop an understanding of the significance of critical thinking integration. Consequently, if a new curriculum is to be planned and a transformation in the education system is to take place, it is vital for all parties and the community as a whole to take the aforementioned implications along with the world's fast changes into consideration.

7.7. A reflection on my PhD journey

My doctoral journey has proven to be a transformative and fruitful experience, offering valuable lessons that transcend the academic realm and deeply influence both my professional and personal life. Throughout the process of conducting this thesis, my focus extended beyond researching the

critical thinking cognitions and practices of participants. I also delved into my own critical thinking development, aspiring to become a discerning researcher and an individual who fully embraces critical thinking. Engaging in this study facilitated my growth as a researcher, involving critical thinking, engaging with the literature, collecting and analysing qualitative data, and crafting the final product. Navigating through rigorous research methodologies provided a profound learning experience that significantly contributed to my personal development. This journey is not just a means to an end but the beginning of a longer path, motivating me to conduct further research in my areas of interest and contribute meaningfully to the academic world.

On a personal level, the PhD experience has been enriching, enabling me to confront and overcome my weaknesses. Patience and persistence have become integral aspects of my character, qualities that I believe will fortify me in overcoming challenges and evolving as a better person. Admittedly, I grappled with confusion and moments of feeling lost, but I successfully navigated through these challenges. The challenges encountered in this journey were not in vain; they served a purpose, even if not immediately apparent. I realised that these challenges were not obstacles but sources of enrichment. Despite being abroad, away from family, and navigating the complexities of the COVID-19 pandemic, this experience of spending four years in the UK proved unforgettable as it allowed me to connect with people from different countries and cultures. I express my sincere gratitude to the Algerian government for granting me this opportunity.

I can say now that this study succeeded in shedding light on the state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes. I am hopeful that this research will inspire further exploration in the field, potentially leading to practical changes in the future. Although the journey was hard, the potential impact on the academic landscape and the prospect of contributing to positive changes in this understudied area in my home country make it all worthwhile.

List of references

Abdaoui, F. and Grine, N. (2020) 'The effect of university education on developing learners' critical thinking abilities: A comparison between freshmen and senior EFL learners at the University of Guelma', *Journal of Psychological and Educational Sciences*, 6 (2), pp.389-398. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349945836_The_effect_of_university_education_on_developing_learners'_critical_thinking_skills_A_comparison_between_freshmen_and_senior_learners_of_English_as_a_Foreign_Language_at_the_University_of_Guelma/citations

Abrami, P. C., Bernard, R. M., Borokhovski, E., Wade, A., Surkes, M., Tamim, R., and Zhang, D. (2008) 'Instructional interventions affecting critical thinking skills and dispositions: A stage 1 meta-analysis', *Review of Educational Research*, 78(4), pp.1102–1134. Available at: doi:10.3102/0034654308326084.

Abrami, P. C., Bernard, R. M., Borokhovski, E., Wade, A., Surkes, M. A., Tamim, R. and Zhang, D. (2008) 'Instructional interventions affecting critical thinking skills and dispositions: A stage 1 meta-analysis', *Review of Educational Research*, 78(4), 1102–1134. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654308326084>

ACTFL (American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages) (2018) *Literacy in language learning*. Available at: <https://www.actfl.org/guiding-principles/literacy-language-learning> (Accessed: 20 August 2020)

Adelman, C., Kemmis, S., and Jenkins, D. (1980) 'Rethinking case study: notes from the second Cambridge Conference', in Simons, H. (Ed.) *Towards a science of the singular*. Norwich, UK: Centre for applied research in education, University of east of Anglia, pp.45-61.

Adeyemi, A. D. (2008) *Approaches to teaching English composition writing at junior secondary schools in Botswana*. PhD thesis. University of South Africa. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10500/2340> (Accessed: 9 June 2021).

Ahouari-idri, N. (2005) 'The LMD System Experience as a Struggle between the Educational Development and Reform: An Analytical Study of the Endeavour of the Academic Year 2004/2005 in Bejaia University with Suggested Solutions' (from the Rencontres Internationales sur le Dispositif LMD –Problèmes et Perspectives, University of Bejaia, 4-5 December), *ResearchGate*. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285594547>

Alagözlü, N. (2007) 'Critical thinking and voice in EFL writing', *Asian EFL Journal*, 9(3), pp. 118-136.

Alazzi, K.F. (2008) 'Teachers' perceptions of critical thinking: a study of Jordanian secondary school social studies teachers', *Soc. Stud.*, 99(6), pp. 243-248. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3200/TSSS.99.6.243-248>

Aliakbari, M. and Sadeghdaghighi, A. (2013) 'Teachers' Perception of the Barriers to Critical Thinking', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 70, pp. 1-5. Available at: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.01.031.

Al-Kindi, N. S. and AL-Mekhlafi, A. M. (2017) 'The practice and challenges of implementing critical thinking skills in Omani post-basic EFL classrooms', *English Language Teaching*, 10(12), pp. 116-133. Available at: URL: <http://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v10n12p116>

Allamnakhrah, A. (2013) 'Learning critical thinking in Saudi Arabia: Student perceptions of secondary pre-service teacher education programs', *Journal of Education and Learning*, 2(1), pp. 197-210. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/jel.v2n1p197>

Alnofaie, H. (2013) 'A framework for implementing critical thinking as a language pedagogy in EFL preparatory programmes', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 10, pp. 154-158. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2013.09.002>

Al-Omari, J. (2008) *Understanding the Arab culture : a practical cross-cultural guide to working in the Arab world*. How To Books.

Al-Saadi, H. (2014) 'Demystifying ontology and epistemology in research methods', *Research Gate*, 1(1), pp.1-10. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260244813>

Alwehaibi, H. (2012) 'Novel program to promote critical thinking among higher education students: Empirical study from Saudi Arabia', *Asian Social Science*, 8(11), pp. 193-204.

Amziane, H. and Guendouzi, A. (2015) 'Algerian EFL course, the digital competence, and the critical thinking skills' (from the International conference proceedings, Bejaia University, August 2015), *Arab World English Journal*, August 2015, pp.70-77. Available at: <https://awej.org/images/conferences/BejaiaProceedings2015/7.pdf>

Anderson, L. W. and Krathwohl, D. R. (2001) *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing*. New York: Longman.

Andrews, S.F. (2000) *Critical thinking in South Dakota public schools grades 3, 4, and 5: The influence of teacher's behaviors, perceptions, and attitudes*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. South Dakota: University of South Dakota.

Angen, M.J. (2000) 'Evaluating interpretive inquiry: reviewing the validity debate and opening the dialogue', *Qualitative Health Research*, 10, pp. 378-395. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/104973230001000308>

Anney, V. N. (2015) 'Ensuring the quality of the findings of qualitative research: looking at trustworthiness criteria', *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 5 (2), pp.272–281. Available at: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/1419/f7b54e6b7f1215717a5056e0709f8946745b.pdf>

Arat, T. (2011) *The usage of communication technologies in higher education*. PhD thesis. Selçuk University, Konya.

Arfae, A. M. (2019) 'The Impact of Teaching Critical Thinking on EFL Learners' Speaking Skill: A Case Study of an Iranian Context', *English Language Teaching*, 13(1), pp. 121-123. Available at: Doi: 10.5539/elt.v13n1p112

Arksey, H. and Knight, P.T. (1999) *Interviewing for social scientists: an introductory resource with examples*. London: Sage.

Arum, R. and Roska, J. (2011) *Academically adrift Limited learning on college campuses*. Chicago, IL: The University of Chicago Press.

Atkinson, D. (1997) 'A critical approach to critical thinking in TESOL', *TESOL Quarterly*, 31 (1), pp.79-95. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3587975>

Atkinson, D. (1997) 'A critical approach to critical thinking in TESOL', *TESOL Quarterly*, 31 (1), pp.79-95. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3587975>

Axinn, W. G., and Lisa D. P. (2006) *Mixed Method Data Collection Strategies*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Baghoussi, M. and El Ouchdi, I. Z. (2019) 'The Implementation of the Project-Based Learning Approach in the Algerian EFL Context: Curriculum Designers' Expectations and Teachers' Obstacles', *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, 10(1), pp. 271-282. Available at: DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no1.23>

Baghoussi, M. and El Ouchdi, I. Z. (2019) 'The Implementation of the Project-Based Learning Approach in the Algerian EFL Context: Curriculum Designers' Expectations and Teachers' Obstacles',

Arab World English Journal (AWEJ), 10(1), pp. 271-282. Available at: DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no1.23>

Bailin, S., Roland C., Jerrold R. C., and Leroi B. D. (1999) 'Common Misconceptions of Critical Thinking', *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 31(3), pp. 269-283. Available at: doi:10.1080/002202799183124

Balanskat, A., Blamire. R., and Kefala, S. (2006) 'The ICT impact report : A review of studies of ICT impact on schools in Europe, European school net.

Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:5258214>

Barnett, R. (1997) *Higher education: a critical business*. Milton Keynes: Open University Press.

Beck, R. N. (1979) *Handbook in social philosophy*. New York: Macmillan.

Belhamidi, S. (2014) 'Collaboration, questioning and encouraging to foster critical thinking', *Literacy Information and Computer Education Journal*, 5(1), pp. 1483-1491. Available at: doi: 10.20533/licej.2040.2589.2014.0198

Bell L., Neary M., and Stevenson H. (2009) *The future of higher education: policy, pedagogy and the student experience*. London: Continuum International Publishing Group.

Benmati, K. L. A (2008) *Is the Algerian educational system weakening? An investigation of the high school curricula and their adequacy with the university curricula*. PhD Thesis. Mentouri University Constantine .Available at: [file:///C:/Users/77901060/Downloads/Benmati%20\(2008\)%20Algerian%20education%20system.pdf](file:///C:/Users/77901060/Downloads/Benmati%20(2008)%20Algerian%20education%20system.pdf) (Accessed: 26 November 2019)

Benmoussat, N. D. and Benmoussat, S. (2018a) 'ELT in Algeria: The hegemony of the teach-to-the-test approach', *English Language and Literature Studies*, 8(2), pp.63-68. Available at: <http://doi.org/10.5539/ells.v8n2p63>.

Benmoussat, N. D. and Benmoussat, S. (2018b) 'English language education in Algeria in the light of the test-oriented teaching approach', *International Journal of Linguistics*, 10(4), pp.29-42. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijl.v10i4.13310>.

Benmoussat, N. D. and Bouyakoub, N. (2019) 'English language education in Algeria: Hostage of an exam-centric education system', *Arab World English Journal*, 10(3), pp. 202-219. Available at: DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no3.14>.

Benmoussat, S. and Benmoussat, N. D. (2018) 'The teach-to-the-test approach: doing harm to the lifelong educational paradigm of Algerian EFL learners', *English Language, Literature & Culture*, 3(1), pp. 1-6. Available at: doi: 10.11648/j.ellc.20180301.11

Bernard, H. R. (2000) *Social Research Methods- Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. California: Sage Publications, Inc.

Beyer, B. K. (2008) 'How to teach thinking skills in social studies and history', *The Social Studies*, 99(5), pp.196-201. Available at: doi:10.3200/TSSS.99.5.196-201.

Biggs, J., and Tang, C. (2011) *Teaching for quality learning at university*. 4th edn. Maidenhead: Open University Press.

Black, S. (2005) 'Teaching students to think critically', *The Education Digest*, 70(6), p.42-47.

Bloom, B.S. (1956) *Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals*. New York: Longman.

Bloomberg, L.D. and Volpe, M. (2012) *Completing your qualitative dissertation: A road map from beginning to end*. London: Sage Publications.

Bowden, J. A. (2004) 'Capabilities-driven curriculum design', in C. Baillie and I. Moore (eds.) *Effective teaching and learning in engineering*, London: Kogan, pp. 36-47.

Bowden, J. A. (2004) 'Competency-based learning', in S. Stein and S. Farmer (eds.) *Connotative learning: the trainer's guide to learning theories and their practical application to training design*, Dubuque, IA: Kendall Hunt Publishing, pp. 91-100.

Bowen, G. A. (2009) 'Document analysis as a qualitative research method', *Qualitative Research, Journal*, 9(2), pp. 27-40. Available at: doi: 10.3316/QRJ0902027

Boyatzis, R. E. (1998) *Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Boynton, P.M. (2005) *The research companion: A practical guide for the social and health sciences*. Hove, E. Sussex: Psychology Press.

- Braun H., Shavelson R., Troitschanskaia, O. and Borowiec, K. (2020) 'Performance assessment of critical thinking: conceptualization, design, and implementation', *Frontiers in Education*, 5(156). Available at: doi: 10.3389/educ.2020.00156
- Braun, H. (2019) 'Performance assessment and standardization in higher education: a problematic conjunction?', *Br. J. Educ. Psychol*, 89, pp. 429-440. Available at: doi: 10.1111/bjep.12274
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77-101. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2019) *Thematic analysis | a reflexive approach*. Available at: <https://www.psych.auckland.ac.nz/en/about/thematic-analysis.html> (Accessed: 25 July 2021)
- British Educational Research Association [BERA] (2018) *Ethical guidelines for educational research*, 4th edn, London. Available at: <https://www.bera.ac.uk/researchers-resources/publications/ethicalguidelines-for-educational-research-2018>
- Brookfield, S. D. (2012) *Teaching for critical thinking: Tools and techniques to help students question their assumptions*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Brown, J. D. (2014) *Mixed methods research for TESOL*. United Kingdom: Edinburgh University Press.
- Browne, M. N., and Keeley, S. M. (2007) *Asking the right questions: A guide to critical thinking*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Bryman, A. (2008) *Social research methods*. 3rd edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Buphate, T. and Esteban, R.H. (2018) 'Integration of critical thinking approaches in Thailand university classrooms: perceptive analysis', *Asian EFL Journal*, 20(6), pp. 414- 428.
- Byrnes, H. (2012) 'Of frameworks and the goals of collegiate foreign language education: Critical reflections', *Applied Linguistics Review*, 3(1), 1-24.
- Chapelle, C. A., and Voss, E. (2021) *Validity argument in language testing: Case studies of validation research*. Cambridge University Press.
- Choy, S. C. and Cheah, P. K. (2009) 'Teacher perceptions of critical thinking among students and its influence on higher education', *International Journal of teaching and learning in Higher Education*, 20(2), 198-206.

Choy, S. C. (2003) *An investigation into the changes in perceptions of and attitudes towards learning English in a Malaysian college*. PhD thesis. University of Exeter, Exeter, U.K.

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2011) *Research methods in education*. 7th edn. London: Routledge.

Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K. (2007) *Research methods in education*. 6th edn. London: Routledge.

Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K. (2018) *Research methods in education*. 8th edn. London: Routledge.

Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K. (2003) *Research methods in education*. 5th edn. London: Routledge.

Cooper, D. C. and Schindler, P.S. (2001) *Business research methods*. 7th edn. New York: McGraw-Hill.

Corbin, J. and Strauss, A. (2008) *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and Procedures for developing grounded theory*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 3rd edn. California: Sage.

Creswell, J. W. (1998) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five Traditions*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.

Creswell, J. W. (2003) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi: SAGE.

Creswell, J. W. (2013) *Research design: qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. 4th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Creswell, J. W. (2015) *Educational research: planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. New York: Pearson.

Creswell, J. W. and Plano Clark, V.L. (2011) *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. London: Sage Publications.

Creswell, J.W. (2007) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches*. 2nd edn. Sage: Thousand Oaks

- Creswell, J.W. (2009) *Research Design*. London: Sage.
- Creswell, J.W. (2013) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches*. 3rd edn. Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- Crotty, M. (1998) *The foundations of social research: meaning and perspective in the research process*. London: Sage.
- Davidson, B. (1998) 'Comments on Dwight Atkinson's 'a critical approach to critical thinking in TESOL', *TESOL Quarterly*, 32(1), pp. 119-123. Available at: <http://www.jstor.com/stable/3587906>
- Davies, M. (2011) 'Introduction to the special issue on critical thinking in higher education', *Higher Education Research & Development*, 30(3), pp. 255-260. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2011.562145>
- Davies, M. (2013) 'Critical thinking and the disciplines reconsidered', *Higher Education Research & Development*, 32(4), pp.529–544. Available at: doi:10.1080/07294360.2012.697878.
- Davies, M. (2015) 'A model of critical thinking in higher education', in Paulsen, M. (ed.) *Higher education: handbook of theory and research*. Switzerland: Springer, Cham, pp 41-92.
- Davies, W. (2019) *Nervous states: democracy and the decline of reason*. W.W. Norton & Company.
- Delmastro, A. L., and Balada, E. (2012) Model and strategies for promoting critical thinking in the classroom of foreign languages, *Synergies Venezuela*, 7, pp. 25-37. <https://gerflint.fr/Base/venezuela7/delmastro.pdf>
- Denscombe, M. (1998) *The good research guide—for small-scale social research projects*. Buckingham, England; Philadelphia, Pa.: Open University Press.
- Denscombe, M. (2007) *The Good Research Guide for Small-Scale Social Research Projects*. Maidenhead: Open University Press.
- Denscombe, M. (2014) *The good research guide*. 4th edn. Maidenhead , UK: Open University Press.
- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (2005) *The sage handbook of qualitative research*.3rd edn. Thousand oaks, CA: Sage.

- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2011) 'Introduction: the discipline and practice of qualitative research', in Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.) *The sage handbook of qualitative research*. 4th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, pp.1-25.
- DeWalt, K. M. and DeWalt, B. R. (2002) *Participant observation: a guide for fieldworkers*. Walnut Creek, CA: Altamira Press.
- Djabri A. (1981) *Language in Algeria: A continuing problem*. PhD thesis. University of Wales.
- Djamaa, S. (2016) 'Reading the book versus 'reading' the film: cinematic adaptations of literature as catalyst for EFL students' critical thinking dispositions', *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 7(2), pp. 252-263. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0702.03>
- Djamaa, S. (2018) 'From book to screen: Adopting cinematic adaptations of literature in the EFL classroom to hone students' critical thinking skills', *Computers in the Schools*, 35(2), pp. 88-110. Available at: doi: 10.1080/07380569.2018.1463010
- Dong, M., Li, F., and Chang, H. (2023) 'Trends and hotspots in critical thinking research over the past two decades: Insights from a bibliometric analysis', *Heliyon*, 9(6). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16934>
- Donmuş, V. E., & Gürol, M. (2014) 'The effect of the use of technology on mathematics achievement: A meta-analysis study', *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(6), pp. 157-162.
- Dornyei, Z. (2007) *Research methods in applied linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Duron, R., Limbach, B., and Waugh, W. (2006) 'Critical thinking framework for any discipline', *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 17(2), 160-166.
- Dwyer, C. P. (2017) *Critical thinking: Conceptual perspectives and practical guidelines*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- El Ouchdi-Miarli, I. (2015b) 'Learning at school in Algeria between internalizing data and developing critical thinking' (from the First international symposium on critical and analytical thinking, Sakarya.
- El Ouchdi-Miarli, I. (2021) 'Learning at School in Algeria between Internalizing Data and Developing Critical Thinking', ResearchGate, Available at: 10.1016/S2215-0366(21)00084-5
- Elder, L., and Paul, R. (2012) *The Thinker's guide to analytic thinking*. Tomales, CA: Foundation for Critical thinking.

- England, K. (1994) 'Getting personal: reflexivity, positionality and feminist research', *Professional Geographer*, 46(1), pp. 80-89. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0033-0124.1994.00080.x>
- Ennis, H. R., and Weir, E. (1985) *The Ennis-Weir Critical Thinking Essay Test*. Midwest publications: Pacific Grove.
- Ennis, R. H. (1998) 'Is critical thinking culturally biased?' *Teaching Philosophy*, 21(1), pp. 15-33. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5840/teachphil19982113>
- Ennis, R. H. (2011) 'Critical thinking: Reflection and perspective (Part I)', *Inquiry: Critical Thinking Across the Disciplines*, 26(1), 4-18. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5840/inquiryctnews20112613>
- Ennis, R. H. (2018) 'Critical thinking across the curriculum: A vision', *TOPOI*, 37(1), pp. 165-184. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11245-016-9401-4>.
- Ennis, R. H. "Critical thinking assessment," In *Critical Thinking and Reasoning: Current Theories, Research, and Practice*, D. Fasko, Ed., Hampton Press, 2003, pp. 179-186.
- Ennis, R.H. (1989) 'Critical thinking and subject specificity: clarification and needed research', *Educational Researcher*, 18 (3), pp. 4-1. Available at: DOI: 10.3102/0013189X018003004
- Ennis, R.H. (1993) 'Critical thinking assessment', *Theory into Practice*, 32(3), pp. 179-186. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405849309543594>
- Ennis, R.H. (2015) 'Critical thinking: A streamlined conception', in Davies M., and Barnett R. (eds) *The palgrave handbook of critical thinking in higher education*. Palgrave Macmillan: New York, pp. 31-47.
- Ennis, R.H., (1996) 'Critical thinking dispositions: their nature and assessability', *Informal Logic*, 18(2-3), pp. 165-182. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.22329/il.v18i2.2378>
- Entelis, J.P. (1981) 'Elite political culture and socialization in Algeria: Tensions and discontinuities', *Middle East Journal*, 35(2), pp. 191-208. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4326199>
- Erlandson, D.A., Harris, E.L., Skipper, B.L. and Allen, S.D., (1993) *Doing naturalistic inquiry: A guide to methods*. London: Sage.
- Erikson, M. G. and Erikson, M. (2019) 'Learning outcomes and critical thinking – good intentions in conflict', *Studies in Higher Education*, 44(12), pp. 2293-2303. Available at: Doi [10.1080/03075079.2018.1486813](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2018.1486813)

Fábíán, G. (2015) 'Non-critical thinking: What if not thinking? Procedia', *Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 186, pp. 699-703.

Fabian, G. (2015) 'The conceptual framework of critical thinking in education: a proposal', *Research Gate*. Available at: DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.16470.24642](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16470.24642)

Facione, P. A. (1990) *The Delphi Report: critical thinking: a statement of expert consensus for purposes of educational assessment and instruction*. Millbrae, CA: California Academic Press.

Facione, P. A. (2000) 'The disposition toward critical thinking: Its character, measurement, and relation to critical thinking skill', *Informal Logic*, 20(1), pp. 61–84. Available at: DOI: 10.22329/il.v20i1.2254

Facione, P.A and Facione N.C. (1992) *California critical thinking disposition inventory*. Academic Press, Millbrae: California.

Finlay, L. (2002) "'Outing" the researcher: the provenance, process, and practice of reflexivity', *Qualitative Health Research*, 12(4), pp. 531-545. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F104973202129120052>

Fisher, A. (2011) *Critical thinking: an introduction*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Fisher, A., and Scriven, M. (1997) *Critical thinking: its definition and assessment*. Norwich: Centre for Research in Critical Thinking, University of East Anglia.

Fox, H. (1994) *Listening to the world: cultural issues in academic writing*. Urbana, IL: National Council of Teachers of English.

Freebody, P. (2003) *Qualitative research in education: Interaction and Practice*. London: Sage.

Freire, P. (2017). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. [Penguin Classics](https://www.penguinclassics.com/)

Gann, D. (2016) 'Multi-step process for critical thinking instruction step one: Explicit instruction through product delivered content', *Tokyo University of Science Research Journal*, 48, pp. 157–171.

Garton, S. and Copland, F. (2010) 'I like this interview; I get cakes and cats!': the effect of prior relationships on interview talk', *Qualitative Research*, 10(5), pp. 533-551. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1468794110375231>

- Gelder, T. (2015) 'Using argument mapping to improve critical thinking skills' in M. Davies and R. Barnett (Eds.) *The Palgrave handbook of critical thinking in higher education*, New York: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 183–192.
- Gherzouli, I. (2019) 'Educational reforms and language planning quandary in Algeria: An illustration with Arabization', *Sustainable Multilingualism*, 15, pp. 27-47. Available at: 10.2478/sm-2019-0012.
- Gillham, B. (2000) *The research interview*. London: Continuum.
- González, J. (2006) *Discernimiento, evolución del pensamiento crítico en la educación superior, El proyecto de la Universidad Icesi*. Universidad ICESI. Cali, Colombia.
- Grabe, W. (2010) *How reading works: Comprehension process. Reading in a second language*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Gray, B. (2008) 'Putting emotion and reflexivity to work in researching migration', *Sociology*, 42(5), pp. 935-952. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0038038508094571>
- Gray, D. E. (2009) *Doing Research in the Real World*. 2nd edn. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore, Washington: SAGE.
- Green, P. (2015) 'Teaching critical thinking for lifelong learning' in M. Davies and R. Barnett (Eds.) *The Palgrave handbook of critical thinking in higher education*, New York: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 107–122.
- Grix, J. (2004) *The foundations of research*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Guba, E. G., and Lincoln, Y. S. (1994) 'Competing paradigms in qualitative research', in Denzin, N. k. and Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.) *Handbook of qualitative research*. London: Sage, pp. 105-117.
- Guest, G., MacQueen, K. M. and Namey, E. E. (2012) *Applied thematic analysis*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Fisher, A., and Scriven, M. (1997) *Critical thinking: its definition and assessment*. Norwich: Centre for Research in Critical Thinking, University of East Anglia.
- Hadjoui, G. and Kheladi, M. (2014) 'Towards an integrative approach to teaching literature in an EFL context', *Impact: International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature*, 2(4), pp. 113-126. Available at :

[https://www.academia.edu/8525240/TOWARDS AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING LITERATURE IN AN EFL CONTEXT](https://www.academia.edu/8525240/TOWARDS_AN_INTEGRATIVE_APPROACH_TO_TEACHING_LITERATURE_IN_AN_EFL_CONTEXT)

Hadley, G., and Boon, A. (2022) *Critical Thinking*. New York: Routledge.

Hager, P. and Kaye, M. (1992) 'Critical Thinking in Teacher Education: A Process-Oriented Research Agenda', *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 17(2), pp. 26-33. Available at: 10.14221/ajte.1992v17n2.4.

Halonen, J. S. (1995) 'Demystifying critical thinking', *Teaching of Psychology*, 22(1), pp. 75–81. https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1207/s15328023top2201_23

Halpern, D. F. (1998) 'Teaching critical thinking for transfer across domains: disposition, skills, structure training, and Metacognitive Monitoring', *American Psychologist*, 53(4), pp. 449-455. Available at: doi:10.1037/0003-066X.53.4.449

Halpern, D. F. (2001) 'Assessing the effectiveness of critical thinking instruction', *The Journal of General Education*, 50(4), pp. 270–286. Available at: DOI: 10.1353/jge.2001.0024

Halpern, D. F. (2014) *Thought and Knowledge: An Introduction to Critical Thinking*. 5th edn. New York and London: Psychology Press.

Hammersley, M. (2013) *What is qualitative research?* London: Bloomsbury Academic.

Hamzah, M. I., Zhaffar, N. M., and Razak, K. A. (2018) 'Barriers in teaching critical thinking in Islamic education. *Creative Education*, 9, pp. 2350-2356. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2018.914175>

Harklau, L. (1994) 'ESL versus mainstream classes: Contrasting L2 learning environments', *TESOL Quarterly*, 28(2), pp 241-272. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3587433>

Harrell, M., and Wetzel, D. (2015) 'Using argument diagramming to teach critical thinking in a first-year writing course' in M. Davies and R. Barnett (Eds.) *The Palgrave handbook of critical thinking in higher education*, New York: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 213–232.

Hart Research Associates (2013) *It takes more than a major: employer priorities for college learning and student success*. Washington, DC: Association of American Colleges and Universities and Hart Research Associates.

Hassan, K. and Madhum, G. (2007) 'Validating the Watson Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal', *Higher Education*, 54, pp.361-383. Available at: DOI: 10.1007/s10734-006-9002-z

Hatch, J. A. (2002) *Doing qualitative research in education settings*. Albany: State University of New York Press.

Hay, E. A. (1987) *The Critical Thinking Movement and Its Implication for the Teaching of Speech Communication* (from the the Annual Meeting of the Speech Communication Association. Boston, MA, 5-8 November 1987), Educational Resources Information Center (ERIC). Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED290196>

Haynes, T., and Bailey, G. (2003) 'Are you and your basic business students asking the right questions?', *Business Education Forum*, 57(3), pp. 33–37. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ660496>

Hemming, H. E. (2000) 'Encouraging critical thinking: "But...what does that mean?"', *Journal of Education*, 35(2), pp. 173-186. Available at: <https://mje.mcgill.ca/article/view/8525>

Hirai, A., Oka, H., Kato, T. and Maeda, H. (2022) 'Development and validation of an English test measuring EFL learners' critical thinking skills', *Language Testing in Asia Lang Test Asia*, 12(45) . Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-022-00193-2>

[Hitchcock, D. \(2020\) 'Critical thinking', in Zalta, E. N. \(ed.\) *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* , URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2020/entries/critical-thinking/>](https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2020/entries/critical-thinking/).

Hitchcock, G. and Hughes, D. (1995) *Research and the teacher*. 2nd edn. London: Routledge.

Ho, I.(1998) *Relationships between motivation/attitude, effort, English proficiency, and socio-cultural educational factors and Taiwan technological university/institute students''*, *English learning strategy use*. PhD thesis. Auburn University.

Hogan, M. (2016) 'What are the key dispositions of good critical thinkers? A collective intelligence analysis of critical thinking dispositions', *Psychology today*. Available at: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/in-one-lifespan/201601/what-are-the-key-dispositions-good-critical-thinkers> (accessed 4/01/2020)

Huber, C. R. and Kuncel, N. R. (2016) 'Does college teach critical thinking? A meta-analysis', *Review of educational research*, 86(2), pp. 431-468.

- Karimi, L. and Veisi. F. (2016) 'The impact of teaching critical thinking skills on reading comprehension of Iranian intermediate EFL learners', *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 6(9), pp. 1869-1876. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17507/tpls.0609.21>
- Kennedy, M., Fisher, M. B., and Ennis, R. H. (1991) 'Critical thinking: Literature review and needed research' in Idol, L. and Jones, B. F. (Eds.) *Educational values and cognitive instruction: Implications for reform*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum, pp. 11-40.
- Kheladi, M. (2019) 'Re-thinking the Practice of Teaching Literature to Enhance EFL Students' Civic Skills: An Algerian Perspective', *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, 10(2), pp. 124-135. Available at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no2.11>
- Ku, K. Y. (2009) 'Assessing students' critical thinking performance: Urging for measurements using multi-response format', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 4(2009), pp. 70–76. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2009.02.001>
- Kubota, R. (1999) 'Japanese culture constructed by discourses: Implications for applied linguistics research and ELT', *TESOL Quarterly*, 33(1), pp. 9–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3588189>
- Kumar, R. (1999) *Research Methodology: A step by-step guide for beginners*. London: Sage Publications.
- Kumar, R. (2005) *Research Methodology*. 2nd edn. SAGE publications.
- Kusumi, T. (2018) 'Critical thinking in support of literacy development: Implications for reading science', *The Science of Reading*, 60, pp. 129–137. Available at: https://doi.org/10.19011/sor.60.3_129.
- Kvale, S. and Brinkmann, S. (2009) *Inter Views: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- Lai, E. R. (2011) 'Critical thinking: A literature review', *Pearson's Research Reports*, 6, pp. 40- 41. Available at: <http://images.pearsonassessments.com/images/tmrs/CriticalThinkingReviewFINAL.pdf>
- Lam, H.P. (1994) 'Methodology washback-an insider's view' (from the International Language in Education Conference, Honk Kong: University of Honk Kong), *Bringing about change in language education*, pp. 83-102.
- Lane, S., and Stone, C. A. (2006) "Performance assessment," in Educational Measurement, 4th Edn, ed. R. L. Brennan (Lanham, MA: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers), pp. 387–432.

- Lantolf, J. P. and Thorne, S. L. (2006) *Sociocultural theory and the genesis of second language development*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Larkin, S. (2009) 'Socially mediated metacognition and learning to write', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 4(3), pp. 149-159. Available at: 149-159. 10.1016/j.tsc.2009.09.003
- Lather, P. (2004) 'Critical inquiry in qualitative research: Feminist and post structural perspectives – science 'after truth'', in De Marrais, K. and Lapan S. D. (eds.) *Foundation for research: methods of inquiry in education and the social sciences*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum, pp. 203-15.
- LeCompte, M. D., and Schensul, J. J. (1999) *Designing and conducting ethnographic research*. Walnut Creek, CA: AltaMira.
- Lee, H., Parsons, D., Kwon, G., Kim, J., Petrova, K., Jeong, E., and Ryu, H. (2016) 'Cooperation begins: Encouraging critical thinking skills through cooperative reciprocity using a mobile learning game', *Computers & Education*, 97, pp. 97–115. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2016.03.006>
- Li, L. (2016) 'Integrating thinking skills in foreign language learning: What can we learn from teachers' perspectives?', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 22, pp. 273–288. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2016.09.008>
- Li, L. (2016) 'Thinking skills and creativity in second language education: Where are we now?', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 22, pp. 267–272. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2016.11.005>
- Liaw, M. L. (2007) 'Content-based reading and writing for critical thinking skills in an EFL context', *English Teaching and learning*, 31(2), pp.45-87. Available at: DOI:[10.6330/ETL.2007.31.2.02](https://doi.org/10.6330/ETL.2007.31.2.02)
- Lichtman, M. (2006). *Qualitative Research in Education: A User's Guide*. California, Sage Publications.
- Lincoln S. Y., and Guba E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Lincoln, Y. S., Lynham, S. A., & Guba, E. G. (2011) 'Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences, revisited', *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*, 4, pp. 97-128.
- Lincoln, Y., and Guba, E. G (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*. London: Sage Publications.

Littlewood, W. (2000) 'Do Asian students really want to listen and obey?', *ELT journal*, 54(1), pp. 31-36. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/54.1.31>

Ma, s., Bhagat, k. k., Spector, j. m., Lin, L., Liu, D., Leng, J., Tiruneh, D. T. and Mancini, J (2020) 'Developing Critical Thinking: A Review of Past Efforts as a Framework for a New Approach for Childhood Learning', in M. Spector, B. Lockee, and M. Childress (eds) *Learning, design, and technology*. Springer, Cham, pp 1–26.

Mami, N. A. (2013) 'Teaching English under the LMD reform: The Algerian experience', *International Scholarly and Scientific Research & Innovation*, 7(4), pp. 243-246. Available at: 910913.doi:doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1081679

Mami, N.A. (2020) 'Citizenship Education in Post-conflict Contexts: The Case of Algeria' in A. Akkari and K. Maleq *Global Citizenship Education: Critical and international Perspectives*. Swizerland: Springer Nature Swizerland AG, pp. 113-124.

Mann, S. (2016) *The research interview: reflective practice and reflexivity in research*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Marin, M.A. and de la Pava, L. (2017)' Conceptions of Critical Thinking from University EFL Teachers' *English Language Teaching*, 10(7), pp.78-88. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v10n7p78>

Marshall, C. & Rossman, G.B. (2006) *Designing qualitative research*. 4th edn. London: Sage.

Mason, J. (2002) *Qualitative researching*. London: Sage.

Mason, M. (2008) 'Critical Thinking and Learning', in Mason. M. (Ed.) *Critical Thinking and Learning*, Marshall, C. and Rossman, G. B. (2016) *designing qualitative research*. 6th edn. Thousand oaks, CA: Sage.

McKinley J (2013) 'Displaying critical thinking in EFL academic writing: a discussion of Japanese to English contrastive rhetoric', *RELC Journal*, 44 (2), pp. 195-208. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0033688213488386>

McMillan, J. H., & Schumacher, S. (2006) *Research in education: Evidence-based inquiry*. 6th edn. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.

McPeck, J. E. (1981) *Critical thinking and education*. New York: St. Martin's Press.

- McPeck, J. E. (1990) 'Critical thinking and subject specificity: A reply to Ennis', *Educational Researcher*, 19(4), pp.10–12. Available at: DOI: 10.3102/0013189X019004010
- Mehta, S.R. and Al-Mahrooqi R. (2015) 'Can thinking be taught? linking critical thinking and writing in an EFL context', *RELC Journal*, 46(1), pp. 23-36. Available at doi:10.1177/0033688214555356
- Melouah, A. (2017) 'Cultural influences on critical thinking development on Algerian higher education EFL classes' (from the International conference on education and new learning technologies. Barcelona, Spain, 3-5 July). Available at: 10.21125/edulearn.2017.0868
- Mercer, J. (2007) 'The challenges of insider research in educational institutions: Wielding a double-edged sword and resolving delicate dilemmas', *Oxford Review of Education*, 33(1), pp. 1–17. Available at: doi:10.1080/03054980601094651
- Merriam, S. B. (1998) *Qualitative research and case study application in education*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Merriam, S. B. (1998) *Qualitative research and case study applications in education: revised and expanded from "Case Study Research in Education"*. Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- Messekher, H and Miliani, M. (2017) *Algeria: Challenges and perspectives*. In *Education in the Arab world*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Metatla, O. (2016) 'Higher education reform in Algeria: reading between the lines', *Open Democracy*, (February). Available at: <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/north-africa-west-asia/higher-education-in-algeria-reading-between-lines-of-lmd-reform/> (Accessed: 20 December 2020)
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M. and Saldaña, J. (2014) *Qualitative data analysis: a methods sourcebook*. 3rd edn. Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A. M. (1994) *Qualitative data analysis: an expanded sourcebook*. 2nd edn. California: Sage.
- Mineshima, M., and Imai, R. (2017) Hihanteki sihkouryoku wo ikuseisuru koudairenkei no kokoromi [Developing critical thinking skills in high school and university: how to make English lessons more intelligent], *The Chubu English Language Education Society*, 46, pp. 133–140. Available at: https://doi.org/10.20713/celes.46.0_133.

Ministry of National Education (MNE) (2006) *Programme of English as a Second Foreign Language, Third Year Secondary School*. Algeria: Algiers.

Mitchell, G. W., Skinner, L. B., and White, B. J. (2010) 'Essential soft skills for success in the twenty-first century workforce as perceived by business educators', *The Delta Pi Epsilon Journal*, 52(1), pp. 43-53. Available at: <https://www.questia.com/read/1P3-2036768821/essential-soft-skills-for-success-in-the-twenty-first>

Mitchell, R. G. (1993) *Secrecy and fieldwork*. London: Sage.

Moore, T. (2011) 'Critical thinking and disciplinary thinking: A continuing debate', *Higher Education Research & Development*, 30(3), pp. 261–274. Available at: doi:10.1080/07294360.2010.501328.

Moore, T. (2013) 'Critical thinking: seven definitions in search of a concept', *Studies in Higher Education*, 38(4), pp. 506-522. Available at: <file:///C:/Users/77901060/Desktop/Critical%20thinking%20seven%20definitions%20in%20search%20of%20a%20concept.pdf>

Moore, T. (2017) 'On the teaching of critical thinking in English for Academic purposes'' in R. Breeze and C. S. Guinda (Eds.) *Essential competencies for English-medium university teaching*. Cham: Springer. National Research Council, pp. 19–36.

Morse J.M., Barrett M., Mayan M., Olson K. and Spiers J. (2002) 'Verification strategies for establishing reliability and validity in qualitative research', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 1(2), pp. 13-22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F160940690200100202>

Morse, J. M. (2015) 'Critical analysis of strategies for determining rigor in qualitative inquiry', *Qualitative Health Research*, 25(9), pp. 1212-1222. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1049732315588501>

Neuman, L. W. (2000) *Social research methods: qualitative and quantitative Approaches*. 4th edn. USA: Allyn and Bacon.

Neuman, W. L. (2012) *Basics of social research: qualitative and quantitative approaches*. 3rd edn. Upper Saddle River, N.J.; Harlow: Pearson Education.

Newby, P. (2010) *Research methods for education*. Pearson Education.

- Nguyen, B. (2017) 'Integrating critical thinking in EFL classes: current practices and prospects', *ResearchGate*. Available at: [Integrating critical thinking in EFL classes: current practices and prospects \(researchgate.net\)](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317111111)
- Nicholas, M. C. and Labig, C. E. (2013) 'Faculty approaches to assessing critical thinking in the humanities and the natural and social sciences: Implications for general education', *The Journal of General Education*, 62, pp. 297–319. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1787/19963777>
- Nickerson, R. (1988) 'On improving thinking through instruction', *Review of Research in Education*, 15(3), pp.3-57. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1167360>
- Norris, S. P. (1985) 'Synthesis of research on critical thinking', *Educational Leadership*, 42 (8), pp. 40-45. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED290196>
- Norris, S. P. (1985) 'Synthesis of research on critical thinking', *Educational Leadership*, 42 (8), pp.40-45. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED290196>
- Norris, S.P. (1992) 'Testing for the disposition to think critically', *Informal Logic*, 14(2), pp. 157-164. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.22329/il.v14i2.2538>
- Norris, S.P., and Ennis, R.H. (1989) *Evaluating critical thinking*. Pacific Grove, CA: Midwest Publications.
- Nosratinia, M., Abbasi, M. and Zaker, A. (2015) 'Promoting second language learners' vocabulary learning strategies: can autonomy and critical thinking make a contribution?', *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*, 44(3). pp 21-30. Available at: [10.7575/aiac.ijalel.v.4n.3p.21](https://www.ijalel.v.4n.3p.21)
- O'Leary, Z. (2014) *The essential guide to doing your research project*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- O'sullivan, N. and Burce. A. (2014) 'Teaching and Learning in Competency Based Education', *The fifth international conference on E-learning (eLearning-2014)*, Belgrade, Serbia, 22-23 September 2014. Available at: [Teaching and Learning in Competency Based Education \(researchgate.net\)](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/261111111)
- Odendahl, T. and Shaw, A.M. (2002) 'Interviewing elites', in J.F. Gubrium and J.A. Holstein (eds) *Handbook of interview research: context and method*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, pp. 299-31.

- Oral Y. (2014) 'A case on teaching critical thinking and argument mapping in a teacher education context', in L.J. Shedletsky and J. S. Beaudry (Eds.) *Cases on teaching critical thinking through visual representation strategies*. IGI Global, Information Science, pp. 119-139.
- Ormston, R., Spencer, L., Barnard, M., and Snape, D. (2014) 'The foundations of qualitative research', in J. Ritchie, J. Lewis, C. Nicholls and R. Ormston (eds.) *Qualitative research practice: a guide for social science students and researchers*. Los Angeles: Sage, pp. 1-25.
- Ozkan-Akan, S. (2003) *Teachers' perceptions of constraints on improving student thinking in high schools*. Master thesis. Middle East technical university. Available at: etd.lib.metu.edu.tr/upload/683631/index.pdf (Accessed: 1 November 2020)
- Pascarella, E. T., and Terenzini, P. T. (2005) *How college affects students: a third decade of research*. 2nd edn. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Patton, M. Q. (2002) *Qualitative evaluation and research methods*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Paul, R. W. (1990) *Critical thinking: What every person needs to survive in a rapidly changing world*. Rohnert Park, CA: Center for Critical Thinking and Moral Critique, Sonoma State University.
- Paul, R. W. (1992) 'Critical thinking: What, why, and how?', *New Directions for Community Colleges*, 1992(77), pp. 3–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cc.36819927703>
- Paul, R. W. (1994) 'Teaching critical thinking in the strong sense', in S.K. Walters (ed.) *Re-Thinking reason: new perspectives in critical thinking*. Albany: SUNY Press, pp. 181-198.
- Pearson, G. (2009) 'The researcher has hooligan: where 'participant' observation means breaking the law', *International journal of social research methodology*, 12(3), pp. 243-255. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570701804250>
- Perkins D.N., Jay, E. and Tishman, S. (1993) 'Beyond abilities: A dispositional theory of thinking', *Merrill-Palmer' Quarterly*, 39(1) , pp. 1-21. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23087298>
- Phillips, R. (1998) 'Some methodological and ethical dilemmas in 'elite-based research', *British Educational Research Journal*, 24(1), pp. 5-20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0141192980240102>

Polit, D.F. and Beck, C.T. (2014) *Essentials of nursing research: appraising evidence for nursing practice*. 8th edn. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

Pring, R. (2000) *Philosophy of educational research*. London: Continuum.

Pring, R. (2015) *Philosophy of educational research*. 3rd edn. London: Bloomsbury Academic.

Prommak, S. (2019) *Critical thinking Cognitions and Pedagogic Practices of Thai EFL University Teachers*. PhD thesis. University of Stirling. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/1893/30307>

Puchta, H. (2012) *Developing thinking skills in the young learners' classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge UP.

Quinn, S., Hogan, M., Dwyer, C., Finn, P. and Fogarty, E., (2020) 'Development and Validation of the Student-Educator Negotiated Critical Thinking Dispositions Scale (SENCTDS)', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 38, pp. 1-17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2020.100710>

Rallis, S., and Rossman, G. (2009) 'Ethics and trustworthiness', in J. Heigham and R. Croker (eds.) *Qualitative research in applied linguistics: A practical introduction*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, pp.263-287.

Ramanathan, V. and Atkinson, D. (1999) 'Individualism, academic writing, and ESL writers', *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 8(1), pp 45-75. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1060-3743\(99\)80112-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1060-3743(99)80112-X)

Ramanathan, V., and Kaplan, R. B. (1996a) 'Some problematic "channels" in the teaching of critical thinking in current L1 composition textbooks: Implications for L2 student-writers', *Issues in Applied Linguistics*, 7(2), pp. 225-249. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0741088301018004004>

Ramanathan, V., and Kaplan, R. B. (1996a) 'Some problematic "channels" in the teaching of critical thinking in current L1 composition textbooks: Implications for L2 student-writers', *Issues in Applied Linguistics*, 7(2), pp. 225-249. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0741088301018004004>

Ramanathan, V., and Kaplan, R. B. (1996b) 'Audience and voice in current L1 composition texts: Some implications for ESL student writers', *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 5(1), pp. 21-34. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1060-3743\(96\)90013-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1060-3743(96)90013-2)

Rear, D. (2019) 'One size fits all? The limitations of standardised assessment in critical thinking', *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 44(5), pp. 664–675. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2018.1526255>.

Reid, S., and Chin, P. (2021) 'Assessing critical thinking in L2: An exploratory study', *Shiken*, 25, pp. 8–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.37546/JALTSIG.TEVAL25.1>

Rezaei, S., Derakhshan, A., and Bagherkazemi, M. (2011) 'Critical thinking in language education', *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 2 (4), pp. 769-777. Available at : [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262187640 Critical Thinking in Language Education](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262187640_Critical_Thinking_in_Language_Education)

Rezig, N. (2011) 'Teaching English in Algeria and educational reforms: an overview on the factors entailing students failure in learning foreign languages at university', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, pp. 1327-1333. Available at: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.370.

Ribbins, P. (2007) 'Interviews in educational research: Conversations with a purpose', in A. R. J. Briggs and M. coleman (eds) *Research methods in educational leadership and management*. London, Sage Publication Ltd, pp.207-223.

Richards, J. C. (2006) *Communicative language teaching today*. Cambridge University Press.

Richards, J. C. and Rodgers, T. S. (2000) *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. 2nd edn. Cambridge University Press.

Richards, J. C. and Rodgers, T. S. (2001) *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. 2nd ed. Cambridge University Press.

Richards, J.C. (2006) 'Materials development and research-making the connection', *Relc Journal*, 37(1), pp.5-26. Available at: 10.1177/0033688206063470

Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Nicholls, C., and Ormston, R. (2003) *Qualitative research practice: a guide for social science students and researchers*. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore, Washington: SAGE publications.

Robson, C. (2011) *Real world research: A resource for users of social research methods in applied settings*. 3rd edn. United Kingdom: Wiley-Blackwell.

Robson, C., and McCartan, K. (2016) *Real world research*. 4th edn. London: John Wiley.

Ruane, J. M. (2005) *Essentials of research methods: a guide to social science research*. Oxford: Blackwell.

Rubin, H., & Rubin, I. (2005) *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data*. London: Sage Publications.

Ruddin, L. P. (2006) 'You can generalise stupid! social scientists, Bent Fryberg, and case study methodology', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(4), pp. 797-812. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1077800406288622>

Saad M., Zawdie G., Derbal A. and Lee R. (May, 2005) 'Issues and Challenges arising from greater role of the university in promoting innovation in developing countries: A comparative study of experiences in Malaysia, Algeria and Ethiopia', *The Triple Helix Conference*, Turin, Italy, 2005. Available at: http://www.triplehelix5.com/pdf/A321_THC5.pdf

Saldaña, J. (2013) *The coding manual of qualitative researchers*. 2nd edn. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi: Sage Publications.

Salmon, M. H. (2013) *Introduction to logic and critical thinking*. 6th edn. Boston, MA: Wadsworth.

Samarasinghe, T. M. (2020) *Developing critical thinking in EFL learners within the perspectives of CHAT: the case of Oman*. EdD thesis, University of Sheffield. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?uin=uk.bl.ethos.736540>

Schweisfurth, M. (2011) 'Learner-centred education in developing country contexts: From solution to problem?', *International Journal of Educational Development*, 31(5), pp.425-432. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.ijedudev.2011.03.005

Shahini, G., and Riaz, A. M. (2011) 'A PBLT approach to teaching ESL speaking, writing, and thinking skills', *ELT journal*, 65(2), pp. 170-179. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccq045>

Shavelson, R. J., Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, O., Beck, K., Schmidt, S., and Marino, J. P. (2019) 'Assessment of university students' critical thinking: next generation performance assessment', *Int. J. Test*, 19, pp. 337–362. Available at: doi: 10.1080/15305058.2018. 1543309

Shell, R. (2001) 'Perceived barriers to teaching for critical thinking by BSN nursing faculty', *Nursing and Health Care Perspectives*, 22(6), pp 286-292. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/16370252>

- Shenton, A. K. (2004) 'Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects', *Education for Information*, 22 (2), pp.63–75. Available at: <https://doi:10.3233/EFI-2004-22201>
- Siegel, H. (1988) *Educating reason: Rationality, critical thinking and education*. New York: Routledge.
- Siegel, H. (1999) 'What (Good) Are Thinking Dispositions?', *Educational Theory*, 49(2), pp. 207–221. Available at: doi:10.1111/j.1741-5446.1999.00207.x
- Silva, E. (2008) *Measuring skills for the 21st century [report]*. Washington, DC: Education Sector.
- Silverman, D. (2006) *Interpreting qualitative data: methods for analysing talk, text and interaction*. 3rd edn. London: Sage.
- Silverman, D. (2013) *Doing qualitative research: a practical handbook*. 4th Edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Simons, H. (2015) 'Interpret in context: generalising from the single case in evaluation', *Evaluation*, 21 (2), pp. 173-188. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1356389015577512>
- Simpon, E. and Courtney, M. (2002) 'Critical thinking in nursing education: literature review', *International Journal of Nursing Practice*, 8, pp.89-98. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1440-172x.2002.00340.x>
- Smith, H. (2009) 'The Foxfire approach to student and community interaction', in L. Shumow (ed.), *Promising practices for family and community involvement during high school*. Charlotte, NC: Information age publishing, pp. 89–104.
- Smith, M.L. (1991) 'Put to the test: The effects of external testing on teachers', *Educational Researcher*, 20(5), pp. 8-11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3102%2F0013189X020005008>
- Sodoma, B. (2006) *Job satisfaction of Iowa public school principals*. University of Northern Iowa.
- Sosu, E. M. (2013) 'The development and psychometric validation of a Critical Thinking Disposition Scale', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 9 , pp. 107-119. Available at: 10.1016/j.tsc.2012.09.002
- Stake, R. E. (2005) 'Qualitative case studies', in Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.) *The sage handbook of qualitative research*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, pp.443-466.
- Stapleton, P. (2001) 'Assessing critical thinking in the writing of Japanese university students: insights about assumptions about content familiarity', *Written Communication*, 18(4), pp. 506-548. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0741088301018004004>

- Stapleton, P. (2001) 'Assessing critical thinking in the writing of Japanese university students: insights about assumptions about content familiarity', *Written Communication*, 18(4), pp. 506-548. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0741088301018004004>
- Stedman, N. P., and Adams, B. L. (2012) 'Identifying faculty's knowledge of critical thinking concepts and perceptions of critical thinking instruction in higher education', *NACTA Journal*, 56(2), pp.9-14.
- Sternberg, R. J. and Halpern D. F. (eds.) (2020) *Critical thinking in psychology*. 2nd edn. Cambridge, UK; New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Stroupe, R. R. (2006) 'Integrating critical thinking throughout ESL curricula', *TESL Reporter*, 39(2), pp. 42–61.
- Sturgis, P. and Smith, P. (2010) 'Assessing the validity of generalized trust questions: what kind of trust are we measuring', *International Journal of Public Opinion Research*, 22 (1), pp. 74-92. Available at : 10.1093/ijpor/edq003
- Sun, Y. (2019) 'Principles of language and critical thinking integrated teaching: TERRIFIC', *Foreign Language Teaching and Research*, 51(6), pp. 825–837.
- Talbi, S. E. (2015) 'Higher Education In Algeria: Where Are We Now?', *International Journal of Engineering Research And Management (IJERM)ISSN*, 2(11), pp. 2349- 2058, Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340818511>
- Tamayo, O. E. (2013) 'Argumentation as a critical thinking constituent in children', *Hallazgos*, 9(17), pp. 211-233. Available at : <http://revistas.usantotomas.edu.co/index.php/hallazgos/article/viewFile/738/1018>
- Taylor, C., and Gibbs, G.R. (2010) What is qualitative data analysis (QDA)?. Available at: http://onlineqda.hud.ac.uk/Intro_QDA/what_is_qda.php. (Accessed: 19 July 2021)
- Tebbs, T.J. (2000) *Assessing teachers' self-efficacy towards teaching thinking skills*. PhD thesis. Connecticut: The University of Connecticut.
- Thomas, G. (2010) 'Doing case study: abduction, not induction, phronesis not theory', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16(7), pp. 575-582. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1077800410372601>
- Touati, M. (2016) 'EFL learners' hindrances in developing critical thinking skills teachers' reflections', *Al Athar*, 15 (26), pp. 115-121. Available at: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/11236>

- Travis, C. and Wade, C. (1997) *Psychology in perspective*. Addison-Wisley Education Publishers Inc.
- Trowler, P. (2003) *Education Policy*. 2nd edn. London: Routledge.
- Tsui, L. (2002) 'Fostering critical thinking through effective pedagogy: Evidence from four institutional case studies', *Journal of Higher Education*, 73(6), pp. 740-763.
- Verschuren, P. J. M. (2003) 'Case study as a research strategy: some ambiguities and opportunities', *International Journal of Research Methodology*, 6(2), pp.121-139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570110106154>
- Walliman, N. (2005) *Your research project: A step-by-step guide for the first-time researcher*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Walliman, N. (2011) *Research methods: the basics*. New York: Routledge.
- Walsh, C.M., Seldomridge, L.A., and Badros, K.K. (2007) 'California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory: Further factor analytic examination', *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 104 (1), pp. 141-151. Available at: 10.2466/pms.104.1.141-151
- Wellington, J.(2000) *Educational research: contemporary issues and practical approaches*. London: Continuum.
- Wen, W. P. and Clément, R. (2003) 'A Chinese conceptualisation of willingness to communicate in ESL', *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 16(1), pp.18-38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908310308666654>
- Wendland, M., Robinson, C., and Williams, P. (2015) 'Thick critical thinking: Toward a new classroom pedagogy', in M. Davies and R. Barnett (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of critical thinking in higher education*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 153–168.
- Whittemore, R., Chase, S. K. and Mandle, C. L. (2001) 'Validity in qualitative research' *Qualitative Health Research*, 11 (4), pp.522–537. Available at: <http://qhr.sagepub.com/cgi/doi/10.1177/104973201129119299>
- Wiles, R. (2013) *What are qualitative research ethics?*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC.
- Wiles, R., Crow, G., Heath, S., and Charles, V. (2008) 'The management of confidentiality and anonymity in social research', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 11 (5), pp. 417-428. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570701622231>

- Williams, R. (1976) *Keywords: A vocabulary of culture and society*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Willingham, D. (2007). Critical thinking: Why is it so hard to teach? *American Educator*, 31(2), pp. 8-19. Available at: DOI:[10.3200/AEPR.109.4.21-32](https://doi.org/10.3200/AEPR.109.4.21-32)
- Willingham, D., T. (2008) 'Critical thinking: why is it so hard to teach?', *Arts Education Policy Review*, 109(4), pp.21-32. Available at: DOI: 10.3200/AEPR.109.4.21-32
- Wilson, K. (2016) 'Critical reading, critical thinking: Delicate scaffolding in English for Academic Purposes (EAP)', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 22, pp. 256–265. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2016.10.002>
- Yang, M., Badger, R., and Yu, Z. (2006) 'A comparative study of peer and teacher feedback in a Chinese EFL writing class', *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 15(3), pp. 179-200. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2006.09.004>
- Yang, Y. and Gamble, J. (2013) 'effective and practical critical thinking-enhanced EFL instruction', *ELT Journal*, 67(4), pp.398-412. Available at: 10.1093/elt/cct038.
- Yang, Y. C. Newby, T.J., and Robert L. B. (2005) 'Using Socratic questioning to promote critical thinking skills through asynchronous discussion forums in distance learning environments', *American Journal of Distance Education*, 19(3), pp. 163-181, Available at: 10.1207/s15389286ajde1903_4
- Yang, Y. T. C., Gamble, J., and Tang, S. Y. S. (2012) 'Voice over Instant Messaging as a Tool for Enhancing the Oral Proficiency and Motivation of English-as-a-Foreign-Language Learners', *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 43(3), pp. 448-464. Available at: [10.1111/j.1467-8535.2011.01204.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2011.01204.x)
- Yang, Y. T. C., Newby, T. J., and Bill, R. L. (2005) 'Using Socratic questioning to promote critical thinking skills through asynchronous discussion forums in distance learning environments', *The American Journal of Distance Education*, 19(3), pp. 163–181. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1207/s15389286ajde1903>
- Yildirim, A. (1993) *Promoting student thinking from the practitioner's point of view: Teachers' conceptions, attitudes and activities*. PhD dissertation. New York: Columbia University.
- Yin, R. K. (2003) *Case study research: Design and methods*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Yin, R. K. (2009) *Case study research: design and methods*. 4th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Yin, R. K. (2014) *Case study research design and methods*. 5th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Zeisel, J. (2006) *inquiry by design*. W.W. Norton and Company: New York.

Zhang, H., Yuan, R. and He, X. (2020) 'Investigating university EFL teachers' perceptions of critical thinking and its teaching: voices from China. *Asia-Pacific Edu Res*, 29, pp. 483–493 (2020). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-020-00500-6>

Zhao, C., Pandian, A. and Singh, M. (2016) 'Instructional strategies for developing critical thinking in EFL classrooms', *English Language Teaching*, 9(10), pp. 14-21 . Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v9n10p14>

Zohar, A. and Y. Dori. Y. (2003) 'Higher-order thinking skills and low-achieving students: Are they mutually exclusive?', *Journal of Learning Sciences*, 12, pp. 145-181. Available at: http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/S15327809JLS1202_1

Appendices

Appendix A: Semi-Structured Interview Schedule

Appendix B: Unstructured Observation Schedule

Appendix C : Consent Form for Teachers

Appendix D: Participant Information Sheet

Appendix E: Teacher's interview Sample

Appendix F: Observation Field Notes Example

Appendix G: Sample Extract from Curriculum Documents Guidelines

Appendix H: Sample data analysis – From extracts to codes and themes

Appendix A

Semi-Structured Interview Schedule

1. General introductory questions: Could you please tell me about your teaching experience? Your enjoyment of teaching English language? And for how long have you been teaching English?
2. What is your understanding or knowledge about critical thinking?
3. What is your opinion about incorporating critical thinking in EFL classes?
4. Do you think that you can teach critical thinking? Please support your answer
5. What types of activities do you arrange in class?
6. When designing your lessons plan, do you consider the integration of critical thinking among your core classroom objectives? Please provide justification
7. What are the characteristics of critical thinking enhancement activities?
8. Have you ever given your students critical thinking activities in class? If so, please give some examples of the activities. If not, why?
9. Do you find the policy in Higher Education towards learning English as second language encouraging to the development of critical thinking in any way? Please support your answer.
10. As a teacher of English, how do you see your role or contribution towards the development of students' critical thinking?
11. According to you, what might contribute to or hinder the development of critical thinking in students? / What are the obstacles or challenges that prevent teachers from integrating critical thinking in their classes?

Appendix B

Unstructured Observation Schedule

Title of the research project: ***The state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes between policy discourse and policy implementation: university teachers' perceptions***

Name of the researcher: **Sarra HOCINI**

School of Education & social sciences

University: _____

Date of the session observed: _____

Class: _____

Time: _____

Subject: _____

Incorporation and Development of Critical Thinking skills in classrooms

1. Objectives of the session/ lesson plans
2. Classroom interactions (teacher and students)
3. Teachers' practices and activities
4. Type of questions
5. Link between the guidelines communicated by the Ministry of Higher Education and the development of critical thinking in actual classroom practices.

Appendix C

Consent Form for Teachers

School of Education & Social Sciences
Paisley Campus

Title of the research project: ***The state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes between policy discourse and policy implementation: university teachers' perceptions***

Name of the researcher: ***Sarra HOCINI***

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.

- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

- 3- I understand that I am going to:
 - b- Participate in an interview (approx. 20-30 minutes).
 - c- Be audio-recorded during the interview.
 - d- Be observed during classroom teaching.

- 4- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

- 5- I consent to being a participant in the project.

Name of the participant: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Name of the Researcher: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

Consent Form for Students

School of Education & Social Sciences
Paisley Campus

Title of the research project: ***The state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes between policy discourse and policy implementation: university teachers' perceptions***

Name of the researcher: ***Sarra HOCINI***

1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.

2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

3- I understand that I am going to be observed during classroom practices.

4- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

5- I consent to being a participant in the project.

Name of the participant: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Name of the Researcher: _____ Date: _____

Signature: _____

Appendix D

Participant Information Sheet

School of Education & Social Sciences
Paisley Campus

Study Title: The state of critical thinking in Algerian EFL classes between policy discourse and policy implementation: university teachers' perceptions

Researcher: Sarra HOCINI

Introduction

This research is carried out by Sarra HOCINI, a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, School of Education and Social Sciences.

What is the purpose of this research?

This study attempts to explore the state of critical thinking in Algerian higher education, particularly within EFL classes. It aims to investigate the extent to which the teaching of critical thinking is encouraged by the Algerian higher educational system (if at all). This research then intends to investigate whether or not the representation of critical thinking in the guidelines communicated by the higher education (if there are any) has moved from the educational agenda to real educational practices. Furthermore, it seeks to examine teachers' conceptualisations of critical thinking, its importance, the teaching approaches and strategies they employ to infuse it in their pedagogy, as well as the factors that they believe may hinder the development of critical thinking in their students.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this research is totally voluntary. As such, those who accept to take part in the study may withdraw at any time of the research process, by contacting the researcher using the contact details provided below, without having to provide reasons. There will be no consequences for their withdrawal.

What will happen to you if you take part?

If you agree to take part in this study, you will be contacted to schedule an interview session at a time that you find suitable. Interviews will take 20-30 minutes. You will also be observed during one of your teaching classes. Interviews will be recorded in order to not lose any important responses and to facilitate data analysis.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen because you are an English language teacher in Algeria at university level.

Are there any potential risks to you in taking part?

No potential risks are anticipated in taking part in this research project, except taking some minutes of your time for the interview.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

As part of conducting an ethical research project, confidentiality and anonymity are given a crucial importance in this study. Therefore, you can remain assured that your identities will be kept anonymous, and pseudonyms will be used to replace your full names. Additionally, I can assure you that your data will be handled with total confidentiality, and that it will be only accessed by myself. All data will be securely stored in my personal password-protected computer and used only for the purpose of the current study. It will be disposed of six months after the completion of the doctoral project.

What will happen next?

If you are happy to be involved in the project, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. The project is extremely grateful for your involvement. Thanks are also expressed to those who have taken the time to read this information sheet but who now choose not to take part.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

If you have any further questions or comments concerning this research, please do not hesitate to contact:

Supervisors' details:

Dr Steve Brown
Lecturer in TESOL
School of Education
University of Glasgow

██

Researcher details:

Sarra Hocini
School of Education & Social Sciences
University of the West of Scotland,
Paisley Campus
Scotland, UK

██

Prof. Donald Gillies
Dean of the School of Education & Social
Sciences
University of the West of Scotland,
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland, UK

██

Personal details withheld.

Appendix E

Teacher's interview Sample

Researcher: Hi, so, my name is Sarra Hocini. I'm a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I would like to thank you so much for accepting to participate in this study, I want you to be aware that your identity will be kept anonymous. And you can withdraw your participation at any time you want without having to explain why. So we start with the first question. It is an introductory question. Could you please tell me about your teaching experience your enjoyment of teaching English? And how long have you been teaching English?

Participant: Thank you for this opportunity. First of all, I would like to say, Well, you're welcome. My name is ... I am a lecturer here at the University of ...Algeria. Well, I have the experience. I had the experience of I've been teaching for like 10 years, almost 10 years. Yes, I started first as a temporary teacher in ... University. After that, I got a chance here at this university, I taught different modules. And it was nice, sometimes it's hard, especially with the students that they don't understand you because like they move from the high school. This is a kind of gap, you know, like they used to do have lectures in Arabic and all of a sudden in English. So it's a bit hard, but we try to make it simple and try to make our Yes, I tried to make my students enjoy the lesson and engage.

R : I myself enjoyed your session when I attended the other day

P: Oh, thank you so much

R: So, what is your understanding or knowledge about critical thinking?

R: Well, for me, I don't have like, theoretical perspective of my own or, but from my experience critical thinking it's about using your skills, receptive skills and productive skills. Well, I can consider myself that critical thinking is the fifth skill after speaking, listening, reading and writing. So it's all about using your ability to analyse synthesise evaluate information, you think about the premises, make connection about premises, infer or form conclusions about given information and things like that.

R: So, you have an idea about. P: maybe. R: what is your opinion about incorporating thinking in EFL classes?

P: you mean in Algeria? Well, I have, you know, like I have, like, my opinion is about making an evaluation between before the use of before adopting LMD system and after. In the classical system, it was like the approach, approach, sorry, was thematic, we rely more on content to deliver information related to a particular topic, like for example, British literature. It's like a historical approach. You start from classism until postmodernism. In American literature, you do the same but with the case study taking American novels and poems from as a case study. But today with this new system, the LMD system. Well, we are focused more on skills, and I believe we are. Yes, yeah, we are focused on the four skills. And even the fifth scale we focus on that is like, it's, it's implicit, not explicit. Because like when we talk about this module: study skills, the four skills? Yeah, it's the four. It's the five skills actually, you see. Yeah. Because we try to make them engaged, asking questions, try to analyse things using English.

R: So since you think that critical thinking is crucial, do you think that you can teach critical thinking? Is it teachable in the first place?

P: I think it is implied it is implied I cannot teach it. It's like grammar. You cannot teach it directly. You can do it indirectly. Yes. Like, for example, problem solving. You can put the students in a situation and you ask them questions, maybe to see their reaction, but to guide them through the steps, and you don't tell them about that. See?

R: what type of activities do you usually arrange in class?

P: Well, before the pandemic we used, group works, presentations, Peer work, yeah, task-based, but because the pandemic, You know, we rely more on the teacher-centred Approach, because we are short of time and we need the cover all of the materials. Yeah, right, time constraints

R. when you, when designing your lesson plan, do you consider the integration of critical thinking among your core classroom objectives?

P: Well, well, when it comes, for example, to teach in literature, I focus more on the content of the literary material. But with study skills, it's like it's an objective objective, because I, my aim is what like to provide my students with the needed in, let's say, information through which I guide them to prove their skills, self management skills, time management skills, task management skills, and even communication skills and critical thinking is related. It's implied sorry.

R: Since you consider critical thinking in the study skills session, according to you what are the characteristics of critical thinking enhancement activities?

P: I think it's the best, Well, I think it's about asking questions. This is one thing, like for example, to make them think through questions, like for example, ask them to visualise concepts, this is another activity, try another activities through each matching activities, which you make them make connections. Yeah, this is so it's all about identification and connection. This is how identification of concepts elements that are related to the concept and connection between the concept, this is through illustrations.

R: So have you ever given your students critical thinking activities in class? If so, can you please provide examples?

P: this year, this year no, because of the pandemic. I focus, R: on delivering the content, P: yes, Exactly. But before, Yes, I remember I remember, I don't remember exactly the example in detail. But when, I guess when I taught my students, second year students about induction and deduction. It was like giving them providing them examples on the board and asking them to make connections about deduction and induction and see the difference.

R: now, moving to the policy and implementation regarding critical thinking, do you find the policy of higher education towards learning English as a second language, encouraging the development of critical thinking in any way?

P: Well, with LMD? First of all, I would like to say I'm not sure. Okay, I'm not. I don't have like an opinion, which is constructive .

R: ok, that's fine, but Have ever received a document that presents critical thinking as an educational objective, throughout your years of teaching?

P: No. You see, because the way we work here is we use the canvas [curriculum document], do you remember the convas? It's about you have like, general guidelines. It's like guidelines of the module, each module, how much hours you have per semester, and is it tutorial, or course, like, for example,

the study skills, we have 45 hours, normally we should, we should deliver information in this time load, it's 45 hours per semester. And normally, we should teach three hours per week. This is before the pandemic, in the pandemic, on the one hour and a half, six sessions, so we see the difference. That's what we cannot have that plan of the learner-centred approach.

R: back to you point about the Canvas, Does it include any educational objectives?

P: Well, when you see that there is something that is like, for example, we have units have units, unit one, for example, in unit one, we have written an expression. So you see, it's about improving the four skills. Unit Two, it's about grammar, linguistics, and phonetics. So it's more importantly, it's about the content of language learning. Then you have Unit Three, it's about civilisation, and literature. So it's like, you want students to think more about culture and its relationship to language. Then we have the unit of methodology, which you have to study skills and reading techniques. And here, I believe there is a plan to enhance critical thinking in the unit of methodology. Because we teach the first year we have study skills after that second year, it's the same module. Then in the third year, it becomes research methodology. And I believe that there is a plan to incorporate critical thinking in the unit of methodology. yeah, that's my opinion.

R: So, as a teacher of English, how do you see your role or contribution towards the development of the students critical thinking?

P: well, my role is crucial, because sometimes I try to provide them with the big picture. Because students, they have experience, but their experience is part maybe of high school family relations. And they come here and they try to make connections to others. Two different things. And I'm trying to give them a chance to see, you know, their experience from another perspective.

R: Thank you. So for the last question, according to you, what might contribute or hinder the development of critical thinking in students? What are the challenges or obstacles that you face? While trying to achieve this aim?

P: it's about class management. Yeah, I don't prefer this traditional way of tables.

R: yes, probably the seating would be the circle, as students would face each other which would facilitate active learning.

P: yes, the circle exactly, If we have, for example, the chance to do e-learning, it gives us the chance to

R: aren't you allowed to change the seating?

P: Yes, we are, but it's time-consuming. It's time and effort-consuming, you know, each time you change. And we have another problem. It's maybe because of the numbers of the students. Yeah, so it's not possible R: yes, it would be very difficult to manage. P: this year in the pandemic, we have in each class, we have 30 students, maybe it's possible. But in previous years, we used to have, like 50 or 45 students in a group. It's not possible, but I believe that class management, it's a big issue, it hinders the development of that kind of skills.

R: Can you think of other challenges, maybe the students resistance to activities that challenge them?

P: Yeah, yes, student resistance, not all, in, for example, 30 students, you can find, like 15, that are not interested in this, these kinds of activities. But with others, I have no problem like 5 to 10

students, they enjoy that. Another thing maybe as a difficulty, I can talk about maybe, sometimes, the restriction of the module, when you teach, for example, literary class. So it's not possible to apply critical thinking maybe you can do that. The focus is on the content. Because, you know, sometimes I ask my students, you should read, for example, things fall apart after that, you come here, and we do the interpretation. And because of their level, and some students, they don't read at all. So I come here, and instead of making connections, interpretation, and try to address issues of critical thinking, I focus on delivering the summary of the novel. And then I summarise themes, symbols, and emotive, so maybe because the nature of the model sometimes doesn't give you a chance to teach critical thinking. But with study skills, I have no problem so far.

R: Okay. Yeah. So do you think that teachers should get training on how to teach critical thinking skills because they are really crucial for academic success and even after that?

P: Yes, I believe that we need that. R: did you have first any type of training concerning that?

P: well, I had training and it was my own training. I remember. Yeah. Because I've been to England. So it was it was possible to communicate with teachers, and share their perspectives about critical thinking, about research because I'm interested in research in literary studies. It's highly now advanced. This is one thing I had the chance with my supervisor, she is British Felicity Han from she's, she's working at Barcelona University Autonoma. So I had the chance. Another training that I had about critical thinking is through Coursera. If you haven't heard about this website, it's a website which delivers or it gives you access to universities, lectures, etc. It offers lectures for free and accessed from different universities around the globe. And I had lectures about critical thinking, about induction, deduction, model thinking and stuff like that.

R: that is great, but what about here, in Algeria. Have you ever received training in Algeria?

P: No. It was my own. In Algeria, No. Because here, we still struggle. You should teach English we focus on that's a good point to make. In Algeria. Officially speaking, we still focus on language learning and language teaching. We don't talk about critical thinking, our focus is just language learning language teaching, and how to make students learn the language not even to think critically, maybe with time, we'll have this chance.

R: Actually, there's a teaching approach that is called the teach-to-the-test approach. Where there is a set of knowledge to be prescribed memorised and reproduced in exams. Actually, some literature argue that the teach-to-the-test approach dominates the EFL classes where all the teachers, students, and parents are all scores, good scores. What do you think about this?

P: Absolutely. I agree. It's a paradigm. It's a paradigm. It's a paradigm and we are still having this paradigm. It's the teacher test paradigm. Because, sometimes I can give you a funny example. I teach master's students reading skills and strategies, and I started giving them skills. How can you use for example, skimming, scanning in the SQ3r method? And then I said, I don't remember which kind of skill scanning, maybe, I said it's possible to skim and scan in, in survey, as well as in reading, and one student said, but it's a bit complicated, sir. Are you going to ask us questions like that in the exam, and I thought, Oh, the students have the exam in mind, not to understand where so, when they came here, the are programmed. I am here just to score.

R: yes, that is really interesting. So, we came to the end. So thank you so much for your time. You've been really helpful. Thank you so much. I cant really thank you enough. P: You are most welcome.

Appendix F

Observation Field Notes Example

- a little bit of chat was taking place, the Teacher wasn't really paying attention to that
 - the Amphitheater was very cold.
 - Students were just chatting.
 - whenever the Teacher touches back, more chat to his place.
 - The Teacher asked some rhetorical questions: Yes/No e.g. who can we say we teach ESP? Can students specialise in civilisation Teacher ESP. The students answered no, the Teacher said because they didn't have a training about ESP in...
 - Some chats can be heard again from time to time.
 - The Teacher asked what is the role of the teacher and explained that he is the presenter, the discussion initiator, the asker and answering a question, guide.
 - What is the task of course designers, asked the students what they thought about it and then answered it.

University: OCB. Dated the session observed: 3/10/12
 Class: Master 1 Time: 9:30.
 Subject: ESP Pr. ~~XXXXXX~~
 - Start at: 09:43.
 - Teacher gave test papers for the students who missed the test.
 - The Teacher made a catchup of the last session.
 - The teacher the lecture took place in an Amphitheater, the teacher was lecturing, the students are relatively passively listening.
 - Some students who have having the test they missed, some checking their phones, however the first two rows were paying close attention.
 - The Teacher explains and asks if everything was clear. I had a difficulty hearing every single word the teacher is saying, echo sound in the Amphitheater.
 - Very few students were interested in the lecture (not TD).
 - The Teacher kept lecturing standing in his place.

- she said when providing the students with handouts which includes the topics to be interpreted presented in the following session.
 - she said only those who are going to present the topic were reading it, the rest might not even have a look at it.

- What a researcher, what is a collaborator she answered it again.
 - [As I asked the Teacher to attend the session, she said these are only lectures, there will be no TD sessions with them, she said in the first semester they have done presentation.]
 - The Teacher asked a question the student in the front line answered, it was hard for me to hear what she was saying giving that I was sitting in the back.
 - (Around 6 students).
 - Noise, Noise, Noise - barely can hear a word.
 - passive students.
 - she asked if there are any question at the end of the observation.
 - Noise, Noise, Noise (from the front).
 - Teacher said that they do presentations to allow the students to have a TD task for TD.

Appendix G

Sample Extract from Curriculum Documents Guidelines

Intitulé du Master : Didactique des Langues Etrangères

Semestre : S1

Intitulé de l'UE : UEF (UEF2) Linguistics

Intitulé de la matière: Applied Linguistics

Crédits : 2

Coefficients : 1

Objectifs de l'enseignement (*Décrire ce que l'étudiant est censé avoir acquis comme compétences après le succès à cette matière – maximum 3 lignes*).

Applied linguistics is introduced at this level to enlarge students' knowledge in the field of linguistics after having dealt with theoretical linguistics in their third-year (and other branches of linguistics in previous years such as descriptive linguistics, general linguistics and microlinguistics). The course seeks to equip students with pertinent information about applied linguistics origins, foundations and scope in general and its application in foreign language teaching in particular.

Connaissances préalables recommandées (*descriptif succinct des connaissances requises pour pouvoir suivre cet enseignement – Maximum 2 lignes*).

- Linguistics (3e Année, Licence)

Contenu de la matière :

1. An Introduction to Applied Linguistics (Branches of Linguistics)
2. Linguistics and Applied linguistics: A Difficult Relationship
3. Applied Linguistics: Subject to Discipline?
4. The Need for Applied Linguistics

Mode d'évaluation : examen écrit

Références (*Livres et photocopiés, sites internet, etc*).

- Alan Davies (1999, 2007) An Introduction to Applied Linguistics. Edinburgh University Press Ltd.
- Guy Cook (2003) Applied Linguistics. Oxford University Press.

Appendix H

Sample data analysis – From extracts to codes and themes

Extracts	Codes	Themes/Subthemes	Clustered under RQ
<p>The course aims at introducing learners to the main theoretical positions that have been advanced to explain first and second language acquisition (Master DID, p.25).</p> <p>The course seeks to equip students with pertinent information about applied linguistics origins, foundations and scope...' (p.29).</p> <p>At this level, students are supposed to <i>expand their knowledge</i> with regard to the teaching of ESP by introducing them to the notions of course, syllabus and curriculum in ESP' (p.46).</p>	<p>Explaining to students theories of first and second language acquisition.</p> <p>Delivering knowledge about applied linguistics.</p> <p>Consolidating the students' knowledge.</p>	<p>Expanding students' knowledge</p>	<p>RQ1</p>
<p>'Incorporating critical thinking in any kind of teaching is of crucial importance given its relevance not only to classroom activities but also to real-life situations and tasks' (Nora).</p> <p>'...And how to be able to discuss things and eventually do research and write something about those topics'(Djamal).</p>	<p>Acknowledging that the significance of CT transcends schools' borders and helps in preparing future citizens.</p> <p>Acknowledging the role of CT in research conduct.</p>	<p>Importance of critical thinking</p>	<p>RQ3</p>

<p>'If we want learners to develop a certain proficiency in the target language, they have to make use of critical thinking, especially for advanced learners' (Reem).</p>	<p>The positive impact of CT on the students' language proficiency.</p>		
<p>Because of the large number of students in each group, it would be very hard for the teacher to organise activities about critical thinking, you try to imagine a classroom of or a classroom which is made up of up to 40 students, how are you going as a teacher, how are you going to control or how are you going to involve all of them in activities, or in problem solving activities? (Mia).</p> <p>'this system in general does not promote life skills. It is all about having greater rates of success among students, but teaching students how to be critical is not really part of the agenda' (Omar).</p> <p>'Sometimes, the students' level itself sometimes I mean, we have, let's say, poor students, I mean, that we cannot develop it, a student who is unable to write, let's say, a correct or coherent paragraph, you cannot expect him to think critically' (Reem).</p>	<p>Dealing with a great number of students.</p> <p>Attributing the lack of critical thinking to the system's and curriculum documents' marginalisation of CT.</p> <p>Associating the lack of critical thinking practice to the students' low level in the English language.</p>	<p>Factors affecting the development of critical thinking in EFL university students</p>	<p>RQ4</p>